

REPUBLIK INDONESIA
KEMENTERIAN HUKUM DAN HAK ASASI MANUSIA

SURAT PENCATATAN CIPTAAN

Dalam rangka perlindungan ciptaan di bidang ilmu pengetahuan, seni dan sastra berdasarkan Undang-Undang Nomor 28 Tahun 2014 tentang Hak Cipta, dengan ini menerangkan:

Nomor dan tanggal permohonan : EC00201934198, 28 Maret 2019

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Kewarganegaraan : Indonesia
Jenis Ciptaan : Program Komputer
Judul Ciptaan : Program Aplikasi Sistem Pakar Pendeteksi Kerusakan Dini Mesin Suzuki All New Ertiga Bensin Menggunakan Metode Forward Chaining

Tanggal dan tempat diumumkan untuk pertama kali di wilayah Indonesia atau di luar wilayah Indonesia : 14 Maret 2019, di Karawang

Jangka waktu perlindungan : Berlaku selama 50 (lima puluh) tahun sejak Ciptaan tersebut pertama kali dilakukan Pengumuman.

Nomor pencatatan : 000138802

adalah benar berdasarkan keterangan yang diberikan oleh Pemohon.
Surat Pencatatan Hak Cipta atau produk Hak terkait ini sesuai dengan Pasal 72 Undang-Undang Nomor 28 Tahun 2014 tentang Hak Cipta.

a.n. MENTERI HUKUM DAN HAK ASASI MANUSIA
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MANUAL BOOK

**APLIKASI PROGRAM SISTEM PAKAR PENDETEKSI KERUSAKAN DINI MESIN SUZUKI
ALL NEW ERTIGA BENSIN MENGGUNAKAN METODE FORWARD CHAINING**

Mobil SUZUKI All New ERTIGA berbahan bakar Bensin

Tahun 2019

1. Tampilan Login Admin

Gambar 1. Menu Login

Tampilan menu untuk login Aplikasi, yang diinput dengan dua masukan yaitu username dan password, jika benar maka akan masuk kedalam Aplikasi Sistem Pakar All New ERTIGA seperti yang tampak pada lampiran index digambar selanjutnya.

2. Tampilan Index Admin

Gambar 2. Index Admin

Yang terlihat pada (Gambar 2) merupakan tampilan yang akan terlihat jika pelaksanaan input login dikatakan benar.

3. Tampilan Kerusakan

The screenshot shows the 'Admin Sistem Pakar' interface with a sidebar on the left containing 'Beranda', 'Kerusakan', 'Gejala', and 'Basis Pengetahuan'. The main content area is titled 'Beranda / Kerusakan' and features a '+ Tambah Kerusakan' button. Below this is a section for 'Data Nama Kerusakan' with a search bar and a table of damage records.

NO	ID Kerusakan	Nama Kerusakan	Jenis Kendaraan	Ops
1	M01	Aera Drop	All New Ertiga	✎ ✖
2	M02	Elektrikal (Sensor, Busi, Coil, Alternator, Fuel Pump, ECM, BCM, TCM dan Switch)	All New Ertiga	✎ ✖
3	M03	Over Head	All New Ertiga	✎ ✖
4	M04	Komponen Mesin Aus (Piston, ChamShaft, Conrod, Valve, Crankshaft, Chain, Rul, Timing Belt, V belt)	All New Ertiga	✎ ✖

Gambar 3. Tampilan Kerusakan.

Jika terdapat kerusakan dan ingin melihat kerusakan apa yang terjadi, maka data akan ditampilkan seperti yang tampak pada (Gambar 3), sehingga akan mengetahui tindakan apa yang harus dilakukan untuk memperbaiki kerusakan tersebut.

4. Input Data Kerusakan

The screenshot shows the 'Admin Sistem Pakar' interface with a sidebar on the left. The main content area is titled 'Beranda / Tambah Kerusakan' and features a '+ Tambah Kerusakan' button. Below this is a form for adding a new damage record with the following fields:

- ID Kerusakan:
- Nama Kerusakan:
- Jenis Kendaraan:
- Teknis:
- Keterangan:

Gambar 4. Input Data Kerusakan

Berbagai macam keadaan kerusakan yang terdapat pada mesin ERTIGA, dapat ditambahkan melalui menu input kerusakan agar kondisi penentuan kerusakan akan dapat dideteksi dengan baik dan akan diperlihatkan seperti yang tampak pada (Gamber 4). Hal ini banyak kegunaan yang dapat diketahui terhadap kerusakan pada mesin ERTIGA.

5. Berhasil menyimpan data Kerusakan

Gambar 5. Penyimpanan Data Kerusakan

Data kerusakan yang telah diinput akan tersimpan dalam database kerusakan, maka perlu dilakukan penyimpanan data, pada saat melakukan klik tombol simpan, maka akan tampak pesan apakah akan disimpan, Jika memang ingin disimpan maka klik tombol OK.

6. Edit Data Kerusakan

Gambar 6. Edit Data Kerusakan.

Jika data kerusakan yang telah diinput terjadi proses revisi, maka data keterangan kerusakan dapat diganti atau diedit melalui menu Edit Data Kerusakan yang tampilannya dapat dilihat pada (Gambar 6), dan setelah terjadi pengeditan data kerusakan lalu lakukan proses penyimpanan agar data menjadi benar telah diedit yang dapat dilihat pada (Gambar 6) untuk menyakinkan data akan disimpan.

7. Simpan Data Edit Kerusakan

Gambar 7. Simpan Data Kerusakan.

Proses penyimpanan yang ada pada kerusakan hanya dapat dilakukan oleh ADMIN saja yang melakukan proses ini, karena untuk menjaga kebenaran data yang mana yang dapat diproses dan data yang mana yang sudah tidak relevan lagi atau dapat dikatakan data sudah tidak layak digunakan.

8. Hapus Data Kerusakan

Gambar 8. Hapus Data Kerusakan.

Pengolahan data kerusakan dapat dilakukan peroses penghapusan data, yang mana data yang sudah tersimpan dalam database yang tidak sesuai lagi atau data yang salah terhadap hasil entry data kerusakan, maka dapat dilakukan penghapusan terhadap data kerusakan yang ada dalam database. Perhatikan tampilan yang ada pada (Gambar 8).

9. Tampilan Data Gejala

NO	ID Gejala	Nama Gejala	Jenis Kendaraan	Opsi
1	G01	Tidak Dapat Starting, Tetapi Didorong Hidup	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus
2	G02	Mesin Tidak Dapat Idling (Pincang)	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus
3	G03	Mesin Normal Ketika Masih Dingin, Cek Engine Tidak Menyala	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus
4	G04	Mesin Normal Ketika Masih Dingin, Cek Engine Menyala	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus
5	G05	Terdapat Detonan	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus
6	G06	Mesin Tidak Dapat Akselerasi	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus

Gambar 9. Tampilan Data Gejala.

Proses pendeteksian terhadap mesin ERTIGA dapat dilihat seperti yang tampak pada (Gambar 9). Pada data tersebut akan terlihat sejauh mana tingkat gejala yang dapat diketahui terhadap mesin ERTIGA dan ini merupakan pengetahuan terhadap kepakaran yang menggunakan program aplikasi pendeteksi kerusakan mesin ERTIGA.

10. Hapus Data Gejala

NO	ID Gejala	Nama Gejala	Jenis Kendaraan	Opsi
1	G01	Tidak D...	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus
2	G02	Mesin T...	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus
3	G03	Mesin R...	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus
4	G04	Mesin Normal Ketika Masih Dingin, Cek Engine Menyala	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus
5	G05	Terdapat Detonan	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus
6	G06	Mesin Tidak Dapat Akselerasi	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus
7	G07	Cek Engine Menyala	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus
8	G08	Indikator Accu Berwarna Merah	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus
9	G09	Mesin Mati Total	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus
10	G10	Accu Lamp Merusak	All New Ertiga	Edit Hapus

Gambar 10. Hapus Data Gejala

Untuk melakukan penghapusan terhadap data gejala, dapat dilakukan dengan memilih menu hapus data gejala, kemudian pilih mana dari sejumlah data gejala yang akan dihapus, lalu lakukan pemilihan pointer pada data gejala yang akan dihapus dan tekan tombol hapus, sehingga akan tampil pernyataan benar akan dihapus, jika ya pilih OK atau sebaliknya jika tidak maka pilih Cancel.

11. Tampil Basis Pengetahuan

ID	NO	Kerusakan	Nama Kerusakan	Gejala	Opsi
1	M01	Accu Drop	Accu Drop	Tidak Dapat Starting, Tetapi Didorong Hidup	
2	M01	Accu Drop	Accu Drop	Indikator Accu Berwarna Merah	
3	M01	Accu Drop	Accu Drop	Accu Meledak	
4	M01	Accu Drop	Accu Drop	Lampu Mati Total	
5	M02	Elektrikal (Sensir, Busi, Coil, Alternator, Fuel Pump, ECM, ...)	Elektrikal (Sensir, Busi, Coil, Alternator, Fuel Pump, ECM, ...)	Mesin Tidak Dapat Idling (Pincang)	

Gambar 11. Tampilan Basis Pengetahuan

Untuk mengetahui kemampuan dari suatu system pakar, diukur melalui basis pengetahuan yang menggambarkan transfer dari seorang pakar kedalam sebuah database yang sebut dengan basis pengetahuan. Didalam data base pengetahuan tersimpan semua system kerja kepakaran terhadap kerusakan mesin ERTIGA. Perhatikan yang tampak pada (Gambar 11). Itulah gambaran basis pengetahuan yang dapat digunakan untuk proses pendeteksian kerusakan pada mesin ERTIGA.

12. Tambah Data Basis Pengetahuan

Gambar 12. Tambah Data Basis Pengetahuan.

Data pengetahuan semakin lama semakin bertambah, Karena dalam implementasinya kerusakan agar mudah dapat diketahui maka basis pengetahuan juga harus bertambah, dan proses penembahan terhadap basis pengetahuan dapat dilakukan dengan memilih menu tambah basis pengetahuan. Maka proses entry penambahan data dapat dilakukan dan jangan lupa untuk melakukan proses penyimpanan kembali atas penambahan data pengetahuan.

13. Admin Logout

Gambar 13. screen Logout.

Tahapan terakhir untuk menyelesaikan penggunaan aplikasi program pendeteksi kerusakan mesin ERTIGA agar data dan proses penggunaan aplikasi system pakar pendeteksi kerusakan mesin ERTIGA terjaga dari para pengguna lain, maka setiap ingin meninggalkan kegiatan sebaiknya lakukan proses Logout seperti yang tertera pada (Gambar 13). Sehingga system akan terjaga dari segala gangguan sehingga aplikasi semakin terjaga dengan baik.

14. Index Beranda User

Gambar 14. Beranda User

Aplikasi pendeteksi kerusakan pada mesin mobil ERTIGA, dapat juga digunakan oleh user yang mana user diberikan hak akses tidak sama dengan hak akses ADMIN, User hanya diberikan dalam skop yang terbatas. Perhatikan (Gambar 14) tampilan hak akses user.

15. Pendeteksi Kerusakan

The screenshot shows a web interface for a Suzuki All New Ertiga Binsin expert damage detection system. At the top, there is a dark header with the text 'Pakar All New Ertiga Binsin' on the left and 'Beranda', 'Pendeteksi Kerusakan', and 'Info Kerusakan' on the right. Below the header, the main heading reads 'SELAMAT DATANG DI SISTEM PAKAR PENDETEKSI KERUSAKAN MOBIL SUZUKI ALL NEW ERTIGA BENSIN'. Underneath, it says 'PENDETEKSI KERUSAKAN'. There is a dropdown menu for 'Jenis Kendaraan' with 'All New Ertiga' selected. A blue button labeled 'CEK KERUSAKAN' is positioned below the dropdown. Below the button, there is a section titled 'HASIL KERUSAKAN' which contains a table with four columns: 'ID Kerusakan', 'Nama Kerusakan', 'Jenis Kendaraan', and 'Detail'. The table is currently empty. At the bottom of the page, there is a dark footer with the text 'Copyright © Yosep Adi Candra 2018'.

Gambar 15. Branda User.

Jika user yang telah melakukan proses login, maka akan ditampilkan seperti yang tampak pada (Gambar 15). Dengan demikian user dapat melakukan proses sesuai hak akses yang diberikan dan tidak lebih dari itu.

16. Tampil Hasil Pendeteksi Kerusakan

The screenshot shows the same web interface as in Gambar 15, but now displaying the results of a damage check. The header and main heading are identical. The 'Jenis Kendaraan' dropdown still shows 'All New Ertiga'. The 'CEK KERUSAKAN' button is present. The 'HASIL KERUSAKAN' section now contains a table with one row of data. The table has four columns: 'ID Kerusakan', 'Nama Kerusakan', 'Jenis Kendaraan', and 'Detail'. The data in the row is: 'M02', 'Elektrikal (Sensor, Busi, Coil, Alternator, Fuel Pump, ECM, BOM, TCM dan Switch)', 'All New Ertiga', and 'Detail'. At the bottom of the page, there is a dark footer with the text 'Copyright © Yosep Adi Candra 2018'.

Gambar 16. Tampilan Hasil Pendeteksi Kerusakan.

User yang melakukan proses untuk melihat pendeteksian hasil kerusakan, maka akan ditampilkan sesuai (Gambar 16), tetapi user dalam hal ini, hanya melihat saja dan tidak bisa melakukan proses editing atau proses lainnya.

17. Detail hasil Pendeteksi Kerusakan

Pakar All New Ertiga Bensin Beranda · Pendeteksi Kerusakan · Info Kerusakan

SELAMAT DATANG DI SISTEM PAKAR IDENTIFIKASI KERUSAKAN MOBIL SUZUKI ALL NEW ERTIGA BENSIN

DETAIL KERUSAKAN

Detail Kerusakan

ID Kerusakan:

Nama Kerusakan:

Jenis Kendaraan:

Gejala:

-
-
-
-

Gambar 17. Hasil Pendeteksian Kerusakan.

Pendeteksian hasil kerusakan yang digunakan oleh user, hanya dapat melihat saja, melainkan tidak dapat merubah atau menambah tampilan, karena dikerjakan oleh system secara automatic. Perlakukan user hanya bersifat melihat saja.

18. Informasi Kerusakan

Pakar All New Ertiga Bensin Beranda · Pendeteksi Kerusakan · Info Kerusakan

SELAMAT DATANG DI SISTEM PAKAR IDENTIFIKASI KERUSAKAN MOBIL SUZUKI ALL NEW ERTIGA BENSIN

DAFTAR KERUSAKAN MOBIL SUZUKI ALL NEW ERTIGA BENSIN

NO	ID Kerusakan	Nama Kerusakan	Jenis Kendaraan	Detail
1	M01	Accu Drop	All New Ertiga	Detail
2	M02	Elektrikal (Sensor, Busi, Coil, Alternator, Fuel Pump, ECM, BCM, TCM dan Switch)	All New Ertiga	Detail
3	M03	Over Head	All New Ertiga	Detail
4	M04	Komponen Mesin Atas (Piston, ChamShaft, Corrod, Valve, Crankshaft, Chain, Rul, Timing Belt, V belt)	All New Ertiga	Detail
5	M05	Mesin Jebol	All New Ertiga	Detail
6	M06	Spring & Balancing	All New Ertiga	Detail

Gambar 18. Informasi Kerusakan.

Informasi hasil kerusakan dapat dilihat oleh user, secara detail sehingga user dapat mengetahui keberadaan fungsi dari aplikasi sisitem pakar pendeteksi kerusakan mesin mobil ERTIGA, sejauh mana pendeteksian dengan aplikasi program ini dapat dilakukan. Perhatikan juga (Gambar 19) hasl detail kerusakan pada mesin ERTIGA.

19. Informasi Detail Kerusakan

Pakar All New Ertiga Bensin Beranda | Pendeteksi Kerusakan | Info Kerusakan

SELAMAT DATANG DI SISTEM PAKAR IDENTIFIKASI KERUSAKAN MOBIL SUZUKI ALL NEW ERTIGA BENSIN

DETAIL KERUSAKAN

Detail Kerusakan:

ID Kerusakan :	M06
Nama Kerusakan :	Spring & Balancing
Jenis Kendaraan :	All New Ertiga
Gejala :	
Teknis :	* Kurangnya perawatan Cade * Terlalu Banyak Bontas yang tinggi dan mengenai jalan yang kurang baik

Informasi detail kerusakan mesin mobil ERTIGA ini , menjadi ukuran dari kemampuan aplikasi program dengan menggunakan system pakar, dan perlu dikembangkan lebih jauh lagi. Karena system ini memberikan gambaran kerusan yang bersifat umum dan sering terjadi pada mesin mobil ERTIGA dan tingkat kerusakan semakin lama akan bertambah secara berkepanjangan waktu. Dengan demikian perngembangan terhadap aplikasi program pedeteksi kerusakan pada mesin ERTIGA ini sepatutnya diperlukan pembelajaran lebih lanjut lagi, agar menjadi lebih baik lagi.

LISTING PROGRAM

APLIKASI PROGRAM SISTEM PAKAR PENDETEKSI KERUSAKAN DINI MESIN SUZUKI ALL NEW ERTIGA BENSIN MENGGUNAKAN METODE FORWARD CHAINING

Script Login

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en" >

<head>
  <meta charset="UTF-8">
  <title>Login Admin</title>
  <link rel="stylesheet" href="css/style-admin.css">
  <link rel="stylesheet" href="css/font-awesome.min.css" type="text/css">
</head>
<body>
<div class="container">
  <div class="info">
    <h1>Login Admin</h1>
  </div>
</div>
<div class="form">
  <div class="thumbnail">
    
  </div>
  <form role="form" method="post" data-toggle="validator" action="ceklogin.php">
    <input type="text" class="form-control" name="username" id="password" maxlength="6"
placeholder="Username">
    <input type="password" class="form-control" name="password" id="password" maxlength="6"
placeholder="Password">
    <button type="submit" id="submit" nama="submit" method="post">Login</button>
    <p class="message">Kembali ke <a href="index.php">Home</a></p>
  </form>
</div>
</body>
</html>
```

Script Salah Login

```
<?php
include('koneksi.php');
$username= $_POST['username'];
$password=$_POST['password'];
$error="";
session_start();
  if (mysqli_connect_errno()) {
    printf("Connect failed: %s\n", mysqli_connect_error());
    exit();
  }
$query = "SELECT * FROM admin WHERE username='$username' and password='$password'";
```

```

$result = $konek_db->query($query) or die($konek_db->error.__LINE__);
if($result->num_rows > 0) {
    session_start();
    $_SESSION['login_user']=$username;
    header('location:admin/homeadmin.php');
}
else {
    header('location:salahlogin.php');
}
?>

```

Script Salah Login

```

<?php
echo '<script type="text/javascript">';
echo 'alert("USERNAME & PASSWORD SALAH ...!");';
echo 'window.location.href = "login.php";';
echo '</script>';
?>

```

Script Connection

```

<?php
//membuat koneksi ke database
$host = 'localhost';
$user = 'root';
$password = '';
$database = 'dbpakarertiga';
$konek_db = mysqli_connect($host, $user, $password, $database);
?>

```

Script Session

```

<?php
include "koneksi.php";
session_start();// Starting Session // Storing Session
$user_check=$_SESSION['login_user'];
$sql="select * from admin where username='$user_check'";
$ses=mysqli_query($konek_db,$sql);
$row =mysqli_fetch_assoc($ses);
if(!isset($_SESSION)){
    echo"$user_check";
}
?>

```

Script Index

```

<?php
include('koneksi.php');

if(isset($_SESSION['login_user'])){

```

```
//header("location: about.php");
}
?>
```

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">
```

```
<head>
```

```
<meta charset="utf-8">
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1, shrink-to-fit=no">
<meta name="description" content="">
<meta name="author" content="">
```

```
<title>Sistem Pakar All New Ertiga Bensin</title>
```

```
<!-- Bootstrap core CSS -->
<link href="vendor/bootstrap/css/bootstrap.min.css" rel="stylesheet">
```

```
<!-- Custom styles for this template -->
<link href="css/modern-business.css" rel="stylesheet">
```

```
</head>
```

```
<body>
```

```
<?php include 'navigasimenu.php';?>
```

```
<header>
```

```
<div id="carouselExampleIndicators" class="carousel slide" data-ride="carousel">
```

```
<ol class="carousel-indicators">
```

```
<li data-target="#carouselExampleIndicators" data-slide-to="0" class="active"></li>
```

```
<li data-target="#carouselExampleIndicators" data-slide-to="1"></li>
```

```
<li data-target="#carouselExampleIndicators" data-slide-to="2"></li>
```

```
</ol>
```

```
<div class="carousel-inner" role="listbox">
```

```
<!-- Slide One - Set the background image for this slide in the line below -->
```

```
<div class="carousel-item active" style="background-image: url('images/slider-00.jpg')">
```

```
<div class="carousel-caption d-none d-md-block">
```

```
<h3></h3>
```

```
<p></p>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<!-- Slide Two - Set the background image for this slide in the line below -->
```

```
<div class="carousel-item" style="background-image: url('images/slider-01.jpg')">
```

```
<div class="carousel-caption d-none d-md-block">
```

```
<h3>Suzuki All New Ertiga Bensin</h3>
```

```
<p></p>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<!-- Slide Three - Set the background image for this slide in the line below -->
```

```
<div class="carousel-item" style="background-image: url('images/slider-02.jpg')">
```

```

        <div class="carousel-caption d-none d-md-block">
            <h3>Suzuki All New Ertiga Bensin</h3>
            <p></p>
        </div>
    </div>
    </div>
    <a class="carousel-control-prev" href="#carouselExampleIndicators" role="button" data-
slide="prev">
        <span class="carousel-control-prev-icon" aria-hidden="true"></span>
        <span class="sr-only">Previous</span>
    </a>
    <a class="carousel-control-next" href="#carouselExampleIndicators" role="button" data-
slide="next">
        <span class="carousel-control-next-icon" aria-hidden="true"></span>
        <span class="sr-only">Next</span>
    </a>
</div>
</header>

```

```
<!-- Page Content -->
```

```
<div class="container">
```

```

    <h1 class="my-4">SELAMAT DATANG DI SISTEM PAKAR PENDETEKSI KERUSAKAN DINI MESIN
SUZUKI ALL NEW ERTIGA BENSIN </h1>

```

```
<!-- Features Section -->
```

```
<div class="row">
```

```

    <div class="col-lg-12">

```

```

        <p align="justify">Website sistem pakar ini bertujuan untuk memberikan kemudahan bagi
masyarakat dalam pendeteksi kerusakan untuk mobil Suzuki All New Ertiga Bensin. Sistem pakar ini
berdasarkan pengetahuan dari seorang pakar (Mekanik, Forman, dan Service Advisor) yang biasa
menangani kerusakan dari mobil Suzuki All New Ertiga Bensin.

```

```

Untuk melakukan proses pendeteksi kerusakannya caranya cukup mudah, yaitu pengguna cukup
memilih gejala-gejala yang mungkin dirasakannya pada mobilnya. Setelah itu sistem akan
menampilkan hasil kerusakan dari mobil tersebut.</p>

```

```

<strong>Jenis kerusakan mobil Suzuki All New Ertiga Bensin yang di identifikasi, yaitu&nbsp;
:</strong>

```

```

    <ol>

```

```

        <?php

```

```

            $kendaraan = mysqli_query($koneksi_db, "SELECT * from kerusakan");

```

```

            $no=1;

```

```

            foreach ($kendaraan as $row){

```

```

                echo "<li>".$row['namakerusakan']."</li>";

```

```

                $no++;

```

```

            }

```

```

        ?>

```

```

    </ol>

```

```

</div>

```

```

<div class="col-lg-6">

```

```

        <!-- -->
    </div>
</div>
<!-- /.row -->
<hr>
<!-- Call to Action Section -->
<div class="row mb-4">
    <div class="col-md-8">
        <p>Untuk Mengidentifikasi Kerusakan pada mobil anda silakan klik button PENDETEKSI
KERUSAKAN</p>
    </div>
    <div class="col-md-4">
        <a class="btn btn-lg btn-secondary btn-block" href="diagnosaertiga.php">PENDETEKSI
KERUSAKAN</a>
    </div>
</div>
</div>
<!-- /.container -->
<?php include 'footer1.php';?>

```

Script Header

```

<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">
<head>
<title>Sistem Pakar Identifikasi Kerusakan Toyota Avanza</title>
<meta charset="utf-8">
<meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/bootstrap.css">
<link rel="stylesheet" href="css/style.css">
<link href="css/dataTables.bootstrap4.css" rel="stylesheet">
<link rel="stylesheet prefetch'
href='https://fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Roboto:400,100,300,500,700,900'>
</head>
<body>
<div class="container wrapper">
<div class="row banner">

</div>

```

Script Navigasi Menu

```

<!-- Navigation -->
<nav class="navbar fixed-top navbar-expand-lg navbar-dark bg-dark fixed-top">
    <div class="container">
        <a class="navbar-brand" href="index.php">Pakar All New Ertiga Bensin</a>
        <button class="navbar-toggler navbar-toggler-right" type="button" data-toggle="collapse" data-
target="#navbarResponsive" aria-controls="navbarResponsive" aria-expanded="false" aria-
label="Toggle navigation">
            <span class="navbar-toggler-icon"></span>
        </button>

```

```

<div class="collapse navbar-collapse" id="navbarResponsive">
  <ul class="navbar-nav ml-auto">
    <li class="nav-item">
      <a class="nav-link" href="index.php">Beranda</a>
    </li>
    <li class="nav-item">
      <a class="nav-link" href="diagnosaertiga.php">Pendeteksi Kerusakan</a>
    </li>
    <li class="nav-item">
      <a class="nav-link" href="daftarkerusakan.php">Info Kerusakan</a>      </li>
    </ul>
  </div>
</div>
</nav>

```

Script Footer

```

<!-- Footer -->
<footer class="py-5 bg-dark">
  <div class="container">
    <p class="m-0 text-center text-white">Copyright &copy; Yosep Adi Candra 2018</p>
  </div>
<!-- /.container -->
</footer>
<!-- Bootstrap core JavaScript -->
<script src="vendor/jquery/jquery.min.js"></script>
<script src="vendor/bootstrap/js/bootstrap.bundle.min.js"></script>
</body>
</html>

```

Script Daftar Kerusakan

```

<?php
include('koneksi.php');
if(isset($_SESSION['login_user'])){
//header("location: about.php");
}
?>
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">
<head>
  <meta charset="utf-8">
  <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1, shrink-to-fit=no">
  <meta name="description" content="">
  <meta name="author" content="">

  <title>Sistem Pakar All New Ertiga</title>
  <!-- Bootstrap core CSS -->
  <link href="vendor/bootstrap/css/bootstrap.min.css" rel="stylesheet">

  <!-- Custom styles for this template -->

```

```

<link href="css/modern-business.css" rel="stylesheet">
</head>
<body>
  <?php include 'navigasimenu.php';?>
  <header>
  </header>
  <!-- Page Content -->
  <div class="container">
    <h1 class="my-4">SELAMAT DATANG DI SISTEM PAKAR IDENTIFIKASI KERUSAKAN MOBIL SUZUKI
    ALL NEW ERTIGA BENSIN</h1>
    <!-- Features Section -->
    <div class="row">
      <div class="col-lg-12">
<div class="container-fluid text-center">
  <div class="row content">

    <div class="col-sm-9 text-left">
      <h3 class="head-title">DAFTAR KERUSAKAN MOBIL SUZUKI ALL NEW ERTIGA BENSIN</h3>

    <div class="panel panel-info">
      <div class="panel-heading"></div>
      <div class="panel-body">
        <div class="box-body table-responsive">
          <table id="example" class="table table-bordered table-striped">
            <thead>
              <tr>
                <th>NO</th>
                <th>ID Kerusakan</th>
                <th>Nama Kerusakan</th>
                <th>Jenis Kendaraan</th>
                <th>Detail</th>
              </tr>
            </thead>

            <?php
            $kendaraan = mysqli_query($koneksi_db, "SELECT * from kerusakan");
            $no=1;
            foreach ($kendaraan as $row){
              echo "<tr>
                <td>$no</td>
                <td>".$row['idkerusakan'].</td>
                <td>".$row['namakerusakan'].</td>
                <td>".$row['jeniskendaraan'].</td>
                <td><a href=\"detailkerusakan.php?id=\".$row['idkerusakan'].\"><i class='glyphicon
glyphicon-search'> Detail</i></a>\".</td>
              </tr>";
              $no++;
            }
            ?>
          </table>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>

```

```

        </div>
    </div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
<p align="justify">&nbsp;</p>
</div>
    <div class="col-lg-6">
        <!-- -->
    </div>
</div>
<!-- /.row -->
<hr>
<!-- Call to Action Section -->
</div>
<!-- /.container -->
<?php include 'footer1.php';?>

```

Script Diagnosis

```

<?php
include('koneksi.php');
if(isset($_SESSION['login_user'])){}
?>
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">
<head>
    <meta charset="utf-8">
    <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1, shrink-to-fit=no">
    <meta name="description" content="">
    <meta name="author" content="">
    <title>Sistem Pakar All New Ertiga Bensin</title>
    <!-- Bootstrap core CSS -->
    <link href="vendor/bootstrap/css/bootstrap.min.css" rel="stylesheet">
    <!-- Custom styles for this template -->
    <link href="css/modern-business.css" rel="stylesheet">
</head>
<body>
    <?php include 'navigasimenu.php';?>
    <header>
</header>
    <!-- Page Content -->
    <div class="container">
        <h1 class="my-4">SELAMAT DATANG DI SISTEM PAKAR PENDETEKSI KERUSAKAN MOBIL SUZUKI
ALL NEW ERTIGA BENSIN</h1>
        <!-- Features Section -->
        <div class="row">
            <div class="col-lg-12">
                <h3 class="head-title">PENDETEKSI KERUSAKAN</h3>
                <form id="form1" name="form1" method="post" action="diagnosaertiga.php">
                    <label for="sel1">Jenis Kendaraan</label>

```

```

<select class="form-control" name="kendaraan" onChange='this.form.submit();'>
  <option>All New Ertiga</option>
  <option>All New Ertiga</option>
</select>
</form>
<form id="form2" name="form2" method="post" action="diagnosaertiga.php">
  <div class="form-group">

    <?php
      if(isset($_POST['kendaraan']))
        if($_POST['kendaraan']!="jeniskendaraan")
          {
            echo "<br><label>Pilih Gejala</label><br>";
            $stampil="select * from gejala where jeniskendaraan= \"".$_POST['kendaraan']."\"";
            $query= mysqli_query($koneksi,$stampil);
            while($hasil=mysqli_fetch_array($query))
            {
              echo "<input type='checkbox' value=\"".$hasil['gejala']."' name='gejala[]' />
                [\".$hasil['idgejala'].\"] - ".$hasil['gejala']."<br>";
            }
          }
    ?>

    </div>
    <button type="submit" name="submit" onClick="return checkDiagnosa()" class="btn btn-
primary">CEK KERUSAKAN</button><br><br>
    <div class="panel panel-info">
      <div class="panel-heading">HASIL KERUSAKAN</div>
      <div class="panel-body">
        <div class="box-body table-responsive">
          <table id="example" class="table table-bordered table-striped">
            <thead>
              <tr>
                <th>ID Kerusakan</th>
                <th>Nama Kerusakan</th>
                <th>Jenis Kendaraan</th>
                <th>Detail</th>
              </tr>
            </thead>
            <?php
              if(isset($_POST['submit'])){
                $gejala = $_POST['gejala'];
                $jumlah_dipilih = count($gejala);
                for($x=0;$x<$jumlah_dipilih;$x++){
                  $stampil ="Select DISTINCT p.idkerusakan, p.namakerusakan, p.jeniskendaraan from
basispengetahuan b, kerusakan p where b.gejala='$gejala[$x]' and
p.namakerusakan=b.namakerusakan group by namakerusakan";
                  $result = mysqli_query($koneksi, $stampil);
                  $hasil = mysqli_fetch_array($result);
                }
                echo "
                <tr>

```

```

                <td>".$hasil['idkerusakan']. "</td>
                <td>".$hasil['namakerusakan']. "</td>
                <td>".$hasil['jeniskendaraan']. "</td>
                <td><a href=\"detailkerusakan.php?id=\".$hasil['idkerusakan']. \"><i
class='glyphicon glyphicon-search'></i>Detail</a></td>
            </tr>
        }
        ?>
    </table>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</form>
<p align="justify">&nbsp;</p>
</div>
<div class="col-lg-6">
    <!-- -->
</div>
</div>
<!-- /.row -->
<hr>
<!-- Call to Action Section -->
</div>
<!-- /.container -->
<?php include 'footer1.php';?>

```

Script Detail Kerusakan

```

<?php
include('koneksi.php');

if(isset($_SESSION['login_user'])){
header("location: about.php");
}
?>
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">

<head>

    <meta charset="utf-8">
    <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1, shrink-to-fit=no">
    <meta name="description" content="">
    <meta name="author" content="">

    <title>Sistem Pakar All New Ertiga</title>

    <!-- Bootstrap core CSS -->
    <link href="vendor/bootstrap/css/bootstrap.min.css" rel="stylesheet">

    <!-- Custom styles for this template -->

```

```

<link href="css/modern-business.css" rel="stylesheet">

</head>

<body>

    <?php include 'navigasimenu.php';?>
    <header>

    </header>

    <!-- Page Content -->
    <div class="container">

        <h1 class="my-4">SELAMAT DATANG DI SISTEM PAKAR IDENTIFIKASI KERUSAKAN MOBIL SUZUKI
        ALL NEW ERTIGA BENSIN</h1>

        <!-- Features Section -->
        <div class="row">
            <div class="col-lg-12">

<div class="container-fluid text-center">
<div class="row content">
<div class="col-sm-12 text-left">
<h3 class="head-title">DETAIL KERUSAKAN</h3>

<div class="panel panel-info">
<div class="panel-heading">Detail Kerusakan</div>
<div class="panel-body">
<div class="box-body table-responsive form-horizontal">

<div class="form-group" method="POST">
<div class="form-row">
    <label class="control-label col-sm-2">ID Kerusakan :</label>
    <div class="col-sm-10">
        <?php
            $stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan where idkerusakan='".$$_GET['id'].'"";
            $sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
            while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
            {
                echo "<input type='text' class='form-control' id='idkerusakan' readonly
value='".$data['idkerusakan']."'>";
            }
        ?>
    </div>
</div>
</div>
</div>

<div class="form-group" method="POST">
<div class="form-row">
    <label class="control-label col-sm-2">Nama Kerusakan :</label>

```

```

<div class="col-sm-10">
  <?php
    $stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan where idkerusakan='".$_$_GET['id']."'";
    $sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
    while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
    {
      echo "<input type='text' class='form-control' id='namakerusakan' readonly
value='".$_$_data['namakerusakan']."'>";
    }
  ?>
</div>
</div>

<div class="form-group" method="POST">
<div class="form-row">
  <label class="control-label col-sm-2">Jenis Kendaraan :</label>
  <div class="col-sm-10">
    <?php
      $stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan where idkerusakan='".$_$_GET['id']."'";
      $sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
      while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
      {
        echo "<input type='text' class='form-control' id='jeniskendaraan' readonly
value='".$_$_data['jeniskendaraan']."'>";
      }
    ?>
  </div>
</div>
</div>

<div class="form-group" method="POST">
<div class="form-row">
  <label class="control-label col-sm-2">Gejala :</label>
  <div class="col-sm-10">
    <?php
      $stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan p, basispengetahuan b where
p.idkerusakan='".$_$_GET['id']."' and p.namakerusakan=b.namakerusakan";
      $sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
      while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
      {
        echo "<input type='text' class='form-control' id='jeniskendaraan' readonly
value='".$_$_data['gejala']."'><br>";
      }
      echo "<input type='text' class='form-control' id='jeniskendaraan' readonly value=''><br>";
    ?>
  </div>
</div>
</div>
<div class="form-group" method="POST">
<div class="form-row">

```



```
{
  "name": "startbootstrap-modern-business",
  "version": "4.1.1",
  "lockfileVersion": 1,
  "requires": true,
  "dependencies": {
    "accepts": {
      "version": "1.3.5",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/accepts/-/accepts-1.3.5.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-63d99gEXl6OxTopywIBcjoZ0a9I=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "mime-types": "~2.1.18",
        "negotiator": "0.6.1"
      }
    },
    "after": {
      "version": "0.8.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/after/-/after-0.8.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-ts5T58OAqqXaOcCval7UF+ufh8=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "ansi-gray": {
      "version": "0.1.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/ansi-gray/-/ansi-gray-0.1.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-KWLPVOyXksSFEKPetSRDaGHvclE=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "ansi-wrap": "0.1.0"
      }
    },
    "ansi-regex": {
      "version": "2.1.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/ansi-regex/-/ansi-regex-2.1.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-w7M6te42DYbg5ijwRorn7yfWVN8=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "ansi-styles": {
      "version": "2.2.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/ansi-styles/-/ansi-styles-2.2.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-tDLdM1i2NM914eRmQ2gkBTPB3b4=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "ansi-wrap": {
      "version": "0.1.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/ansi-wrap/-/ansi-wrap-0.1.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-qCJQ3bABXponyoLoLqYDu/pF768=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "anymatch": {

```

```
    "version": "1.3.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/anymatch/-/anymatch-1.3.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-0XNayC8ITHQ2OI8aljNCN3sSx6hsr/1+rlcDAotXJR7C1oZZHCNsfpbKwMjRA3Uqb5tF1Rae2oloTr4xpq+WjA==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "micromatch": "^2.1.5",
      "normalize-path": "^2.0.0"
    }
  },
  "archy": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/archy/-/archy-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-+cjbN1fMHde8N5rHeyxipckGjEA=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "arr-diff": {
    "version": "2.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/arr-diff/-/arr-diff-2.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-jzuCf5Vai9ZpaX5KQlasPOrjVs8=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "arr-flatten": "^1.0.1"
    }
  },
  "arr-flatten": {
    "version": "1.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/arr-flatten/-/arr-flatten-1.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-L3hKV5R/p5o81R7O02IGnwpDm6E982XhtbuwSe3O4qOtMMMtodicaSA1Cny2U+aCXcNpml+m4dPsvsJ3jatg==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "arr-union": {
    "version": "3.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/arr-union/-/arr-union-3.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-45sJrqne+Gao8gbiiK9jkZuuOcQ=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "array-differ": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/array-differ/-/array-differ-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-7/UuN1gknTO+QCuLuOVkuytdQDE=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "array-each": {
    "version": "1.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/array-each/-/array-each-1.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-p5SvDAWrF1KEbudToflRoFugxE8=",
    "dev": true
  }
```

```

    },
    "array-slice": {
      "version": "1.1.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/array-slice/-/array-slice-1.1.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-B1qMD3RBP7O8o0H2KbrXDyB0lccejMF15+87Lvlor12ONPRHP6gTjXMNkt/d3ZuOGbAe66hFmaCfECI24Ufp6w==",
      "dev": true
    },
    },
    "array-uniq": {
      "version": "1.0.3",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/array-uniq/-/array-uniq-1.0.3.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-r2ld6Jcx/dOBYiUdThY39sk/bY=",
      "dev": true
    },
    },
    "array-unique": {
      "version": "0.2.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/array-unique/-/array-unique-0.2.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-odl8yvy8JiXMcPrc6zalDFiwGIM=",
      "dev": true
    },
    },
    "arraybuffer.slice": {
      "version": "0.0.7",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/arraybuffer.slice/-/arraybuffer.slice-0.0.7.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-wGUIVQXuehL5TCqQun8OW81jGzAWycqzFF8IFp+GOM5BXLyJ3bKNsYC4daB7n6XjCqxQA/qgTJ+8ANR3acjrog==",
      "dev": true
    },
    },
    "assign-symbols": {
      "version": "1.0.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/assign-symbols/-/assign-symbols-1.0.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-WWZ/QfrdTyDMvCu5a41Pf3jsA2c=",
      "dev": true
    },
    },
    "async": {
      "version": "1.5.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/async/-/async-1.5.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-7GphrlZIDAww8skHJVhjiCJL5Zyo=",
      "dev": true
    },
    },
    "async-each": {
      "version": "1.0.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/async-each/-/async-each-1.0.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-GdOGodntxufByF04iu28xW0zYCO=",
      "dev": true
    },
    },
    "async-each-series": {
      "version": "0.1.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/async-each-series/-/async-each-series-0.1.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-dhfBkXQB/Yykooqtzj266Yr+tDI=",

```

```

    "dev": true
  },
  "async-limiter": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/async-limiter/-/async-limiter-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-jp/ufNooOiO+L211eZOoSyzpOITMx1rBITauYykG3BRYPu8h0UcxsPNB04RR5vo4Tyz3+ay17tR6JVf9qz
YWg==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "atob": {
    "version": "2.1.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/atob/-/atob-2.1.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-ri1acpR38onWDDf5amMUoi3Wwio=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "axios": {
    "version": "0.17.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/axios/-/axios-0.17.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-LY4+XQvb1zJ/kbyBT1xXZg+Bgk0=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "follow-redirects": "^1.2.5",
      "is-buffer": "^1.1.5"
    }
  },
  "backo2": {
    "version": "1.0.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/backo2/-/backo2-1.0.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-MasayLEpNjRj41s+u2n038+6eUc=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "balanced-match": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/balanced-match/-/balanced-match-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-ibTRmasr7kneFk6gK4nORi1xt2c=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "base": {
    "version": "0.11.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/base/-/base-0.11.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-5T6P4xPgpp0YDFvSWwEZ4NoE3aM4QBQXDzmVbraCkFj8zHM+mba8SyqB5DbZWYR7mYHo6Y7BdQo
3MoA4m0TeQg==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "cache-base": "^1.0.1",
      "class-utils": "^0.3.5",
      "component-emitter": "^1.2.1",
      "define-property": "^1.0.0",
      "isobject": "^3.0.1",

```

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    "mixin-deep": "^1.2.0",
    "pascalcase": "^0.1.1"
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "define-property": {
      "version": "1.0.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/define-property/-/define-property-1.0.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-dp66rz9KY6rTr56NMEybnm/sOY=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "is-descriptor": "^1.0.0"
      }
    },
    "is-accessor-descriptor": {
      "version": "1.0.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-accessor-descriptor/-/is-accessor-descriptor-1.0.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-m5hnHTkcvSPfpx3AKlytIPb7J+XykHvJP2B9bZDjlhLloEq4XoK64Vg7boZIVWYK6LUY94dYPEE7Lh0ZkZKcQ==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "kind-of": "^6.0.0"
      }
    },
    "is-data-descriptor": {
      "version": "1.0.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-data-descriptor/-/is-data-descriptor-1.0.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-jbRXY1FmtAoCjQkVmlIVywuqDFUbaOeDjmed1tOGPrsMhtJA4rD9tkgA0F1qJ3gRFRXcHYVkleaP50Q5rE/jLQ==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "kind-of": "^6.0.0"
      }
    },
    "is-descriptor": {
      "version": "1.0.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-descriptor/-/is-descriptor-1.0.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-2eis5WqQGV7peooDyLmNEPurps9+SXX5c9pL3xEB+4e9HnGuDa7mB7kHxHw4CbqS9k1T2hOH3miL8n8WtiYVtg==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "is-accessor-descriptor": "^1.0.0",
        "is-data-descriptor": "^1.0.0",
        "kind-of": "^6.0.2"
      }
    },
    "isobject": {
      "version": "3.0.1",

```

```
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isobject/-/isobject-3.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-TkMekrEalzFjaqH5yNHMvP2reN8=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "kind-of": {
    "version": "6.0.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-6.0.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-SVAeR3xh3G+00TjVwLfr32tT8L1vW4eLW4e2rvM0rwUq0t8IQDOWYSeLK01U900jz
s5kLOcnH0XqDO+FvuaLX8DDJz18CGFk7VYgH40QoKPUQhW4e2rvM0rwUq0t8IQDOWYSeLK01U900jz
BTme2QqA==",
    "dev": true
  }
},
"base64-arraybuffer": {
  "version": "0.1.5",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/base64-arraybuffer/-/base64-arraybuffer-0.1.5.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-c5JncZ17Whl0etZmqLzUv5xunOg=",
  "dev": true
},
"base64id": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/base64id/-/base64id-1.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-R2iMuZu2gE8OBtPnY7HDLIfY5rY=",
  "dev": true
},
"batch": {
  "version": "0.6.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/batch/-/batch-0.6.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-3DQxT05nkxgJP8dgJyUl+UvyXBY=",
  "dev": true
},
"beeper": {
  "version": "1.1.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/beeper/-/beeper-1.1.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-5tXqjF2tABMEpwsiy4RH9ppy+Ak=",
  "dev": true
},
"better-assert": {
  "version": "1.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/better-assert/-/better-assert-1.0.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-QIZrnhueC1W0gYIDEeaPr/rrxSI=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "callsite": "1.0.0"
  }
},
"binary-extensions": {
  "version": "1.11.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/binary-extensions/-/binary-extensions-1.11.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-RqoXUftqL5PuXmibsQh9SxTGwU=",
```

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    "dev": true
  },
  "blob": {
    "version": "0.0.4",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/blob/-/blob-0.0.4.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-vPEwUspURj8w+fx+lbnkdjCpSSE=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "bootstrap": {
    "version": "4.1.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/bootstrap/-/bootstrap-4.1.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-SpiDSOcbg4J/PjVSt4ny5eY6j74VbVSjROY4Fb/WIUXBV9cnb5luyR4KnPvNoXuGnBK1T+nJIWqRsvU3yP8Mcg=="
  },
  "brace-expansion": {
    "version": "1.1.8",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/brace-expansion/-/brace-expansion-1.1.8.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-wHshHHyVLsH479Uad+8NHTmQopl=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "balanced-match": "^1.0.0",
      "concat-map": "0.0.1"
    }
  },
  "braces": {
    "version": "1.8.5",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/braces/-/braces-1.8.5.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-uneWLhLf+WnWt2cR6RS3N4V79qc=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "expand-range": "^1.8.1",
      "preserve": "^0.2.0",
      "repeat-element": "^1.1.2"
    }
  },
  "browser-sync": {
    "version": "2.24.5",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/browser-sync/-/browser-sync-2.24.5.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-r6ZRYncfYRGerw4Rh5S8Q9x9WKDdrwH572hd3ofsYgn0Px6a6EqXiLBVTCss2+2a45G9ZgjRHSeo9YY56UpgKw==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "browser-sync-ui": "v1.0.1",
      "bs-recipes": "1.3.4",
      "chokidar": "1.7.0",
      "connect": "3.6.6",
      "connect-history-api-fallback": "^1.5.0",
      "dev-ip": "^1.0.1",
      "easy-extender": "2.3.2",

```

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    "eazy-logger": "3.0.2",
    "etag": "^1.8.1",
    "fresh": "^0.5.2",
    "fs-extra": "3.0.1",
    "http-proxy": "1.15.2",
    "immutable": "3.8.2",
    "localtunnel": "1.9.0",
    "micromatch": "2.3.11",
    "opn": "4.0.2",
    "portscanner": "2.1.1",
    "qs": "6.2.3",
    "raw-body": "^2.3.2",
    "resp-modifier": "6.0.2",
    "rx": "4.1.0",
    "serve-index": "1.9.1",
    "serve-static": "1.13.2",
    "server-destroy": "1.0.1",
    "socket.io": "2.1.1",
    "ua-parser-js": "0.7.17",
    "yargs": "6.4.0"
  }
},
"browser-sync-ui": {
  "version": "1.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/browser-sync-ui/-/browser-sync-ui-1.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-
RlXmwVvCUFhRd1zxp7m2FfLnXHf59x4Gtj8HFwTA//3VgYI3AKkaQAuDL8KDJnE59XqCshxZa13JYuIWtZ
IKQg==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "async-each-series": "0.1.1",
    "connect-history-api-fallback": "^1.1.0",
    "immutable": "^3.7.6",
    "server-destroy": "1.0.1",
    "socket.io-client": "2.0.4",
    "stream-throttle": "^0.1.3"
  }
},
"bs-recipes": {
  "version": "1.3.4",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/bs-recipes/-/bs-recipes-1.3.4.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-DS1NSKcYyMBEdp/ct4IZLci2IYU=",
  "dev": true
},
"builtin-modules": {
  "version": "1.1.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/builtin-modules/-/builtin-modules-1.1.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-Jw8HbFpywC9bZaR9+Uxf46J4iS8=",
  "dev": true
},
"bytes": {

```

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    "version": "3.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/bytes/-/bytes-3.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-0ygVQE1olpn4Wk6k+odV3ROpYEg=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "cache-base": {
    "version": "1.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/cache-base/-/cache-base-1.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-
AKcdTnFSWATd5/GCPRxr2ChwIj85CeyrEyjRHlKxQ56d4XJMGym0uAiKn0xbLOGOl3+yRpOTi484dVCEc
5AUzQ==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "collection-visit": "^1.0.0",
      "component-emitter": "^1.2.1",
      "get-value": "^2.0.6",
      "has-value": "^1.0.0",
      "isobject": "^3.0.1",
      "set-value": "^2.0.0",
      "to-object-path": "^0.3.0",
      "union-value": "^1.0.0",
      "unset-value": "^1.0.0"
    }
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "isobject": {
      "version": "3.0.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isobject/-/isobject-3.0.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-TkMekrEalzFjaqH5yNHMvP2reN8=",
      "dev": true
    }
  }
},
"callsite": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/callsite/-/callsite-1.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-KAOY5dZkvXQDi28JBRU+borxvCA=",
  "dev": true
},
"camelcase": {
  "version": "3.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/camelcase/-/camelcase-3.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-MvxLn82vhF/N9+c7uXysImHwqwo=",
  "dev": true
},
"chalk": {
  "version": "1.1.3",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/chalk/-/chalk-1.1.3.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-qBFcVeSnAv5NFQq9OHKCKn4J/Jg=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "ansi-styles": "^2.2.1",

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    "escape-string-regexp": "^1.0.2",
    "has-ansi": "^2.0.0",
    "strip-ansi": "^3.0.0",
    "supports-color": "^2.0.0"
  }
},
"chokidar": {
  "version": "1.7.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/chokidar/-/chokidar-1.7.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-eY5ol3gVHIB2tLN5e3SjNortGg=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "anymatch": "^1.3.0",
    "async-each": "^1.0.0",
    "fsevents": "^1.0.0",
    "glob-parent": "^2.0.0",
    "inherits": "^2.0.1",
    "is-binary-path": "^1.0.0",
    "is-glob": "^2.0.0",
    "path-is-absolute": "^1.0.0",
    "readdirp": "^2.0.0"
  }
},
"class-utils": {
  "version": "0.3.6",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/class-utils/-/class-utils-0.3.6.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-qOhPa/Fj7s6TY8H8esGu5QNpMMQxz79h+urzrNYN6mn+9BnxIDGf5QZ+XeCDsxSjPqsSR56XOZOJmpeurnLMeg==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "arr-union": "^3.1.0",
    "define-property": "^0.2.5",
    "isobject": "^3.0.0",
    "static-extend": "^0.1.1"
  }
},
"dependencies": {
  "define-property": {
    "version": "0.2.5",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/define-property/-/define-property-0.2.5.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-w1se+RjsPJKPmlvFe+BKrOxcgRY=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-descriptor": "^0.1.0"
    }
  }
},
"isobject": {
  "version": "3.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isobject/-/isobject-3.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-TkMekrEalzFjaqH5yNHMvP2reN8=",
  "dev": true
}

```

```

    }
  }
},
"cliui": {
  "version": "3.2.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/cliui/-/cliui-3.2.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-EgYBU3qRbSmUD5NNo7SNWFo5IT0=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "string-width": "^1.0.1",
    "strip-ansi": "^3.0.1",
    "wrap-ansi": "^2.0.0"
  }
},
"clone": {
  "version": "1.0.4",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/clone/-/clone-1.0.4.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-2jCcwmpPfFZIMalypAheco8fNfH4=",
  "dev": true
},
"clone-stats": {
  "version": "0.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/clone-stats/-/clone-stats-0.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-ul+UqCzzi4eR1YBG6kAprYjKmdE=",
  "dev": true
},
"code-point-at": {
  "version": "1.1.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/code-point-at/-/code-point-at-1.1.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-DQcLTQQ6W+ozovGkDi7bPZpMz3c=",
  "dev": true
},
"collection-visit": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/collection-visit/-/collection-visit-1.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-S8A3PBZLwykbTTaMgpzxqApZ3KA=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "map-visit": "^1.0.0",
    "object-visit": "^1.0.0"
  }
},
"color-support": {
  "version": "1.1.3",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/color-support/-/color-support-1.1.3.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-qiBjkpbMLO/HL68y+lh4q0/O1MZfj2RX6X/KmMa3+gJD3z+Wwl1ZzDHysvqHGS3mP6mznPckpXmw1nI9cJyRg==",
  "dev": true
},
"commander": {

```

```
    "version": "2.16.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/commander/-/commander-2.16.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-sVXqkLSaotK9at437sFIFpyOcJonxe0yST/AG9DkQKUDIE6lqGIMv4SfAQSKaJbSdVEJYItASCrBiVQHq1HQ
ew==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "component-bind": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/component-bind/-/component-bind-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-AMyIq33Nk4l8AAllGx06jh5zu9E=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "component-emitter": {
    "version": "1.2.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/component-emitter/-/component-emitter-1.2.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-E3kY1teCg/ffemt8WmPhQOaUJeY=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "component-inherit": {
    "version": "0.0.3",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/component-inherit/-/component-inherit-0.0.3.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-ZF/ErfWLcrZJ1crmUTVhnbJv8UM=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "concat-map": {
    "version": "0.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/concat-map/-/concat-map-0.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-2Klr13/Wjfd5OnMDajug1UBdR3s=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "connect": {
    "version": "3.6.6",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/connect/-/connect-3.6.6.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Ce/2xVr3l24TcTWnJXSFieG9SQ=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "debug": "2.6.9",
      "finalhandler": "1.1.0",
      "parseurl": "~1.3.2",
      "utils-merge": "1.0.1"
    }
  },
  "connect-history-api-fallback": {
    "version": "1.5.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/connect-history-api-fallback/-/connect-history-api-fallback-1.5.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-sGhzk0vF40T+9hGhlqb6rgruAVo=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "cookie": {
```

```

    "version": "0.3.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/cookie/-/cookie-0.3.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-5+Ch+e9DtMi6klxcWpboBtFoc7s=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "copy-descriptor": {
    "version": "0.1.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/copy-descriptor/-/copy-descriptor-0.1.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Z29us8OZl8LuGsOpJP1hHSPV40=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "core-util-is": {
    "version": "1.0.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/core-util-is/-/core-util-is-1.0.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-tf1UlgqivFq1eqtxQMlAdUUDwac=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "dateformat": {
    "version": "2.2.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/dateformat/-/dateformat-2.2.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-QGXiATz5+5Ft39gu+1Bq1MZ2kGI=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "debug": {
    "version": "2.6.9",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/debug/-/debug-2.6.9.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-bC7EldJnJnPbAP+1EotYvqZsb3ecl5wi6Bfi6BJTUcNowp6cvspg0jXznRTKDjm/E7AdgFBVeAPVMNcKGs
HMA==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "ms": "2.0.0"
    }
  },
  "decamelize": {
    "version": "1.2.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/decamelize/-/decamelize-1.2.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-9INNFRSCabIDUue+4m9QH5oZEpA=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "decode-uri-component": {
    "version": "0.2.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/decode-uri-component/-/decode-uri-component-
0.2.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-6zkTMzRYd1y4TNGh+uBiEGu4dUU=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "defaults": {
    "version": "1.0.3",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/defaults/-/defaults-1.0.3.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-xlYFHpgX2f8I7YgUd/P+QBnz730=",

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"dev": true,
"requires": {
  "clone": "^1.0.2"
},
"define-property": {
  "version": "2.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/define-property/-/define-property-2.0.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-jwK2UV4cnPpbCG7+VRARKTZPUWowwXA8bzH5NP6ud0oeAxyYPuGZUAC7hMugpCdz4BeSZI2DI9k66CHJ/46ZYQ==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "is-descriptor": "^1.0.2",
    "isobject": "^3.0.1"
},
"dependencies": {
  "is-accessor-descriptor": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-accessor-descriptor/-/is-accessor-descriptor-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-m5hnHTkcVsPfqx3AKlyttIPb7J+XykHvJP2B9bZDjlhLloEq4XoK64Vg7boZIVVWYK6LUY94dYPEE7Lh0ZkZKcQ==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "kind-of": "^6.0.0"
    }
},
"is-data-descriptor": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-data-descriptor/-/is-data-descriptor-1.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-jbRXY1FmtAoCjQkVmlIVyuuqDFUbaOeDjmed1tOGPrsMhtJA4rD9tkgA0F1qJ3gRFRXcHYVkdEaP50Q5rE/jLQ==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "kind-of": "^6.0.0"
  }
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"is-descriptor": {
  "version": "1.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-descriptor/-/is-descriptor-1.0.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-2eis5WqQGV7peooDyLmNEPurps9+SXX5c9pL3xEB+4e9HnGuDa7mB7kHxHw4CbqS9k1T2hOH3miL8n8WtiYVtg==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "is-accessor-descriptor": "^1.0.0",
    "is-data-descriptor": "^1.0.0",
    "kind-of": "^6.0.2"

```

```

    }
  },
  "isobject": {
    "version": "3.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isobject/-/isobject-3.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-TkMekrEalzFjaqH5yNHMvP2reN8=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "kind-of": {
    "version": "6.0.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-6.0.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-s5kLOcnH0XqDO+FvuaLX8DDjZ18CGFk7VygH40QoKPUQhW4e2rvM0rwUq0t8IQDOwYSeLK01U90Ojz
BTme2QqA==",
    "dev": true
  }
},
"depd": {
  "version": "1.1.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/depd/-/depd-1.1.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-m81S4UwJd2PnSbJ0xDRu0uVgtak=",
  "dev": true
},
"deprecated": {
  "version": "0.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/deprecated/-/deprecated-0.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-+cmvVGSvoeepcUWKi97yqpTVuxk=",
  "dev": true
},
"destroy": {
  "version": "1.0.4",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/destroy/-/destroy-1.0.4.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-l4hXRCxEJ5CBmE+N5RiBYJqvYA=",
  "dev": true
},
"detect-file": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/detect-file/-/detect-file-1.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-8NZtA2cqglyxtzvbP+YjEMjIUrc=",
  "dev": true
},
"dev-ip": {
  "version": "1.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/dev-ip/-/dev-ip-1.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-p2o+OYVb56ASu4rBbLgPPADcKPA=",
  "dev": true
},
"duplexer2": {
  "version": "0.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/duplexer2/-/duplexer2-0.0.2.tgz",

```

```
"integrity": "sha1-xhTc9n4vsUmVqRcR5aYX6KYKMds=",
"dev": true,
"requires": {
  "readable-stream": "~1.1.9"
},
"dependencies": {
  "isarray": {
    "version": "0.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isarray/-/isarray-0.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-ihis/Kmo9Bd+Cav8YDiTmwXR7t8=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "readable-stream": {
    "version": "1.1.14",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/readable-stream/-/readable-stream-1.1.14.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-fPTFTvZI44EwhMY23SB54WbAgdk=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "core-util-is": "~1.0.0",
      "inherits": "~2.0.1",
      "isarray": "0.0.1",
      "string_decoder": "~0.10.x"
    }
  },
  "string_decoder": {
    "version": "0.10.31",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/string_decoder/-/string_decoder-0.10.31.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-YuIDvEF2bGwoyfyEMB2rHFMQ+pQ=",
    "dev": true
  }
},
"easy-extender": {
  "version": "2.3.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/easy-extender/-/easy-extender-2.3.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-PTJI/r4rFZYHMMW2PnPSRwWZIIh0=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "lodash": "^3.10.1"
  }
},
"easy-logger": {
  "version": "3.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/eazy-logger/-/eazy-logger-3.0.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-oyWqXIPROiIliJsqxBE7K5Y29Pw=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "tfunk": "^3.0.1"
  }
},
"ee-first": {
```

```

    "version": "1.1.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/ee-first/-/ee-first-1.1.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-WQxhFWsK4vTwJVcyoViyZrxWsh0=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "encodeurl": {
    "version": "1.0.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/encodeurl/-/encodeurl-1.0.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-rT/OyG7C0CkyL1oCw6mmBslbP1k=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "end-of-stream": {
    "version": "0.1.5",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/end-of-stream/-/end-of-stream-0.1.5.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-jhdyBsPICDfYVjLouTWd/osvbq8=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "once": "~1.3.0"
    }
  },
  "engine.io": {
    "version": "3.2.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/engine.io/-/engine.io-3.2.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-mRbgmAtQ4GAIKwuPnnAvXXwdPhEx+jkc0OBCLrXuD/CRvwNK3AxsRsnqK4FSqmAMRRHryVJP8TopOvmEaA64fKw==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "accepts": "~1.3.4",
      "base64id": "1.0.0",
      "cookie": "0.3.1",
      "debug": "~3.1.0",
      "engine.io-parser": "~2.1.0",
      "ws": "~3.3.1"
    }
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "debug": {
      "version": "3.1.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/debug/-/debug-3.1.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-OX8XqP7/1a9cqkxYw2yXss15f26NKWBpDXQd0/uK/KPqdQhxbPa994honzjcE2VqQpDslf55723cKPUOGSmMY3g==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "ms": "2.0.0"
      }
    }
  }
},
"engine.io-client": {
  "version": "3.1.6",

```

```

    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/engine.io-client/-/engine.io-client-3.1.6.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-
hnuHsFluXnsKONDs4Hv6SvUrgdYx1pk2NqfaDMW+GWdGfU3+/V25Cj7I8a0x92idSpa5PIhJRKxPvp9mn
oLsfg==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "component-emitter": "1.2.1",
      "component-inherit": "0.0.3",
      "debug": "~3.1.0",
      "engine.io-parser": "~2.1.1",
      "has-cors": "1.1.0",
      "indexOf": "0.0.1",
      "parseqs": "0.0.5",
      "parseuri": "0.0.5",
      "ws": "~3.3.1",
      "xmlhttprequest-ssl": "~1.5.4",
      "yeast": "0.1.2"
    },
    "dependencies": {
      "debug": {
        "version": "3.1.0",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/debug/-/debug-3.1.0.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha512-
OX8XqP7/1a9cqkxYw2yXss15f26NKWBpDXQd0/uK/KPqdQhxbPa994honzjCE2VqQpDslf55723cKPUOG
SmMY3g==",
        "dev": true,
        "requires": {
          "ms": "2.0.0"
        }
      }
    }
  },
  "engine.io-parser": {
    "version": "2.1.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/engine.io-parser/-/engine.io-parser-2.1.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-
dlnLFzr80RijZ1rGpx1+56/uFoH7/7InH3kZt+Ms6hT8tNx3NGW/WNSA/f8As1WkOfkuyb3tnRyuXGxus
clMw==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "after": "0.8.2",
      "arraybuffer.slice": "~0.0.7",
      "base64-arraybuffer": "0.1.5",
      "blob": "0.0.4",
      "has-binary2": "~1.0.2"
    }
  },
  "error-ex": {
    "version": "1.3.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/error-ex/-/error-ex-1.3.2.tgz",

```

```
    "integrity": "sha512-7dFHNmqeFSEt2ZBsCriorKnn3Z2pj+fd9kml6QoWw4//DL+icEBfc0U7qJCisqrTsKTjw4fNFy2pW9OqStD84g==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-arrayish": "^0.2.1"
    }
  },
  "escape-html": {
    "version": "1.0.3",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/escape-html/-/escape-html-1.0.3.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Aljq5NPQwJdN4cFpGI7wBR0dGYg=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "escape-string-regexp": {
    "version": "1.0.5",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/escape-string-regexp/-/escape-string-regexp-1.0.5.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-G2HAViGQqN/2rjuyzwIAyhMLhtQ=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "etag": {
    "version": "1.8.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/etag/-/etag-1.8.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Qa4u62XvpjIorr/qg6x9eSmbClc=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "eventemitter3": {
    "version": "1.2.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/eventemitter3/-/eventemitter3-1.2.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-HIaZHYFq0eUEdQ5zh0Ik7PO+xQg=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "expand-brackets": {
    "version": "0.1.5",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/expand-brackets/-/expand-brackets-0.1.5.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-3wcoTjQqgHzXM6xa9yQR5YHRF3s=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-posix-bracket": "^0.1.0"
    }
  },
  "expand-range": {
    "version": "1.8.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/expand-range/-/expand-range-1.8.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-opnv/TNf4nleuujiv+x5ZE/IUzc=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "fill-range": "^2.1.0"
    }
  },
}
```

```

"expand-tilde": {
  "version": "2.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/expand-tilde/-/expand-tilde-2.0.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-l+gBqgUt8CRU3kawK/YhZCzchQl=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "homedir-polyfill": "^1.0.1"
  }
},
"extend": {
  "version": "3.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/extend/-/extend-3.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-p1Xqe8Gt/MWjHOfnYtuq3F5jZEq=",
  "dev": true
},
"extend-shallow": {
  "version": "3.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/extend-shallow/-/extend-shallow-3.0.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-Jqcarwc7OfshJxcnRhMcJwQCjbg=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "assign-symbols": "^1.0.0",
    "is-extendable": "^1.0.1"
  }
},
"dependencies": {
  "is-extendable": {
    "version": "1.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-extendable/-/is-extendable-1.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-arnXMxT1hhoKo9k1LZdmlNyJdDDfy2v0fXjFlmoka+i8ul/6WlBvGe9bhM74OpNPQPMGUToDtz+KXa1PneJxOA==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-plain-object": "^2.0.4"
    }
  }
},
"extglob": {
  "version": "0.3.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/extglob/-/extglob-0.3.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-Lhj/PS9JqydlzskCPwEdqo2DSaE=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "is-extglob": "^1.0.0"
  }
},
"fancy-log": {
  "version": "1.3.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/fancy-log/-/fancy-log-1.3.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-9BEl49hPLn2JpD0G2VjI94vha+E=",

```

```

    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "ansi-gray": "^0.1.1",
      "color-support": "^1.1.3",
      "time-stamp": "^1.0.0"
    }
  },
  "filename-regex": {
    "version": "2.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/filename-regex/-/filename-regex-2.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-wcS5vuPglyXdsQa3XB4wH+LxiyY=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "fill-range": {
    "version": "2.2.4",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/fill-range/-/fill-range-2.2.4.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-cnrcbj01+j2gTG921VZPnHbjmdAf8oQV/iGeV2kZxGSyfYjjTyY79ErsK1WJWMPw6DaApEX72binqJE+/d+5Q==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-number": "^2.1.0",
      "isobject": "^2.0.0",
      "randomatic": "^3.0.0",
      "repeat-element": "^1.1.2",
      "repeat-string": "^1.5.2"
    }
  },
  "finalhandler": {
    "version": "1.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/finalhandler/-/finalhandler-1.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-zgtoVbRYU+eRsvzGgARTiCU91/U=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "debug": "2.6.9",
      "encodeurl": "~1.0.1",
      "escape-html": "~1.0.3",
      "on-finished": "~2.3.0",
      "parseurl": "~1.3.2",
      "statuses": "~1.3.1",
      "unpipe": "~1.0.0"
    }
  },
  "find-index": {
    "version": "0.1.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/find-index/-/find-index-0.1.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Z101iyyjiS15Whq0cjL4tuLg3eQ=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "find-up": {
    "version": "1.1.2",

```

```

    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/find-up/-/find-up-1.1.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-ay6YlrGizpgq2TWE0zK1TyyTQ8=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "path-exists": "^2.0.0",
      "pinkie-promise": "^2.0.0"
    }
  },
  "findup-sync": {
    "version": "2.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/findup-sync/-/findup-sync-2.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-kyaxSlwi0aYIhlCoaQGy2akKLLw=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "detect-file": ^1.0.0,
      "is-glob": ^3.1.0,
      "micromatch": ^3.0.4,
      "resolve-dir": ^1.0.1
    }
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "arr-diff": {
      "version": "4.0.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/arr-diff/-/arr-diff-4.0.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-1kYQdP6/7HHn4VI1dhoyml3HxSA=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "array-unique": {
      "version": "0.3.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/array-unique/-/array-unique-0.3.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-qJS3XUvE9s1nnvMkSp/Y9Gri1Cg=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "braces": {
      "version": "2.3.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/braces/-/braces-2.3.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-aNdbnj9P8PjdXU4ybaWLK2IF3jc/EoDYbC7AazW6to3TRsfXxscC9UXOB5iDiEQrkyIbWp2SLQda4+QAa7nc3w==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "arr-flatten": ^1.1.0,
        "array-unique": ^0.3.2,
        "extend-shallow": ^2.0.1,
        "fill-range": ^4.0.0,
        "isobject": ^3.0.1,
        "repeat-element": ^1.1.2,
        "snapdragon": ^0.8.1,
        "snapdragon-node": ^2.0.1,
        "split-string": ^3.0.2,
        "to-regex": ^3.0.1
      }
    },

```

```

"dependencies": {
  "extend-shallow": {
    "version": "2.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/extend-shallow/-/extend-shallow-2.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Ua99YUrZqfYQ6huvu5idaxxWiQ8=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-extendable": "^0.1.0"
    }
  }
},
"expand-brackets": {
  "version": "2.1.4",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/expand-brackets/-/expand-brackets-2.1.4.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-t3c14xXOMPa27/D4OwQVGiJEil=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "debug": "^2.3.3",
    "define-property": "^0.2.5",
    "extend-shallow": "^2.0.1",
    "posix-character-classes": "^0.1.0",
    "regex-not": "^1.0.0",
    "snapdragon": "^0.8.1",
    "to-regex": "^3.0.1"
  }
},
"dependencies": {
  "define-property": {
    "version": "0.2.5",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/define-property/-/define-property-0.2.5.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-w1se+RjsPJKPmlvFe+BKrOxcgRY=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-descriptor": "^0.1.0"
    }
  }
},
"extend-shallow": {
  "version": "2.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/extend-shallow/-/extend-shallow-2.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-Ua99YUrZqfYQ6huvu5idaxxWiQ8=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "is-extendable": "^0.1.0"
  }
},
"is-accessor-descriptor": {
  "version": "0.1.6",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-accessor-descriptor/-/is-accessor-descriptor-0.1.6.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-qeEss66Nh2cn7u84Q/igiXtcmNY=",
  "dev": true,

```

```

    "requires": {
      "kind-of": "^3.0.2"
    },
    "dependencies": {
      "kind-of": {
        "version": "3.2.2",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-3.2.2.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha1-MeohpzS6ubuw8yRm2JOupR5KPGQ=",
        "dev": true,
        "requires": {
          "is-buffer": "^1.1.5"
        }
      }
    }
  },
  "is-data-descriptor": {
    "version": "0.1.4",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-data-descriptor/-/is-data-descriptor-0.1.4.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-C17mSDiOLIYCgueT8YVv7D8wG1Y=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "kind-of": "^3.0.2"
    },
    "dependencies": {
      "kind-of": {
        "version": "3.2.2",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-3.2.2.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha1-MeohpzS6ubuw8yRm2JOupR5KPGQ=",
        "dev": true,
        "requires": {
          "is-buffer": "^1.1.5"
        }
      }
    }
  },
  "is-descriptor": {
    "version": "0.1.6",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-descriptor/-/is-descriptor-0.1.6.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-avDYr0SB3DwO9zsMov0gKCESFYqCnE4hq/4z3TdUlukEy5t9C0YRq77HLLrsN52NAcqXKaepeCD0n+B0arnVG3Hg==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-accessor-descriptor": "^0.1.6",
      "is-data-descriptor": "^0.1.4",
      "kind-of": "^5.0.0"
    }
  },
  "kind-of": {
    "version": "5.1.0",

```

```

    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-5.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-NGEernH6F2vUuXDH+OlbckW7/wOcfDRHaZ7VWtqCztfHri/++YKmP51OdWeGPuqCOba6kk2OTe5d02
VmTB80Pw==",
    "dev": true
  }
},
"extglob": {
  "version": "2.0.4",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/extglob/-/extglob-2.0.4.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-Nmb6QXkELsuBr24CJSkilo6UHHgbekK5UiZgfE6UHD3Eb27YC6oD+bhcT+tJ6cl8dmsgdQxnWlcry8ksBIB
Lpw==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "array-unique": "^0.3.2",
    "define-property": "^1.0.0",
    "expand-brackets": "^2.1.4",
    "extend-shallow": "^2.0.1",
    "fragment-cache": "^0.2.1",
    "regex-not": "^1.0.0",
    "snapdragon": "^0.8.1",
    "to-regex": "^3.0.1"
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "define-property": {
      "version": "1.0.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/define-property/-/define-property-1.0.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-dp66rz9KY6rTr56NMEybvnm/sOY=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "is-descriptor": "^1.0.0"
      }
    },
    "extend-shallow": {
      "version": "2.0.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/extend-shallow/-/extend-shallow-2.0.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-Ua99YUrZqfYQ6huvu5idaxxWiQ8=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "is-extendable": "^0.1.0"
      }
    }
  },
  "fill-range": {
    "version": "4.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/fill-range/-/fill-range-4.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-1USBHUKPmOsGpj3EAtJAPDKMOPc=",
    "dev": true,

```

```

    "requires": {
      "extend-shallow": "^2.0.1",
      "is-number": "^3.0.0",
      "repeat-string": "^1.6.1",
      "to-regex-range": "^2.1.0"
    },
    "dependencies": {
      "extend-shallow": {
        "version": "2.0.1",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/extend-shallow/-/extend-shallow-2.0.1.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha1-Ua99YUrZqfYQ6huvu5idaxxWiQ8=",
        "dev": true,
        "requires": {
          "is-extendable": "^0.1.0"
        }
      }
    }
  },
  "is-accessor-descriptor": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-accessor-descriptor/-/is-accessor-descriptor-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-m5hnHTkcsVsfpx3AKlyttIPb7J+XykHvJP2B9bZDjhlLioEq4XoK64Vg7boZIVWYK6LUY94dYPEE7Lh0ZkZKcQ==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "kind-of": "^6.0.0"
    }
  },
  "is-data-descriptor": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-data-descriptor/-/is-data-descriptor-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-jbRXY1FmtAoCjQkVmIVyWuuqDFUbaOeDjmed1tOGPrsMhtJA4rD9tkgA0F1qJ3gRFRXcHYVkdEAP50Q5rE/jLQ==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "kind-of": "^6.0.0"
    }
  },
  "is-descriptor": {
    "version": "1.0.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-descriptor/-/is-descriptor-1.0.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-2eis5WqQGV7peooDyLmNEPurps9+SXX5c9pL3xEB+4e9HnGuDa7mB7kHxHw4CbqS9k1T2hOH3miL8n8WtiYVtg==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-accessor-descriptor": "^1.0.0",
      "is-data-descriptor": "^1.0.0",
    }
  }

```

```

    "kind-of": "^6.0.2"
  }
},
"is-extglob": {
  "version": "2.1.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-extglob/-/is-extglob-2.1.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-qlwCU1eR8C7TfHahueqXc8gz+MI=",
  "dev": true
},
"is-glob": {
  "version": "3.1.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-glob/-/is-glob-3.1.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-e6WuJCF4BKxwcHuWkiVnSGzD6Eo=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "is-extglob": "^2.1.0"
  }
},
"is-number": {
  "version": "3.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-number/-/is-number-3.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-JP1iAaR4LPUFYcgQJ2r8fRLXEZU=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "kind-of": "^3.0.2"
  }
},
"dependencies": {
  "kind-of": {
    "version": "3.2.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-3.2.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-MeohpzS6ubuw8yRm2JOupR5KPGQ=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-buffer": "^1.1.5"
    }
  }
}
},
"isobject": {
  "version": "3.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isobject/-/isobject-3.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-TkMekrEalzFjaqH5yNHMvP2reN8=",
  "dev": true
},
"kind-of": {
  "version": "6.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-6.0.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-S5BqE4q0wU3X7U9AqGQ8CJeywvYV64F3eD5nU2WxT1yZHQ8T3OjOsK+Zb5Dz4kQvIz4K1pYCdq0W0m88A==",
  "dev": true
}
s5kLOcnH0XqDO+VvuaLX8DDjZ18CGFk7VyG40QoKPUQhW4e2rvM0rwUq0t8IQDOWySeLK01U90Qjz
BTme2QqA==",
  "dev": true
}

```

```

    },
    "micromatch": {
      "version": "3.1.10",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/micromatch/-/micromatch-3.1.10.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-MWikgl9n9M3w+bpsY3He8L+w9eF9338xRl8IAO5viDizwSzziFEyUzo2xrrloB64ADbTf8uA8vRqqttdTO
mccg==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "arr-diff": "^4.0.0",
        "array-unique": "^0.3.2",
        "braces": "^2.3.1",
        "define-property": "^2.0.2",
        "extend-shallow": "^3.0.2",
        "extglob": "^2.0.4",
        "fragment-cache": "^0.2.1",
        "kind-of": "^6.0.2",
        "nanomatch": "^1.2.9",
        "object.pick": "^1.3.0",
        "regex-not": "^1.0.0",
        "snapdragon": "^0.8.1",
        "to-regex": "^3.0.2"
      }
    }
  },
  "fined": {
    "version": "1.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/fined/-/fined-1.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-s33IRLdqL15wgeiE98CuNE8VNHY=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "expand-tilde": "^2.0.2",
      "is-plain-object": "^2.0.3",
      "object.defaults": "^1.1.0",
      "object.pick": "^1.2.0",
      "parse-filepath": "^1.0.1"
    }
  },
  "first-chunk-stream": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/first-chunk-stream/-/first-chunk-stream-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Wb+1DNkF9g18OUzT2ayqtOatk04=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "flagged-respawn": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/flagged-respawn/-/flagged-respawn-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Tnmumy6zi/hrO7Vr8+ClaqX8q9c=",
    "dev": true
  },

```

```

"follow-redirects": {
  "version": "1.5.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/follow-redirects/-/follow-redirects-1.5.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-v9G1hpaqq1ZZR6pBD1+kI7O24PhDvNGNodjS3MdcEqyrahCp8zbtvp+2B/krUnSmUH80lbAS7MrdeK5I
yIlgKg==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "debug": "^3.1.0"
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "debug": {
      "version": "3.1.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/debug/-/debug-3.1.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-OX8XqP7/1a9cqkxYw2yXss15f26NKWBpDXQd0/uK/KPqdQhxbPa994honzjcE2VqQpDsIf55723cKPUOG
SmMY3g==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "ms": "2.0.0"
      }
    }
  }
},
"font-awesome": {
  "version": "4.7.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/font-awesome/-/font-awesome-4.7.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-j6jPBBGhoxr9B7BtKQK7n8gVoTM="
},
"for-in": {
  "version": "1.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/for-in/-/for-in-1.0.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-gQaNKVqBQuwKxybG4iAMMPttXoA=",
  "dev": true
},
"for-own": {
  "version": "0.1.5",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/for-own/-/for-own-0.1.5.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-UmXGgaTyINq78XyVCbZ2OqhFEM4=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "for-in": "^1.0.1"
  }
},
"fragment-cache": {
  "version": "0.2.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/fragment-cache/-/fragment-cache-0.2.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-QpD60n8T6Jvn8zeZxrxaCr//DRk=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "map-cache": "^0.2.2"
  }
}

```

```

    }
  },
  "fresh": {
    "version": "0.5.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/fresh/-/fresh-0.5.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-PYyt2Q2XZWn6g1qx+OSyOhBWBac=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "fs-extra": {
    "version": "3.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/fs-extra/-/fs-extra-3.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-N5TzeMWLNC6n27sjCvEJxLO2lpE=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "graceful-fs": "^4.1.2",
      "jsonfile": "^3.0.0",
      "universalify": "^0.1.0"
    }
  },
  "fsevents": {
    "version": "1.2.4",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/fsevents/-/fsevents-1.2.4.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-z8H8/diyk76B7q5wg+Ud0+CqzcAF3mBBI/bA5ne5zrRUUlvNkKY//D3BqyH571KuAC4Nr7Rw7CjWX4r0y9DvNg==",
    "dev": true,
    "optional": true,
    "requires": {
      "nan": "^2.9.2",
      "node-pre-gyp": "^0.10.0"
    }
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "abbrev": {
      "version": "1.1.1",
      "bundled": true,
      "dev": true,
      "optional": true
    },
    "ansi-regex": {
      "version": "2.1.1",
      "bundled": true,
      "dev": true
    },
    "aproba": {
      "version": "1.2.0",
      "bundled": true,
      "dev": true,
      "optional": true
    },
    "are-we-there-yet": {
      "version": "1.1.4",

```

```
"bundled": true,
"dev": true,
"optional": true,
"requires": {
  "delegates": "^1.0.0",
  "readable-stream": "^2.0.6"
}
},
"balanced-match": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true
},
"brace-expansion": {
  "version": "1.1.11",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "balanced-match": "^1.0.0",
    "concat-map": "0.0.1"
  }
},
"chownr": {
  "version": "1.0.1",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"code-point-at": {
  "version": "1.1.0",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true
},
"concat-map": {
  "version": "0.0.1",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true
},
"console-control-strings": {
  "version": "1.1.0",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true
},
"core-util-is": {
  "version": "1.0.2",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"debug": {
  "version": "2.6.9",
```

```
"bundled": true,
"dev": true,
"optional": true,
"requires": {
  "ms": "2.0.0"
}
},
"deep-extend": {
  "version": "0.5.1",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"delegates": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"detect-libc": {
  "version": "1.0.3",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"fs-minipass": {
  "version": "1.2.5",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true,
  "requires": {
    "minipass": "^2.2.1"
  }
},
"fs.realpath": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"gauge": {
  "version": "2.7.4",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true,
  "requires": {
    "aproba": "^1.0.3",
    "console-control-strings": "^1.0.0",
    "has-unicode": "^2.0.0",
    "object-assign": "^4.1.0",
    "signal-exit": "^3.0.0",
```

```
    "string-width": "^1.0.1",
    "strip-ansi": "^3.0.1",
    "wide-align": "^1.1.0"
  }
},
"glob": {
  "version": "7.1.2",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true,
  "requires": {
    "fs.realpath": "^1.0.0",
    "inflight": "^1.0.4",
    "inherits": "2",
    "minimatch": "^3.0.4",
    "once": "^1.3.0",
    "path-is-absolute": "^1.0.0"
  }
},
"has-unicode": {
  "version": "2.0.1",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"iconv-lite": {
  "version": "0.4.21",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true,
  "requires": {
    "safer-buffer": "^2.1.0"
  }
},
"ignore-walk": {
  "version": "3.0.1",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true,
  "requires": {
    "minimatch": "^3.0.4"
  }
},
"inflight": {
  "version": "1.0.6",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true,
  "requires": {
    "once": "^1.3.0",
    "wrappy": "1"
  }
}
```

```
    }
  },
  "inherits": {
    "version": "2.0.3",
    "bundled": true,
    "dev": true
  },
  "ini": {
    "version": "1.3.5",
    "bundled": true,
    "dev": true,
    "optional": true
  },
  "is-fullwidth-code-point": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "bundled": true,
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "number-is-nan": "^1.0.0"
    }
  },
  "isarray": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "bundled": true,
    "dev": true,
    "optional": true
  },
  "minimatch": {
    "version": "3.0.4",
    "bundled": true,
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "brace-expansion": "^1.1.7"
    }
  },
  "minimist": {
    "version": "0.0.8",
    "bundled": true,
    "dev": true
  },
  "minipass": {
    "version": "2.2.4",
    "bundled": true,
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "safe-buffer": "^5.1.1",
      "yallist": "^3.0.0"
    }
  },
  "minizlib": {
    "version": "1.1.0",
```

```
"bundled": true,
"dev": true,
"optional": true,
"requires": {
  "minipass": "^2.2.1"
}
},
"mkdirp": {
  "version": "0.5.1",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "minimist": "0.0.8"
  }
},
"ms": {
  "version": "2.0.0",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"needle": {
  "version": "2.2.0",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true,
  "requires": {
    "debug": "^2.1.2",
    "iconv-lite": "^0.4.4",
    "sax": "^1.2.4"
  }
},
"node-pre-gyp": {
  "version": "0.10.0",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true,
  "requires": {
    "detect-libc": "^1.0.2",
    "mkdirp": "^0.5.1",
    "needle": "^2.2.0",
    "nopt": "^4.0.1",
    "npm-packlist": "^1.1.6",
    "npmlog": "^4.0.2",
    "rc": "^1.1.7",
    "rimraf": "^2.6.1",
    "semver": "^5.3.0",
    "tar": "^4"
  }
},
"nopt": {
```

```
"version": "4.0.1",
"bundled": true,
"dev": true,
"optional": true,
"requires": {
  "abbrev": "1",
  "osenv": "^0.1.4"
}
},
"npm-bundled": {
  "version": "1.0.3",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"npm-packlist": {
  "version": "1.1.10",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true,
  "requires": {
    "ignore-walk": "^3.0.1",
    "npm-bundled": "^1.0.1"
  }
},
"npmlog": {
  "version": "4.1.2",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true,
  "requires": {
    "are-we-there-yet": "~1.1.2",
    "console-control-strings": "~1.1.0",
    "gauge": "~2.7.3",
    "set-blocking": "~2.0.0"
  }
},
"number-is-nan": {
  "version": "1.0.1",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true
},
"object-assign": {
  "version": "4.1.1",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"once": {
  "version": "1.4.0",
  "bundled": true,
```

```
"dev": true,
"requires": {
  "wrappy": "1"
}
},
"os-homedir": {
  "version": "1.0.2",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"os-tmpdir": {
  "version": "1.0.2",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"osenv": {
  "version": "0.1.5",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true,
  "requires": {
    "os-homedir": "^1.0.0",
    "os-tmpdir": "^1.0.0"
  }
},
"path-is-absolute": {
  "version": "1.0.1",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"process-nextick-args": {
  "version": "2.0.0",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"rc": {
  "version": "1.2.7",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true,
  "requires": {
    "deep-extend": "^0.5.1",
    "ini": "~1.3.0",
    "minimist": "^1.2.0",
    "strip-json-comments": "~2.0.1"
  }
},
"dependencies": {
```

```
    "minimist": {
      "version": "1.2.0",
      "bundled": true,
      "dev": true,
      "optional": true
    }
  },
  "readable-stream": {
    "version": "2.3.6",
    "bundled": true,
    "dev": true,
    "optional": true,
    "requires": {
      "core-util-is": "~1.0.0",
      "inherits": "~2.0.3",
      "isarray": "~1.0.0",
      "process-nextick-args": "~2.0.0",
      "safe-buffer": "~5.1.1",
      "string_decoder": "~1.1.1",
      "util-deprecate": "~1.0.1"
    }
  },
  "rimraf": {
    "version": "2.6.2",
    "bundled": true,
    "dev": true,
    "optional": true,
    "requires": {
      "glob": "^7.0.5"
    }
  },
  "safe-buffer": {
    "version": "5.1.1",
    "bundled": true,
    "dev": true
  },
  "safer-buffer": {
    "version": "2.1.2",
    "bundled": true,
    "dev": true,
    "optional": true
  },
  "sax": {
    "version": "1.2.4",
    "bundled": true,
    "dev": true,
    "optional": true
  },
  "semver": {
    "version": "5.5.0",
```

```
"bundled": true,
"dev": true,
"optional": true
},
"set-blocking": {
  "version": "2.0.0",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"signal-exit": {
  "version": "3.0.2",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"string-width": {
  "version": "1.0.2",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "code-point-at": "^1.0.0",
    "is-fullwidth-code-point": "^1.0.0",
    "strip-ansi": "^3.0.0"
  }
},
"string_decoder": {
  "version": "1.1.1",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true,
  "requires": {
    "safe-buffer": "~5.1.0"
  }
},
"strip-ansi": {
  "version": "3.0.1",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "ansi-regex": "^2.0.0"
  }
},
"strip-json-comments": {
  "version": "2.0.1",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"tar": {
  "version": "4.4.1",
```

```
"bundled": true,
"dev": true,
"optional": true,
"requires": {
  "chownr": "^1.0.1",
  "fs-minipass": "^1.2.5",
  "minipass": "^2.2.4",
  "minizlib": "^1.1.0",
  "mkdirp": "^0.5.0",
  "safe-buffer": "^5.1.1",
  "yallist": "^3.0.2"
}
},
"util-deprecate": {
  "version": "1.0.2",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"wide-align": {
  "version": "1.1.2",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true,
  "requires": {
    "string-width": "^1.0.2"
  }
},
"wrapappy": {
  "version": "1.0.2",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true
},
"yallist": {
  "version": "3.0.2",
  "bundled": true,
  "dev": true
}
}
},
"gaze": {
  "version": "0.5.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/gaze/-/gaze-0.5.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-QLcJU30k0dRXZ9taklaJ3+aaxE8=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "globule": "~0.1.0"
  }
},
"get-caller-file": {
  "version": "1.0.2",
```

```
"resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/get-caller-file/-/get-caller-file-1.0.2.tgz",
"integrity": "sha1-9wLmMSfn4jHBYKgMFVSstw1QR+U=",
"dev": true
},
"get-value": {
  "version": "2.0.6",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/get-value/-/get-value-2.0.6.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-3BXKHGcjh8p2vTesCjlbogQqLCg=",
  "dev": true
},
"glob": {
  "version": "4.5.3",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/glob/-/glob-4.5.3.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-xstz0yJsHv7wTePFbQEvAzd+4V8=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "inflight": "^1.0.4",
    "inherits": "2",
    "minimatch": "^2.0.1",
    "once": "^1.3.0"
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "minimatch": {
      "version": "2.0.10",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/minimatch/-/minimatch-2.0.10.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-jQh8OcazjAAbl/ynzm00HoCvusc=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "brace-expansion": "^1.0.0"
      }
    }
  }
},
"glob-base": {
  "version": "0.3.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/glob-base/-/glob-base-0.3.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-27Fk9ilbHAscZ4Kuoyi0I98Oo8Q=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "glob-parent": "^2.0.0",
    "is-glob": "^2.0.0"
  }
},
"glob-parent": {
  "version": "2.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/glob-parent/-/glob-parent-2.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-gTg9ctsFT8zPUzbaqQLxgvbtuyg=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "is-glob": "^2.0.0"
  }
}
```

```

},
"glob-stream": {
  "version": "3.1.18",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/glob-stream/-/glob-stream-3.1.18.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-kXCl8St5Awb9/lmPMT+PeVT9FDs=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "glob": "^4.3.1",
    "glob2base": "^0.0.12",
    "minimatch": "^2.0.1",
    "ordered-read-streams": "^0.1.0",
    "through2": "^0.6.1",
    "unique-stream": "^1.0.0"
  }
},
"dependencies": {
  "isarray": {
    "version": "0.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isarray/-/isarray-0.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-ihis/Kmo9Bd+Cav8YDiTmwXR7t8=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "minimatch": {
    "version": "2.0.10",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/minimatch/-/minimatch-2.0.10.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-jQh8OcazjAAbl/ynzm00HoCvusc=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "brace-expansion": "^1.0.0"
    }
  },
  "readable-stream": {
    "version": "1.0.34",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/readable-stream/-/readable-stream-1.0.34.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Elgg40vIQtLyqq+v5MKRbuMsFXw=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "core-util-is": "~1.0.0",
      "inherits": "~2.0.1",
      "isarray": "0.0.1",
      "string_decoder": "~0.10.x"
    }
  },
  "string_decoder": {
    "version": "0.10.31",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/string_decoder/-/string_decoder-0.10.31.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-YuIDvEF2bGwoyfyEMB2rHFMQ+pQ=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "through2": {
    "version": "0.6.5",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/through2/-/through2-0.6.5.tgz",

```

```

    "integrity": "sha1-QaucZ7KdVyCQcUEOHXp6lozTrUg=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "readable-stream": ">=1.0.33-1 <1.1.0-0",
      "xtend": ">=4.0.0 <4.1.0-0"
    }
  }
},
"glob-watcher": {
  "version": "0.0.6",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/glob-watcher/-/glob-watcher-0.0.6.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-uVtKjfdLOcgymLDAXJeLTZo7cQs=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "gaze": "^0.5.1"
  }
},
"glob2base": {
  "version": "0.0.12",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/glob2base/-/glob2base-0.0.12.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-nUGbPijxLoOjYhZKJ3BVkiycDVY=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "find-index": "^0.1.1"
  }
},
"global-modules": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/global-modules/-/global-modules-1.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-sKzpEkf11GpOFuw0Zjzmt4B4UZwjOcG757PPvrfhxcLFbq0wpsgpOqxpptxFiCG4DtG93M6XRvbF2oGd
ev7bg==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "global-prefix": "^1.0.1",
    "is-windows": "^1.0.1",
    "resolve-dir": "^1.0.0"
  }
},
"global-prefix": {
  "version": "1.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/global-prefix/-/global-prefix-1.0.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-2/dDxsFJklk8ZVVoy2btMsASLr4=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "expand-tilde": "^2.0.2",
    "homedir-polyfill": "^1.0.1",
    "ini": "^1.3.4",
    "is-windows": "^1.0.1",
    "which": "^1.2.14"
  }
}

```

```

    }
  },
  "globule": {
    "version": "0.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/globule/-/globule-0.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-2cjt3h2nnRJaFRt5UzuXhnY0auU=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "glob": "~3.1.21",
      "lodash": "~1.0.1",
      "minimatch": "~0.2.11"
    }
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "glob": {
      "version": "3.1.21",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/glob/-/glob-3.1.21.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-0p4KBV3qUTj00H7UDomC6DwgZs0=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "graceful-fs": "~1.2.0",
        "inherits": "1",
        "minimatch": "~0.2.11"
      }
    },
    "graceful-fs": {
      "version": "1.2.3",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/graceful-fs/-/graceful-fs-1.2.3.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-FaSAaldUfLLS2/J/QuiajDRRs2Q=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "inherits": {
      "version": "1.0.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/inherits/-/inherits-1.0.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-ykMJ2t7mtUzAuNJH6NfHoJdb3Js=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "lodash": {
      "version": "1.0.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash/-/lodash-1.0.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-j1dWDIO1n8JwvT1WG2kAQ0MOJVE=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "minimatch": {
      "version": "0.2.14",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/minimatch/-/minimatch-0.2.14.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-x054BXT2PG+aCQ6Q775u9TppdWo=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "lru-cache": "2",
        "sigmund": "~1.0.0"
      }
    }
  }
}

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    }
  }
},
"logg": {
  "version": "1.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/logg/-/logg-1.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-
ynYqXLoluBKf9XGR1gA59yEJisIL7YHEH4xr3ZziHB5/yl4qWfaK8Js9jGe6gBGCSCVKqiyO30WnRZADvem
UNw==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "sparkles": "^1.0.0"
  }
},
"graceful-fs": {
  "version": "4.1.11",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/graceful-fs/-/graceful-fs-4.1.11.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-Dovf5NHduIVNZOBOp8AOKgJuVlg=",
  "dev": true
},
"gulp": {
  "version": "3.9.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/gulp/-/gulp-3.9.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-VxzKWSjdQK9IFPxAEYZgFsE4RbQ=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "archy": "^1.0.0",
    "chalk": "^1.0.0",
    "deprecated": "^0.0.1",
    "gulp-util": "^3.0.0",
    "interpret": "^1.0.0",
    "liftoff": "^2.1.0",
    "minimist": "^1.1.0",
    "orchestrator": "^0.3.0",
    "pretty-hrtime": "^1.0.0",
    "semver": "^4.1.0",
    "tildify": "^1.0.0",
    "v8flags": "^2.0.2",
    "vinyl-fs": "^0.3.0"
  }
},
"dependencies": {
  "semver": {
    "version": "4.3.6",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/semver/-/semver-4.3.6.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-MAvG4OhjdPe6YQaLWx7NV/xlMto=",
    "dev": true
  }
}
},
"gulp-util": {
  "version": "3.0.8",

```

```
"resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/gulp-util/-/gulp-util-3.0.8.tgz",
"integrity": "sha1-AFTh50RQLifATBh8PxsQXdVLu08=",
"dev": true,
"requires": {
  "array-differ": "^1.0.0",
  "array-uniq": "^1.0.2",
  "beeper": "^1.0.0",
  "chalk": "^1.0.0",
  "dateformat": "^2.0.0",
  "fancy-log": "^1.1.0",
  "gulplog": "^1.0.0",
  "has-gulplog": "^0.1.0",
  "lodash._reescape": "^3.0.0",
  "lodash._reevaluate": "^3.0.0",
  "lodash._reinterpolate": "^3.0.0",
  "lodash.template": "^3.0.0",
  "minimist": "^1.1.0",
  "multipipe": "^0.1.2",
  "object-assign": "^3.0.0",
  "replace-ext": "0.0.1",
  "through2": "^2.0.0",
  "vinyl": "^0.5.0"
},
"dependencies": {
  "object-assign": {
    "version": "3.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/object-assign/-/object-assign-3.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-m+3VvygIXlJvKR+f/QiBi1Un1h/I=",
    "dev": true
  }
},
"gulplog": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/gulplog/-/gulplog-1.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-4oxNRdBey77YGDY86PnFkmlp/+U=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "glogg": "^1.0.0"
  }
},
"has-ansi": {
  "version": "2.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/has-ansi/-/has-ansi-2.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-NPUEnOHs3ysGSa8+8k5F7TVBbZE=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "ansi-regex": "^2.0.0"
  }
},
"has-binary2": {
```

```
"version": "1.0.3",
"resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/has-binary2/-/has-binary2-1.0.3.tgz",
"integrity": "sha512-G1LWKhDSvhGeAQ8mPVQlqNcOB2sJdwATtZKl2pDKKHfpf/rYj24lkinxf69bIJBnsvtqqNU+L3SL50vzZhX
Onw==",
"dev": true,
"requires": {
  "isarray": "2.0.1"
},
"has-cors": {
  "version": "1.1.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/has-cors/-/has-cors-1.1.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-XkdHk/fqmEP Ru5nCPu9J/xJv/zk=",
  "dev": true
},
"has-gulplog": {
  "version": "0.1.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/has-gulplog/-/has-gulplog-0.1.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-ZBTIKRNpfaUVkDI9r7EvlpZ4Ec4=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "sparkles": "^1.0.0"
  }
},
"has-value": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/has-value/-/has-value-1.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-GLKB2lhbHFxR3vJMkw7SmgvmsXc=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "get-value": "^2.0.6",
    "has-values": "^1.0.0",
    "isobject": "^3.0.0"
  }
},
"dependencies": {
  "isobject": {
    "version": "3.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isobject/-/isobject-3.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-TkMekrEalzFjaqH5yNHMvP2reN8=",
    "dev": true
  }
},
"has-values": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/has-values/-/has-values-1.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-lbC2P+whRmGab+V/51Yo1aOe/k8=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "is-number": "^3.0.0",

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    "kind-of": "^4.0.0"
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "is-number": {
      "version": "3.0.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-number/-/is-number-3.0.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-JP1iAaR4LPUFYcgQJ2r8fRLXEZU=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "kind-of": "^3.0.2"
      },
      "dependencies": {
        "kind-of": {
          "version": "3.2.2",
          "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-3.2.2.tgz",
          "integrity": "sha1-MeohpzS6ubuw8yRm2JOupR5KPGQ=",
          "dev": true,
          "requires": {
            "is-buffer": "^1.1.5"
          }
        }
      }
    },
    "kind-of": {
      "version": "4.0.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-4.0.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-IIE989cSkosgc3hpGkUGb65y3Vc=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "is-buffer": "^1.1.5"
      }
    }
  },
  "homedir-polyfill": {
    "version": "1.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/homedir-polyfill/-/homedir-polyfill-1.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-TCu8inWJmP7r9e1oWA921GdotLw=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "parse-passwd": "^1.0.0"
    }
  },
  "hosted-git-info": {
    "version": "2.7.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/hosted-git-info/-/hosted-git-info-2.7.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-7T/BxH19zbcCTa8XkMIbK5ITo1WtGkFi3GvdWEyNuc4Vex7/9Dqbnp4f4JMydcfj9HCg4zUWFTL3Za6lapg5/w==",
    "dev": true
  },

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```

"http-errors": {
  "version": "1.6.3",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/http-errors/-/http-errors-1.6.3.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-i1VoC7S+KDoLW/TqLjhYC+HZMg0=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "depd": "~1.1.2",
    "inherits": "2.0.3",
    "setprototypeof": "1.1.0",
    "statuses": ">= 1.4.0 < 2"
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "statuses": {
      "version": "1.5.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/statuses/-/statuses-1.5.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-Fhx9rBd2Wf2YEfQ3cfqZOBR4Yow=",
      "dev": true
    }
  }
},
"http-proxy": {
  "version": "1.15.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/http-proxy/-/http-proxy-1.15.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-ZC/cr/5S00SNK9o7AHnpQJBk2jE=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "eventemitter3": "1.x.x",
    "requires-port": "1.x.x"
  }
},
"iconv-lite": {
  "version": "0.4.23",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/iconv-lite/-/iconv-lite-0.4.23.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-
neyTUVFtahjf0mB3dZT77u+8O0QB89jFdnBkd5P1JgYPbPaia3gXXOVL2fq8VyU2gMMD7SaN7QukTB/p
mXYvDA==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "safer-buffer": ">= 2.1.2 < 3"
  }
},
"immutable": {
  "version": "3.8.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/immutable/-/immutable-3.8.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-wkOZUUvbs5kT2vKBN28VMOEErfM=",
  "dev": true
},
"indexof": {
  "version": "0.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/indexof/-/indexof-0.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-gtwzbSMrkGIXnQWrMpOmYFn9Q10=",

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    "dev": true
  },
  "inflight": {
    "version": "1.0.6",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/inflight/-/inflight-1.0.6.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Sb1jMdfQLQwJvJEKEHW6gWW1bfk=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "once": "^1.3.0",
      "wrappy": "1"
    }
  },
  "inherits": {
    "version": "2.0.3",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/inherits/-/inherits-2.0.3.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-YzwsG+PaQqUC9SRmAiSA9CCCYd4=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "ini": {
    "version": "1.3.5",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/ini/-/ini-1.3.5.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-RZY5hulKCMRWDUqZIEi72f/ImXKMvuszcmBduliQ3nnWbx9X/ZBQO7DijMEYS9EhHbB2qacRUMtC7sv
Lwe0lcw==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "interpret": {
    "version": "1.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/interpret/-/interpret-1.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-ftGxQQxqDg94z5XTuEQMY/eLhhQ=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "invert-kv": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/invert-kv/-/invert-kv-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-EEqOSqym09jNFXqO+L+rLXo//bY=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "is-absolute": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-absolute/-/is-absolute-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-dOWoqflvcydARa360Gvv18DZ/gRuHki2NU/wU5X1ZFzdYfH29nkiNZsF3mp4OJ3H4yo9Mx8A/uAGNzpz
PN3yBA==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-relative": "^1.0.0",
      "is-windows": "^1.0.1"
    }
  },
  "is-accessor-descriptor": {

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```
    "version": "0.1.6",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-accessor-descriptor/-/is-accessor-descriptor-0.1.6.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-qeEss66Nh2cn7u84Q/igiXtcmNY=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "kind-of": "^3.0.2"
    }
  },
  "is-arrayish": {
    "version": "0.2.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-arrayish/-/is-arrayish-0.2.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-d8mYQFJ6qOyxqLppe4BkWnqSap0=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "is-binary-path": {
    "version": "1.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-binary-path/-/is-binary-path-1.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-dfFmQrSA8YenEcGUfh/TpKdIWJg=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "binary-extensions": "^1.0.0"
    }
  },
  "is-buffer": {
    "version": "1.1.6",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-buffer/-/is-buffer-1.1.6.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-NcdALwpXkTm5ZvVbK7owOUSvVvBKDgKP5/ewfXEznmQFfs4ZRmanOeKBTJRVjka3QFoN6XJ+9F3USqfHqTaU5w==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "is-builtin-module": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-builtin-module/-/is-builtin-module-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-VAVy0096wxGfj3bDDLwbHgN6/74=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "builtin-modules": "^1.0.0"
    }
  },
  "is-data-descriptor": {
    "version": "0.1.4",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-data-descriptor/-/is-data-descriptor-0.1.4.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-C17mSDiOLIYCGueT8YVv7D8wG1Y=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "kind-of": "^3.0.2"
    }
  },
  "is-descriptor": {
```

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    "version": "0.1.6",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-descriptor/-/is-descriptor-0.1.6.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-avDYr0SB3DwO9zsMov0gKCESFYqCnE4hq/4z3TdUlukEy5t9C0YRq7HLrsN52NAcqXKaepeCD0n+B0arn
VG3Hg==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-accessor-descriptor": "^0.1.6",
      "is-data-descriptor": "^0.1.4",
      "kind-of": "^5.0.0"
    },
    "dependencies": {
      "kind-of": {
        "version": "5.1.0",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-5.1.0.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha512-NGEernH6F2vUuXDh+OlbcKW7/wOcfdRHaZ7VWtqCztfHri/++YKmP51OdWeGPuqCOba6kk2OTe5d02
VmTB80Pw==",
        "dev": true
      }
    }
  },
  "is-dotfile": {
    "version": "1.0.3",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-dotfile/-/is-dotfile-1.0.3.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-pqLzL/Ot+wT1yiXs0Pa4PPeYoeE=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "is-equal-shallow": {
    "version": "0.1.3",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-equal-shallow/-/is-equal-shallow-0.1.3.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-ljgJj8lh3gvPpdnqxMRdY4qhTQ=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-primitive": "^2.0.0"
    }
  },
  "is-extendable": {
    "version": "0.1.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-extendable/-/is-extendable-0.1.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-YrEQ4omkcUGOPsNqYX1HLjAd/lk=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "is-extglob": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-extglob/-/is-extglob-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-rEaBd8SUNAWgkvyPKXYMb/xiBsA=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "is-fullwidth-code-point": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
```

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    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-fullwidth-code-point/-/is-fullwidth-code-point-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-754xOG8DGn8NZDr4L95QxFvAMs=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "number-is-nan": "^1.0.0"
    }
  },
  "is-glob": {
    "version": "2.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-glob/-/is-glob-2.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-0Jb5JqPe1WAPP9/ZEZjLCijC2GM=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-extglob": "^1.0.0"
    }
  },
  "is-number": {
    "version": "2.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-number/-/is-number-2.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Afy7s5NGOISPL0ZszhbezknbkI8=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "kind-of": "^3.0.2"
    }
  },
  "is-number-like": {
    "version": "1.0.8",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-number-like/-/is-number-like-1.0.8.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-6rZi3ezCyFcn5L71ywzz2bS5b2Igl1En3eTlZlvKjz1n3IZLAYMbKYAIQgFmEu0GENg92ziU/faEOA/aixjbA=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "lodash.isfinite": "^3.3.2"
    }
  },
  "is-odd": {
    "version": "2.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-odd/-/is-odd-2.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-OTiixgpZAT1M4NHgS5IguFp/Vz2VI3U7Goh4/HA1adtwyLtSBrxYlcSYkhpAE07s4fKEcjrFxyvtQBND4vFQyQ==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-number": "^4.0.0"
    }
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "is-number": {
      "version": "4.0.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-number/-/is-number-4.0.0.tgz",

```

```
    "integrity": "sha512-
rSkIcAlf1OmFdyAqbnWTLVelsQ58uvZ66S/ZyawjWqlviTWCjg2PzVGw8WUA+nNuPTqb4wgA+NszrJ+0
8LlgQ==",
    "dev": true
  }
},
"is-plain-object": {
  "version": "2.0.4",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-plain-object/-/is-plain-object-2.0.4.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-
h5PpgXkWitc38BBMYawTYMWJHFZJVnBquFE57xFpjB8pJFiF6gZ+bU+Wyl/yqXiFR5mdLsgYNaPe8ua06
Uv9Og==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "isobject": "^3.0.1"
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "isobject": {
      "version": "3.0.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isobject/-/isobject-3.0.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-TkMekrEalzFjaqH5yNHMvP2reN8=",
      "dev": true
    }
  }
},
"is-posix-bracket": {
  "version": "0.1.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-posix-bracket/-/is-posix-bracket-0.1.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-MzTceXdDaOkvAW5vwAql9c1ua8Q=",
  "dev": true
},
"is-primitive": {
  "version": "2.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-primitive/-/is-primitive-2.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-IHurkWOEmcB7Kt8kCkGochADRXU=",
  "dev": true
},
"is-relative": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-relative/-/is-relative-1.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-
Kw/ReK0iqwKeuOMITLFuj0jbPAmEiOslwyIXvbfaf6QfmN9pkD1M+8pdk7RI/dTKbH34/XBFMbgD4iMJh
LQbGA==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "is-unc-path": "^1.0.0"
  }
},
"is-unc-path": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
```

```
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-unc-path/-/is-unc-path-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-
mrGpVd0fs7WWLfvStvgF6iEJnbjDFZh9/emhRDcGWTduTfNHd9CHeUwH3gYIjdbwo4On6hunkztwOa
Aw0yIIQ==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "unc-path-regex": "^0.1.2"
    }
  },
  "is-utf8": {
    "version": "0.2.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-utf8/-/is-utf8-0.2.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Sw2hRCEE0bM2NA6AeX6GXPOffXI=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "is-windows": {
    "version": "1.0.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-windows/-/is-windows-1.0.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-
eXK1Ulnq2bPmjyX6e3VHlzMLobc4J94i4AWn+Hpq3OU5KkrRC96OAcR3PRJ/pGu6m8TRnBHP9dkXQVs
T/COVIA==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "isarray": {
    "version": "2.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isarray/-/isarray-2.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-o32U7ZzaLVmGXJ92/llu4fM4dB4=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "isexe": {
    "version": "2.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isexe/-/isexe-2.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-6PvzdNxVb/iUehDcsFctYz8s+hA=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "isobject": {
    "version": "2.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isobject/-/isobject-2.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-8GVWEJaj8dou9GJy+BxIQNh+DIk=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "isarray": "1.0.0"
    }
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "isarray": {
      "version": "1.0.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isarray/-/isarray-1.0.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-u5NdSFgsuhaMBoNJV6VKPgcSTxE=",
      "dev": true
    }
  }
}
```

```

    },
    "jquery": {
      "version": "3.3.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/jquery/-/jquery-3.3.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-
UblDcmxp5np52/ENotGxILe6aGMvmF4R8S6tZjsP6Knsaxd/xp3Zrh50cG93IR6nPXYUFwzN3ZSOQI0wRJ
NdGg=="
    },
    "jsonfile": {
      "version": "3.0.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/jsonfile/-/jsonfile-3.0.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-peZG9I9T9mLEQVx2daAzHQmS7GY=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "graceful-fs": "^4.1.6"
      }
    },
    "kind-of": {
      "version": "3.2.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-3.2.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-MeohpzS6ubuw8yRm2JOupR5KPGQ=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "is-buffer": "^1.1.5"
      }
    },
    "lcid": {
      "version": "1.0.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lcid/-/lcid-1.0.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-MlRMr6C8SDo4Z7S28rIQYIHRuDU=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "invert-kv": "^1.0.0"
      }
    },
    "liftoff": {
      "version": "2.5.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/liftoff/-/liftoff-2.5.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-lAkpG7Mc6oYbvxCnwVooyvdcMew=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "extend": "^3.0.0",
        "findup-sync": "^2.0.0",
        "fined": "^1.0.1",
        "flagged-respawn": "^1.0.0",
        "is-plain-object": "^2.0.4",
        "object.map": "^1.0.0",
        "rechoir": "^0.6.2",
        "resolve": "^1.1.7"
      }
    },
  },

```

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"limiter": {
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  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/limiter/-/limiter-1.1.3.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-
zrycniMsLw/3ZxTbW7HCez56rcFGecWTx5OZNplzcXUUmJLmoYArC6qdJzmAN5BWiNXGcpjhF9RQ1HS
v5zebEw==",
  "dev": true
},
"load-json-file": {
  "version": "1.1.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/load-json-file/-/load-json-file-1.1.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-lWkFcl1YtLqOwiYbBPWFmCmTdMA=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "graceful-fs": "^4.1.2",
    "parse-json": "^2.2.0",
    "pify": "^2.0.0",
    "pinkie-promise": "^2.0.0",
    "strip-bom": "^2.0.0"
  }
},
"localtunnel": {
  "version": "1.9.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/localtunnel/-/localtunnel-1.9.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-
wCiiIHJ8kKlCwKtQE3m1VRABvsH2ZuOkiOpZUofUCf6Q42v3VIZ+Q0YfX1Z4sYDRj0muiKL1bLvz1FeoxSP
O0w==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "axios": "0.17.1",
    "debug": "2.6.8",
    "openurl": "1.1.1",
    "yargs": "6.6.0"
  }
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"dependencies": {
  "debug": {
    "version": "2.6.8",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/debug/-/debug-2.6.8.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-5zFTHKLt4n0YgiJCfaF4lDaP9Pw=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "ms": "2.0.0"
    }
  }
},
"yargs": {
  "version": "6.6.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/yargs/-/yargs-6.6.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-eC7CHvQDNF+DCoCMo9UTr1YGUgg=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "camelcase": "^3.0.0",

```

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    "cliui": "^3.2.0",
    "decamelize": "^1.1.1",
    "get-caller-file": "^1.0.1",
    "os-locale": "^1.4.0",
    "read-pkg-up": "^1.0.1",
    "require-directory": "^2.1.1",
    "require-main-filename": "^1.0.1",
    "set-blocking": "^2.0.0",
    "string-width": "^1.0.2",
    "which-module": "^1.0.0",
    "y18n": "^3.2.1",
    "yargs-parser": "^4.2.0"
  }
}
},
"lodash": {
  "version": "3.10.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash/-/lodash-3.10.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-W/Rejkm6QYnhfUgnid/RW9FAt7Y=",
  "dev": true
},
"lodash._basecopy": {
  "version": "3.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash._basecopy/-/lodash._basecopy-3.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-jaDmqHbPNEwK2KVIghEd08XHjY=",
  "dev": true
},
"lodash._basetostring": {
  "version": "3.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash._basetostring/-/lodash._basetostring-3.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-0YYdh3+CSIL2aYMTyvPuFVZqB9U=",
  "dev": true
},
"lodash._basevalues": {
  "version": "3.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash._basevalues/-/lodash._basevalues-3.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-W3dXyoAr3j0yl1A+JjAIIp32Ybc=",
  "dev": true
},
"lodash._getnative": {
  "version": "3.9.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash._getnative/-/lodash._getnative-3.9.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-VvwH3t5G1hzc3mh9ZdPuy6o6r/U=",
  "dev": true
},
"lodash._isiterateecall": {
  "version": "3.0.9",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash._isiterateecall/-/lodash._isiterateecall-3.0.9.tgz",

```

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    "integrity": "sha1-UgOte6Ql+uhCRg5pbbnPPmqsbXw=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "lodash._reescape": {
    "version": "3.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash._reescape/-/lodash._reescape-3.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Kx1vXf4HyKNVdT5fJ/rH8c3hYWo=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "lodash._reevaluate": {
    "version": "3.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash._reevaluate/-/lodash._reevaluate-3.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-WLx0xAZkITrgsSTYBpltrKQx4u0=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "lodash._reinterpolate": {
    "version": "3.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash._reinterpolate/-/lodash._reinterpolate-3.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-DM8tiRzq8Ds2Y8eWU4t1rG4RTZ0=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "lodash._root": {
    "version": "3.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash._root/-/lodash._root-3.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-+6HEUkwZ7ppfgTa0YJ8BfPTE1pl=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "lodash.escape": {
    "version": "3.2.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash.escape/-/lodash.escape-3.2.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-mV7g3BjBtlzJLv+ucaEKq1tldpg=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "lodash._root": "^3.0.0"
    }
  },
  "lodash.isarguments": {
    "version": "3.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash.isarguments/-/lodash.isarguments-3.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-L1c9hcaiQon/AGY7SRwdM4/zRYo=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "lodash.isarray": {
    "version": "3.0.4",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash.isarray/-/lodash.isarray-3.0.4.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-eeTriMNqgSKvhvhEqpvNhRtfu1U=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "lodash.isfinite": {
    "version": "3.3.2",

```

```
"resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash.isfinite/-/lodash.isfinite-3.3.2.tgz",
"integrity": "sha1-+4m2WpqAKBgz8LdHizpRBPiY67M=",
"dev": true
},
"lodash.keys": {
  "version": "3.1.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash.keys/-/lodash.keys-3.1.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-TbwEcrFWvICgsoaFXRvQsMZWCYo=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "lodash._getnative": "^3.0.0",
    "lodash.isarguments": "^3.0.0",
    "lodash.isarray": "^3.0.0"
  }
},
"lodash.restparam": {
  "version": "3.6.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash.restparam/-/lodash.restparam-3.6.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-k2pOMJ7zMKdkXtQUWYbiWuWyCAU=",
  "dev": true
},
"lodash.template": {
  "version": "3.6.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash.template/-/lodash.template-3.6.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-+M3sxhaaJVvpCYrosMU9N4kx0U8=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "lodash._basecopy": "^3.0.0",
    "lodash._basetostring": "^3.0.0",
    "lodash._basevalues": "^3.0.0",
    "lodash._isiterateecall": "^3.0.0",
    "lodash._reinterpolate": "^3.0.0",
    "lodash.escape": "^3.0.0",
    "lodash.keys": "^3.0.0",
    "lodash.restparam": "^3.0.0",
    "lodash.templatesettings": "^3.0.0"
  }
},
"lodash.templatesettings": {
  "version": "3.1.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lodash.templatesettings/-/lodash.templatesettings-3.1.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-+zB4RHU7Zrnxr6VOJix0UwfbqOU=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "lodash._reinterpolate": "^3.0.0",
    "lodash.escape": "^3.0.0"
  }
},
"lru-cache": {
  "version": "2.7.3",
```

```
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/lru-cache/-/lru-cache-2.7.3.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-bUUk6LIV+V1PW1iFH0Id1y+06VI=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "make-iterator": {
    "version": "1.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/make-iterator/-/make-iterator-1.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-pxiuXh0iVEq7VM7KMIhs5gxsfxCux2URptUQaXo4iZZJxBzTPOLE2BumO5dbfVYq/hBJFBR/a1mFDmOx5AGmw==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "kind-of": "^6.0.2"
    },
    "dependencies": {
      "kind-of": {
        "version": "6.0.2",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-6.0.2.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha512-s5kLOcnH0XqDO+FvuaLX8DDjZ18CGFk7VygH40QoKPUQhW4e2rvM0rwUq0t8IQDOwYSelK01U90OjzBTme2QqA==",
        "dev": true
      }
    }
  },
  "map-cache": {
    "version": "0.2.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/map-cache/-/map-cache-0.2.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-wyq9C9ZSXZsFFkW7TyasXcmKDb8=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "map-visit": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/map-visit/-/map-visit-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-7Nyo8TFE5mDxtb1B8S80edmN+48=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "object-visit": "^1.0.0"
    }
  },
  "math-random": {
    "version": "1.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/math-random/-/math-random-1.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-izqsWlUkZuSXXjepn97syHgH6w=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "micromatch": {
    "version": "2.3.11",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/micromatch/-/micromatch-2.3.11.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-hmd8I9FyCzY0MdBNDRUpO9OMFWU=",
    "dev": true,
  },
```

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"requires": {
  "arr-diff": "^2.0.0",
  "array-unique": "^0.2.1",
  "braces": "^1.8.2",
  "expand-brackets": "^0.1.4",
  "extglob": "^0.3.1",
  "filename-regex": "^2.0.0",
  "is-extglob": "^1.0.0",
  "is-glob": "^2.0.1",
  "kind-of": "^3.0.2",
  "normalize-path": "^2.0.1",
  "object.omit": "^2.0.0",
  "parse-glob": "^3.0.4",
  "regex-cache": "^0.4.2"
}
},
"mime": {
  "version": "1.4.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/mime/-/mime-1.4.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-Kl1+qOZu5DcW6wayYHSzR/tXKCDC5Om4s1z2QJjDULzLcmf3DvzS7oluY4HCTrc+9FiKmWUgeNLg7W3
ulQvxtQ==",
  "dev": true
},
"mime-db": {
  "version": "1.33.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/mime-db/-/mime-db-1.33.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-BHJ/EKruNIqJf/QahvxwQZXKygoQ256myeN/Ew+THcAa5q+PjyTTMMeNQC4DZw5AwfvelsUrA6B67N
KMqXDbzQ==",
  "dev": true
},
"mime-types": {
  "version": "2.1.18",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/mime-types/-/mime-types-2.1.18.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-lc/aahn+t4/SWV/qcmumYjymLsWfN3ELhpmVuUFjgsORruuZPVSwaQryq+HHGvO/SI2KVX26bx+En+zh
M8g8hQ==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "mime-db": "~1.33.0"
  }
},
"minimatch": {
  "version": "3.0.4",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/minimatch/-/minimatch-3.0.4.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-lc/aahn+t4/SWV/qcmumYjymLsWfN3ELhpmVuUFjgsORruuZPVSwaQryq+HHGvO/SI2KVX26bx+En+zh
M8g8hQ==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {

```

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    "brace-expansion": "^1.1.7"
  },
  "minimist": {
    "version": "1.2.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/minimist/-/minimist-1.2.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-o1A1sg9BOD7sH7kU9M1d95omQoQ=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "mixin-deep": {
    "version": "1.3.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/mixin-deep/-/mixin-deep-1.3.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-8ZltLHeEgaqEvd5IYBXfm4EZSFCX29Jb9K+IAHhDKzReKBQKj3R+7NOF6tjqYi9t4oI8VUfaWITJQm86wnXGNQ==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "for-in": "^1.0.2",
      "is-extendable": "^1.0.1"
    },
    "dependencies": {
      "is-extendable": {
        "version": "1.0.1",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-extendable/-/is-extendable-1.0.1.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha512-arnXMxT1hhoKo9k1LZdmlNnyJdDDfy2v0fXjFlmOk4+i8ul/6WlIbVge9bhM74OpNPQPMGUToDtz+KXa1PneJxOA==",
        "dev": true,
        "requires": {
          "is-plain-object": "^2.0.4"
        }
      }
    }
  },
  "mkdirp": {
    "version": "0.5.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/mkdirp/-/mkdirp-0.5.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-MAV00OrGz3+MR2fzhkjWaX11yQM=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "minimist": "0.0.8"
    },
    "dependencies": {
      "minimist": {
        "version": "0.0.8",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/minimist/-/minimist-0.0.8.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha1-hX/Kv8M5fSYluCKCYuhqp6ARsFO=",
        "dev": true
      }
    }
  },
},

```

```

"ms": {
  "version": "2.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/ms/-/ms-2.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-VgiurfwAvmwpAd9fmGF4jeDVI8g=",
  "dev": true
},
"multipipe": {
  "version": "0.1.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/multipipe/-/multipipe-0.1.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-Ko8t33Du1WTf8tV/HhoTfZ8FB4s=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "duplexer2": "0.0.2"
  }
},
"nan": {
  "version": "2.10.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/nan/-/nan-2.10.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-bAdJv7fBLhWC+/BlS0Oza+mvTaNQTP+1RyhvhvD95pgUJz6XM5IzgmXOkItJ9tkoCiplvAnXI1tNmmUD/eScyA==",
  "dev": true,
  "optional": true
},
"nanomatch": {
  "version": "1.2.9",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/nanomatch/-/nanomatch-1.2.9.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-118661013041392T1b531324w01314739429408911790018347218346246766",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "arr-diff": "^4.0.0",
    "array-unique": "^0.3.2",
    "define-property": "^2.0.2",
    "extend-shallow": "^3.0.2",
    "fragment-cache": "^0.2.1",
    "is-odd": "^2.0.0",
    "is-windows": "^1.0.2",
    "kind-of": "^6.0.2",
    "object.pick": "^1.3.0",
    "regex-not": "^1.0.0",
    "snapdragon": "^0.8.1",
    "to-regex": "^3.0.1"
  }
},
"dependencies": {
  "arr-diff": {
    "version": "4.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/arr-diff/-/arr-diff-4.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-1UJ1+P8L4BkMJL3o2B06ZtG88Y=",
    "dev": true
  }
}

```

```

    },
    "array-unique": {
      "version": "0.3.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/array-unique/-/array-unique-0.3.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-qJS3XUvE9s1nnvMkSp/Y9Gri1Cg=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "kind-of": {
      "version": "6.0.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-6.0.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-s5kLOcnH0XqDO+FvuaLX8DDjZ18CGFk7VygH40QoKPUQhW4e2rvM0rwUq0t8IQDOWYSeLK01U90Ojz
BTme2QqA==",
      "dev": true
    }
  },
  "natives": {
    "version": "1.1.3",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/natives/-/natives-1.1.3.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-BZGSYV4YOLxzoTK73l0/s/0sH9l8SHs2ocReMH1f8JYSh5FUWu4ZrKcPjDkRkWXV6HFR/pZDz7bwWOVA
Y07q77g==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "negotiator": {
    "version": "0.6.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/negotiator/-/negotiator-0.6.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-KzJxhOiZIQEXeyhWP7XnECrNDKk=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "normalize-package-data": {
    "version": "2.4.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/normalize-package-data/-/normalize-package-data-
2.4.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-9jjUFbTPfEy3R/ad/2oNbKtW9Hgovi5O1FvFWKkKbINXoN/Oou6+9+KKohPK13Yc3/TyunyWhJp6gvRNR
/PPAw==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "hosted-git-info": "^2.1.4",
      "is-builtin-module": "^1.0.0",
      "semver": "2 || 3 || 4 || 5",
      "validate-npm-package-license": "^3.0.1"
    }
  },
  "normalize-path": {
    "version": "2.1.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/normalize-path/-/normalize-path-2.1.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-GrKLVW4Zg2Oowab35vogE3/mrtk=",
    "dev": true,

```

```
"requires": {
  "remove-trailing-separator": "^1.0.1"
},
"number-is-nan": {
  "version": "1.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/number-is-nan/-/number-is-nan-1.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-CXtgK1NCKIIsGvuHkDGDNPQaAR0=",
  "dev": true
},
"object-assign": {
  "version": "4.1.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/object-assign/-/object-assign-4.1.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-lQmtx5ZYh8/AXLvUQsrlv7s2CGM=",
  "dev": true
},
"object-component": {
  "version": "0.0.3",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/object-component/-/object-component-0.0.3.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-8MaapQ78IbhmwYb0AKM3acsvEpE=",
  "dev": true
},
"object-copy": {
  "version": "0.1.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/object-copy/-/object-copy-0.1.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-fn2Fi3gb18mRpBupde04EnVOmYw=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "copy-descriptor": "^0.1.0",
    "define-property": "^0.2.5",
    "kind-of": "^3.0.3"
  }
},
"dependencies": {
  "define-property": {
    "version": "0.2.5",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/define-property/-/define-property-0.2.5.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-w1se+RjsPJKPmlvFe+BKR0xcgRY=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-descriptor": "^0.1.0"
    }
  }
},
"object-path": {
  "version": "0.9.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/object-path/-/object-path-0.9.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-D9mnT8X60a45aLWGvaXGMr1sBaU=",
  "dev": true
},
"object-visit": {
```

```
"version": "1.0.1",
"resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/object-visit/-/object-visit-1.0.1.tgz",
"integrity": "sha1-95xEk68MU3e1n+OdOV5BBC3QRbs=",
"dev": true,
"requires": {
  "isobject": "^3.0.0"
},
"dependencies": {
  "isobject": {
    "version": "3.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isobject/-/isobject-3.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-TkMekrEalzFjaqH5yNHMvP2reN8=",
    "dev": true
  }
}
},
"object.defaults": {
  "version": "1.1.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/object.defaults/-/object.defaults-1.1.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-On+GgzS0B96gbaFtiNXNKeQ1/s8=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "array-each": "^1.0.1",
    "array-slice": "^1.0.0",
    "for-own": "^1.0.0",
    "isobject": "^3.0.0"
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "for-own": {
      "version": "1.0.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/for-own/-/for-own-1.0.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-xjMy9BXO3EsE2/5wz4NkIMU8tEs=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "for-in": "^1.0.1"
      }
    },
    "isobject": {
      "version": "3.0.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isobject/-/isobject-3.0.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-TkMekrEalzFjaqH5yNHMvP2reN8=",
      "dev": true
    }
  }
},
"object.map": {
  "version": "1.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/object.map/-/object.map-1.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-z4Plncj8wK1fQIDh94s7gb2AHTc=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
```

```
    "for-own": "^1.0.0",
    "make-iterator": "^1.0.0"
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "for-own": {
      "version": "1.0.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/for-own/-/for-own-1.0.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-xjMy9BXO3EsE2/5wz4NklMU8tEs=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "for-in": "^1.0.1"
      }
    }
  }
},
"object.omit": {
  "version": "2.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/object.omit/-/object.omit-2.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-Gpx0SCznbnufjHbKNXmuKITr0fo=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "for-own": "^0.1.4",
    "is-extendable": "^0.1.1"
  }
},
"object.pick": {
  "version": "1.3.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/object.pick/-/object.pick-1.3.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-h6EKxMFpS9Lhy/U1kaZhQftd10c=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "isobject": "^3.0.1"
  }
},
"dependencies": {
  "isobject": {
    "version": "3.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isobject/-/isobject-3.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-TkMekrEalzFjaqH5yNHMvP2reN8=",
    "dev": true
  }
}
},
"on-finished": {
  "version": "2.3.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/on-finished/-/on-finished-2.3.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-IPeZzIGwg811M3mSoWlxqi2QaUc=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "ee-first": "1.1.1"
  }
},
}
```

```
"once": {
  "version": "1.3.3",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/once/-/once-1.3.3.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-suJhVXzkwxTsgwTz+oJmPkKXyiA=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "wrappy": "1"
  }
},
"openurl": {
  "version": "1.1.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/openurl/-/openurl-1.1.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-OHW0sO96UsFW8NtB1GCduw+Us4c=",
  "dev": true
},
"opn": {
  "version": "4.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/opn/-/opn-4.0.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-erwi5kTf9jsKltWrfyeQwPAavJU=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "object-assign": "^4.0.1",
    "pinkie-promise": "^2.0.0"
  }
},
"orchestrator": {
  "version": "0.3.8",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/orchestrator/-/orchestrator-0.3.8.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-FOfp4nZPcxX7rBhOUGx6pt+UrX4=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "end-of-stream": "~0.1.5",
    "sequencify": "~0.0.7",
    "stream-consume": "~0.1.0"
  }
},
"ordered-read-streams": {
  "version": "0.1.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/ordered-read-streams/-/ordered-read-streams-0.1.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-VZamvjrRHO6abbtijQ1LLVS8SY=",
  "dev": true
},
"os-homedir": {
  "version": "1.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/os-homedir/-/os-homedir-1.0.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-7xJiDNuDoM94MFox+8VISGqf7M=",
  "dev": true
},
"os-locale": {
  "version": "1.4.0",
```

```
"resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/os-locale/-/os-locale-1.4.0.tgz",
"integrity": "sha1-IPnxuKe00XoveWDsT0gCYA8FNk=",
"dev": true,
"requires": {
  "lcid": "^1.0.0"
}
},
"parse-filepath": {
"version": "1.0.2",
"resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/parse-filepath/-/parse-filepath-1.0.2.tgz",
"integrity": "sha1-pjISf1Oq89FYdvWHLz/6x2PWYJE=",
"dev": true,
"requires": {
  "is-absolute": "^1.0.0",
  "map-cache": "^0.2.0",
  "path-root": "^0.1.1"
}
},
"parse-glob": {
"version": "3.0.4",
"resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/parse-glob/-/parse-glob-3.0.4.tgz",
"integrity": "sha1-ssN2z7EfNVE7rdFz7wu246OIORw=",
"dev": true,
"requires": {
  "glob-base": "^0.3.0",
  "is-dotfile": "^1.0.0",
  "is-extglob": "^1.0.0",
  "is-glob": "^2.0.0"
}
},
"parse-json": {
"version": "2.2.0",
"resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/parse-json/-/parse-json-2.2.0.tgz",
"integrity": "sha1-9ID0BDTVgHQfhGkIn43qGPVaTck=",
"dev": true,
"requires": {
  "error-ex": "^1.2.0"
}
},
"parse-passwd": {
"version": "1.0.0",
"resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/parse-passwd/-/parse-passwd-1.0.0.tgz",
"integrity": "sha1-bVuTskVpk7I9N/QKOC1vFmao5cY=",
"dev": true
},
"parseqs": {
"version": "0.0.5",
"resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/parseqs/-/parseqs-0.0.5.tgz",
"integrity": "sha1-1SCKNzjkZ2bikbouXNoSSGouJ0=",
"dev": true,
"requires": {
```

```
    "better-assert": "~1.0.0"
  }
},
"parseuri": {
  "version": "0.0.5",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/parseuri/-/parseuri-0.0.5.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-gCBKUNTbt3m/3G6+J3jZDkvOMgo=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "better-assert": "~1.0.0"
  }
},
"parseurl": {
  "version": "1.3.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/parseurl/-/parseurl-1.3.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-/CidTtiZMRIGDBViUyYs3I3mW/M=",
  "dev": true
},
"pascalcase": {
  "version": "0.1.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/pascalcase/-/pascalcase-0.1.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-s2PIXoAGym/iF4TS2yK9FdeRfxQ=",
  "dev": true
},
"path-exists": {
  "version": "2.1.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/path-exists/-/path-exists-2.1.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-D+tsZPD8UY2adU3V77YscCJ2H0s=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "pinkie-promise": "^2.0.0"
  }
},
"path-is-absolute": {
  "version": "1.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/path-is-absolute/-/path-is-absolute-1.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-F0uSaHNVNP+8es5r9TpanhtcX18=",
  "dev": true
},
"path-parse": {
  "version": "1.0.5",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/path-parse/-/path-parse-1.0.5.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-PBrfhx6pzWyUMbbqK9dKD/BVxME=",
  "dev": true
},
"path-root": {
  "version": "0.1.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/path-root/-/path-root-0.1.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-mkpoFMrBwM1zNgqV8yCDyOpHRbc=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
```

```
    "path-root-regex": "^0.1.0"
  }
},
"path-root-regex": {
  "version": "0.1.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/path-root-regex/-/path-root-regex-0.1.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-v8zcfWxLcUsi0PsONGNcsBLqW0=",
  "dev": true
},
"path-type": {
  "version": "1.1.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/path-type/-/path-type-1.1.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-WcRPfuSR2nBNpBXaWkBwuk+P5EE=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "graceful-fs": "^4.1.2",
    "pify": "^2.0.0",
    "pinkie-promise": "^2.0.0"
  }
},
"pify": {
  "version": "2.3.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/pify/-/pify-2.3.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-7RQaasBDqEnqWISY59yosVMw6Qw=",
  "dev": true
},
"pinkie": {
  "version": "2.0.4",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/pinkie/-/pinkie-2.0.4.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-clVrgM+g1lqXToDnckjoDtT3+HA=",
  "dev": true
},
"pinkie-promise": {
  "version": "2.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/pinkie-promise/-/pinkie-promise-2.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-ITXW36ejWMBprJsXh3YogihFD/o=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "pinkie": "^2.0.0"
  }
},
"portscanner": {
  "version": "2.1.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/portscanner/-/portscanner-2.1.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-6rtAnk3iSVD1oqUW01rnaTQ/u5Y=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "async": "1.5.2",
    "is-number-like": "^1.0.3"
  }
},
}
```

```

    "posix-character-classes": {
      "version": "0.1.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/posix-character-classes/-/posix-character-classes-0.1.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-AerA/jta9xoqbAL+q7jB/vfgDqs=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "preserve": {
      "version": "0.2.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/preserve/-/preserve-0.2.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-gV7R9uvGWSb4ZbMQwHE7yzMVzks=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "pretty-hrtime": {
      "version": "1.0.3",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/pretty-hrtime/-/pretty-hrtime-1.0.3.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-t+PqQkNaTJsnWdmeDyAesZWALuE=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "process-nextick-args": {
      "version": "1.0.7",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/process-nextick-args/-/process-nextick-args-1.0.7.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-FQ4gt1ZZCtP5EJPyWk8q2L/zC6M=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "qs": {
      "version": "6.2.3",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/qs/-/qs-6.2.3.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-HPyyXBCpsrSDBT/zn138kjOQjP4=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "randomatic": {
      "version": "3.0.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/randomatic/-/randomatic-3.0.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-VdxFOIEY3mNO5PtSRkkle/hPJDHvQhK21oa73K4yAc9qmp6N429gAyF1gZMOTMeS0/AYzaV/2Trcef+NalonSA==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "is-number": "^4.0.0",
        "kind-of": "^6.0.0",
        "math-random": "^1.0.1"
      }
    },
    "dependencies": {
      "is-number": {
        "version": "4.0.0",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-number/-/is-number-4.0.0.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha512-Vq2k9/V7vGC2NpOG6DQzRqHwX3Jwz933UkPM0c2n9XfZk49wqY196em7XqRwQQMAw4sX9Y8VIb4tu2wvZw=="
      }
    },
    "dev": true
  }
}

```

```

    },
    "kind-of": {
      "version": "6.0.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-6.0.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-s5kLOcnH0XqDO+FvuaLX8DDJZ18CGFk7VygH40QoKPUQhW4e2rvM0rwUq0t8IQDOWySeLK01U90Qjz
BTme2QqA==",
      "dev": true
    }
  },
  "range-parser": {
    "version": "1.2.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/range-parser/-/range-parser-1.2.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-9JvmtleJTdxA3MIKMi9hEJLgDV4=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "raw-body": {
    "version": "2.3.3",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/raw-body/-/raw-body-2.3.3.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-9esiElv1BrZol3rCDuOuKCBRbuApGGaDPQfjSfIGxdy4oyzqghxu6klEkkVlvBje+FF0BX9coEv8KqW6X/7nj
w==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "bytes": "3.0.0",
      "http-errors": "1.6.3",
      "iconv-lite": "0.4.23",
      "unpipe": "1.0.0"
    }
  },
  "read-pkg": {
    "version": "1.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/read-pkg/-/read-pkg-1.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-9f+qXs0pyzHAR0vKfXVra7KePyg=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "load-json-file": "^1.0.0",
      "normalize-package-data": "^2.3.2",
      "path-type": "^1.0.0"
    }
  },
  "read-pkg-up": {
    "version": "1.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/read-pkg-up/-/read-pkg-up-1.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-nWPBMnbAZZGNV/ACpX9AobZD+wI=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "find-up": "^1.0.0",
      "read-pkg": "^1.0.0"
    }
  }
}

```

```
  },
  "readable-stream": {
    "version": "2.3.3",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/readable-stream/-/readable-stream-2.3.3.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-m+qzzcn7KUXEmd1gMbchF+Y2elUbieUaxkWtptyHywrX0rE8QEYqPC07Vuy4Wm32/xE16NcdBctb8S0
Xe/5leQ==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "core-util-is": "~1.0.0",
      "inherits": "~2.0.3",
      "isarray": "~1.0.0",
      "process-nextick-args": "~1.0.6",
      "safe-buffer": "~5.1.1",
      "string_decoder": "~1.0.3",
      "util-deprecate": "~1.0.1"
    },
    "dependencies": {
      "isarray": {
        "version": "1.0.0",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isarray/-/isarray-1.0.0.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha1-u5NdSFgsuhaMBoNJV6VKPgcSTxE=",
        "dev": true
      }
    }
  },
  "readdirp": {
    "version": "2.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/readdirp/-/readdirp-2.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-TtCtBg3zBzMAXIRANz9y0cxkLXg=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "graceful-fs": "^4.1.2",
      "minimatch": "^3.0.2",
      "readable-stream": "^2.0.2",
      "set-immediate-shim": "^1.0.1"
    }
  },
  "rechoir": {
    "version": "0.6.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/rechoir/-/rechoir-0.6.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-hSBLVNuoLVdC4oyWdW70OvUOM4Q=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "resolve": "^1.1.6"
    }
  },
  "regex-cache": {
    "version": "0.4.4",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/regex-cache/-/regex-cache-0.4.4.tgz",
```

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    "integrity": "sha512-
nVIZwtCjkC9YgvWkpM55B5rBhBYRZhAaJbgcFYXXsHnbZ9UZI9nnVWYZpBlCqv9ho2eZryPnWrZGsOdP
wVWXWQ==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-equal-shallow": "^0.1.3"
    }
  },
  "regex-not": {
    "version": "1.0.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/regex-not/-/regex-not-1.0.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-
J6SDjUgDxQj5NusnOtdFxDwN/+HWykr8GELwctJ7mdqhcyy1xEc4SRFHUXvxTp661YaVKAjfRLZ9cCqS6t
n32A==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "extend-shallow": "^3.0.2",
      "safe-regex": "^1.1.0"
    }
  },
  "remove-trailing-separator": {
    "version": "1.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/remove-trailing-separator/-/remove-trailing-
separator-1.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-wkvOKig62tW8P1jg1IJJuSN52O8=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "repeat-element": {
    "version": "1.1.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/repeat-element/-/repeat-element-1.1.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-7wiaF40Ug7quTZPrmLT55OEdmQo=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "repeat-string": {
    "version": "1.6.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/repeat-string/-/repeat-string-1.6.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-jcrkcOHlirwtYA//Sndihtp15jc=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "replace-ext": {
    "version": "0.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/replace-ext/-/replace-ext-0.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-KbvZIHinOfC8zitO5B6DeVNSKSQ=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "require-directory": {
    "version": "2.1.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/require-directory/-/require-directory-2.1.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-jGStX9MnqxyXbiNE/+f3kqam30l=",
    "dev": true
  },
}
```

```

"require-main-filename": {
  "version": "1.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/require-main-filename/-/require-main-filename-1.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-l/cXtp1leE9fUmpsWqj/3aBVpNE=",
  "dev": true
},
"requires-port": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/requires-port/-/requires-port-1.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-kI0mAdOaxlXgkc8NpcbmlNw9yv8=",
  "dev": true
},
"resolve": {
  "version": "1.7.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/resolve/-/resolve-1.7.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-c7rwLofp8g1U+h1KNyHL/jicrKg1Ek4q+Lr33AL65uZTinUZHe30D5HlyN5V9NW0JX1D5dXQ4jqW5I7Sy/kGfw==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "path-parse": "^1.0.5"
  }
},
"resolve-dir": {
  "version": "1.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/resolve-dir/-/resolve-dir-1.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-eaQGRMNivoLybv/nOcm7U4IEb0M=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "expand-tilde": "^2.0.0",
    "global-modules": "^1.0.0"
  }
},
"resolve-url": {
  "version": "0.2.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/resolve-url/-/resolve-url-0.2.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-LGN/53yJOv0qZj/iGqkiAGjiBSo=",
  "dev": true
},
"resp-modifier": {
  "version": "6.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/resp-modifier/-/resp-modifier-6.0.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-sSTeXE+6/LpUH0j/pzlw9KpFa08=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "debug": "^2.2.0",
    "minimatch": "^3.0.2"
  }
},
"ret": {

```

```

    "version": "0.1.15",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/ret/-/ret-0.1.15.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-
TTIYpa+OL+vMMNG24xSIQGEJ3B/RzEfUilct7b5G/ytav+wPrplCpVMFuWzXbkecJrb6IYo1iFb0S9v37754
mg==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "rx": {
    "version": "4.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/rx/-/rx-4.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-pfE/957zt0D+MKqAP7CfmIBdR4I=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "safe-buffer": {
    "version": "5.1.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/safe-buffer/-/safe-buffer-5.1.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-
kKvNjn6Mm93gAczWVJg7wH+wGYWNRdHdWvpUmHyEsgCtlww03bqPtV4tR5tuPaUhtOo/kvhVwd8
XwwOllGYkbg==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "safe-regex": {
    "version": "1.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/safe-regex/-/safe-regex-1.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-QKNmnzsHfr6UPURinhV91IAjvy4=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "ret": "~0.1.10"
    }
  },
  "safer-buffer": {
    "version": "2.1.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/safer-buffer/-/safer-buffer-2.1.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-
YZo3K82SD7Riyi0E1EQPojLz7kpepnSQI9IyPbHHg1XXXevb5dJI7tpyN2ADxGcQbHG7vcyRHk0cbwqcQri
Utg==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "semver": {
    "version": "5.5.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/semver/-/semver-5.5.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-
4SJ3dm0WAwWy/NVeioZh5AntkdJoWKxHxcmyP622fOkgHa4z3R0TdBJICINyaSDE6uNwVc8gZr+ZinwZ
AH4xIA==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "send": {
    "version": "0.16.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/send/-/send-0.16.2.tgz",

```

```
    "integrity": "sha512-
E64YFPUsFHEFBvbbjr44NCLtI1AohxQ8ZSiJQLskAdKuriYEP6VyGEsRDH8ScozGpkaX1BGvhanqCwkce
Zw==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "debug": "2.6.9",
      "depd": "~1.1.2",
      "destroy": "~1.0.4",
      "encodeurl": "~1.0.2",
      "escape-html": "~1.0.3",
      "etag": "~1.8.1",
      "fresh": "0.5.2",
      "http-errors": "~1.6.2",
      "mime": "1.4.1",
      "ms": "2.0.0",
      "on-finished": "~2.3.0",
      "range-parser": "~1.2.0",
      "statuses": "~1.4.0"
    },
    "dependencies": {
      "statuses": {
        "version": "1.4.0",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/statuses/-/statuses-1.4.0.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha512-
zhSctt8v2NdrRIPQpCNTw/heZLtfUDqxBM1udqikb/Hbk52LK4nQSwr10u77iopCW5LsyHpuXSOGnEc48
mLeew==",
        "dev": true
      }
    }
  },
  "sequencify": {
    "version": "0.0.7",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/sequencify/-/sequencify-0.0.7.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-kM/xnQLgcCf9dn9erT57ldHnOAw=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "serve-index": {
    "version": "1.9.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/serve-index/-/serve-index-1.9.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-03aNabHn2C5c4FD/9bRTvqEqkjk=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "accepts": "~1.3.4",
      "batch": "0.6.1",
      "debug": "2.6.9",
      "escape-html": "~1.0.3",
      "http-errors": "~1.6.2",
      "mime-types": "~2.1.17",
      "parseurl": "~1.3.2"
    }
  },
}
```

```

"serve-static": {
  "version": "1.13.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/serve-static/-/serve-static-1.13.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-
p/tJrO4U387R9oMjb1oj7qSMaMfmOyd4j9hOFoxZe2baQszgHcSWjuya/CiT5kgZZKRudHNOA0pYXOI
8rQ5nw==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "encodeurl": "~1.0.2",
    "escape-html": "~1.0.3",
    "parseurl": "~1.3.2",
    "send": "0.16.2"
  }
},
"server-destroy": {
  "version": "1.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/server-destroy/-/server-destroy-1.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-8Tv5K0QrnD55OD5hzDmYtdFObN0=",
  "dev": true
},
"set-blocking": {
  "version": "2.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/set-blocking/-/set-blocking-2.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-BF+XgtARppoA93TgrJDkrPYkPc=",
  "dev": true
},
"set-immediate-shim": {
  "version": "1.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/set-immediate-shim/-/set-immediate-shim-1.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-SysbJ+uAip+NzEgaWOXlb1mfP2E=",
  "dev": true
},
"set-value": {
  "version": "2.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/set-value/-/set-value-2.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-
hw0yxk9GT/Hr5yJEYnHNKYXkIA8mVJgd9ditYZCe16ZzcaELYYcfvaXesNACK2O8O0nTIPQcQhGUQj8JLz
eeg==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "extend-shallow": "^2.0.1",
    "is-extendable": "^0.1.1",
    "is-plain-object": "^2.0.3",
    "split-string": "^3.0.1"
  }
},
"dependencies": {
  "extend-shallow": {
    "version": "2.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/extend-shallow/-/extend-shallow-2.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Ua99YUrZqfYQ6huvu5idaxxWiQ8=",
    "dev": true,

```

```

    "requires": {
      "is-extendable": "^0.1.0"
    }
  },
  "setprototypeof": {
    "version": "1.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/setprototypeof/-/setprototypeof-1.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-BvE/TwpZX4FXExxOxZyRGQQv651MSwmWKZGqvmPcRijDqWub67kTKuIMx43cZZrS/cBBzwBcNDWoF
xt2XEFlpQ==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "sigmund": {
    "version": "1.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/sigmund/-/sigmund-1.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-P/IfGYytIXX587eBhT/ZTQ0ZtZA=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "snapdragon": {
    "version": "0.8.2",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/snapdragon/-/snapdragon-0.8.2.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-FtyOnWN/wCHTVXOMwvSv26d+ko5vWIIDD6zoUJ7LW8vh+ZBC8QdljveRP+crNrtBwioEUWy/4dMtbBj
A4ioNlg==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "base": "^0.11.1",
      "debug": "^2.2.0",
      "define-property": "^0.2.5",
      "extend-shallow": "^2.0.1",
      "map-cache": "^0.2.2",
      "source-map": "^0.5.6",
      "source-map-resolve": "^0.5.0",
      "use": "^3.1.0"
    }
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "define-property": {
      "version": "0.2.5",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/define-property/-/define-property-0.2.5.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-w1se+RjsPjkPmlvFe+BKrOxcgRY=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "is-descriptor": "^0.1.0"
      }
    }
  },
  "extend-shallow": {
    "version": "2.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/extend-shallow/-/extend-shallow-2.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Ua99YUrZqfYQ6huvu5idaxxWiQ8=",

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      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "is-extendable": "^0.1.0"
      }
    }
  },
  "snapdragon-node": {
    "version": "2.1.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/snapdragon-node/-/snapdragon-node-2.1.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-O27I4xaMYt/RSQ5TR3vpWCAB5Kb/czIcquFOM/C4fyCLnBZUc1PkjTAMjof2pBWaSTwOUd6qUHcFGVG
j7alwnw==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "define-property": "^1.0.0",
      "isobject": "^3.0.0",
      "snapdragon-util": "^3.0.1"
    },
    "dependencies": {
      "define-property": {
        "version": "1.0.0",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/define-property/-/define-property-1.0.0.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha1-dp66rz9KY6rTr56NMEybnm/sOY=",
        "dev": true,
        "requires": {
          "is-descriptor": "^1.0.0"
        }
      },
      "is-accessor-descriptor": {
        "version": "1.0.0",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-accessor-descriptor/-/is-accessor-descriptor-
1.0.0.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha512-m5hnHTkcVsPfqx3AKlyttIPb7J+XykHvJP2B9bZDjlhLioEeq4XoK64Vg7boZIVWYK6LUY94dYPEE7Lh0ZkZK
cQ==",
        "dev": true,
        "requires": {
          "kind-of": "^6.0.0"
        }
      },
      "is-data-descriptor": {
        "version": "1.0.0",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-data-descriptor/-/is-data-descriptor-1.0.0.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha512-jbRXY1FmtAoCjQkVmIVyWuuqDFUbaOeDjmed1tOGPrsMhtJA4rD9tkgA0F1qJ3gRFRXcHYVkdeaP50Q5
rE/jLQ==",
        "dev": true,
        "requires": {
          "kind-of": "^6.0.0"
        }
      }
    }
  }
}

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```

    },
    "is-descriptor": {
      "version": "1.0.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-descriptor/-/is-descriptor-1.0.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-2eis5WqQGV7peooDyLmNEPurps9+SXX5c9pL3xEB+4e9HnGuDa7mB7kHxHw4CbqS9k1T2hOH3miL8n8WtiYVtg==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "is-accessor-descriptor": "^1.0.0",
        "is-data-descriptor": "^1.0.0",
        "kind-of": "^6.0.2"
      }
    },
    "isobject": {
      "version": "3.0.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isobject/-/isobject-3.0.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-TkMekrEalzFjaqH5yNHMvP2reN8=",
      "dev": true
    },
    "kind-of": {
      "version": "6.0.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-6.0.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-SQA4115+k2dEa66Q8XgkH44E656u0G5Bc748t61T3yZ6jZvYl8zUCNc4xP9XtuGqM4yL8H5w3y86/4w==",
      "dev": true
    },
    "snapdragon-util": {
      "version": "3.0.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/snapdragon-util/-/snapdragon-util-3.0.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-mbKkMdQKsjX4BAL4bRYTj21edOf8cN7XHdYUJEE+Zn99hVEYcMvKPct1IqNe7+AZPirn8BCDOQBHQZknqmKIZQ==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "kind-of": "^3.2.0"
      }
    },
    "socket.io": {
      "version": "2.1.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/socket.io/-/socket.io-2.1.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-rORq9c+7W0DAK3cleWNSyfv/qKXV99hV4tZe+gGLfBECw3XEhBy7x85F3wypA9688LKjtwO9pX9L33/xQl8yA==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "debug": "~3.1.0",
        "engine.io": "~3.2.0",

```

```

    "has-binary2": "~1.0.2",
    "socket.io-adapter": "~1.1.0",
    "socket.io-client": "2.1.1",
    "socket.io-parser": "~3.2.0"
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "debug": {
      "version": "3.1.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/debug/-/debug-3.1.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-OX8XqP7/1a9cqkxYw2yXss15f26NKWBpDXQd0/uK/KPqdQhxbPa994hznjcE2VqQpDsIf55723cKPUOG
SmMY3g==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "ms": "2.0.0"
      }
    },
    "engine.io-client": {
      "version": "3.2.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/engine.io-client/-/engine.io-client-3.2.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-y5AbkytWeM4jQr7m/koQLc5AxpRKC1hEVUb/s1FUAWElJq5AzzJJ4NLvzuKPuxtDi5Mq755WuDvZ6lv2rXj
4PTzw==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "component-emitter": "1.2.1",
        "component-inherit": "0.0.3",
        "debug": "~3.1.0",
        "engine.io-parser": "~2.1.1",
        "has-cors": "1.1.0",
        "indexof": "0.0.1",
        "parseqs": "0.0.5",
        "parseuri": "0.0.5",
        "ws": "~3.3.1",
        "xmlhttprequest-ssl": "~1.5.4",
        "yeast": "0.1.2"
      }
    },
    "socket.io-client": {
      "version": "2.1.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/socket.io-client/-/socket.io-client-2.1.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-jxnFyhAuFxFyfqlduQlhqTcOEQSn+OHKvFAxWaNWa7ecP7xSNk2Dx/3UEsDcY7NcFafxNvKPmmO7H
TwTxGQ==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "backo2": "1.0.2",
        "base64-arraybuffer": "0.1.5",
        "component-bind": "1.0.0",
        "component-emitter": "1.2.1",
        "debug": "~3.1.0",

```

```

    "engine.io-client": "~3.2.0",
    "has-binary2": "~1.0.2",
    "has-cors": "1.1.0",
    "indexof": "0.0.1",
    "object-component": "0.0.3",
    "parseqs": "0.0.5",
    "parseuri": "0.0.5",
    "socket.io-parser": "~3.2.0",
    "to-array": "0.1.4"
  }
},
"socket.io-parser": {
  "version": "3.2.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/socket.io-parser/-/socket.io-parser-3.2.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-FYiBx7rc/KORMJlgsXysfIWx/RlvtqZbyGLIHZvjfmPTPeuD/I8MaW7cfFrj5tRltICJdgwflhfZ3NVVbVLFQA=
=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "component-emitter": "1.2.1",
    "debug": "~3.1.0",
    "isarray": "2.0.1"
  }
}
},
"socket.io-adapter": {
  "version": "1.1.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/socket.io-adapter/-/socket.io-adapter-1.1.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-KoBeihTWNyEk3ZFZrUUC+MsH8Gs=",
  "dev": true
},
"socket.io-client": {
  "version": "2.0.4",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/socket.io-client/-/socket.io-client-2.0.4.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-CRilUkBtxeVAs4Dc2Xr8SmQzL44=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "backo2": "1.0.2",
    "base64-arraybuffer": "0.1.5",
    "component-bind": "1.0.0",
    "component-emitter": "1.2.1",
    "debug": "~2.6.4",
    "engine.io-client": "~3.1.0",
    "has-cors": "1.1.0",
    "indexof": "0.0.1",
    "object-component": "0.0.3",
    "parseqs": "0.0.5",
    "parseuri": "0.0.5",
    "socket.io-parser": "~3.1.1",
    "to-array": "0.1.4"
  }
}

```

```

    }
  },
  "socket.io-parser": {
    "version": "3.1.3",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/socket.io-parser/-/socket.io-parser-3.1.3.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-gOa2HPqLguqAczs3dMECuA1RgoGFPyvDqcbadeEdCWY9g59kdUAz3YRmaJBnkXflrHNwB7Q12Gkf/OCZ
XfdHR7g==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "component-emitter": "1.2.1",
      "debug": "~3.1.0",
      "has-binary2": "~1.0.2",
      "isarray": "2.0.1"
    }
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "debug": {
      "version": "3.1.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/debug/-/debug-3.1.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-OX8XqP7/1a9cqkxYw2yXss15f26NKWBpDXQd0/uK/KPqdQhxbPa994honzjcE2VqQpDslf55723cKPUOG
SmMY3g==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "ms": "2.0.0"
      }
    }
  }
},
"source-map": {
  "version": "0.5.7",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/source-map/-/source-map-0.5.7.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-igOdLRAh0i0eoUyA2OpGi6LvP8w=",
  "dev": true
},
"source-map-resolve": {
  "version": "0.5.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/source-map-resolve/-/source-map-resolve-0.5.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-0KW2wvzfxm8NCTb30z0LMNYPqWCdDGE2viwzUaucqJdkTRXtZiSY3I+2A6nVAjmdOy0I4gU8DwnVVG
sk9jvP2A==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "atob": "^2.0.0",
    "decode-uri-component": "^0.2.0",
    "resolve-url": "^0.2.1",
    "source-map-url": "^0.4.0",
    "urix": "^0.1.0"
  }
},
"source-map-url": {

```

```

    "version": "0.4.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/source-map-url/-/source-map-url-0.4.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-PpNdfd1zYxuXZZIW1VEo6HtQhKM=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "sparkles": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/sparkles/-/sparkles-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Gsu/tZJDbRC76PeFt8xvgoFQEsM=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "spdx-correct": {
    "version": "3.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/spdx-correct/-/spdx-correct-3.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-N19o9z5cEyc8yQQPukRCZ9EUmb4HUPnrmaL/fxS2pBo2jbfCFRVuFZ/oFC+vZz0MNNk0h80iMn5/S6qGZOL5+g==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "spdx-expression-parse": "^3.0.0",
      "spdx-license-ids": "^3.0.0"
    }
  },
  "spdx-exceptions": {
    "version": "2.1.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/spdx-exceptions/-/spdx-exceptions-2.1.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-4K1NsmrlCU1JJgUrtgEeTVyfx8VaYea9J9LvARxhbHtVtohPs/gFGG5yy49beySjIIIMhhXZ4QqujIZEfS4l6Cg==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "spdx-expression-parse": {
    "version": "3.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/spdx-expression-parse/-/spdx-expression-parse-3.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-Yg6D3XpRD4kkOmTpdgbUiEJFKghJH03fIC1OPII5h/0sO6neh2jqRDVHOQ4o/LMea0tgCkbMgea5ip/e+MkWyg==",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "spdx-exceptions": "^2.1.0",
      "spdx-license-ids": "^3.0.0"
    }
  },
  "spdx-license-ids": {
    "version": "3.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/spdx-license-ids/-/spdx-license-ids-3.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-2+EPwgbnmOI8HjGBXXMd9NAu02vLjOO1nWw4kmeRDFyHn+M/ETfHxQUK0oXg8ctgVnI9t3rosNVsZ1jG61nDA==",
    "dev": true
  }

```

```

    },
    "split-string": {
      "version": "3.1.0",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/split-string/-/split-string-3.1.0.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-NzNVhJDYpwceVVii8/Hu6DKfD2G+NrQHIS/V/qgv763EYudVwEcMQNxd2lh+0VrUByXN/oJkI5grOhYW
vQUYiw==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "extend-shallow": "^3.0.0"
      }
    },
    "static-extend": {
      "version": "0.1.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/static-extend/-/static-extend-0.1.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-YICcOcv/VTNyJv1eC1IPNB8ftcY=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "define-property": "^0.2.5",
        "object-copy": "^0.1.0"
      }
    },
    "dependencies": {
      "define-property": {
        "version": "0.2.5",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/define-property/-/define-property-0.2.5.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha1-w1se+RjsPjkPmlvFe+BKR0xcgRY=",
        "dev": true,
        "requires": {
          "is-descriptor": "^0.1.0"
        }
      }
    }
  },
  "statuses": {
    "version": "1.3.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/statuses/-/statuses-1.3.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-+vUbnrdKrvOzrPStX2Gr8ky3uT4=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "stream-consume": {
    "version": "0.1.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/stream-consume/-/stream-consume-0.1.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-tNa3hzgkjEP7XbCkbRXe1jpg+ievoa0O4SCFIMOYEscGSS4JJsckGL8swUyAa/ApGU3Ae4t6Honor4HhL+t
Ryg==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "stream-throttle": {
    "version": "0.1.3",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/stream-throttle/-/stream-throttle-0.1.3.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-rdV8jXzHOoFjDTHNVdOWHP7qcM=",

```

```
"dev": true,
"requires": {
  "commander": "^2.2.0",
  "limiter": ^1.0.5"
}
},
"string-width": {
  "version": "1.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/string-width/-/string-width-1.0.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-EYvfW4zcUaKn5w0hHgfnLmxB9M=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "code-point-at": ^1.0.0",
    "is-fullwidth-code-point": ^1.0.0",
    "strip-ansi": ^3.0.0"
  }
},
"string_decoder": {
  "version": "1.0.3",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/string_decoder/-/string_decoder-1.0.3.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-4AH6Z5fzNNBcH+6XDMfA/BTt87skxqJlO0IAh3Dker5zThcAxG6mKz+iGu308UKoPPQ8DcqX/4JhujzltRa+hQ==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "safe-buffer": ~5.1.0"
  }
},
"strip-ansi": {
  "version": "3.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/strip-ansi/-/strip-ansi-3.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-ajhfulU9IS1f8F0Oiq+UJ43GPc8=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "ansi-regex": ^2.0.0"
  }
},
"strip-bom": {
  "version": "2.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/strip-bom/-/strip-bom-2.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-YhmoVhZSBJHzV4i9vxRHqZx+aw4=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "is-utf8": ^0.2.0"
  }
},
"supports-color": {
  "version": "2.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/supports-color/-/supports-color-2.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-U10EXOa2Nj+kARcIRimZXp3zJM=",
  "dev": true
}
```

```
},
"tfunk": {
  "version": "3.1.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/tfunk/-/tfunk-3.1.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-OORBT8ZJd9h6/apy+sttKfgve1s=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "chalk": "^1.1.1",
    "object-path": "^0.9.0"
  }
},
"through2": {
  "version": "2.0.3",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/through2/-/through2-2.0.3.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-AARWmzfHx0ujnEPzzteNGtIBQL4=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "readable-stream": "^2.1.5",
    "xtend": "~4.0.1"
  }
},
"tildify": {
  "version": "1.2.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/tildify/-/tildify-1.2.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-3OwD9V3Km3qj5bBPIYF+tW5jWlo=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "os-homedir": "^1.0.0"
  }
},
"time-stamp": {
  "version": "1.1.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/time-stamp/-/time-stamp-1.1.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-dkpaEa9QVhkhsTPztE5hhofg9cM=",
  "dev": true
},
"to-array": {
  "version": "0.1.4",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/to-array/-/to-array-0.1.4.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-F+bBH3PdTz10zaek/zl46a2b+JA=",
  "dev": true
},
"to-object-path": {
  "version": "0.3.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/to-object-path/-/to-object-path-0.3.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-KXWIt7Dn4KwI4E5nL4XB9JmeF68=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "kind-of": "^3.0.2"
  }
},

```

```

    "to-regex": {
      "version": "3.0.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/to-regex/-/to-regex-3.0.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-
FWtleNAtZ/Ki2qtqej2CXT0ayOH9bHDQF+Q48VpWyDXjbYxA4Yz8iDB31zXOBUIOHKKidDbqGVrTUvQ
MPmBGBw==",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "define-property": "^2.0.2",
        "extend-shallow": ^3.0.2",
        "regex-not": ^1.0.2",
        "safe-regex": ^1.1.0"
      }
    },
    "to-regex-range": {
      "version": "2.1.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/to-regex-range/-/to-regex-range-2.1.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-fIDBe53+vlmeJzZ+DU3VWQFB2zg=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "is-number": ^3.0.0",
        "repeat-string": ^1.6.1"
      }
    },
    "dependencies": {
      "is-number": {
        "version": "3.0.0",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/is-number/-/is-number-3.0.0.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha1-JP1iAaR4LPUFYcgQJ2r8fRLXEZU=",
        "dev": true,
        "requires": {
          "kind-of": ^3.0.2"
        }
      }
    }
  },
  "ua-parser-js": {
    "version": "0.7.17",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/ua-parser-js/-/ua-parser-js-0.7.17.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-
uRdSdu1oA1rncCQL7sCj8vSyZkgtL7faaw9Tc9rZ3mGgraQ7+Pdx7w5mnOSF3gw9ZNG6oc+KXfkon3bKu
ROm0g==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "ultron": {
    "version": "1.1.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/ultron/-/ultron-1.1.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha512-
UIEXBNeYmKptWH6z8ZnqTeS8fV74zG0/eRU9VGkppz+LIJNs8W/zM/L+7ctCkRrgbNnnR0xxw4bKOR0c
WON00g==",
    "dev": true
  },

```

```

"unc-path-regex": {
  "version": "0.1.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/unc-path-regex/-/unc-path-regex-0.1.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-5z3T17DXxe2G+6xrCufYxqadUPo=",
  "dev": true
},
"union-value": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/union-value/-/union-value-1.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-XHHDTLW61dzt4+oM0IHulqhrqQ=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "arr-union": "^3.1.0",
    "get-value": "^2.0.6",
    "is-extendable": "^0.1.1",
    "set-value": "^0.4.3"
  }
},
"dependencies": {
  "extend-shallow": {
    "version": "2.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/extend-shallow/-/extend-shallow-2.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Ua99YUrZqfYQ6huvu5idaxxWiQ8=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "is-extendable": "^0.1.0"
    }
  }
},
"set-value": {
  "version": "0.4.3",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/set-value/-/set-value-0.4.3.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-fbCPnT0i3H945Trzw79GZuzfzPE=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "extend-shallow": "^2.0.1",
    "is-extendable": "^0.1.1",
    "is-plain-object": "^2.0.1",
    "to-object-path": "^0.3.0"
  }
}
},
"unique-stream": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/unique-stream/-/unique-stream-1.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-1ZpKdUJ0R9mqbJHnAmP40mpLEEs=",
  "dev": true
},
"universalify": {
  "version": "0.1.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/universalify/-/universalify-0.1.2.tgz",

```

```
    "integrity": "sha512-
rBJeI5CXAlmy1pV+617WB9J63U6XcazHHF2f2dbJix4XzpUF0RS3Zbj0FGIOCAva5P/d/GBOYaACQ1w+0a
zUkg==",
    "dev": true
  },
  "unpipe": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/unpipe/-/unpipe-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-sr9O6FFKrmFltIF4KdIbLvSZBOW=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "unset-value": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/unset-value/-/unset-value-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-g3aHP30jNRef+x5vw6jtDfyKtVk=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "has-value": "^0.3.1",
      "isobject": "^3.0.0"
    }
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "has-value": {
      "version": "0.3.1",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/has-value/-/has-value-0.3.1.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha1-ex9YutpiyoJ+wKIHgCVISEWZXh8=",
      "dev": true,
      "requires": {
        "get-value": "^2.0.3",
        "has-values": "^0.1.4",
        "isobject": "^2.0.0"
      }
    },
    "dependencies": {
      "isobject": {
        "version": "2.1.0",
        "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isobject/-/isobject-2.1.0.tgz",
        "integrity": "sha1-8GVWEJaj8dou9GJy+BXIQNh+DIk=",
        "dev": true,
        "requires": {
          "isarray": "1.0.0"
        }
      }
    }
  },
  "has-values": {
    "version": "0.1.4",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/has-values/-/has-values-0.1.4.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-bWHeldkd/Km5oCCJrThL/49it3E=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "isarray": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
```

```

    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isarray/-/isarray-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-u5NdSFgsuhaMBoNJV6VKPgcSTxE=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "isobject": {
    "version": "3.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isobject/-/isobject-3.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-TkMekrEalzFjaqH5yNHMvP2reN8=",
    "dev": true
  }
},
"urix": {
  "version": "0.1.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/urix/-/urix-0.1.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-2pN/emLiH+wf0Y1Js1wpNQZ6bHI=",
  "dev": true
},
"use": {
  "version": "3.1.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/use/-/use-3.1.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-6UJEqM/L+mzC3ZJNM56Q4DFGLX/evKGRg15UJHGB9X5j5Z3AFbgZvjUh2yq/UJUY4U5dh7Fal++XbNg1uzpRAw==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "kind-of": "^6.0.2"
  },
  "dependencies": {
    "kind-of": {
      "version": "6.0.2",
      "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/kind-of/-/kind-of-6.0.2.tgz",
      "integrity": "sha512-s5kLOcnHOXqDO+FvuaLX8DDJz18CGFk7VygH40QoKPUQhW4e2rvM0rwUq0t8IQDOwYSelK01U90OjzBTme2QqA==",
      "dev": true
    }
  }
},
"user-home": {
  "version": "1.1.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/user-home/-/user-home-1.1.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-K1viOjK2Onyd640PKNSFcko98ZA=",
  "dev": true
},
"util-deprecate": {
  "version": "1.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/util-deprecate/-/util-deprecate-1.0.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-RQ1Nyfpw3nMnYvvS1KKJgUGaDM8=",
  "dev": true
},

```

```
"utils-merge": {
  "version": "1.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/utils-merge/-/utils-merge-1.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-n5VxD1CiZ5R7LMwSR0HBAoQn5xM=",
  "dev": true
},
"v8flags": {
  "version": "2.1.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/v8flags/-/v8flags-2.1.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-qrGh+jDUX4jdMhFIh1rALAtV5bQ=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "user-home": "^1.1.1"
  }
},
"validate-npm-package-license": {
  "version": "3.0.3",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/validate-npm-package-license/-/validate-npm-package-license-3.0.3.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-63ZOUnL4SIXj4L0NixR3L1lcjO38crAbgrTpl28t8jjrfuiOBL5Iygm+60qPs/KsZGzPNg6Smnc/oY16QTjF0g=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "spdx-correct": "^3.0.0",
    "spdx-expression-parse": "^3.0.0"
  }
},
"vinyl": {
  "version": "0.5.3",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/vinyl/-/vinyl-0.5.3.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-sEVbOPxeDPMNQyUTLkYZcMIJHN4=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "clone": "^1.0.0",
    "clone-stats": "^0.0.1",
    "replace-ext": "0.0.1"
  }
},
"vinyl-fs": {
  "version": "0.3.14",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/vinyl-fs/-/vinyl-fs-0.3.14.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-mmhRzhysHBzqX+hsCTHWIMLPqeY=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "defaults": "^1.0.0",
    "glob-stream": "^3.1.5",
    "glob-watcher": "^0.0.6",
    "graceful-fs": "^3.0.0",
    "mkdirp": "^0.5.0",
    "strip-bom": "^1.0.0",
  }
}
```

```
"through2": "^0.6.1",
"vinyl": "^0.4.0"
},
"dependencies": {
  "clone": {
    "version": "0.2.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/clone/-/clone-0.2.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-xhJqkK1Pctv1rNskPMN3JP6T/B8=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "graceful-fs": {
    "version": "3.0.11",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/graceful-fs/-/graceful-fs-3.0.11.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-dhPHeKGV6mLyXGMKCG1/Osu92Bg=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "natives": "^1.1.0"
    }
  },
  "isarray": {
    "version": "0.0.1",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/isarray/-/isarray-0.0.1.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-ihis/Kmo9Bd+Cav8YDiTmwXR7t8=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "readable-stream": {
    "version": "1.0.34",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/readable-stream/-/readable-stream-1.0.34.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-Elgg40vIQtLyqq+v5MKRbuMsFXw=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "core-util-is": "~1.0.0",
      "inherits": "~2.0.1",
      "isarray": "0.0.1",
      "string_decoder": "~0.10.x"
    }
  },
  "string_decoder": {
    "version": "0.10.31",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/string_decoder/-/string_decoder-0.10.31.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-YuIDvEF2bGwoyfyEMB2rHFMQ+pQ=",
    "dev": true
  },
  "strip-bom": {
    "version": "1.0.0",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/strip-bom/-/strip-bom-1.0.0.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-hbiGLzhEtabV7IRnqTWYFzo295Q=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "first-chunk-stream": "^1.0.0",
      "is-utf8": "^0.2.0"
    }
  }
}
```

```

    }
  },
  "through2": {
    "version": "0.6.5",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/through2/-/through2-0.6.5.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-QaucZ7KdVyCQcUEOHXp6lozTrUg=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "readable-stream": ">=1.0.33-1 <1.1.0-0",
      "xtend": ">=4.0.0 <4.1.0-0"
    }
  },
  "vinyl": {
    "version": "0.4.6",
    "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/vinyl/-/vinyl-0.4.6.tgz",
    "integrity": "sha1-LzVsh6VQoIVGHza76ypbqL94SEc=",
    "dev": true,
    "requires": {
      "clone": "^0.2.0",
      "clone-stats": "^0.0.1"
    }
  }
},
"which": {
  "version": "1.3.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/which/-/which-1.3.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-
xcJpopdamTuY5duC/KnTTNBraPK54YwpenP4IzxU8H91GudWpFv38u0CKjclE1Wi2EH2EDz5LRcHcKbCI
zqGyg==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "isexe": "^2.0.0"
  }
},
"which-module": {
  "version": "1.0.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/which-module/-/which-module-1.0.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-u6Y8qGGUiZT/MHc2CJ47IlgJsKk8=",
  "dev": true
},
"window-size": {
  "version": "0.2.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/window-size/-/window-size-0.2.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-tDFbtCFKPXY6+7okuE/ok2YsHU=",
  "dev": true
},
"wrap-ansi": {
  "version": "2.1.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/wrap-ansi/-/wrap-ansi-2.1.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-2Pw9KE3QV5T+hJc8rs3Rz4JP3YU=",

```

```
"dev": true,
"requires": {
  "string-width": "^1.0.1",
  "strip-ansi": "^3.0.1"
}
},
"wrappy": {
  "version": "1.0.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/wrappy/-/wrappy-1.0.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-tSQ9jz7BqjXxNkYFvA0QNuMKtp8=",
  "dev": true
},
"ws": {
  "version": "3.3.3",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/ws/-/ws-3.3.3.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha512-nnWLa/NwZSt4KQJu51MYICcSQ5g7INpOrOMt4XV8j4dqTXdmlUmSHQ8/oLC069ckre0fRsgfvsKwbTdt
KLCDkA==",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "async-limiter": "~1.0.0",
    "safe-buffer": "~5.1.0",
    "ultron": "~1.1.0"
  }
},
"xmlhttprequest-ssl": {
  "version": "1.5.5",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/xmlhttprequest-ssl/-/xmlhttprequest-ssl-1.5.5.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-wodrBhaKrcQOV9I+gRkayPQ5iz4=",
  "dev": true
},
"xtend": {
  "version": "4.0.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/xtend/-/xtend-4.0.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-pcbVMr5lbiPbgg77IDofBJmNY68=",
  "dev": true
},
"y18n": {
  "version": "3.2.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/y18n/-/y18n-3.2.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-bRX7qITAhnnA136I53WegR4H+kE=",
  "dev": true
},
"yargs": {
  "version": "6.4.0",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/yargs/-/yargs-6.4.0.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-gW4ahm1VmMzzTIWW3c4i2S2kkNQ=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "camelcase": "^3.0.0",
    "cliui": "^3.2.0",

```

```

    "decamelize": "^1.1.1",
    "get-caller-file": "^1.0.1",
    "os-locale": "^1.4.0",
    "read-pkg-up": "^1.0.1",
    "require-directory": "^2.1.1",
    "require-main-filename": "^1.0.1",
    "set-blocking": "^2.0.0",
    "string-width": "^1.0.2",
    "which-module": "^1.0.0",
    "window-size": "^0.2.0",
    "y18n": "^3.2.1",
    "yargs-parser": "^4.1.0"
  }
},
"yargs-parser": {
  "version": "4.2.1",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/yargs-parser/-/yargs-parser-4.2.1.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-KczqwNxPA8ble0qfIX3RjJ90hwx=",
  "dev": true,
  "requires": {
    "camelcase": "^3.0.0"
  }
},
"yeast": {
  "version": "0.1.2",
  "resolved": "https://registry.npmjs.org/yeast/-/yeast-0.1.2.tgz",
  "integrity": "sha1-AI4G2AIDIMNy28L47XagymyKxBk=",
  "dev": true
}
}
}

```

Script Package

```

{
  "title": "Modern Business",
  "name": "startbootstrap-modern-business",
  "version": "4.1.1",
  "description": "A multipurpose HTML website template built with Bootstrap",
  "keywords": [
    "css",
    "sass",
    "html",
    "responsive",
    "theme",
    "template"
  ],
  "homepage": "https://startbootstrap.com/template-overviews/modern-business",
  "bugs": {
    "url": "https://github.com/BlackrockDigital/startbootstrap-modern-business/issues",
    "email": "feedback@startbootstrap.com"
  }
}

```

```

},
"license": "MIT",
"author": "Start Bootstrap",
"contributors": [
  "David Miller (http://davidmiller.io/)"
],
"repository": {
  "type": "git",
  "url": "https://github.com/BlackrockDigital/startbootstrap-modern-business.git"
},
"dependencies": {
  "bootstrap": "4.1.1",
  "font-awesome": "^4.7.0",
  "jquery": "3.3.1"
},
"devDependencies": {
  "browser-sync": "2.24.5",
  "gulp": "^3.9.1"
}
}

```

UNTUK BAGIAN ADMIN

Script basis pengetahuan

```

<?php
include('../koneksi.php');

if(isset($_SESSION['login_user'])){
  header("location: about.php");
}
?>

<?php include '../admin/header.php';?>

<div class="content-wrapper">
<div class="container-fluid">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
  <li class="breadcrumb-item">
    <a href="homeadmin.php">Beranda</a>
  </li>
  <li class="breadcrumb-item active">Tambah Basis Pengetahuan</li>
</ol>

<div class="card mb-3">
<div class="card-header">
  <i class="fa fa-file"></i> Tambah Basis Pengetahuan</div>
<div class="col-sm-12 card-body text-left">

  <form id="form1" name="form1" method="post" data-toggle="validator" role="form"
action="abasispengetahuan.php">

```

```

<div class="form-group">
  <div class="form-row">
    <label for="sel1" class="control-label col-sm-2">Jenis Kendaraan
  :</label>
    <div class="col-sm-10">
      <input type="text" class="form-control" name="jeniskendaraan"
value="All New Ertiga Bensin" readonly>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>
</form>

```

```

<form id="form1" name="form1" method="post" data-toggle="validator" role="form">
  <div class="form-group">
    <div class="form-row">
      <label for="sel1" class="control-label col-sm-2">Pilih Kerusakan
    :</label>
      <div class="col-sm-10">
        <select class="form-control" name="kerusakan" required>
          <option>Nama Kerusakan</option>
          <?php
            $kerusakan = mysqli_query($konek_db, "SELECT * from kerusakan");
            foreach ($kerusakan as $row){
              echo "
value="".$row['namakerusakan']."">".$row['idkerusakan']. " ".$row['namakerusakan'].</option>";
            }
          ?>
        </select>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</form>

```

```

<div class="form-group">
  <div class="form-row">
    <div class="panel panel-primary">
      <label for="sel2" class="control-label col-sm-12 panel-heading">Pilih Gejala :</label>
      <div class="panel-body">
        <form id="form2" name="form2" method="post" action="diagnosa.php">
          <?php
            $gejala = mysqli_query($konek_db, "select * from gejala");
            foreach ($gejala as $row){
              echo "<label class='wrap-check'>
                <input type='checkbox' value="".$row['gejala']."" name='gejala[]' /> [".$row['idgejala']."]
- ".$row['gejala']. " <span class='cr'><i class='cr-icon glyphicon glyphicon-ok'></i></span>
                </label>";
            }
          ?>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>

```

```

<br>
<button type="submit" name="submit" class="btn btn-primary btn-block">Simpan</button>

<?php
    if(isset($_POST['submit'])){
        $kerusakan= $_POST['kerusakan'];
        $gejala = $_POST['gejala'];
        $jumlah_dipilih = count($gejala);
        for($x=0;$x<$jumlah_dipilih;$x++){
            $hasil= mysqli_query($konek_db, "INSERT INTO basispengetahuan
(namakerusakan, gejala) values('$kerusakan','$gejala[$x]')");
            if($hasil){
                echo '<script type="text/javascript">';
                echo 'alert("Data basis pengetahuan berhasil ditambahkan");';
                echo 'window.location.href = "basispengetahuan.php";';
                echo '</script>';
            }
        }
    }
?>
</form>
</form>
</div>
</div>
</div>

<?php include '../admin/footer.php';?>

```

Script delete pengetahuan

```

<?php
include('../koneksi.php');
$query="DELETE from basispengetahuan where namakerusakan='".$_GET['id']."'";
mysqli_query($konek_db, $query);
header("location:basispengetahuan.php");
?>

```

Script delete gejala

```

<?php
include('../koneksi.php');
$query="DELETE from gejala where idgejala='".$_GET['id']."'";
mysqli_query($konek_db, $query);
header("location:gejala.php");
?>

```

Sript delete kerusakan

```

<?php
include('../koneksi.php');

```

```
$query="DELETE from kerusakan where idkerusakan='".$_GET['id'].'"";
mysqli_query($konek_db, $query);
header("location:kerusakan.php");
?>
```

Script detail penyakit

```
<?php
include('../koneksi.php');
```

```
if(isset($_SESSION['login_user'])){
header("location: about.php");
}
?>
```

```
<?php include '../admin/header.php';?>
```

```
<div class="content-wrapper">
<div class="container-fluid">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item">
<a href="homeadmin.php">Beranda</a>
</li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active">Detail Kerusakan</li>
</ol>
```

```
<div class="card mb-3">
<div class="card-header">
<i class="fa fa-file"></i> Detail Kerusakan</div>
<div class="col-sm-12 card-body text-left">
```

```
<div class="form-group" method="POST">
<div class="form-row">
<label class="control-label col-sm-2">ID Kerusakan :</label>
<div class="col-sm-10">
<?php
$stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan where idkerusakan='".$_GET['id'].'"";
$sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
{
echo "<input type='text' class='form-control' id='idkerusakan' readonly
value='".$_$data['idkerusakan']."'>";
}
?>
</div>
</div>
</div>
```

```
<div class="form-group" method="POST">
<div class="form-row">
<label class="control-label col-sm-2">Nama Kerusakan :</label>
```

```

<div class="col-sm-10">
  <?php
    $stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan where idkerusakan='".$_$_GET['id']."'";
    $sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
    while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
    {
      echo "<input type='text' class='form-control' id='namakerusakan' readonly
value='".$_$_data['namakerusakan']."'>";
    }
  ?>
</div>
</div>
</div>

```

```

<div class="form-group" method="POST">
  <div class="form-row">
    <label class="control-label col-sm-2">Jenis Kendaraan :</label>
    <div class="col-sm-10">
      <?php
        $stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan where idkerusakan='".$_$_GET['id']."'";
        $sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
        while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
        {
          echo "<input type='text' class='form-control' id='jeniskendaraan' readonly
value='".$_$_data['jeniskendaraan']."'>";
        }
      ?>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>

```

```

<div class="form-group" method="POST">
  <div class="form-row">
    <label class="control-label col-sm-2">Gejala :</label>
    <div class="col-sm-10">
      <?php
        $stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan p, basispengetahuan b where
p.idkerusakan='".$_$_GET['id']."' and p.namakerusakan=b.namakerusakan";
        $sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
        while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
        {
          echo "<input style='margin-top: 10px;' type='text' class='form-control'
id='jeniskendaraan' readonly value='".$_$_data['gejala']."'>";
        }
        echo "<input type='text' style='margin-top: 10px;' class='form-control' id='jeniskendaraan'
readonly value=''>";
      ?>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>

```

```

<div class="form-group" method="POST">
  <div class="form-row">
    <label class="control-label col-sm-2">Teknis :</label>
    <div class="col-sm-10">
      <?php
        $stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan where idkerusakan='".$_$_GET['id'].'"";
        $sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
        while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
        {
          echo   "<textarea      rows='8'      class='form-control'      id='penanganan'
readonly>".$data['teknis'].</textarea>";
        }
      ?>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>

```

```

<div class="form-group" method="POST">
  <div class="form-row">
    <label class="control-label col-sm-2">Keterangan :</label>
    <div class="col-sm-10">
      <?php
        $stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan where idkerusakan='".$_$_GET['id'].'"";
        $sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
        while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
        {
          echo   "<textarea      rows='8'      class='form-control'      id='penanganan'
readonly>".$data['keterangan'].</textarea>";
        }
      ?>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>
</div>
</div>

```

```
<?php include './admin/footer.php';?>
```

Script edit gejala

```

<?php
include('./koneksi.php');

if(isset($_SESSION['login_user'])){
header("location: about.php");
}
?>

<?php include './admin/header.php';?>

```

```

<div class="content-wrapper">
<div class="container-fluid">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item">
<a href="homeadmin.php">Beranda</a>
</li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active">Edit Gejala</li>
</ol>

<div class="card mb-3">
<div class="card-header">
<i class="fa fa-file"></i> Edit Gejala</div>
<div class="col-sm-12 card-body text-left">

<form method="post" class="form-horizontal" data-toggle="validator" role="form">
<div class="form-group">
<div class="form-row">
<label class="control-label col-sm-2">ID Gejala :</label>
<div class="col-sm-10">
<?php
$stampil = "SELECT * FROM gejala where idgejala='".$$_GET['id']."'";
$sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
{
echo "<input type='text' name='idgejala' class='form-control' id='idgejala' readonly
value='".$data['idgejala']."'>";
}
?>
</div>
</div>
</div>

<div class="form-group">
<div class="form-row">
<label class="control-label col-sm-2">Nama Gejala :</label>
<div class="col-sm-10">
<?php
$stampil = "SELECT * FROM gejala where idgejala='".$$_GET['id']."'";
$sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
{
echo "<input type='text' class='form-control' id='gejala' name='gejala'
value='".$data['gejala']."'>";
}
?>
</div>
</div>
</div>

<div class="form-group">

```

```

<div class="form-row">
    <label class="control-label col-sm-2">Jenis Kendaraan :</label>
    <div class="col-sm-10">
        <?php
            $stampil = "SELECT * FROM gejala where idgejala='".$$_GET['id']."'";
            $sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
            while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
            {
                echo      "<input      type='text'      class='form-control'      id='jeniskendaraan'
name='jeniskendaraan' readonly value='".$data['jeniskendaraan']."'>";
            }
        ?>
    </div>
</div>
</div>

<br>
<button type="submit" name ="submit" class="btn btn-primary btn-block">Simpan</button>

<?php
    if(isset($_POST['submit'])){
        $id = $_GET['id'];
        $gejala    = $_POST['gejala'];
        $jeniskendaraan = $_POST['jeniskendaraan'];

        $query="update      gejala      SET      gejala='".$$_POST['gejala']."',
jeniskendaraan='".$$_POST['jeniskendaraan']."' WHERE idgejala='$id'";

        $result=mysqli_query($konek_db, $query);
        if($result){
            echo '<script type="text/javascript">';
            echo 'alert("Data gejala berhasil dirubah");';
            echo 'window.location.href = "gejala.php";';
            echo '</script>';
        }
    }
    ?>
</form>

</div>
</div>
</div>

<?php include './admin/footer.php';?>

```

Script Edit kerusakan

```

<?php
include('./koneksi.php');

if(isset($_SESSION['login_user'])){

```

```
header("location: about.php");
}
?>
```

```
<?php include '../admin/header.php';?>
```

```
<div class="content-wrapper">
<div class="container-fluid">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item">
<a href="homeadmin.php">Beranda</a>
</li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active">Edit Kerusakan</li>
</ol>
```

```
<div class="card mb-3">
<div class="card-header">
<i class="fa fa-file"></i> Edit Kerusakan</div>
<div class="col-sm-12 card-body">
```

```
<form method="post" class="form-horizontal" data-toggle="validator" role="form">
<div class="form-group">
<div class="form-row">
<label class="control-label col-sm-2">ID Kerusakan :</label>
<div class="col-sm-10">
<?php
$stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan where idkerusakan='".$_GET['id']."'";
$sql = mysqli_query ($koneksi,$stampil);
while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
{
echo "<input type='text' class='form-control' id='idkerusakan' name='idkerusakan'
disabled value='".$_data['idkerusakan']."'>";
}
?>
</div>
</div>
</div>
```

```
<div class="form-group">
<div class="form-row">
<label class="control-label col-sm-2">Nama Kerusakan :</label>
<div class="col-sm-10">
<?php
$stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan where idkerusakan='".$_GET['id']."'";
$sql = mysqli_query ($koneksi,$stampil);
while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
{
echo "<input type='text' class='form-control' id='namakerusakan'
name='namakerusakan' value='".$_data['namakerusakan']."'>";
}
?>
```

```

        </div>
    </div>
</div>

<div class="form-group">
    <div class="form-row">
        <label class="control-label col-sm-2">Jenis Kendaraan :</label>
        <div class="col-sm-10">
            <?php
                $stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan where idkerusakan='".$_._GET['id'].'"";
                $sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
                while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
                {
                    echo    "<input    type='text'    class='form-control'    id='jeniskendaraan'
name='jeniskendaraan' readonly value='".$_._data['jeniskendaraan'].'" data-error='Isi kolom dengan
benar'>";
                }
            ?>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>

<div class="form-group" method="POST">
    <div class="form-row">
        <label class="control-label col-sm-2">Gejala :</label>
        <div class="col-sm-10">
            <?php
                $stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan p, basispengetahuan b where
p.idkerusakan='".$_._GET['id'].'" and p.namakerusakan=b.namakerusakan";
                $sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
                while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
                {
                    echo    "<input    style='margin-top: 10px;'    type='text'    class='form-control'
id='jeniskendaraan' readonly value='".$_._data['gejala'].'">";
                }
                echo "<input style='margin-top: 10px;' type='text' class='form-control' id='jeniskendaraan'
readonly value='>";
            ?>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>

<div class="form-group">
    <div class="form-row">
        <label class="control-label col-sm-2">Teknis :</label>
        <div class="col-sm-10">
            <?php
                $stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan where idkerusakan='".$_._GET['id'].'"";
                $sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
                while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
                {

```

```

        echo    "<textarea    rows='8'    class='form-control'    id='teknis'    name='teknis'
>".$data['teknis']."</textarea>";
    }
    ?>
        </div>
</div>
</div>

<div class="form-group">
    <div class="form-row">
        <label class="control-label col-sm-2">Keterangan :</label>
        <div class="col-sm-10">
            <?php
                $stampil = "SELECT * FROM kerusakan where idkerusakan='".$$_GET['id']."'";
                $sql = mysqli_query ($konek_db,$stampil);
                while($data = mysqli_fetch_array ($sql))
                {
                    echo    "<textarea    rows='8'    class='form-control'    id='keterangan'
name='keterangan'>".$data['keterangan']."</textarea>";
                }
            ?>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>

<br>
<button type="submit" name ="submit" class="btn btn-primary btn-block">Simpan</button>

<?php
    if(isset($_POST['submit'])){
        $id = $_GET['id'];
        $namakerusakan = $_POST['namakerusakan'];
        $jeniskendaraan = $_POST['jeniskendaraan'];
        $teknis = $_POST['teknis'];
        $keterangan = $_POST['keterangan'];

        $query="update  kerusakan  SET  namakerusakan='".$$_POST['namakerusakan']."',
jeniskendaraan='".$$_POST['jeniskendaraan']."',          teknis='".$$_POST['teknis']."',
keterangan='".$$_POST['keterangan']."' WHERE idkerusakan='$id'";

        $result=mysqli_query($konek_db, $query);
        if($result){
            echo '<script type="text/javascript">';
            echo 'alert("Data kerusakan berhasil dirubah");';
            echo 'window.location.href = "kerusakan.php";';
            echo '</script>';
        }
    }
    ?>
</form>
</div>

```

```
</div>
</div>
```

```
<?php include '../admin/footer.php';?>
```

Script Input gejala

```
<?php
include('../koneksi.php');

if(isset($_SESSION['login_user'])){
header("location: about.php");
}
?>
```

```
<?php include '../admin/header.php';?>
```

```
<div class="content-wrapper">
<div class="container-fluid">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item">
<a href="homeadmin.php">Beranda</a>
</li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active">Tambah Gejala</li>
</ol>
```

```
<div class="card mb-3">
<div class="card-header">
<i class="fa fa-file"></i> Tambah Gejala</div>
<div class="col-sm-12 card-body text-left">
```

```
<form class="form-horizontal" data-toggle="validator" role="form" method="post"
action="ainputgejala.php">
<div class="form-group">
<div class="form-row">
<label class="control-label col-sm-2" for="nama">ID Gejala
:</label>
```

```
<div class="col-sm-10">
<input type="text" class="form-control" required
name="idgejala" data-error="Isi kolom dengan benar">
<div class="help-block with-errors" role="alert"></div>
</div>
```

```
</div>
</div>
```

```
<div class="form-group">
<div class="form-row">
<label class="control-label col-sm-2" for="nama">Nama Gejala
:</label>
<div class="col-sm-10">
```

```

                                <input type="text" class="form-control" required
name="gejala" data-error="Isi kolom dengan benar">
                                <div class="help-block with-errors" role="alert"></div>
                                </div>
                                </div>

                                <div class="form-group">
                                <div class="form-row">
                                <label class="control-label col-sm-2" for="alamat">Jenis Kendaraan
: </label>
                                <div class="col-sm-10">
                                <select class="form-control" name="jeniskendaraan"
onChange='this.form.submit();'>
                                <option>All New Ertiga</option>
                                </select>
                                </div>
                                </div>
                                </div>

                                <br>
                                <button type="submit" name="submit" class="btn btn-primary btn-block">Tambah</button>

                                <?php
                                if(isset($_POST['submit'])){
                                $idgejala = $_POST['idgejala'];
                                $gejala = $_POST['gejala'];
                                $jeniskendaraan = $_POST['jeniskendaraan'];

                                $query="INSERT INTO gejala SET
idgejala='$idgejala',gejala='$gejala',jeniskendaraan='$jeniskendaraan'";
                                $result=mysqli_query($koneksi_db, $query);
                                if($result){
                                echo '<script type="text/javascript">';
                                echo 'alert("Data Gejala berhasil ditambahkan");';
                                echo 'window.location.href = "gejala.php";';
                                echo '</script>';
                                }
                                }
                                ?>
                                </form>

                                </div>
                                </div>
                                </div>

                                <?php include '../admin/footer.php';?>

```

Script input kerusakan

```

<?php
include('../koneksi.php');

```

```
if(isset($_SESSION['login_user'])){
header("location: about.php");
}
?>
```

```
<?php include '../admin/header.php';?>
```

```
<div class="content-wrapper">
<div class="container-fluid">
<ol class="breadcrumb">
<li class="breadcrumb-item">
<a href="homeadmin.php">Beranda</a>
</li>
<li class="breadcrumb-item active">Tambah Kerusakan</li>
</ol>

<div class="card mb-3">
<div class="card-header">
<i class="fa fa-file"></i> Tambah Kerusakan</div>
<div class="col-sm-12 card-body text-left">
<form class="form-horizontal" method="post" data-toggle="validator" role="form"
action="ainputkerusakan.php">
<div class="form-group">
<div class="form-row">
<label class="control-label col-sm-2" for="nama">ID Kerusakan :</label>
<div class="col-sm-10">
<input type="text" class="form-control" required name="idkerusakan" data-error="Isi
kolom dengan benar">
<div class="help-block with-errors" role="alert"></div>
</div>
</div>
</div>

<div class="form-group">
<div class="form-row">
<label class="control-label col-sm-2" for="nama">Nama Kerusakan :</label>
<div class="col-sm-10">
<input type="text" class="form-control" required
name="namakerusakan" data-error="Isi kolom dengan benar">
<div class="help-block with-errors" role="alert"></div>
</div>
</div>

<div class="form-group">
<div class="form-row">
<label class="control-label col-sm-2" for="alamat">Jenis Kendaraan
:</label>
<div class="col-sm-10">
```

```

        <select class="form-control" name="jeniskendaraan"
onChange='this.form.submit();' required>
        <option>All New Ertiga</option>
    </select>
</div>
    </div>
</div>

<div class="form-group">
    <div class="form-row">
        <label class="control-label col-sm-2" for="alamat">Teknis :</label>
        <div class="col-sm-10">
            <textarea rows='8' class="form-control" name="teknis"></textarea>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>

<div class="form-group">
    <div class="form-row">
        <label class="control-label col-sm-2" for="alamat">Keterangan :</label>
        <div class="col-sm-10">
            <textarea rows='8' class="form-control" name="keterangan"></textarea>
        </div>
    </div>
</div>

<br>
<button type="submit" name ="submit" class="btn btn-primary btn-block">Tambah</button>

<?php
    if(isset($_POST['submit'])){

        $idkerusakan = $_POST['idkerusakan'];
        $namakerusakan = $_POST['namakerusakan'];
        $jeniskendaraan = $_POST['jeniskendaraan'];
        $teknis = $_POST['teknis'];
        $keterangan = $_POST['keterangan'];

        $query="INSERT INTO kerusakan SET
idkerusakan='$idkerusakan',namakerusakan='$namakerusakan',jeniskendaraan='$jeniskendaraan',te
knis='$teknis', keterangan='$keterangan'";

        $result=mysqli_query($koneksi_db, $query);
        if($result){
            echo '<script type="text/javascript">';
            echo 'alert("Data kerusakan berhasil ditambahkan");';
            echo 'window.location.href = "kerusakan.php";';
            echo '</script>';
        }
    }
?>

```

```
</form>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
</div>
```

```
<?php include '../admin/footer.php';?>
```

Script basis pengetahuan

```
<?php
```

```
include('../koneksi.php');
```

```
if(isset($_SESSION['login_user'])){
```

```
header("location: about.php");
```

```
}
```

```
?>
```

```
<?php include '../admin/header.php';?>
```

```
<div class="content-wrapper">
```

```
<div class="container-fluid">
```

```
<ol class="breadcrumb">
```

```
<li class="breadcrumb-item">
```

```
<a href="homeadmin.php">Beranda</a>
```

```
</li>
```

```
<li class="breadcrumb-item active">Basis Pengetahuan</li>
```

```
</ol>
```

```
<div class="col-md-12 text-left">
```

```
<div class="row">
```

```
<a href="abasispengetahuan.php" class="col-md-3 form-group btn btn-primary btn-block"><i class="fa fa-plus" aria-hidden="true"></i> Tambah Basis Pengetahuan</a>
```

```
<div class="card mb-3">
```

```
<div class="card-header">
```

```
<i class="fa fa-file"></i> Data Basis Pengetahuan</div>
```

```
<div class="card-body">
```

```
<div class="table-responsive">
```

```
<div class="row">
```

```
<table id="example" class="table table-bordered dataTable">
```

```
<thead>
```

```
<tr>
```

```
<th>NO</th>
```

```
<th>Id Kerusakan</th>
```

```
<th>Nama Kerusakan</th>
```

```
<th>Gejala</th>
```

```
<th>Opsi</th>
```

```
</tr>
```

```
</thead>
```

```
<?php
```

```

        $pengetahuan = mysqli_query($konek_db, "Select p.idkerusakan, p.jeniskendaraan,
b.namakerusakan, b.gejala from basispengetahuan b, kerusakan p where
p.namakerusakan=b.namakerusakan");
        $no=1;
        foreach ($pengetahuan as $row){
            echo "<tr>
                <td>$no</td>
                <td>".$row['idkerusakan'].</td>
                <td>".$row['namakerusakan'].</td>
                <td>".$row['gejala'].</td>
                <td><a href=\"adeletebasispengetahuan.php?id=".$row['namakerusakan'].\"
onclick='return checkDelete()'><i class='fa fa-trash'></i></a>".</td>
            </tr>";
            $no++;
        }
    ?>

```

```
</table>
```

```

</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>

```

```

<script language="JavaScript" type="text/javascript">
function checkDelete(){
    return confirm('Yakin menghapus data ini?');
}
</script>

```

```
<?php include '../admin/footer.php';?>
```

Script Footer

```

<footer class="sticky-footer">
    <div class="container">
        <div class="text-center">
            <small>Copyright 2018 © Yosep Adi Candra 2018.</small>
        </div>
    </div>
</footer>

<a class="scroll-to-top rounded" href="#page-top">
    <i class="fa fa-angle-up"></i>
</a>

```

```

<div class="modal fade" id="exampleModal" tabindex="-1" role="dialog" aria-
labelledby="exampleModalLabel" aria-hidden="true">
  <div class="modal-dialog" role="document">
    <div class="modal-content">
      <div class="modal-header">
        <h5 class="modal-title" id="exampleModalLabel">Yakin Keluar?</h5>
        <button class="close" type="button" data-dismiss="modal" aria-label="Close">
          <span aria-hidden="true">x</span>
        </button>
      </div>
      <div class="modal-body">Pilih "Keluar" Untuk Mengakhiri Halaman Admin Ini.</div>
      <div class="modal-footer">
        <button class="btn btn-secondary" type="button" data-dismiss="modal">Batal</button>
        <a class="btn btn-primary" href="logout.php">Keluar</a>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>
</div>

<script src="../js/jquery.min.js"></script>
<script src="../js/bootstrap.bundle.min.js"></script>
<script src="../js/jquery.easing.min.js"></script>
<script src="../js/jquery.dataTables.js"></script>
<script src="../js/dataTables.bootstrap4.js"></script>
<script src="../js/sb-admin.min.js"></script>
<script src="../js/sb-admin-datatables.min.js"></script>

<script type="text/javascript">
  $(document).ready(function() {
    $('#example').DataTable();
  });
</script>

</div>

</body>
</html>

```

Script gejala

```

<?php
include('../koneksi.php');

if(isset($_SESSION['login_user'])){
header("location: about.php");
}
?>

<?php include '../admin/header.php';?>

<div class="content-wrapper">

```

```

<div class="container-fluid">
  <ol class="breadcrumb">
    <li class="breadcrumb-item">
      <a href="homeadmin.php">Beranda</a>
    </li>
    <li class="breadcrumb-item active">Gejala</li>
  </ol>

  <div class="col-md-12 text-left">
    <div class="row">
      <a href="ainputgejala.php" class="col-md-3 form-group btn btn-primary btn-block"><i class="fa
fa-plus" aria-hidden="true"></i> Tambah Gejala</a>

      <div class="card mb-3">
        <div class="card-header">
          <i class="fa fa-file"></i> Data Nama Gejala</div>

        <div class="card-body">
          <div class="table-responsive">
            <div class="row">
              <table id="example" class="table table-bordered dataTable">
                <thead>
                  <tr>
                    <th>NO</th>
                    <th>ID Gejala</th>
                    <th>Nama Gejala</th>
                    <th>Jenis Kendaraan</th>
                    <th>Opsi</th>
                  </tr>
                </thead>

                <?php
                $gejala = mysqli_query($konek_db, "SELECT * from gejala");
                $no=1;
                foreach ($gejala as $row){
                  echo "<tr>
                    <td>$no</td>
                    <td>". $row['idgejala']. "</td>
                    <td>". $row['gejala']. "</td>
                    <td>". $row['jeniskendaraan']. "</td>
                    <td><a href=\"aeditgejala.php?id=\". $row['idgejala']. "\"><i class='fa fa-pencil'></i></a>". "
                    || <a href=\"adeletegejala.php?id=\". $row['idgejala']. "\" onclick='return checkDelete()'><i class='fa
fa-trash'></i></a>". "</td>
                  </tr>";
                  $no++;
                }
                ?>

              </table>

            </div>
          </div>
        </div>
      </div>
    </div>
  </div>

```

```
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
```

```
<script language="JavaScript" type="text/javascript">
function checkDelete(){
    return confirm('Yakin menghapus data gejala ini?');
}
</script>
```

```
<?php include '../admin/footer.php';?>
```

Script Header

```
<?php
include "../session.php";
?>
```

```
<!DOCTYPE html>
<html lang="en">
<head>
    <title>Admin Sistem Pakar</title>
    <meta charset="utf-8">
    <meta name="viewport" content="width=device-width, initial-scale=1">

    <link href="../css/bootstrap4.min.css" rel="stylesheet">
    <link href="../css/font-awesome.min.css" rel="stylesheet" type="text/css">
    <link href="../css/dataTables.bootstrap4.css" rel="stylesheet">
    <link href="../css/sb-admin.min.css" rel="stylesheet">
    <link
        rel='stylesheet
        href='https://fonts.googleapis.com/css?family=Roboto:400,100,300,500,700,900'>
        prefetch'
</head>
```

```
<body class="fixed-nav sticky-footer bg-dark" id="page-top">
<!-- Navigation-->
<nav class="navbar navbar-expand-lg navbar-dark bg-dark fixed-top" id="mainNav">
    <a class="navbar-brand" href="homeadmin.php">Admin Sistem Pakar</a>
    <button class="navbar-toggler navbar-toggler-right" type="button" data-toggle="collapse" data-
target="#navbarResponsive" aria-controls="navbarResponsive" aria-expanded="false" aria-
label="Toggle navigation">
        <span class="navbar-toggler-icon"></span>
    </button>
    <div class="collapse navbar-collapse" id="navbarResponsive">
        <ul class="navbar-nav navbar-sidenav" id="exampleAccordion">
            <li class="nav-item" data-toggle="tooltip" data-placement="right" title="Dashboard">
                <a class="nav-link" href="homeadmin.php">
                    <i class="fa fa-fw fa-dashboard"></i>
```

```

        <span class="nav-link-text">Beranda</span>
    </a>
</li>
<li class="nav-item" data-toggle="tooltip" data-placement="right" title="Charts">
    <a class="nav-link" href="kerusakan.php">
        <i class="fa fa-fw fa-cog"></i>
        <span class="nav-link-text">Kerusakan</span>
    </a>
</li>
<li class="nav-item" data-toggle="tooltip" data-placement="right" title="Tables">
    <a class="nav-link" href="gejala.php">
        <i class="fa fa-fw fa-plus-circle"></i>
        <span class="nav-link-text">Gejala</span>
    </a>
</li>

<li class="nav-item" data-toggle="tooltip" data-placement="right" title="Link">
    <a class="nav-link" href="basispengetahuan.php">
        <i class="fa fa-fw fa-link"></i>
        <span class="nav-link-text">Basis Pengetahuan</span>
    </a>
</li>
</ul>
<ul class="navbar-nav sidenav-toggler">
    <li class="nav-item">
        <a class="nav-link text-center" id="sidenavToggler">
            <i class="fa fa-fw fa-angle-left"></i>
        </a>
    </li>
</ul>
<ul class="navbar-nav ml-auto">

    <li class="nav-item">
        <a class="btn btn-primary btn-block" target="_blank" href="../index.php">View Site</a>
    </li>

    <li class="nav-item">
        <a class="nav-link" data-toggle="modal" data-target="#exampleModal">
            <i class="fa fa-fw fa-sign-out"></i>Logout</a>
        </li>

</ul>
</div>
</nav>

```

Script home admin

```
<?php include '../admin/header.php';?>
```

```
<div class="content-wrapper">
```

```

<div class="container-fluid">
  <ol class="breadcrumb">
    <li class="breadcrumb-item">
      <a href="homeadmin.php">Beranda</a>
    </li>
  </ol>
  <h1 class="text-admin">Selamat datang di halaman admin sistem pakar pendeteksi kerusakan
mobil Suzuki All New Ertiga Bensin</h1>
</div>

```

```
<?php include '../admin/footer.php';?>
```

Script kerusakan

```

<?php
include('../koneksi.php');
if(isset($_SESSION['login_user'])){
header("location: about.php");
}
?>

```

```
<?php include '../admin/header.php';?>
```

```

<div class="content-wrapper">
<div class="container-fluid">
  <ol class="breadcrumb">
    <li class="breadcrumb-item">
      <a href="homeadmin.php">Beranda</a>
    </li>
    <li class="breadcrumb-item active">Kerusakan</li>
  </ol>

```

```

<div class="col-md-12 text-left">
  <div class="row">
    <a href="ainputkerusakan.php" class="col-md-3 form-group btn btn-primary btn-block"><i
class="fa fa-plus" aria-hidden="true"></i> Tambah Kerusakan</a>
  </div>

```

```

  <div class="card mb-3">
    <div class="card-header">
      <i class="fa fa-file"></i> Data Nama Kerusakan</div>

```

```

  <div class="card-body">
    <div class="table-responsive">
      <div class="row">
        <table id="example" class="table table-bordered dataTable">
          <thead>
            <tr>
              <th>NO</th>
              <th>ID Kerusakan</th>
              <th>Nama Kerusakan</th>
              <th>Jenis Kendaraan</th>
            </tr>

```

```

        <th>Opsi</th>
    </tr>
</thead>

<?php
    $kendaraan = mysqli_query($koneksi, "SELECT * from kerusakan");
    $no=1;
    foreach ($kendaraan as $row){
        echo "<tr>
            <td>$no</td>
            <td>". $row['idkerusakan']. "</td>
            <td>". $row['namakerusakan']. "</td>
            <td>". $row['jeniskendaraan']. "</td>
            <td><a href='\"aeditkerusakan.php?id=\". $row['idkerusakan']. \"'><i class='fa fa-pencil'></i></a>\" || <a href='\"adeletekerusakan.php?id=\". $row['idkerusakan']. \"'\" onclick='return checkDelete()'><i class='fa fa-trash'></i></a>\".</td>
            </tr>";
        $no++;
    }
?>

</table>

</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>
</div>

<script language="JavaScript" type="text/javascript">
function checkDelete(){
    return confirm('Yakin menghapus data kerusakan ini?');
}
</script>

<?php include '../admin/footer.php';?>

```

Script Logout

```

<?php
session_destroy();
echo "<script>alert('Terima kasih, Anda Berhasil Logout!')</script>";
header("location: ../index.php");
?>

```

Coding di CSS

Script bootstrap

```
/*!
 * Bootstrap v3.3.7 (http://getbootstrap.com)
 * Copyright 2011-2016 Twitter, Inc.
 * Licensed under MIT (https://github.com/twbs/bootstrap/blob/master/LICENSE)
 */
/*! normalize.css v3.0.3 | MIT License | github.com/necolas/normalize.css */
html {
  font-family: sans-serif;
  -webkit-text-size-adjust: 100%;
  -ms-text-size-adjust: 100%;
}
body {
  margin: 0;
}
article,
aside,
details,
figcaption,
figure,
footer,
header,
hgroup,
main,
menu,
nav,
section,
summary {
  display: block;
}
audio,
canvas,
progress,
video {
  display: inline-block;
  vertical-align: baseline;
}
audio:not([controls]) {
  display: none;
  height: 0;
}
[hidden],
template {
  display: none;
}
a {
  background-color: transparent;
}
a:active,
a:hover {
  outline: 0;
}
```

```
abbr[title] {
  border-bottom: 1px dotted;
}
b,
strong {
  font-weight: bold;
}
dfn {
  font-style: italic;
}
h1 {
  margin: .67em 0;
  font-size: 2em;
}
mark {
  color: #000;
  background: #ff0;
}
small {
  font-size: 80%;
}
sub,
sup {
  position: relative;
  font-size: 75%;
  line-height: 0;
  vertical-align: baseline;
}
sup {
  top: -.5em;
}
sub {
  bottom: -.25em;
}
img {
  border: 0;
}
svg:not(:root) {
  overflow: hidden;
}
figure {
  margin: 1em 40px;
}
hr {
  height: 0;
  -webkit-box-sizing: content-box;
  -moz-box-sizing: content-box;
  box-sizing: content-box;
}
pre {
  overflow: auto;
```

```
}
code,
kbd,
pre,
samp {
  font-family: monospace, monospace;
  font-size: 1em;
}
button,
input,
optgroup,
select,
textarea {
  margin: 0;
  font: inherit;
  color: inherit;
}
button {
  overflow: visible;
}
button,
select {
  text-transform: none;
}
button,
html input[type="button"],
input[type="reset"],
input[type="submit"] {
  -webkit-appearance: button;
  cursor: pointer;
}
button[disabled],
html input[disabled] {
  cursor: default;
}
button::-moz-focus-inner,
input::-moz-focus-inner {
  padding: 0;
  border: 0;
}
input {
  line-height: normal;
}
input[type="checkbox"],
input[type="radio"] {
  -webkit-box-sizing: border-box;
  -moz-box-sizing: border-box;
  box-sizing: border-box;
  padding: 0;
}
input[type="number"]::-webkit-inner-spin-button,
```

```

input[type="number"]::-webkit-outer-spin-button {
  height: auto;
}
input[type="search"] {
  -webkit-box-sizing: content-box;
  -moz-box-sizing: content-box;
  box-sizing: content-box;
  -webkit-appearance: textfield;
}
input[type="search"]::-webkit-search-cancel-button,
input[type="search"]::-webkit-search-decoration {
  -webkit-appearance: none;
}
fieldset {
  padding: .35em .625em .75em;
  margin: 0 2px;
  border: 1px solid #c0c0c0;
}
legend {
  padding: 0;
  border: 0;
}
textarea {
  overflow: auto;
}
optgroup {
  font-weight: bold;
}
table {
  border-spacing: 0;
  border-collapse: collapse;
}
td,
th {
  padding: 0;
}
/*! Source: https://github.com/h5bp/html5-boilerplate/blob/master/src/css/main.css */
@media print {
  *,
  *:before,
  *:after {
    color: #000 !important;
    text-shadow: none !important;
    background: transparent !important;
    -webkit-box-shadow: none !important;
    box-shadow: none !important;
  }
  a,
  a:visited {
    text-decoration: underline;
  }
}

```

```
a[href]:after {
  content: " (" attr(href) ")";
}
abbr[title]:after {
  content: " (" attr(title) ")";
}
a[href^="#"]:after,
a[href^="javascript:"]:after {
  content: "";
}
pre,
blockquote {
  border: 1px solid #999;

  page-break-inside: avoid;
}
thead {
  display: table-header-group;
}
tr,
img {
  page-break-inside: avoid;
}
img {
  max-width: 100% !important;
}
p,
h2,
h3 {
  orphans: 3;
  widows: 3;
}
h2,
h3 {
  page-break-after: avoid;
}
.navbar {
  display: none;
}
.btn > .caret,
.dropdown > .btn > .caret {
  border-top-color: #000 !important;
}
.label {
  border: 1px solid #000;
}
.table {
  border-collapse: collapse !important;
}
.table td,
.table th {
```

```

    background-color: #fff !important;
}
.table-bordered th,
.table-bordered td {
    border: 1px solid #ddd !important;
}
}
@font-face {
    font-family: 'Glyphicons Halflings';

    src: url('../fonts/glyphicons-halflings-regular.eot');
    src: url('../fonts/glyphicons-halflings-regular.eot?#iefix') format('embedded-opentype'),
url('../fonts/glyphicons-halflings-regular.woff2') format('woff2'), url('../fonts/glyphicons-halflings-regular.woff') format('woff'), url('../fonts/glyphicons-halflings-regular.ttf') format('truetype'),
url('../fonts/glyphicons-halflings-regular.svg#glyphicons_halfllingsregular') format('svg');
}
.glyphicon {
    position: relative;
    top: 1px;
    display: inline-block;
    font-family: 'Glyphicons Halflings';
    font-style: normal;
    font-weight: normal;
    line-height: 1;

    -webkit-font-smoothing: antialiased;
    -moz-osx-font-smoothing: grayscale;
}
.glyphicon-asterisk:before {
    content: "\002a";
}
.glyphicon-plus:before {
    content: "\002b";
}
.glyphicon-euro:before,
.glyphicon-eur:before {
    content: "\20ac";
}
.glyphicon-minus:before {
    content: "\2212";
}
.glyphicon-cloud:before {
    content: "\2601";
}
.glyphicon-envelope:before {
    content: "\2709";
}
.glyphicon-pencil:before {
    content: "\270f";
}
.glyphicon-glass:before {

```

```
    content: "\e001";
}
.glyphicon-music:before {
    content: "\e002";
}
.glyphicon-search:before {
    content: "\e003";
}
.glyphicon-heart:before {
    content: "\e005";
}
.glyphicon-star:before {
    content: "\e006";
}
.glyphicon-star-empty:before {
    content: "\e007";
}
.glyphicon-user:before {
    content: "\e008";
}
.glyphicon-film:before {
    content: "\e009";
}
.glyphicon-th-large:before {
    content: "\e010";
}
.glyphicon-th:before {
    content: "\e011";
}
.glyphicon-th-list:before {
    content: "\e012";
}
.glyphicon-ok:before {
    content: "\e013";
}
.glyphicon-remove:before {
    content: "\e014";
}
.glyphicon-zoom-in:before {
    content: "\e015";
}
.glyphicon-zoom-out:before {
    content: "\e016";
}
.glyphicon-off:before {
    content: "\e017";
}
.glyphicon-signal:before {
    content: "\e018";
}
.glyphicon-cog:before {
```

```
    content: "\e019";
}
.glyphicon-trash:before {
    content: "\e020";
}
.glyphicon-home:before {
    content: "\e021";
}
.glyphicon-file:before {
    content: "\e022";
}
.glyphicon-time:before {
    content: "\e023";
}
.glyphicon-road:before {
    content: "\e024";
}
.glyphicon-download-alt:before {
    content: "\e025";
}
.glyphicon-download:before {
    content: "\e026";
}
.glyphicon-upload:before {
    content: "\e027";
}
.glyphicon-inbox:before {
    content: "\e028";
}
.glyphicon-play-circle:before {
    content: "\e029";
}
.glyphicon-repeat:before {
    content: "\e030";
}
.glyphicon-refresh:before {
    content: "\e031";
}
.glyphicon-list-alt:before {
    content: "\e032";
}
.glyphicon-lock:before {
    content: "\e033";
}
.glyphicon-flag:before {
    content: "\e034";
}
.glyphicon-headphones:before {
    content: "\e035";
}
.glyphicon-volume-off:before {
```

```
    content: "\e036";
}
.glyphicon-volume-down:before {
  content: "\e037";
}
.glyphicon-volume-up:before {
  content: "\e038";
}
.glyphicon-qr-code:before {
  content: "\e039";
}
.glyphicon-barcode:before {
  content: "\e040";
}
.glyphicon-tag:before {
  content: "\e041";
}
.glyphicon-tags:before {
  content: "\e042";
}
.glyphicon-book:before {
  content: "\e043";
}
.glyphicon-bookmark:before {
  content: "\e044";
}
.glyphicon-print:before {
  content: "\e045";
}
.glyphicon-camera:before {
  content: "\e046";
}
.glyphicon-font:before {
  content: "\e047";
}
.glyphicon-bold:before {
  content: "\e048";
}
.glyphicon-italic:before {
  content: "\e049";
}
.glyphicon-text-height:before {
  content: "\e050";
}
.glyphicon-text-width:before {
  content: "\e051";
}
.glyphicon-align-left:before {
  content: "\e052";
}
.glyphicon-align-center:before {
```

```
    content: "\e053";
}
.glyphicon-align-right:before {
  content: "\e054";
}
.glyphicon-align-justify:before {
  content: "\e055";
}
.glyphicon-list:before {
  content: "\e056";
}
.glyphicon-indent-left:before {
  content: "\e057";
}
.glyphicon-indent-right:before {
  content: "\e058";
}
.glyphicon-facetime-video:before {
  content: "\e059";
}
.glyphicon-picture:before {
  content: "\e060";
}
.glyphicon-map-marker:before {
  content: "\e062";
}
.glyphicon-adjust:before {
  content: "\e063";
}
.glyphicon-tint:before {
  content: "\e064";
}
.glyphicon-edit:before {
  content: "\e065";
}
.glyphicon-share:before {
  content: "\e066";
}
.glyphicon-check:before {
  content: "\e067";
}
.glyphicon-move:before {
  content: "\e068";
}
.glyphicon-step-backward:before {
  content: "\e069";
}
.glyphicon-fast-backward:before {
  content: "\e070";
}
.glyphicon-backward:before {
```

```
    content: "\e071";
}
.glyphicon-play:before {
    content: "\e072";
}
.glyphicon-pause:before {
    content: "\e073";
}
.glyphicon-stop:before {
    content: "\e074";
}
.glyphicon-forward:before {
    content: "\e075";
}
.glyphicon-fast-forward:before {
    content: "\e076";
}
.glyphicon-step-forward:before {
    content: "\e077";
}
.glyphicon-eject:before {
    content: "\e078";
}
.glyphicon-chevron-left:before {
    content: "\e079";
}
.glyphicon-chevron-right:before {
    content: "\e080";
}
.glyphicon-plus-sign:before {
    content: "\e081";
}
.glyphicon-minus-sign:before {
    content: "\e082";
}
.glyphicon-remove-sign:before {
    content: "\e083";
}
.glyphicon-ok-sign:before {
    content: "\e084";
}
.glyphicon-question-sign:before {
    content: "\e085";
}
.glyphicon-info-sign:before {
    content: "\e086";
}
.glyphicon-screenshot:before {
    content: "\e087";
}
.glyphicon-remove-circle:before {
```

```
    content: "\e088";
}
.glyphicon-ok-circle:before {
  content: "\e089";
}
.glyphicon-ban-circle:before {
  content: "\e090";
}
.glyphicon-arrow-left:before {
  content: "\e091";
}
.glyphicon-arrow-right:before {
  content: "\e092";
}
.glyphicon-arrow-up:before {
  content: "\e093";
}
.glyphicon-arrow-down:before {
  content: "\e094";
}
.glyphicon-share-alt:before {
  content: "\e095";
}
.glyphicon-resize-full:before {
  content: "\e096";
}
.glyphicon-resize-small:before {
  content: "\e097";
}
.glyphicon-exclamation-sign:before {
  content: "\e101";
}
.glyphicon-gift:before {
  content: "\e102";
}
.glyphicon-leaf:before {
  content: "\e103";
}
.glyphicon-fire:before {
  content: "\e104";
}
.glyphicon-eye-open:before {
  content: "\e105";
}
.glyphicon-eye-close:before {
  content: "\e106";
}
.glyphicon-warning-sign:before {
  content: "\e107";
}
.glyphicon-plane:before {
```

```
    content: "\e108";
}
.glyphicon-calendar:before {
  content: "\e109";
}
.glyphicon-random:before {
  content: "\e110";
}
.glyphicon-comment:before {
  content: "\e111";
}
.glyphicon-magnet:before {
  content: "\e112";
}
.glyphicon-chevron-up:before {
  content: "\e113";
}
.glyphicon-chevron-down:before {
  content: "\e114";
}
.glyphicon-retweet:before {
  content: "\e115";
}
.glyphicon-shopping-cart:before {
  content: "\e116";
}
.glyphicon-folder-close:before {
  content: "\e117";
}
.glyphicon-folder-open:before {
  content: "\e118";
}
.glyphicon-resize-vertical:before {
  content: "\e119";
}
.glyphicon-resize-horizontal:before {
  content: "\e120";
}
.glyphicon-hdd:before {
  content: "\e121";
}
.glyphicon-bullhorn:before {
  content: "\e122";
}
.glyphicon-bell:before {
  content: "\e123";
}
.glyphicon-certificate:before {
  content: "\e124";
}
.glyphicon-thumbs-up:before {
```

```
    content: "\e125";
}
.glyphicon-thumbs-down:before {
    content: "\e126";
}
.glyphicon-hand-right:before {
    content: "\e127";
}
.glyphicon-hand-left:before {
    content: "\e128";
}
.glyphicon-hand-up:before {
    content: "\e129";
}
.glyphicon-hand-down:before {
    content: "\e130";
}
.glyphicon-circle-arrow-right:before {
    content: "\e131";
}
.glyphicon-circle-arrow-left:before {
    content: "\e132";
}
.glyphicon-circle-arrow-up:before {
    content: "\e133";
}
.glyphicon-circle-arrow-down:before {
    content: "\e134";
}
.glyphicon-globe:before {
    content: "\e135";
}
.glyphicon-wrench:before {
    content: "\e136";
}
.glyphicon-tasks:before {
    content: "\e137";
}
.glyphicon-filter:before {
    content: "\e138";
}
.glyphicon-briefcase:before {
    content: "\e139";
}
.glyphicon-fullscreen:before {
    content: "\e140";
}
.glyphicon-dashboard:before {
    content: "\e141";
}
.glyphicon-paperclip:before {
```

```
    content: "\e142";
}
.glyphicon-heart-empty:before {
    content: "\e143";
}
.glyphicon-link:before {
    content: "\e144";
}
.glyphicon-phone:before {
    content: "\e145";
}
.glyphicon-pushpin:before {
    content: "\e146";
}
.glyphicon-usd:before {
    content: "\e148";
}
.glyphicon-gbp:before {
    content: "\e149";
}
.glyphicon-sort:before {
    content: "\e150";
}
.glyphicon-sort-by-alphabet:before {
    content: "\e151";
}
.glyphicon-sort-by-alphabet-alt:before {
    content: "\e152";
}
.glyphicon-sort-by-order:before {
    content: "\e153";
}
.glyphicon-sort-by-order-alt:before {
    content: "\e154";
}
.glyphicon-sort-by-attributes:before {
    content: "\e155";
}
.glyphicon-sort-by-attributes-alt:before {
    content: "\e156";
}
.glyphicon-unchecked:before {
    content: "\e157";
}
.glyphicon-expand:before {
    content: "\e158";
}
.glyphicon-collapse-down:before {
    content: "\e159";
}
.glyphicon-collapse-up:before {
```

```
    content: "\e160";
}
.glyphicon-log-in:before {
  content: "\e161";
}
.glyphicon-flash:before {
  content: "\e162";
}
.glyphicon-log-out:before {
  content: "\e163";
}
.glyphicon-new-window:before {
  content: "\e164";
}
.glyphicon-record:before {
  content: "\e165";
}
.glyphicon-save:before {
  content: "\e166";
}
.glyphicon-open:before {
  content: "\e167";
}
.glyphicon-saved:before {
  content: "\e168";
}
.glyphicon-import:before {
  content: "\e169";
}
.glyphicon-export:before {
  content: "\e170";
}
.glyphicon-send:before {
  content: "\e171";
}
.glyphicon-floppy-disk:before {
  content: "\e172";
}
.glyphicon-floppy-saved:before {
  content: "\e173";
}
.glyphicon-floppy-remove:before {
  content: "\e174";
}
.glyphicon-floppy-save:before {
  content: "\e175";
}
.glyphicon-floppy-open:before {
  content: "\e176";
}
.glyphicon-credit-card:before {
```

```
    content: "\e177";
}
.glyphicon-transfer:before {
    content: "\e178";
}
.glyphicon-cutlery:before {
    content: "\e179";
}
.glyphicon-header:before {
    content: "\e180";
}
.glyphicon-compressed:before {
    content: "\e181";
}
.glyphicon-earphone:before {
    content: "\e182";
}
.glyphicon-phone-alt:before {
    content: "\e183";
}
.glyphicon-tower:before {
    content: "\e184";
}
.glyphicon-stats:before {
    content: "\e185";
}
.glyphicon-sd-video:before {
    content: "\e186";
}
.glyphicon-hd-video:before {
    content: "\e187";
}
.glyphicon-subtitles:before {
    content: "\e188";
}
.glyphicon-sound-stereo:before {
    content: "\e189";
}
.glyphicon-sound-dolby:before {
    content: "\e190";
}
.glyphicon-sound-5-1:before {
    content: "\e191";
}
.glyphicon-sound-6-1:before {
    content: "\e192";
}
.glyphicon-sound-7-1:before {
    content: "\e193";
}
.glyphicon-copyright-mark:before {
```

```
    content: "\e194";
}
.glyphicon-registration-mark:before {
    content: "\e195";
}
.glyphicon-cloud-download:before {
    content: "\e197";
}
.glyphicon-cloud-upload:before {
    content: "\e198";
}
.glyphicon-tree-conifer:before {
    content: "\e199";
}
.glyphicon-tree-deciduous:before {
    content: "\e200";
}
.glyphicon-cd:before {
    content: "\e201";
}
.glyphicon-save-file:before {
    content: "\e202";
}
.glyphicon-open-file:before {
    content: "\e203";
}
.glyphicon-level-up:before {
    content: "\e204";
}
.glyphicon-copy:before {
    content: "\e205";
}
.glyphicon-paste:before {
    content: "\e206";
}
.glyphicon-alert:before {
    content: "\e209";
}
.glyphicon-equalizer:before {
    content: "\e210";
}
.glyphicon-king:before {
    content: "\e211";
}
.glyphicon-queen:before {
    content: "\e212";
}
.glyphicon-pawn:before {
    content: "\e213";
}
.glyphicon-bishop:before {
```

```
    content: "\e214";
}
.glyphicon-knight:before {
  content: "\e215";
}
.glyphicon-baby-formula:before {
  content: "\e216";
}
.glyphicon-tent:before {
  content: "\26fa";
}
.glyphicon-blackboard:before {
  content: "\e218";
}
.glyphicon-bed:before {
  content: "\e219";
}
.glyphicon-apple:before {
  content: "\f8ff";
}
.glyphicon-erase:before {
  content: "\e221";
}
.glyphicon-hourglass:before {
  content: "\231b";
}
.glyphicon-lamp:before {
  content: "\e223";
}
.glyphicon-duplicate:before {
  content: "\e224";
}
.glyphicon-piggy-bank:before {
  content: "\e225";
}
.glyphicon-scissors:before {
  content: "\e226";
}
.glyphicon-bitcoin:before {
  content: "\e227";
}
.glyphicon-btc:before {
  content: "\e227";
}
.glyphicon-xbt:before {
  content: "\e227";
}
.glyphicon-yen:before {
  content: "\00a5";
}
.glyphicon-jpy:before {
```

```
    content: "\00a5";
}
.glyphicon-ruble:before {
    content: "\20bd";
}
.glyphicon-rub:before {
    content: "\20bd";
}
.glyphicon-scale:before {
    content: "\e230";
}
.glyphicon-ice-lolly:before {
    content: "\e231";
}
.glyphicon-ice-lolly-tasted:before {
    content: "\e232";
}
.glyphicon-education:before {
    content: "\e233";
}
.glyphicon-option-horizontal:before {
    content: "\e234";
}
.glyphicon-option-vertical:before {
    content: "\e235";
}
.glyphicon-menu-hamburger:before {
    content: "\e236";
}
.glyphicon-modal-window:before {
    content: "\e237";
}
.glyphicon-oil:before {
    content: "\e238";
}
.glyphicon-grain:before {
    content: "\e239";
}
.glyphicon-sunglasses:before {
    content: "\e240";
}
.glyphicon-text-size:before {
    content: "\e241";
}
.glyphicon-text-color:before {
    content: "\e242";
}
.glyphicon-text-background:before {
    content: "\e243";
}
.glyphicon-object-align-top:before {
```

```
    content: "\e244";
}
.glyphicon-object-align-bottom:before {
    content: "\e245";
}
.glyphicon-object-align-horizontal:before {
    content: "\e246";
}
.glyphicon-object-align-left:before {
    content: "\e247";
}
.glyphicon-object-align-vertical:before {
    content: "\e248";
}
.glyphicon-object-align-right:before {
    content: "\e249";
}
.glyphicon-triangle-right:before {
    content: "\e250";
}
.glyphicon-triangle-left:before {
    content: "\e251";
}
.glyphicon-triangle-bottom:before {
    content: "\e252";
}
.glyphicon-triangle-top:before {
    content: "\e253";
}
.glyphicon-console:before {
    content: "\e254";
}
.glyphicon-superscript:before {
    content: "\e255";
}
.glyphicon-subscript:before {
    content: "\e256";
}
.glyphicon-menu-left:before {
    content: "\e257";
}
.glyphicon-menu-right:before {
    content: "\e258";
}
.glyphicon-menu-down:before {
    content: "\e259";
}
.glyphicon-menu-up:before {
    content: "\e260";
}
* {
```

```
-webkit-box-sizing: border-box;
-moz-box-sizing: border-box;
  box-sizing: border-box;
}
*:before,
*:after {
  -webkit-box-sizing: border-box;
  -moz-box-sizing: border-box;
  box-sizing: border-box;
}
html {
  font-size: 10px;

  -webkit-tap-highlight-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, 0);
}
body {
  font-family: "Helvetica Neue", Helvetica, Arial, sans-serif;
  font-size: 14px;
  line-height: 1.42857143;
  color: #333;
  background-color: #fff;
}
input,
button,
select,
textarea {
  font-family: inherit;
  font-size: inherit;
  line-height: inherit;
}
a {
  color: #337ab7;
  text-decoration: none;
}
a:hover,
a:focus {
  color: #23527c;
  text-decoration: none;
}
a:focus {
  outline: 5px auto -webkit-focus-ring-color;
  outline-offset: -2px;
}
figure {
  margin: 0;
}
img {
  vertical-align: middle;
}
.img-responsive,
.thumbnail > img,
```

```
.thumbnail a > img,
.carousel-inner > .item > img,
.carousel-inner > .item > a > img {
  display: block;
  max-width: 100%;
  height: auto;
}
.img-rounded {
  border-radius: 6px;
}
.img-thumbnail {
  display: inline-block;
  max-width: 100%;
  height: auto;
  padding: 4px;
  line-height: 1.42857143;
  background-color: #fff;
  border: 1px solid #ddd;
  border-radius: 4px;
  -webkit-transition: all .2s ease-in-out;
  -o-transition: all .2s ease-in-out;
  transition: all .2s ease-in-out;
}
.img-circle {
  border-radius: 50%;
}
hr {
  margin-top: 20px;
  margin-bottom: 20px;
  border: 0;
  border-top: 1px solid #eee;
}
.sr-only {
  position: absolute;
  width: 1px;
  height: 1px;
  padding: 0;
  margin: -1px;
  overflow: hidden;
  clip: rect(0, 0, 0, 0);
  border: 0;
}
.sr-only-focusable:active,
.sr-only-focusable:focus {
  position: static;
  width: auto;
  height: auto;
  margin: 0;
  overflow: visible;
  clip: auto;
}
```

```
[role="button"] {
  cursor: pointer;
}
h1,
h2,
h3,
h4,
h5,
h6,
.h1,
.h2,
.h3,
.h4,
.h5,
.h6 {
  font-family: inherit;
  font-weight: 500;
  line-height: 1.1;
  color: inherit;
}
h1 small,
h2 small,
h3 small,
h4 small,
h5 small,
h6 small,
.h1 small,
.h2 small,
.h3 small,
.h4 small,
.h5 small,
.h6 small,
h1 .small,
h2 .small,
h3 .small,
h4 .small,
h5 .small,
h6 .small,
.h1 .small,
.h2 .small,
.h3 .small,
.h4 .small,
.h5 .small,
.h6 .small {
  font-weight: normal;
  line-height: 1;
  color: #777;
}
h1,
.h1,
h2,
```

```
.h2,  
h3,  
.h3 {  
  margin-top: 20px;  
  margin-bottom: 10px;  
}  
h1 small,  
.h1 small,  
h2 small,  
.h2 small,  
h3 small,  
.h3 small,  
h1 .small,  
.h1 .small,  
h2 .small,  
.h2 .small,  
h3 .small,  
.h3 .small {  
  font-size: 65%;  
}  
h4,  
.h4,  
h5,  
.h5,  
h6,  
.h6 {  
  margin-top: 10px;  
  margin-bottom: 10px;  
}  
h4 small,  
.h4 small,  
h5 small,  
.h5 small,  
h6 small,  
.h6 small,  
h4 .small,  
.h4 .small,  
h5 .small,  
.h5 .small,  
h6 .small,  
.h6 .small {  
  font-size: 75%;  
}  
h1,  
.h1 {  
  font-size: 36px;  
}  
h2,  
.h2 {  
  font-size: 30px;  
}
```

```
h3,
.h3 {
  font-size: 24px;
}
h4,
.h4 {
  font-size: 18px;
}
h5,
.h5 {
  font-size: 14px;
}
h6,
.h6 {
  font-size: 12px;
}
p {
  margin: 0 0 10px;
}
.lead {
  margin-bottom: 20px;
  font-size: 16px;
  font-weight: 300;
  line-height: 1.4;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .lead {
    font-size: 21px;
  }
}
small,
.small {
  font-size: 85%;
}
mark,
.mark {
  padding: .2em;
  background-color: #fcf8e3;
}
.text-left {
  text-align: left;
}
.text-right {
  text-align: right;
}
.text-center {
  text-align: center;
}
.text-justify {
  text-align: justify;
}
```

```
.text-nowrap {
  white-space: nowrap;
}
.text-lowercase {
  text-transform: lowercase;
}
.text-uppercase {
  text-transform: uppercase;
}
.text-capitalize {
  text-transform: capitalize;
}
.text-muted {
  color: #777;
}
.text-primary {
  color: #337ab7;
}
a.text-primary:hover,
a.text-primary:focus {
  color: #286090;
}
.text-success {
  color: #3c763d;
}
a.text-success:hover,
a.text-success:focus {
  color: #2b542c;
}
.text-info {
  color: #31708f;
}
a.text-info:hover,
a.text-info:focus {
  color: #245269;
}
.text-warning {
  color: #8a6d3b;
}
a.text-warning:hover,
a.text-warning:focus {
  color: #66512c;
}
.text-danger {
  color: #a94442;
}
a.text-danger:hover,
a.text-danger:focus {
  color: #843534;
}
.bg-primary {
```

```
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #337ab7;
}
a.bg-primary:hover,
a.bg-primary:focus {
    background-color: #286090;
}
.bg-success {
    background-color: #dff0d8;
}
a.bg-success:hover,
a.bg-success:focus {
    background-color: #c1e2b3;
}
.bg-info {
    background-color: #d9edf7;
}
a.bg-info:hover,
a.bg-info:focus {
    background-color: #afd9ee;
}
.bg-warning {
    background-color: #fcf8e3;
}
a.bg-warning:hover,
a.bg-warning:focus {
    background-color: #f7ecb5;
}
.bg-danger {
    background-color: #f2dede;
}
a.bg-danger:hover,
a.bg-danger:focus {
    background-color: #e4b9b9;
}
.page-header {
    padding-bottom: 9px;
    margin: 40px 0 20px;
    border-bottom: 1px solid #eee;
}
ul,
ol {
    margin-top: 0;
    margin-bottom: 10px;
}
ul ul,
ol ul,
ul ol,
ol ol {
    margin-bottom: 0;
}
```

```
.list-unstyled {
  padding-left: 0;
  list-style: none;
}
.list-inline {
  padding-left: 0;
  margin-left: -5px;
  list-style: none;
}
.list-inline > li {
  display: inline-block;
  padding-right: 5px;
  padding-left: 5px;
}
dl {
  margin-top: 0;
  margin-bottom: 20px;
}
dt,
dd {
  line-height: 1.42857143;
}
dt {
  font-weight: bold;
}
dd {
  margin-left: 0;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .dl-horizontal dt {
    float: left;
    width: 160px;
    overflow: hidden;
    clear: left;
    text-align: right;
    text-overflow: ellipsis;
    white-space: nowrap;
  }
  .dl-horizontal dd {
    margin-left: 180px;
  }
}
abbr[title],
abbr[data-original-title] {
  cursor: help;
  border-bottom: 1px dotted #777;
}
.initialism {
  font-size: 90%;
  text-transform: uppercase;
}
```

```
blockquote {
  padding: 10px 20px;
  margin: 0 0 20px;
  font-size: 17.5px;
  border-left: 5px solid #eee;
}
blockquote p:last-child,
blockquote ul:last-child,
blockquote ol:last-child {
  margin-bottom: 0;
}
blockquote footer,
blockquote small,
blockquote .small {
  display: block;
  font-size: 80%;
  line-height: 1.42857143;
  color: #777;
}
blockquote footer:before,
blockquote small:before,
blockquote .small:before {
  content: '\2014 \00A0';
}
.blockquote-reverse,
blockquote.pull-right {
  padding-right: 15px;
  padding-left: 0;
  text-align: right;
  border-right: 5px solid #eee;
  border-left: 0;
}
.blockquote-reverse footer:before,
blockquote.pull-right footer:before,
.blockquote-reverse small:before,
blockquote.pull-right small:before,
.blockquote-reverse .small:before,
blockquote.pull-right .small:before {
  content: "";
}
.blockquote-reverse footer:after,
blockquote.pull-right footer:after,
.blockquote-reverse small:after,
blockquote.pull-right small:after,
.blockquote-reverse .small:after,
blockquote.pull-right .small:after {
  content: '\00A0 \2014';
}
address {
  margin-bottom: 20px;
  font-style: normal;
}
```

```
    line-height: 1.42857143;
}
code,
kbd,
pre,
samp {
    font-family: Menlo, Monaco, Consolas, "Courier New", monospace;
}
code {
    padding: 2px 4px;
    font-size: 90%;
    color: #c7254e;
    background-color: #f9f2f4;
    border-radius: 4px;
}
kbd {
    padding: 2px 4px;
    font-size: 90%;
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #333;
    border-radius: 3px;
    -webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 -1px 0 rgba(0, 0, 0, .25);
    box-shadow: inset 0 -1px 0 rgba(0, 0, 0, .25);
}
kbd kbd {
    padding: 0;
    font-size: 100%;
    font-weight: bold;
    -webkit-box-shadow: none;
    box-shadow: none;
}
pre {
    display: block;
    padding: 9.5px;
    margin: 0 0 10px;
    font-size: 13px;
    line-height: 1.42857143;
    color: #333;
    word-break: break-all;
    word-wrap: break-word;
    background-color: #f5f5f5;
    border: 1px solid #ccc;
    border-radius: 4px;
}
pre code {
    padding: 0;
    font-size: inherit;
    color: inherit;
    white-space: pre-wrap;
    background-color: transparent;
    border-radius: 0;
```

```

}
.pre-scrollable {
  max-height: 340px;
  overflow-y: scroll;
}
.container {
  padding-right: 15px;
  padding-left: 15px;
  margin-right: auto;
  margin-left: auto;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .container {
    width: 750px;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 992px) {
  .container {
    width: 970px;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 1200px) {
  .container {
    width: 970px;
  }
}
.container-fluid {
  padding-right: 15px;
  padding-left: 15px;
  margin-right: auto;
  margin-left: auto;
}
.row {
  margin-right: -15px;
  margin-left: -15px;
}
.col-xs-1, .col-sm-1, .col-md-1, .col-lg-1, .col-xs-2, .col-sm-2, .col-md-2, .col-lg-2, .col-xs-3, .col-sm-3,
.col-md-3, .col-lg-3, .col-xs-4, .col-sm-4, .col-md-4, .col-lg-4, .col-xs-5, .col-sm-5, .col-md-5, .col-lg-5,
.col-xs-6, .col-sm-6, .col-md-6, .col-lg-6, .col-xs-7, .col-sm-7, .col-md-7, .col-lg-7, .col-xs-8, .col-sm-8,
.col-md-8, .col-lg-8, .col-xs-9, .col-sm-9, .col-md-9, .col-lg-9, .col-xs-10, .col-sm-10, .col-md-10, .col-lg-
10, .col-xs-11, .col-sm-11, .col-md-11, .col-lg-11, .col-xs-12, .col-sm-12, .col-md-12, .col-lg-12 {
  position: relative;
  min-height: 1px;
  padding-right: 15px;
  padding-left: 15px;
}
.col-xs-1, .col-xs-2, .col-xs-3, .col-xs-4, .col-xs-5, .col-xs-6, .col-xs-7, .col-xs-8, .col-xs-9, .col-xs-10, .col-
xs-11, .col-xs-12 {
  float: left;
}
.col-xs-12 {

```

```
width: 100%;
}
.col-xs-11 {
width: 91.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-10 {
width: 83.33333333%;
}
.col-xs-9 {
width: 75%;
}
.col-xs-8 {
width: 66.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-7 {
width: 58.33333333%;
}
.col-xs-6 {
width: 50%;
}
.col-xs-5 {
width: 41.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-4 {
width: 33.33333333%;
}
.col-xs-3 {
width: 25%;
}
.col-xs-2 {
width: 16.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-1 {
width: 8.33333333%;
}
.col-xs-pull-12 {
right: 100%;
}
.col-xs-pull-11 {
right: 91.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-pull-10 {
right: 83.33333333%;
}
.col-xs-pull-9 {
right: 75%;
}
.col-xs-pull-8 {
right: 66.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-pull-7 {
```

```
    right: 58.33333333%;
  }
.col-xs-pull-6 {
  right: 50%;
}
.col-xs-pull-5 {
  right: 41.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-pull-4 {
  right: 33.33333333%;
}
.col-xs-pull-3 {
  right: 25%;
}
.col-xs-pull-2 {
  right: 16.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-pull-1 {
  right: 8.33333333%;
}
.col-xs-pull-0 {
  right: auto;
}
.col-xs-push-12 {
  left: 100%;
}
.col-xs-push-11 {
  left: 91.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-push-10 {
  left: 83.33333333%;
}
.col-xs-push-9 {
  left: 75%;
}
.col-xs-push-8 {
  left: 66.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-push-7 {
  left: 58.33333333%;
}
.col-xs-push-6 {
  left: 50%;
}
.col-xs-push-5 {
  left: 41.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-push-4 {
  left: 33.33333333%;
}
.col-xs-push-3 {
```

```
    left: 25%;
  }
.col-xs-push-2 {
  left: 16.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-push-1 {
  left: 8.33333333%;
}
.col-xs-push-0 {
  left: auto;
}
.col-xs-offset-12 {
  margin-left: 100%;
}
.col-xs-offset-11 {
  margin-left: 91.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-offset-10 {
  margin-left: 83.33333333%;
}
.col-xs-offset-9 {
  margin-left: 75%;
}
.col-xs-offset-8 {
  margin-left: 66.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-offset-7 {
  margin-left: 58.33333333%;
}
.col-xs-offset-6 {
  margin-left: 50%;
}
.col-xs-offset-5 {
  margin-left: 41.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-offset-4 {
  margin-left: 33.33333333%;
}
.col-xs-offset-3 {
  margin-left: 25%;
}
.col-xs-offset-2 {
  margin-left: 16.66666667%;
}
.col-xs-offset-1 {
  margin-left: 8.33333333%;
}
.col-xs-offset-0 {
  margin-left: 0;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
```

```
.col-sm-1, .col-sm-2, .col-sm-3, .col-sm-4, .col-sm-5, .col-sm-6, .col-sm-7, .col-sm-8, .col-sm-9, .col-  
sm-10, .col-sm-11, .col-sm-12 {  
  float: left;  
}  
.col-sm-12 {  
  width: 100%;  
}  
.col-sm-11 {  
  width: 91.66666667%;  
}  
.col-sm-10 {  
  width: 83.33333333%;  
}  
.col-sm-9 {  
  width: 75%;  
}  
.col-sm-8 {  
  width: 66.66666667%;  
}  
.col-sm-7 {  
  width: 58.33333333%;  
}  
.col-sm-6 {  
  width: 50%;  
}  
.col-sm-5 {  
  width: 41.66666667%;  
}  
.col-sm-4 {  
  width: 33.33333333%;  
}  
.col-sm-3 {  
  width: 25%;  
}  
.col-sm-2 {  
  width: 16.66666667%;  
}  
.col-sm-1 {  
  width: 8.33333333%;  
}  
.col-sm-pull-12 {  
  right: 100%;  
}  
.col-sm-pull-11 {  
  right: 91.66666667%;  
}  
.col-sm-pull-10 {  
  right: 83.33333333%;  
}  
.col-sm-pull-9 {  
  right: 75%;  
}
```

```
}  
.col-sm-pull-8 {  
  right: 66.66666667%;  
}  
.col-sm-pull-7 {  
  right: 58.33333333%;  
}  
.col-sm-pull-6 {  
  right: 50%;  
}  
.col-sm-pull-5 {  
  right: 41.66666667%;  
}  
.col-sm-pull-4 {  
  right: 33.33333333%;  
}  
.col-sm-pull-3 {  
  right: 25%;  
}  
.col-sm-pull-2 {  
  right: 16.66666667%;  
}  
.col-sm-pull-1 {  
  right: 8.33333333%;  
}  
.col-sm-pull-0 {  
  right: auto;  
}  
.col-sm-push-12 {  
  left: 100%;  
}  
.col-sm-push-11 {  
  left: 91.66666667%;  
}  
.col-sm-push-10 {  
  left: 83.33333333%;  
}  
.col-sm-push-9 {  
  left: 75%;  
}  
.col-sm-push-8 {  
  left: 66.66666667%;  
}  
.col-sm-push-7 {  
  left: 58.33333333%;  
}  
.col-sm-push-6 {  
  left: 50%;  
}  
.col-sm-push-5 {  
  left: 41.66666667%;
```

```
}
.col-sm-push-4 {
  left: 33.33333333%;
}
.col-sm-push-3 {
  left: 25%;
}
.col-sm-push-2 {
  left: 16.66666667%;
}
.col-sm-push-1 {
  left: 8.33333333%;
}
.col-sm-push-0 {
  left: auto;
}
.col-sm-offset-12 {
  margin-left: 100%;
}
.col-sm-offset-11 {
  margin-left: 91.66666667%;
}
.col-sm-offset-10 {
  margin-left: 83.33333333%;
}
.col-sm-offset-9 {
  margin-left: 75%;
}
.col-sm-offset-8 {
  margin-left: 66.66666667%;
}
.col-sm-offset-7 {
  margin-left: 58.33333333%;
}
.col-sm-offset-6 {
  margin-left: 50%;
}
.col-sm-offset-5 {
  margin-left: 41.66666667%;
}
.col-sm-offset-4 {
  margin-left: 33.33333333%;
}
.col-sm-offset-3 {
  margin-left: 25%;
}
.col-sm-offset-2 {
  margin-left: 16.66666667%;
}
.col-sm-offset-1 {
  margin-left: 8.33333333%;
}
```

```
}
.col-sm-offset-0 {
  margin-left: 0;
}
}
@media (min-width: 992px) {
.col-md-1, .col-md-2, .col-md-3, .col-md-4, .col-md-5, .col-md-6, .col-md-7, .col-md-8, .col-md-9,
.col-md-10, .col-md-11, .col-md-12 {
  float: left;
}
.col-md-12 {
  width: 100%;
}
.col-md-11 {
  width: 91.66666667%;
}
.col-md-10 {
  width: 83.33333333%;
}
.col-md-9 {
  width: 75%;
}
.col-md-8 {
  width: 66.66666667%;
}
.col-md-7 {
  width: 58.33333333%;
}
.col-md-6 {
  width: 50%;
}
.col-md-5 {
  width: 41.66666667%;
}
.col-md-4 {
  width: 33.33333333%;
}
.col-md-3 {
  width: 25%;
}
.col-md-2 {
  width: 16.66666667%;
}
.col-md-1 {
  width: 8.33333333%;
}
.col-md-pull-12 {
  right: 100%;
}
.col-md-pull-11 {
  right: 91.66666667%;
```

```
}
.col-md-pull-10 {
  right: 83.33333333%;
}
.col-md-pull-9 {
  right: 75%;
}
.col-md-pull-8 {
  right: 66.66666667%;
}
.col-md-pull-7 {
  right: 58.33333333%;
}
.col-md-pull-6 {
  right: 50%;
}
.col-md-pull-5 {
  right: 41.66666667%;
}
.col-md-pull-4 {
  right: 33.33333333%;
}
.col-md-pull-3 {
  right: 25%;
}
.col-md-pull-2 {
  right: 16.66666667%;
}
.col-md-pull-1 {
  right: 8.33333333%;
}
.col-md-pull-0 {
  right: auto;
}
.col-md-push-12 {
  left: 100%;
}
.col-md-push-11 {
  left: 91.66666667%;
}
.col-md-push-10 {
  left: 83.33333333%;
}
.col-md-push-9 {
  left: 75%;
}
.col-md-push-8 {
  left: 66.66666667%;
}
.col-md-push-7 {
  left: 58.33333333%;
```

```
}
.col-md-push-6 {
  left: 50%;
}
.col-md-push-5 {
  left: 41.66666667%;
}
.col-md-push-4 {
  left: 33.33333333%;
}
.col-md-push-3 {
  left: 25%;
}
.col-md-push-2 {
  left: 16.66666667%;
}
.col-md-push-1 {
  left: 8.33333333%;
}
.col-md-push-0 {
  left: auto;
}
.col-md-offset-12 {
  margin-left: 100%;
}
.col-md-offset-11 {
  margin-left: 91.66666667%;
}
.col-md-offset-10 {
  margin-left: 83.33333333%;
}
.col-md-offset-9 {
  margin-left: 75%;
}
.col-md-offset-8 {
  margin-left: 66.66666667%;
}
.col-md-offset-7 {
  margin-left: 58.33333333%;
}
.col-md-offset-6 {
  margin-left: 50%;
}
.col-md-offset-5 {
  margin-left: 41.66666667%;
}
.col-md-offset-4 {
  margin-left: 33.33333333%;
}
.col-md-offset-3 {
  margin-left: 25%;
```

```
}
.col-md-offset-2 {
  margin-left: 16.66666667%;
}
.col-md-offset-1 {
  margin-left: 8.33333333%;
}
.col-md-offset-0 {
  margin-left: 0;
}
}
@media (min-width: 1200px) {
.col-lg-1, .col-lg-2, .col-lg-3, .col-lg-4, .col-lg-5, .col-lg-6, .col-lg-7, .col-lg-8, .col-lg-9, .col-lg-10, .col-lg-
11, .col-lg-12 {
  float: left;
}
.col-lg-12 {
  width: 100%;
}
.col-lg-11 {
  width: 91.66666667%;
}
.col-lg-10 {
  width: 83.33333333%;
}
.col-lg-9 {
  width: 75%;
}
.col-lg-8 {
  width: 66.66666667%;
}
.col-lg-7 {
  width: 58.33333333%;
}
.col-lg-6 {
  width: 50%;
}
.col-lg-5 {
  width: 41.66666667%;
}
.col-lg-4 {
  width: 33.33333333%;
}
.col-lg-3 {
  width: 25%;
}
.col-lg-2 {
  width: 16.66666667%;
}
.col-lg-1 {
  width: 8.33333333%;
}
```

```
}
.col-lg-pull-12 {
  right: 100%;
}
.col-lg-pull-11 {
  right: 91.66666667%;
}
.col-lg-pull-10 {
  right: 83.33333333%;
}
.col-lg-pull-9 {
  right: 75%;
}
.col-lg-pull-8 {
  right: 66.66666667%;
}
.col-lg-pull-7 {
  right: 58.33333333%;
}
.col-lg-pull-6 {
  right: 50%;
}
.col-lg-pull-5 {
  right: 41.66666667%;
}
.col-lg-pull-4 {
  right: 33.33333333%;
}
.col-lg-pull-3 {
  right: 25%;
}
.col-lg-pull-2 {
  right: 16.66666667%;
}
.col-lg-pull-1 {
  right: 8.33333333%;
}
.col-lg-pull-0 {
  right: auto;
}
.col-lg-push-12 {
  left: 100%;
}
.col-lg-push-11 {
  left: 91.66666667%;
}
.col-lg-push-10 {
  left: 83.33333333%;
}
.col-lg-push-9 {
  left: 75%;
```

```
}  
.col-lg-push-8 {  
  left: 66.66666667%;  
}  
.col-lg-push-7 {  
  left: 58.33333333%;  
}  
.col-lg-push-6 {  
  left: 50%;  
}  
.col-lg-push-5 {  
  left: 41.66666667%;  
}  
.col-lg-push-4 {  
  left: 33.33333333%;  
}  
.col-lg-push-3 {  
  left: 25%;  
}  
.col-lg-push-2 {  
  left: 16.66666667%;  
}  
.col-lg-push-1 {  
  left: 8.33333333%;  
}  
.col-lg-push-0 {  
  left: auto;  
}  
.col-lg-offset-12 {  
  margin-left: 100%;  
}  
.col-lg-offset-11 {  
  margin-left: 91.66666667%;  
}  
.col-lg-offset-10 {  
  margin-left: 83.33333333%;  
}  
.col-lg-offset-9 {  
  margin-left: 75%;  
}  
.col-lg-offset-8 {  
  margin-left: 66.66666667%;  
}  
.col-lg-offset-7 {  
  margin-left: 58.33333333%;  
}  
.col-lg-offset-6 {  
  margin-left: 50%;  
}  
.col-lg-offset-5 {  
  margin-left: 41.66666667%;
```

```

}
.col-lg-offset-4 {
  margin-left: 33.33333333%;
}
.col-lg-offset-3 {
  margin-left: 25%;
}
.col-lg-offset-2 {
  margin-left: 16.66666667%;
}
.col-lg-offset-1 {
  margin-left: 8.33333333%;
}
.col-lg-offset-0 {
  margin-left: 0;
}
}
table {
  background-color: transparent;
}
caption {
  padding-top: 8px;
  padding-bottom: 8px;
  color: #777;
  text-align: left;
}
th {
  text-align: left;
}
.table {
  width: 100%;
  max-width: 100%;
  margin-bottom: 20px;
}
.table > thead > tr > th,
.table > tbody > tr > th,
.table > tfoot > tr > th,
.table > thead > tr > td,
.table > tbody > tr > td,
.table > tfoot > tr > td {
  padding: 8px;
  line-height: 1.42857143;
  vertical-align: top;
  border-top: 1px solid #ddd;
}
.table > thead > tr > th {
  vertical-align: bottom;
  border-bottom: 2px solid #ddd;
}
.table > caption + thead > tr:first-child > th,
.table > colgroup + thead > tr:first-child > th,

```

```

.table > thead:first-child > tr:first-child > th,
.table > caption + thead > tr:first-child > td,
.table > colgroup + thead > tr:first-child > td,
.table > thead:first-child > tr:first-child > td {
  border-top: 0;
}
.table > tbody + tbody {
  border-top: 2px solid #ddd;
}
.table .table {
  background-color: #fff;
}
.table-condensed > thead > tr > th,
.table-condensed > tbody > tr > th,
.table-condensed > tfoot > tr > th,
.table-condensed > thead > tr > td,
.table-condensed > tbody > tr > td,
.table-condensed > tfoot > tr > td {
  padding: 5px;
}
.table-bordered {
  border: 1px solid #ddd;
}
.table-bordered > thead > tr > th,
.table-bordered > tbody > tr > th,
.table-bordered > tfoot > tr > th,
.table-bordered > thead > tr > td,
.table-bordered > tbody > tr > td,
.table-bordered > tfoot > tr > td {
  border: 1px solid #ddd;
}
.table-bordered > thead > tr > th,
.table-bordered > thead > tr > td {
  border-bottom-width: 2px;
}
.table-striped > tbody > tr:nth-of-type(odd) {
  background-color: #f9f9f9;
}
.table-hover > tbody > tr:hover {
  background-color: #f5f5f5;
}
table col[class*="col-"] {
  position: static;
  display: table-column;
  float: none;
}
table td[class*="col-"],
table th[class*="col-"] {
  position: static;
  display: table-cell;
  float: none;
}

```

```
}  
.table > thead > tr > td.active,  
.table > tbody > tr > td.active,  
.table > tfoot > tr > td.active,  
.table > thead > tr > th.active,  
.table > tbody > tr > th.active,  
.table > tfoot > tr > th.active,  
.table > thead > tr.active > td,  
.table > tbody > tr.active > td,  
.table > tfoot > tr.active > td,  
.table > thead > tr.active > th,  
.table > tbody > tr.active > th,  
.table > tfoot > tr.active > th {  
  background-color: #f5f5f5;  
}  
.table-hover > tbody > tr > td.active:hover,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr > th.active:hover,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr.active:hover > td,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr:hover > .active,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr.active:hover > th {  
  background-color: #e8e8e8;  
}  
.table > thead > tr > td.success,  
.table > tbody > tr > td.success,  
.table > tfoot > tr > td.success,  
.table > thead > tr > th.success,  
.table > tbody > tr > th.success,  
.table > tfoot > tr > th.success,  
.table > thead > tr.success > td,  
.table > tbody > tr.success > td,  
.table > tfoot > tr.success > td,  
.table > thead > tr.success > th,  
.table > tbody > tr.success > th,  
.table > tfoot > tr.success > th {  
  background-color: #dff0d8;  
}  
.table-hover > tbody > tr > td.success:hover,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr > th.success:hover,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr.success:hover > td,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr:hover > .success,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr.success:hover > th {  
  background-color: #d0e9c6;  
}  
.table > thead > tr > td.info,  
.table > tbody > tr > td.info,  
.table > tfoot > tr > td.info,  
.table > thead > tr > th.info,  
.table > tbody > tr > th.info,  
.table > tfoot > tr > th.info,  
.table > thead > tr.info > td,  
.table > tbody > tr.info > td,
```

```
.table > tfoot > tr.info > td,  
.table > thead > tr.info > th,  
.table > tbody > tr.info > th,  
.table > tfoot > tr.info > th {  
  background-color: #d9edf7;  
}  
.table-hover > tbody > tr > td.info:hover,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr > th.info:hover,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr.info:hover > td,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr:hover > .info,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr.info:hover > th {  
  background-color: #c4e3f3;  
}  
.table > thead > tr > td.warning,  
.table > tbody > tr > td.warning,  
.table > tfoot > tr > td.warning,  
.table > thead > tr > th.warning,  
.table > tbody > tr > th.warning,  
.table > tfoot > tr > th.warning,  
.table > thead > tr.warning > td,  
.table > tbody > tr.warning > td,  
.table > tfoot > tr.warning > td,  
.table > thead > tr.warning > th,  
.table > tbody > tr.warning > th,  
.table > tfoot > tr.warning > th {  
  background-color: #fcf8e3;  
}  
.table-hover > tbody > tr > td.warning:hover,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr > th.warning:hover,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr.warning:hover > td,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr:hover > .warning,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr.warning:hover > th {  
  background-color: #faf2cc;  
}  
.table > thead > tr > td.danger,  
.table > tbody > tr > td.danger,  
.table > tfoot > tr > td.danger,  
.table > thead > tr > th.danger,  
.table > tbody > tr > th.danger,  
.table > tfoot > tr > th.danger,  
.table > thead > tr.danger > td,  
.table > tbody > tr.danger > td,  
.table > tfoot > tr.danger > td,  
.table > thead > tr.danger > th,  
.table > tbody > tr.danger > th,  
.table > tfoot > tr.danger > th {  
  background-color: #f2dede;  
}  
.table-hover > tbody > tr > td.danger:hover,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr > th.danger:hover,  
.table-hover > tbody > tr.danger:hover > td,
```

```

.table-hover > tbody > tr:hover > .danger,
.table-hover > tbody > tr.danger:hover > th {
  background-color: #ebcccc;
}
.table-responsive {
  min-height: .01%;
  overflow-x: auto;
}
@media screen and (max-width: 767px) {
  .table-responsive {
    width: 100%;
    margin-bottom: 15px;
    overflow-y: hidden;
    -ms-overflow-style: -ms-autohiding-scrollbar;
    border: 1px solid #ddd;
  }
  .table-responsive > .table {
    margin-bottom: 0;
  }
  .table-responsive > .table > thead > tr > th,
  .table-responsive > .table > tbody > tr > th,
  .table-responsive > .table > tfoot > tr > th,
  .table-responsive > .table > thead > tr > td,
  .table-responsive > .table > tbody > tr > td,
  .table-responsive > .table > tfoot > tr > td {
    white-space: nowrap;
  }
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered {
    border: 0;
  }
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > thead > tr > th:first-child,
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tbody > tr > th:first-child,
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr > th:first-child,
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > thead > tr > td:first-child,
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tbody > tr > td:first-child,
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr > td:first-child {
    border-left: 0;
  }
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > thead > tr > th:last-child,
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tbody > tr > th:last-child,
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr > th:last-child,
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > thead > tr > td:last-child,
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tbody > tr > td:last-child,
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr > td:last-child {
    border-right: 0;
  }
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tbody > tr:last-child > th,
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr:last-child > th,
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tbody > tr:last-child > td,
  .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr:last-child > td {
    border-bottom: 0;
  }
}

```

```
}
}
fieldset {
  min-width: 0;
  padding: 0;
  margin: 0;
  border: 0;
}
legend {
  display: block;
  width: 100%;
  padding: 0;
  margin-bottom: 20px;
  font-size: 21px;
  line-height: inherit;
  color: #333;
  border: 0;
  border-bottom: 1px solid #e5e5e5;
}
label {
  display: inline-block;
  max-width: 100%;
  margin-bottom: 5px;
  font-weight: bold;
}
input[type="search"] {
  -webkit-box-sizing: border-box;
  -moz-box-sizing: border-box;
  box-sizing: border-box;
}
input[type="radio"],
input[type="checkbox"] {
  margin: 4px 0 0;
  margin-top: 1px \9;
  line-height: normal;
}
input[type="file"] {
  display: block;
}
input[type="range"] {
  display: block;
  width: 100%;
}
select[multiple],
select[size] {
  height: auto;
}
input[type="file"]:focus,
input[type="radio"]:focus,
input[type="checkbox"]:focus {
  outline: 5px auto -webkit-focus-ring-color;
```

```
    outline-offset: -2px;
  }
  output {
    display: block;
    padding-top: 7px;
    font-size: 14px;
    line-height: 1.42857143;
    color: #555;
  }
  .form-control {
    display: block;
    width: 100%;
    height: 34px;
    padding: 6px 12px;
    font-size: 14px;
    line-height: 1.42857143;
    color: #555;
    background-color: #fff;
    background-image: none;
    border: 1px solid #ccc;
    border-radius: 4px;
    -webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
    box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
    -webkit-transition: border-color ease-in-out .15s, -webkit-box-shadow ease-in-out .15s;
    -o-transition: border-color ease-in-out .15s, box-shadow ease-in-out .15s;
    transition: border-color ease-in-out .15s, box-shadow ease-in-out .15s;
  }
  .form-control:focus {
    border-color: #66afe9;
    outline: 0;
    -webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075), 0 0 8px rgba(102, 175, 233, .6);
    box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075), 0 0 8px rgba(102, 175, 233, .6);
  }
  .form-control::-moz-placeholder {
    color: #999;
    opacity: 1;
  }
  .form-control:-ms-input-placeholder {
    color: #999;
  }
  .form-control::-webkit-input-placeholder {
    color: #999;
  }
  .form-control::-ms-expand {
    background-color: transparent;
    border: 0;
  }
  .form-control[disabled],
  .form-control[readonly],
  fieldset[disabled] .form-control {
    background-color: #eee;
```

```
    opacity: 1;
}
.form-control[disabled],
fieldset[disabled] .form-control {
    cursor: not-allowed;
}
textarea.form-control {
    height: auto;
}
input[type="search"] {
    -webkit-appearance: none;
}
@media screen and (-webkit-min-device-pixel-ratio: 0) {
    input[type="date"].form-control,
    input[type="time"].form-control,
    input[type="datetime-local"].form-control,
    input[type="month"].form-control {
        line-height: 34px;
    }
    input[type="date"].input-sm,
    input[type="time"].input-sm,
    input[type="datetime-local"].input-sm,
    input[type="month"].input-sm,
    .input-group-sm input[type="date"],
    .input-group-sm input[type="time"],
    .input-group-sm input[type="datetime-local"],
    .input-group-sm input[type="month"] {
        line-height: 30px;
    }
    input[type="date"].input-lg,
    input[type="time"].input-lg,
    input[type="datetime-local"].input-lg,
    input[type="month"].input-lg,
    .input-group-lg input[type="date"],
    .input-group-lg input[type="time"],
    .input-group-lg input[type="datetime-local"],
    .input-group-lg input[type="month"] {
        line-height: 46px;
    }
}
.form-group {
    margin-bottom: 15px;
}
.radio,
.checkbox {
    position: relative;
    display: block;
    margin-top: 10px;
    margin-bottom: 10px;
}
.radio label,
```

```
.checkbox label {
  min-height: 20px;
  padding-left: 20px;
  margin-bottom: 0;
  font-weight: normal;
  cursor: pointer;
}
.radio input[type="radio"],
.radio-inline input[type="radio"],
.checkbox input[type="checkbox"],
.checkbox-inline input[type="checkbox"] {
  position: absolute;
  margin-top: 4px \9;
  margin-left: -20px;
}
.radio + .radio,
.checkbox + .checkbox {
  margin-top: -5px;
}
.radio-inline,
.checkbox-inline {
  position: relative;
  display: inline-block;
  padding-left: 20px;
  margin-bottom: 0;
  font-weight: normal;
  vertical-align: middle;
  cursor: pointer;
}
.radio-inline + .radio-inline,
.checkbox-inline + .checkbox-inline {
  margin-top: 0;
  margin-left: 10px;
}
input[type="radio"][disabled],
input[type="checkbox"][disabled],
input[type="radio"].disabled,
input[type="checkbox"].disabled,
fieldset[disabled] input[type="radio"],
fieldset[disabled] input[type="checkbox"] {
  cursor: not-allowed;
}
.radio-inline.disabled,
.checkbox-inline.disabled,
fieldset[disabled] .radio-inline,
fieldset[disabled] .checkbox-inline {
  cursor: not-allowed;
}
.radio.disabled label,
.checkbox.disabled label,
fieldset[disabled] .radio label,
```

```
fieldset[disabled] .checkbox label {
  cursor: not-allowed;
}
.form-control-static {
  min-height: 34px;
  padding-top: 7px;
  padding-bottom: 7px;
  margin-bottom: 0;
}
.form-control-static.input-lg,
.form-control-static.input-sm {
  padding-right: 0;
  padding-left: 0;
}
.input-sm {
  height: 30px;
  padding: 5px 10px;
  font-size: 12px;
  line-height: 1.5;
  border-radius: 3px;
}
select.input-sm {
  height: 30px;
  line-height: 30px;
}
textarea.input-sm,
select[multiple].input-sm {
  height: auto;
}
.form-group-sm .form-control {
  height: 30px;
  padding: 5px 10px;
  font-size: 12px;
  line-height: 1.5;
  border-radius: 3px;
}
.form-group-sm select.form-control {
  height: 30px;
  line-height: 30px;
}
.form-group-sm textarea.form-control,
.form-group-sm select[multiple].form-control {
  height: auto;
}
.form-group-sm .form-control-static {
  height: 30px;
  min-height: 32px;
  padding: 6px 10px;
  font-size: 12px;
  line-height: 1.5;
}
```

```
.input-lg {
  height: 46px;
  padding: 10px 16px;
  font-size: 18px;
  line-height: 1.3333333;
  border-radius: 6px;
}
select.input-lg {
  height: 46px;
  line-height: 46px;
}
textarea.input-lg,
select[multiple].input-lg {
  height: auto;
}
.form-group-lg .form-control {
  height: 46px;
  padding: 10px 16px;
  font-size: 18px;
  line-height: 1.3333333;
  border-radius: 6px;
}
.form-group-lg select.form-control {
  height: 46px;
  line-height: 46px;
}
.form-group-lg textarea.form-control,
.form-group-lg select[multiple].form-control {
  height: auto;
}
.form-group-lg .form-control-static {
  height: 46px;
  min-height: 38px;
  padding: 11px 16px;
  font-size: 18px;
  line-height: 1.3333333;
}
.has-feedback {
  position: relative;
}
.has-feedback .form-control {
  padding-right: 42.5px;
}
.form-control-feedback {
  position: absolute;
  top: 0;
  right: 0;
  z-index: 2;
  display: block;
  width: 34px;
  height: 34px;
```

```
line-height: 34px;
text-align: center;
pointer-events: none;
}
.input-lg + .form-control-feedback,
.input-group-lg + .form-control-feedback,
.form-group-lg .form-control + .form-control-feedback {
width: 46px;
height: 46px;
line-height: 46px;
}
.input-sm + .form-control-feedback,
.input-group-sm + .form-control-feedback,
.form-group-sm .form-control + .form-control-feedback {
width: 30px;
height: 30px;
line-height: 30px;
}
.has-success .help-block,
.has-success .control-label,
.has-success .radio,
.has-success .checkbox,
.has-success .radio-inline,
.has-success .checkbox-inline,
.has-success.radio label,
.has-success.checkbox label,
.has-success.radio-inline label,
.has-success.checkbox-inline label {
color: #3c763d;
}
.has-success .form-control {
border-color: #3c763d;
-webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
}
.has-success .form-control:focus {
border-color: #2b542c;
-webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075), 0 0 6px #67b168;
box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075), 0 0 6px #67b168;
}
.has-success .input-group-addon {
color: #3c763d;
background-color: #dff0d8;
border-color: #3c763d;
}
.has-success .form-control-feedback {
color: #3c763d;
}
.has-warning .help-block,
.has-warning .control-label,
.has-warning .radio,
```

```
.has-warning .checkbox,
.has-warning .radio-inline,
.has-warning .checkbox-inline,
.has-warning.radio label,
.has-warning.checkbox label,
.has-warning.radio-inline label,
.has-warning.checkbox-inline label {
  color: #8a6d3b;
}
.has-warning .form-control {
  border-color: #8a6d3b;
  -webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
  box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
}
.has-warning .form-control:focus {
  border-color: #66512c;
  -webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075), 0 0 6px #c0a16b;
  box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075), 0 0 6px #c0a16b;
}
.has-warning .input-group-addon {
  color: #8a6d3b;
  background-color: #fcf8e3;
  border-color: #8a6d3b;
}
.has-warning .form-control-feedback {
  color: #8a6d3b;
}
.has-error .help-block,
.has-error .control-label,
.has-error .radio,
.has-error .checkbox,
.has-error .radio-inline,
.has-error .checkbox-inline,
.has-error.radio label,
.has-error.checkbox label,
.has-error.radio-inline label,
.has-error.checkbox-inline label {
  color: #a94442;
}
.has-error .form-control {
  border-color: #a94442;
  -webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
  box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
}
.has-error .form-control:focus {
  border-color: #843534;
  -webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075), 0 0 6px #ce8483;
  box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075), 0 0 6px #ce8483;
}
.has-error .input-group-addon {
  color: #a94442;
}
```

```
background-color: #f2dede;
border-color: #a94442;
}
.has-error .form-control-feedback {
color: #a94442;
}
.has-feedback label ~ .form-control-feedback {
top: 25px;
}
.has-feedback label.sr-only ~ .form-control-feedback {
top: 0;
}
.help-block {
display: block;
margin-top: 5px;
margin-bottom: 10px;
color: #737373;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
.form-inline .form-group {
display: inline-block;
margin-bottom: 0;
vertical-align: middle;
}
.form-inline .form-control {
display: inline-block;
width: auto;
vertical-align: middle;
}
.form-inline .form-control-static {
display: inline-block;
}
.form-inline .input-group {
display: inline-table;
vertical-align: middle;
}
.form-inline .input-group .input-group-addon,
.form-inline .input-group .input-group-btn,
.form-inline .input-group .form-control {
width: auto;
}
.form-inline .input-group > .form-control {
width: 100%;
}
.form-inline .control-label {
margin-bottom: 0;
vertical-align: middle;
}
.form-inline .radio,
.form-inline .checkbox {
display: inline-block;
```

```
margin-top: 0;
margin-bottom: 0;
vertical-align: middle;
}
.form-inline .radio label,
.form-inline .checkbox label {
padding-left: 0;
}
.form-inline .radio input[type="radio"],
.form-inline .checkbox input[type="checkbox"] {
position: relative;
margin-left: 0;
}
.form-inline .has-feedback .form-control-feedback {
top: 0;
}
}
.form-horizontal .radio,
.form-horizontal .checkbox,
.form-horizontal .radio-inline,
.form-horizontal .checkbox-inline {
padding-top: 7px;
margin-top: 0;
margin-bottom: 0;
}
.form-horizontal .radio,
.form-horizontal .checkbox {
min-height: 27px;
}
.form-horizontal .form-group {
margin-right: -15px;
margin-left: -15px;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
.form-horizontal .control-label {
padding-top: 7px;
margin-bottom: 0;
text-align: right;
}
}
.form-horizontal .has-feedback .form-control-feedback {
right: 15px;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
.form-horizontal .form-group-lg .control-label {
padding-top: 11px;
font-size: 18px;
}
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
.form-horizontal .form-group-sm .control-label {
```

```
padding-top: 6px;
font-size: 12px;
}
}
.btn {
display: inline-block;
padding: 6px 12px;
margin-bottom: 0;
font-size: 14px;
font-weight: normal;
line-height: 1.42857143;
text-align: center;
white-space: nowrap;
vertical-align: middle;
-ms-touch-action: manipulation;
touch-action: manipulation;
cursor: pointer;
-webkit-user-select: none;
-moz-user-select: none;
-ms-user-select: none;
user-select: none;
background-image: none;
border: 1px solid transparent;
border-radius: 4px;
}
.btn:focus,
.btn:active:focus,
.btn.active:focus,
.btn.focus,
.btn.active.focus,
.btn.active.focus {
outline: 5px auto -webkit-focus-ring-color;
outline-offset: -2px;
}
.btn:hover,
.btn:focus,
.btn.focus {
color: #333;
text-decoration: none;
}
.btn:active,
.btn.active {
background-image: none;
outline: 0;
-webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 3px 5px rgba(0, 0, 0, .125);
box-shadow: inset 0 3px 5px rgba(0, 0, 0, .125);
}
.btn.disabled,
.btn[disabled],
fieldset[disabled] .btn {
cursor: not-allowed;
```

```
filter: alpha(opacity=65);
-webkit-box-shadow: none;
  box-shadow: none;
opacity: .65;
}
a.btn.disabled,
fieldset[disabled] a.btn {
  pointer-events: none;
}
.btn-default {
  color: #333;
  background-color: #fff;
  border-color: #ccc;
}
.btn-default:focus,
.btn-default.focus {
  color: #333;
  background-color: #e6e6e6;
  border-color: #8c8c8c;
}
.btn-default:hover {
  color: #333;
  background-color: #e6e6e6;
  border-color: #adadad;
}
.btn-default:active,
.btn-default.active,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-default {
  color: #333;
  background-color: #e6e6e6;
  border-color: #adadad;
}
.btn-default:active:hover,
.btn-default.active:hover,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-default:hover,
.btn-default:active:focus,
.btn-default.active:focus,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-default:focus,
.btn-default:active.focus,
.btn-default.active.focus,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-default.focus {
  color: #333;
  background-color: #d4d4d4;
  border-color: #8c8c8c;
}
.btn-default:active,
.btn-default.active,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-default {
  background-image: none;
}
.btn-default.disabled:hover,
```

```
.btn-default[disabled]:hover,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-default:hover,
.btn-default.disabled:focus,
.btn-default[disabled]:focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-default:focus,
.btn-default.disabled:focus,
.btn-default[disabled].focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-default.focus {
  background-color: #fff;
  border-color: #ccc;
}
.btn-default .badge {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #333;
}
.btn-primary {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #EF3B3A;
  border-color: #b93130;
}
.btn-primary:focus,
.btn-primary.focus {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #286090;
  border-color: #122b40;
}
.btn-primary:hover {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #d03c3b;
  border-color: #b93130;
}
.btn-primary:active,
.btn-primary.active,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-primary {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #286090;
  border-color: #204d74;
}
.btn-primary:active:hover,
.btn-primary.active:hover,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-primary:hover,
.btn-primary:active:focus,
.btn-primary.active:focus,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-primary:focus,
.btn-primary:active.focus,
.btn-primary.active.focus,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-primary.focus {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #204d74;
  border-color: #122b40;
}
```

```
.btn-primary:active,  
.btn-primary.active,  
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-primary {  
  background-image: none;  
}  
.btn-primary.disabled:hover,  
.btn-primary[disabled]:hover,  
fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary:hover,  
.btn-primary.disabled:focus,  
.btn-primary[disabled]:focus,  
fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary:focus,  
.btn-primary.disabled.focus,  
.btn-primary[disabled].focus,  
fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary.focus {  
  background-color: #337ab7;  
  border-color: #2e6da4;  
}  
.btn-primary .badge {  
  color: #337ab7;  
  background-color: #fff;  
}  
.btn-success {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #5cb85c;  
  border-color: #4cae4c;  
}  
.btn-success:focus,  
.btn-success.focus {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #449d44;  
  border-color: #255625;  
}  
.btn-success:hover {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #449d44;  
  border-color: #398439;  
}  
.btn-success:active,  
.btn-success.active,  
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-success {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #449d44;  
  border-color: #398439;  
}  
.btn-success:active:hover,  
.btn-success.active:hover,  
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-success:hover,  
.btn-success:active:focus,  
.btn-success.active:focus,  
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-success:focus,  
.btn-success.active.focus,
```

```
.btn-success.active.focus,  
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-success.focus {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #398439;  
  border-color: #255625;  
}  
.btn-success:active,  
.btn-success.active,  
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-success {  
  background-image: none;  
}  
.btn-success.disabled:hover,  
.btn-success[disabled]:hover,  
fieldset[disabled] .btn-success:hover,  
.btn-success.disabled:focus,  
.btn-success[disabled]:focus,  
fieldset[disabled] .btn-success:focus,  
.btn-success.disabled.focus,  
.btn-success[disabled].focus,  
fieldset[disabled] .btn-success.focus {  
  background-color: #5cb85c;  
  border-color: #4cae4c;  
}  
.btn-success .badge {  
  color: #5cb85c;  
  background-color: #fff;  
}  
.btn-info {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #5bc0de;  
  border-color: #46b8da;  
}  
.btn-info:focus,  
.btn-info.focus {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #31b0d5;  
  border-color: #1b6d85;  
}  
.btn-info:hover {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #31b0d5;  
  border-color: #269abc;  
}  
.btn-info:active,  
.btn-info.active,  
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-info {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #31b0d5;  
  border-color: #269abc;  
}  
.btn-info:active:hover,
```

```
.btn-info.active:hover,  
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-info:hover,  
.btn-info.active:focus,  
.btn-info.active:focus,  
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-info:focus,  
.btn-info.active.focus,  
.btn-info.active.focus,  
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-info.focus {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #269abc;  
  border-color: #1b6d85;  
}  
.btn-info.active,  
.btn-info.active,  
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-info {  
  background-image: none;  
}  
.btn-info.disabled:hover,  
.btn-info[disabled]:hover,  
fieldset[disabled] .btn-info:hover,  
.btn-info.disabled:focus,  
.btn-info[disabled]:focus,  
fieldset[disabled] .btn-info:focus,  
.btn-info.disabled.focus,  
.btn-info[disabled].focus,  
fieldset[disabled] .btn-info.focus {  
  background-color: #5bc0de;  
  border-color: #46b8da;  
}  
.btn-info .badge {  
  color: #5bc0de;  
  background-color: #fff;  
}  
.btn-warning {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #f0ad4e;  
  border-color: #eea236;  
}  
.btn-warning:focus,  
.btn-warning.focus {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #ec971f;  
  border-color: #985f0d;  
}  
.btn-warning:hover {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #ec971f;  
  border-color: #d58512;  
}  
.btn-warning.active,  
.btn-warning.active,
```

```
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-warning {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #ec971f;
  border-color: #d58512;
}
.btn-warning:active:hover,
.btn-warning.active:hover,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-warning:hover,
.btn-warning:active:focus,
.btn-warning.active:focus,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-warning:focus,
.btn-warning:active.focus,
.btn-warning.active.focus,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-warning.focus {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #d58512;
  border-color: #985f0d;
}
.btn-warning:active,
.btn-warning.active,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-warning {
  background-image: none;
}
.btn-warning.disabled:hover,
.btn-warning[disabled]:hover,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning:hover,
.btn-warning.disabled:focus,
.btn-warning[disabled]:focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning:focus,
.btn-warning.disabled.focus,
.btn-warning[disabled].focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning.focus {
  background-color: #f0ad4e;
  border-color: #eea236;
}
.btn-warning .badge {
  color: #f0ad4e;
  background-color: #fff;
}
.btn-danger {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #d9534f;
  border-color: #d43f3a;
}
.btn-danger:focus,
.btn-danger.focus {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #c9302c;
  border-color: #761c19;
}
.btn-danger:hover {
```

```
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #c9302c;
    border-color: #ac2925;
}
.btn-danger:active,
.btn-danger.active,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-danger {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #c9302c;
    border-color: #ac2925;
}
.btn-danger:active:hover,
.btn-danger.active:hover,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-danger:hover,
.btn-danger:active:focus,
.btn-danger.active:focus,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-danger:focus,
.btn-danger:active.focus,
.btn-danger.active.focus,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-danger.focus {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #ac2925;
    border-color: #761c19;
}
.btn-danger:active,
.btn-danger.active,
.open > .dropdown-toggle.btn-danger {
    background-image: none;
}
.btn-danger.disabled:hover,
.btn-danger[disabled]:hover,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger:hover,
.btn-danger.disabled:focus,
.btn-danger[disabled]:focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger:focus,
.btn-danger.disabled.focus,
.btn-danger[disabled].focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger.focus {
    background-color: #d9534f;
    border-color: #d43f3a;
}
.btn-danger .badge {
    color: #d9534f;
    background-color: #fff;
}
.btn-link {
    font-weight: normal;
    color: #337ab7;
    border-radius: 0;
}
.btn-link,
```

```
.btn-link:active,  
.btn-link.active,  
.btn-link[disabled],  
fieldset[disabled] .btn-link {  
  background-color: transparent;  
  -webkit-box-shadow: none;  
  box-shadow: none;  
}  
.btn-link,  
.btn-link:hover,  
.btn-link:focus,  
.btn-link:active {  
  border-color: transparent;  
}  
.btn-link:hover,  
.btn-link:focus {  
  color: #23527c;  
  text-decoration: underline;  
  background-color: transparent;  
}  
.btn-link[disabled]:hover,  
fieldset[disabled] .btn-link:hover,  
.btn-link[disabled]:focus,  
fieldset[disabled] .btn-link:focus {  
  color: #777;  
  text-decoration: none;  
}  
.btn-lg,  
.btn-group-lg > .btn {  
  padding: 10px 16px;  
  font-size: 18px;  
  line-height: 1.3333333;  
  border-radius: 6px;  
}  
.btn-sm,  
.btn-group-sm > .btn {  
  padding: 5px 10px;  
  font-size: 12px;  
  line-height: 1.5;  
  border-radius: 3px;  
}  
.btn-xs,  
.btn-group-xs > .btn {  
  padding: 1px 5px;  
  font-size: 12px;  
  line-height: 1.5;  
  border-radius: 3px;  
}  
.btn-block {  
  display: block;  
  width: 100%;
```

```
}
.btn-block + .btn-block {
  margin-top: 5px;
}
input[type="submit"].btn-block,
input[type="reset"].btn-block,
input[type="button"].btn-block {
  width: 100%;
}
.fade {
  opacity: 0;
  -webkit-transition: opacity .15s linear;
  -o-transition: opacity .15s linear;
  transition: opacity .15s linear;
}
.fade.in {
  opacity: 1;
}
.collapse {
  display: none;
}
.collapse.in {
  display: block;
}
tr.collapse.in {
  display: table-row;
}
tbody.collapse.in {
  display: table-row-group;
}
.collapsing {
  position: relative;
  height: 0;
  overflow: hidden;
  -webkit-transition-timing-function: ease;
  -o-transition-timing-function: ease;
  transition-timing-function: ease;
  -webkit-transition-duration: .35s;
  -o-transition-duration: .35s;
  transition-duration: .35s;
  -webkit-transition-property: height, visibility;
  -o-transition-property: height, visibility;
  transition-property: height, visibility;
}
.caret {
  display: inline-block;
  width: 0;
  height: 0;
  margin-left: 2px;
  vertical-align: middle;
  border-top: 4px dashed;
```

```
border-top: 4px solid \9;
border-right: 4px solid transparent;
border-left: 4px solid transparent;
}
.dropup,
.dropdown {
  position: relative;
}
.dropdown-toggle:focus {
  outline: 0;
}
.dropdown-menu {
  position: absolute;
  top: 100%;
  left: 0;
  z-index: 1000;
  display: none;
  float: left;
  min-width: 160px;
  padding: 5px 0;
  margin: 2px 0 0;
  font-size: 14px;
  text-align: left;
  list-style: none;
  background-color: #fff;
  -webkit-background-clip: padding-box;
  background-clip: padding-box;
  border: 1px solid #ccc;
  border: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .15);
  border-radius: 4px;
  -webkit-box-shadow: 0 6px 12px rgba(0, 0, 0, .175);
  box-shadow: 0 6px 12px rgba(0, 0, 0, .175);
}
.dropdown-menu.pull-right {
  right: 0;
  left: auto;
}
.dropdown-menu .divider {
  height: 1px;
  margin: 9px 0;
  overflow: hidden;
  background-color: #e5e5e5;
}
.dropdown-menu > li > a {
  display: block;
  padding: 3px 20px;
  clear: both;
  font-weight: normal;
  line-height: 1.42857143;
  color: #333;
  white-space: nowrap;
```

```
}
.dropdown-menu > li > a:hover,
.dropdown-menu > li > a:focus {
  color: #262626;
  text-decoration: none;
  background-color: #f5f5f5;
}
.dropdown-menu > .active > a,
.dropdown-menu > .active > a:hover,
.dropdown-menu > .active > a:focus {
  color: #fff;
  text-decoration: none;
  background-color: #337ab7;
  outline: 0;
}
.dropdown-menu > .disabled > a,
.dropdown-menu > .disabled > a:hover,
.dropdown-menu > .disabled > a:focus {
  color: #777;
}
.dropdown-menu > .disabled > a:hover,
.dropdown-menu > .disabled > a:focus {
  text-decoration: none;
  cursor: not-allowed;
  background-color: transparent;
  background-image: none;
  filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled = false);
}
.open > .dropdown-menu {
  display: block;
}
.open > a {
  outline: 0;
}
.dropdown-menu-right {
  right: 0;
  left: auto;
}
.dropdown-menu-left {
  right: auto;
  left: 0;
}
.dropdown-header {
  display: block;
  padding: 3px 20px;
  font-size: 12px;
  line-height: 1.42857143;
  color: #777;
  white-space: nowrap;
}
.dropdown-backdrop {
```

```
position: fixed;
top: 0;
right: 0;
bottom: 0;
left: 0;
z-index: 990;
}
.pull-right > .dropdown-menu {
right: 0;
left: auto;
}
.dropdown .caret,
.navbar-fixed-bottom .dropdown .caret {
content: "";
border-top: 0;
border-bottom: 4px dashed;
border-bottom: 4px solid \9;
}
.dropdown .dropdown-menu,
.navbar-fixed-bottom .dropdown .dropdown-menu {
top: auto;
bottom: 100%;
margin-bottom: 2px;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
.navbar-right .dropdown-menu {
right: 0;
left: auto;
}
.navbar-right .dropdown-menu-left {
right: auto;
left: 0;
}
}
.btn-group,
.btn-group-vertical {
position: relative;
display: inline-block;
vertical-align: middle;
}
.btn-group > .btn,
.btn-group-vertical > .btn {
position: relative;
float: left;
}
.btn-group > .btn:hover,
.btn-group-vertical > .btn:hover,
.btn-group > .btn:focus,
.btn-group-vertical > .btn:focus,
.btn-group > .btn.active,
.btn-group-vertical > .btn.active,
```

```
.btn-group > .btn.active,  
.btn-group-vertical > .btn.active {  
  z-index: 2;  
}  
.btn-group .btn + .btn,  
.btn-group .btn + .btn-group,  
.btn-group .btn-group + .btn,  
.btn-group .btn-group + .btn-group {  
  margin-left: -1px;  
}  
.btn-toolbar {  
  margin-left: -5px;  
}  
.btn-toolbar .btn,  
.btn-toolbar .btn-group,  
.btn-toolbar .input-group {  
  float: left;  
}  
.btn-toolbar > .btn,  
.btn-toolbar > .btn-group,  
.btn-toolbar > .input-group {  
  margin-left: 5px;  
}  
.btn-group > .btn:not(:first-child):not(:last-child):not(.dropdown-toggle) {  
  border-radius: 0;  
}  
.btn-group > .btn:first-child {  
  margin-left: 0;  
}  
.btn-group > .btn:first-child:not(:last-child):not(.dropdown-toggle) {  
  border-top-right-radius: 0;  
  border-bottom-right-radius: 0;  
}  
.btn-group > .btn:last-child:not(:first-child),  
.btn-group > .dropdown-toggle:not(:first-child) {  
  border-top-left-radius: 0;  
  border-bottom-left-radius: 0;  
}  
.btn-group > .btn-group {  
  float: left;  
}  
.btn-group > .btn-group:not(:first-child):not(:last-child) > .btn {  
  border-radius: 0;  
}  
.btn-group > .btn-group:first-child:not(:last-child) > .btn:last-child,  
.btn-group > .btn-group:first-child:not(:last-child) > .dropdown-toggle {  
  border-top-right-radius: 0;  
  border-bottom-right-radius: 0;  
}  
.btn-group > .btn-group:last-child:not(:first-child) > .btn:first-child {  
  border-top-left-radius: 0;
```

```

border-bottom-left-radius: 0;
}
.btn-group .dropdown-toggle:active,
.btn-group.open .dropdown-toggle {
outline: 0;
}
.btn-group > .btn + .dropdown-toggle {
padding-right: 8px;
padding-left: 8px;
}
.btn-group > .btn-lg + .dropdown-toggle {
padding-right: 12px;
padding-left: 12px;
}
.btn-group.open .dropdown-toggle {
-webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 3px 5px rgba(0, 0, 0, .125);
box-shadow: inset 0 3px 5px rgba(0, 0, 0, .125);
}
.btn-group.open .dropdown-toggle.btn-link {
-webkit-box-shadow: none;
box-shadow: none;
}
.btn .caret {
margin-left: 0;
}
.btn-lg .caret {
border-width: 5px 5px 0;
border-bottom-width: 0;
}
.dropdown .btn-lg .caret {
border-width: 0 5px 5px;
}
.btn-group-vertical > .btn,
.btn-group-vertical > .btn-group,
.btn-group-vertical > .btn-group > .btn {
display: block;
float: none;
width: 100%;
max-width: 100%;
}
.btn-group-vertical > .btn-group > .btn {
float: none;
}
.btn-group-vertical > .btn + .btn,
.btn-group-vertical > .btn + .btn-group,
.btn-group-vertical > .btn-group + .btn,
.btn-group-vertical > .btn-group + .btn-group {
margin-top: -1px;
margin-left: 0;
}
.btn-group-vertical > .btn:not(:first-child):not(:last-child) {

```

```

border-radius: 0;
}
.btn-group-vertical > .btn:first-child:not(:last-child) {
border-top-left-radius: 4px;
border-top-right-radius: 4px;
border-bottom-right-radius: 0;
border-bottom-left-radius: 0;
}
.btn-group-vertical > .btn:last-child:not(:first-child) {
border-top-left-radius: 0;
border-top-right-radius: 0;
border-bottom-right-radius: 4px;
border-bottom-left-radius: 4px;
}
.btn-group-vertical > .btn-group:not(:first-child):not(:last-child) > .btn {
border-radius: 0;
}
.btn-group-vertical > .btn-group:first-child:not(:last-child) > .btn:last-child,
.btn-group-vertical > .btn-group:first-child:not(:last-child) > .dropdown-toggle {
border-bottom-right-radius: 0;
border-bottom-left-radius: 0;
}
.btn-group-vertical > .btn-group:last-child:not(:first-child) > .btn:first-child {
border-top-left-radius: 0;
border-top-right-radius: 0;
}
.btn-group-justified {
display: table;
width: 100%;
table-layout: fixed;
border-collapse: separate;
}
.btn-group-justified > .btn,
.btn-group-justified > .btn-group {
display: table-cell;
float: none;
width: 1%;
}
.btn-group-justified > .btn-group .btn {
width: 100%;
}
.btn-group-justified > .btn-group .dropdown-menu {
left: auto;
}
[data-toggle="buttons"] > .btn input[type="radio"],
[data-toggle="buttons"] > .btn-group > .btn input[type="radio"],
[data-toggle="buttons"] > .btn input[type="checkbox"],
[data-toggle="buttons"] > .btn-group > .btn input[type="checkbox"] {
position: absolute;
clip: rect(0, 0, 0, 0);
pointer-events: none;
}

```

```

}
.input-group {
  position: relative;
  display: table;
  border-collapse: separate;
}
.input-group[class*="col-"] {
  float: none;
  padding-right: 0;
  padding-left: 0;
}
.input-group .form-control {
  position: relative;
  z-index: 2;
  float: left;
  width: 100%;
  margin-bottom: 0;
}
.input-group .form-control:focus {
  z-index: 3;
}
.input-group-lg > .form-control,
.input-group-lg > .input-group-addon,
.input-group-lg > .input-group-btn > .btn {
  height: 46px;
  padding: 10px 16px;
  font-size: 18px;
  line-height: 1.3333333;
  border-radius: 6px;
}
select.input-group-lg > .form-control,
select.input-group-lg > .input-group-addon,
select.input-group-lg > .input-group-btn > .btn {
  height: 46px;
  line-height: 46px;
}
textarea.input-group-lg > .form-control,
textarea.input-group-lg > .input-group-addon,
textarea.input-group-lg > .input-group-btn > .btn,
select[multiple].input-group-lg > .form-control,
select[multiple].input-group-lg > .input-group-addon,
select[multiple].input-group-lg > .input-group-btn > .btn {
  height: auto;
}
.input-group-sm > .form-control,
.input-group-sm > .input-group-addon,
.input-group-sm > .input-group-btn > .btn {
  height: 30px;
  padding: 5px 10px;
  font-size: 12px;
  line-height: 1.5;
}

```

```
border-radius: 3px;
}
select.input-group-sm > .form-control,
select.input-group-sm > .input-group-addon,
select.input-group-sm > .input-group-btn > .btn {
  height: 30px;
  line-height: 30px;
}
textarea.input-group-sm > .form-control,
textarea.input-group-sm > .input-group-addon,
textarea.input-group-sm > .input-group-btn > .btn,
select[multiple].input-group-sm > .form-control,
select[multiple].input-group-sm > .input-group-addon,
select[multiple].input-group-sm > .input-group-btn > .btn {
  height: auto;
}
.input-group-addon,
.input-group-btn,
.input-group .form-control {
  display: table-cell;
}
.input-group-addon:not(:first-child):not(:last-child),
.input-group-btn:not(:first-child):not(:last-child),
.input-group .form-control:not(:first-child):not(:last-child) {
  border-radius: 0;
}
.input-group-addon,
.input-group-btn {
  width: 1%;
  white-space: nowrap;
  vertical-align: middle;
}
.input-group-addon {
  padding: 6px 12px;
  font-size: 14px;
  font-weight: normal;
  line-height: 1;
  color: #555;
  text-align: center;
  background-color: #eee;
  border: 1px solid #ccc;
  border-radius: 4px;
}
.input-group-addon.input-sm {
  padding: 5px 10px;
  font-size: 12px;
  border-radius: 3px;
}
.input-group-addon.input-lg {
  padding: 10px 16px;
  font-size: 18px;
}
```

```

border-radius: 6px;
}
.input-group-addon input[type="radio"],
.input-group-addon input[type="checkbox"] {
margin-top: 0;
}
.input-group .form-control:first-child,
.input-group-addon:first-child,
.input-group-btn:first-child > .btn,
.input-group-btn:first-child > .btn-group > .btn,
.input-group-btn:first-child > .dropdown-toggle,
.input-group-btn:last-child > .btn:not(:last-child):not(.dropdown-toggle),
.input-group-btn:last-child > .btn-group:not(:last-child) > .btn {
border-top-right-radius: 0;
border-bottom-right-radius: 0;
}
.input-group-addon:first-child {
border-right: 0;
}
.input-group .form-control:last-child,
.input-group-addon:last-child,
.input-group-btn:last-child > .btn,
.input-group-btn:last-child > .btn-group > .btn,
.input-group-btn:last-child > .dropdown-toggle,
.input-group-btn:first-child > .btn:not(:first-child),
.input-group-btn:first-child > .btn-group:not(:first-child) > .btn {
border-top-left-radius: 0;
border-bottom-left-radius: 0;
}
.input-group-addon:last-child {
border-left: 0;
}
.input-group-btn {
position: relative;
font-size: 0;
white-space: nowrap;
}
.input-group-btn > .btn {
position: relative;
}
.input-group-btn > .btn + .btn {
margin-left: -1px;
}
.input-group-btn > .btn:hover,
.input-group-btn > .btn:focus,
.input-group-btn > .btn:active {
z-index: 2;
}
.input-group-btn:first-child > .btn,
.input-group-btn:first-child > .btn-group {
margin-right: -1px;
}

```

```
}
.input-group-btn:last-child > .btn,
.input-group-btn:last-child > .btn-group {
  z-index: 2;
  margin-left: -1px;
}
.nav {
  padding-left: 0;
  margin-bottom: 0;
  list-style: none;
}
.nav > li {
  position: relative;
  display: block;
}
.nav > li > a {
  position: relative;
  display: block;
  padding: 10px 15px;
}
.nav > li > a:hover,
.nav > li > a:focus {
  text-decoration: none;
  background-color: #eee;
}
.nav > li.disabled > a {
  color: #777;
}
.nav > li.disabled > a:hover,
.nav > li.disabled > a:focus {
  color: #777;
  text-decoration: none;
  cursor: not-allowed;
  background-color: transparent;
}
.nav .open > a,
.nav .open > a:hover,
.nav .open > a:focus {
  background-color: #eee;
  border-color: #337ab7;
}
.nav .nav-divider {
  height: 1px;
  margin: 9px 0;
  overflow: hidden;
  background-color: #e5e5e5;
}
.nav > li > a > img {
  max-width: none;
}
.nav-tabs {
```

```
border-bottom: 1px solid #ddd;
}
.nav-tabs > li {
  float: left;
  margin-bottom: -1px;
}
.nav-tabs > li > a {
  margin-right: 2px;
  line-height: 1.42857143;
  border: 1px solid transparent;
  border-radius: 4px 4px 0 0;
}
.nav-tabs > li > a:hover {
  border-color: #eee #eee #ddd;
}
.nav-tabs > li.active > a,
.nav-tabs > li.active > a:hover,
.nav-tabs > li.active > a:focus {
  color: #555;
  cursor: default;
  background-color: #fff;
  border: 1px solid #ddd;
  border-bottom-color: transparent;
}
.nav-tabs.nav-justified {
  width: 100%;
  border-bottom: 0;
}
.nav-tabs.nav-justified > li {
  float: none;
}
.nav-tabs.nav-justified > li > a {
  margin-bottom: 5px;
  text-align: center;
}
.nav-tabs.nav-justified > .dropdown .dropdown-menu {
  top: auto;
  left: auto;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .nav-tabs.nav-justified > li {
    display: table-cell;
    width: 1%;
  }
  .nav-tabs.nav-justified > li > a {
    margin-bottom: 0;
  }
}
.nav-tabs.nav-justified > li > a {
  margin-right: 0;
  border-radius: 4px;
```

```
}
.nav-tabs.nav-justified > .active > a,
.nav-tabs.nav-justified > .active > a:hover,
.nav-tabs.nav-justified > .active > a:focus {
  border: 1px solid #ddd;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .nav-tabs.nav-justified > li > a {
    border-bottom: 1px solid #ddd;
    border-radius: 4px 4px 0 0;
  }
  .nav-tabs.nav-justified > .active > a,
  .nav-tabs.nav-justified > .active > a:hover,
  .nav-tabs.nav-justified > .active > a:focus {
    border-bottom-color: #fff;
  }
}
.nav-pills > li {
  float: left;
}
.nav-pills > li > a {
  border-radius: 4px;
}
.nav-pills > li + li {
  margin-left: 2px;
}
.nav-pills > li.active > a,
.nav-pills > li.active > a:hover,
.nav-pills > li.active > a:focus {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #337ab7;
}
.nav-stacked > li {
  float: none;
}
.nav-stacked > li + li {
  margin-top: 2px;
  margin-left: 0;
}
.nav-justified {
  width: 100%;
}
.nav-justified > li {
  float: none;
}
.nav-justified > li > a {
  margin-bottom: 5px;
  text-align: center;
}
.nav-justified > .dropdown .dropdown-menu {
  top: auto;
```

```
left: auto;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .nav-justified > li {
    display: table-cell;
    width: 1%;
  }
  .nav-justified > li > a {
    margin-bottom: 0;
  }
}
.nav-tabs-justified {
  border-bottom: 0;
}
.nav-tabs-justified > li > a {
  margin-right: 0;
  border-radius: 4px;
}
.nav-tabs-justified > .active > a,
.nav-tabs-justified > .active > a:hover,
.nav-tabs-justified > .active > a:focus {
  border: 1px solid #ddd;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .nav-tabs-justified > li > a {
    border-bottom: 1px solid #ddd;
    border-radius: 4px 4px 0 0;
  }
  .nav-tabs-justified > .active > a,
  .nav-tabs-justified > .active > a:hover,
  .nav-tabs-justified > .active > a:focus {
    border-bottom-color: #fff;
  }
}
.tab-content > .tab-pane {
  display: none;
}
.tab-content > .active {
  display: block;
}
.nav-tabs .dropdown-menu {
  margin-top: -1px;
  border-top-left-radius: 0;
  border-top-right-radius: 0;
}
.navbar {
  position: relative;
  min-height: 50px;
  margin-bottom: 20px;
  border: 1px solid transparent;
}
```

```
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .navbar {
    border-radius: 4px;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .navbar-header {
    float: left;
  }
}
.navbar-collapse {
  padding-right: 15px;
  padding-left: 15px;
  overflow-x: visible;
  -webkit-overflow-scrolling: touch;
  border-top: 1px solid transparent;
  -webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .1);
  box-shadow: inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .1);
}
.navbar-collapse.in {
  overflow-y: auto;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .navbar-collapse {
    width: auto;
    border-top: 0;
    -webkit-box-shadow: none;
    box-shadow: none;
  }
  .navbar-collapse.collapse {
    display: block !important;
    height: auto !important;
    padding-bottom: 0;
    overflow: visible !important;
  }
  .navbar-collapse.in {
    overflow-y: visible;
  }
  .navbar-fixed-top .navbar-collapse,
  .navbar-static-top .navbar-collapse,
  .navbar-fixed-bottom .navbar-collapse {
    padding-right: 0;
    padding-left: 0;
  }
}
.navbar-fixed-top .navbar-collapse,
.navbar-fixed-bottom .navbar-collapse {
  max-height: 340px;
}
}
@media (max-device-width: 480px) and (orientation: landscape) {
  .navbar-fixed-top .navbar-collapse,
```

```
.navbar-fixed-bottom .navbar-collapse {
  max-height: 200px;
}
}
.container > .navbar-header,
.container-fluid > .navbar-header,
.container > .navbar-collapse,
.container-fluid > .navbar-collapse {
  margin-right: -15px;
  margin-left: -15px;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .container > .navbar-header,
  .container-fluid > .navbar-header,
  .container > .navbar-collapse,
  .container-fluid > .navbar-collapse {
    margin-right: 0;
    margin-left: 0;
  }
}
}
.navbar-static-top {
  z-index: 1000;
  border-width: 0 0 1px;
}
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .navbar-static-top {
    border-radius: 0;
  }
}
}
.navbar-fixed-top,
.navbar-fixed-bottom {
  position: fixed;
  right: 0;
  left: 0;
  z-index: 1030;
}
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .navbar-fixed-top,
  .navbar-fixed-bottom {
    border-radius: 0;
  }
}
}
.navbar-fixed-top {
  top: 0;
  border-width: 0 0 1px;
}
}
.navbar-fixed-bottom {
  bottom: 0;
  margin-bottom: 0;
  border-width: 1px 0 0;
}
}
```

```
.navbar-brand {
  float: left;
  height: 50px;
  padding: 15px 15px;
  font-size: 18px;
  line-height: 20px;
}
.navbar-brand:hover,
.navbar-brand:focus {
  text-decoration: none;
}
.navbar-brand > img {
  display: block;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .navbar > .container .navbar-brand,
  .navbar > .container-fluid .navbar-brand {
    margin-left: -15px;
  }
}
.navbar-toggle {
  position: relative;
  float: right;
  padding: 9px 10px;
  margin-top: 8px;
  margin-right: 15px;
  margin-bottom: 8px;
  background-color: transparent;
  background-image: none;
  border: 1px solid transparent;
  border-radius: 4px;
}
.navbar-toggle:focus {
  outline: 0;
}
.navbar-toggle .icon-bar {
  display: block;
  width: 22px;
  height: 2px;
  border-radius: 1px;
}
.navbar-toggle .icon-bar + .icon-bar {
  margin-top: 4px;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .navbar-toggle {
    display: none;
  }
}
.navbar-nav {
  margin: 7.5px -15px;
```

```

}
.navbar-nav > li > a {
  padding-top: 10px;
  padding-bottom: 10px;
  line-height: 20px;
}
@media (max-width: 767px) {
  .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu {
    position: static;
    float: none;
    width: auto;
    margin-top: 0;
    background-color: transparent;
    border: 0;
    -webkit-box-shadow: none;
    box-shadow: none;
  }
  .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > li > a,
  .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu .dropdown-header {
    padding: 5px 15px 5px 25px;
  }
  .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > li > a {
    line-height: 20px;
  }
  .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > li > a:hover,
  .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > li > a:focus {
    background-image: none;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .navbar-nav {
    float: left;
    margin: 0;
  }
  .navbar-nav > li {
    float: left;
  }
  .navbar-nav > li > a {
    padding-top: 15px;
    padding-bottom: 15px;
  }
}
.navbar-form {
  padding: 10px 15px;
  margin-top: 8px;
  margin-right: -15px;
  margin-bottom: 8px;
  margin-left: -15px;
  border-top: 1px solid transparent;
  border-bottom: 1px solid transparent;
  -webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .1), 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .1);
}

```

```
        box-shadow: inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .1), 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .1);
    }
    @media (min-width: 768px) {
        .navbar-form .form-group {
            display: inline-block;
            margin-bottom: 0;
            vertical-align: middle;
        }
        .navbar-form .form-control {
            display: inline-block;
            width: auto;
            vertical-align: middle;
        }
        .navbar-form .form-control-static {
            display: inline-block;
        }
        .navbar-form .input-group {
            display: inline-table;
            vertical-align: middle;
        }
        .navbar-form .input-group .input-group-addon,
        .navbar-form .input-group .input-group-btn,
        .navbar-form .input-group .form-control {
            width: auto;
        }
        .navbar-form .input-group > .form-control {
            width: 100%;
        }
        .navbar-form .control-label {
            margin-bottom: 0;
            vertical-align: middle;
        }
        .navbar-form .radio,
        .navbar-form .checkbox {
            display: inline-block;
            margin-top: 0;
            margin-bottom: 0;
            vertical-align: middle;
        }
        .navbar-form .radio label,
        .navbar-form .checkbox label {
            padding-left: 0;
        }
        .navbar-form .radio input[type="radio"],
        .navbar-form .checkbox input[type="checkbox"] {
            position: relative;
            margin-left: 0;
        }
        .navbar-form .has-feedback .form-control-feedback {
            top: 0;
        }
    }
```

```
}
@media (max-width: 767px) {
  .navbar-form .form-group {
    margin-bottom: 5px;
  }
  .navbar-form .form-group:last-child {
    margin-bottom: 0;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .navbar-form {
    width: auto;
    padding-top: 0;
    padding-bottom: 0;
    margin-right: 0;
    margin-left: 0;
    border: 0;
    -webkit-box-shadow: none;
    box-shadow: none;
  }
}
.navbar-nav > li > .dropdown-menu {
  margin-top: 0;
  border-top-left-radius: 0;
  border-top-right-radius: 0;
}
.navbar-fixed-bottom .navbar-nav > li > .dropdown-menu {
  margin-bottom: 0;
  border-top-left-radius: 4px;
  border-top-right-radius: 4px;
  border-bottom-right-radius: 0;
  border-bottom-left-radius: 0;
}
.navbar-btn {
  margin-top: 8px;
  margin-bottom: 8px;
}
.navbar-btn.btn-sm {
  margin-top: 10px;
  margin-bottom: 10px;
}
.navbar-btn.btn-xs {
  margin-top: 14px;
  margin-bottom: 14px;
}
.navbar-text {
  margin-top: 15px;
  margin-bottom: 15px;
}
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .navbar-text {
```

```
float: left;
margin-right: 15px;
margin-left: 15px;
}
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
.navbar-left {
float: left !important;
}
.navbar-right {
float: right !important;
margin-right: -15px;
}
.navbar-right ~ .navbar-right {
margin-right: 0;
}
}
.navbar-default {
background-color: #f8f8f8;
border-color: #e7e7e7;
}
.navbar-default .navbar-brand {
color: #777;
}
.navbar-default .navbar-brand:hover,
.navbar-default .navbar-brand:focus {
color: #5e5e5e;
background-color: transparent;
}
.navbar-default .navbar-text {
color: #777;
}
.navbar-default .navbar-nav > li > a {
color: #777;
}
.navbar-default .navbar-nav > li > a:hover,
.navbar-default .navbar-nav > li > a:focus {
color: #333;
background-color: transparent;
}
.navbar-default .navbar-nav > .active > a,
.navbar-default .navbar-nav > .active > a:hover,
.navbar-default .navbar-nav > .active > a:focus {
color: #555;
background-color: #e7e7e7;
}
.navbar-default .navbar-nav > .disabled > a,
.navbar-default .navbar-nav > .disabled > a:hover,
.navbar-default .navbar-nav > .disabled > a:focus {
color: #ccc;
background-color: transparent;
}
```

```
}
.navbar-default .navbar-toggle {
  border-color: #ddd;
}
.navbar-default .navbar-toggle:hover,
.navbar-default .navbar-toggle:focus {
  background-color: #ddd;
}
.navbar-default .navbar-toggle .icon-bar {
  background-color: #888;
}
.navbar-default .navbar-collapse,
.navbar-default .navbar-form {
  border-color: #e7e7e7;
}
.navbar-default .navbar-nav > .open > a,
.navbar-default .navbar-nav > .open > a:hover,
.navbar-default .navbar-nav > .open > a:focus {
  color: #555;
  background-color: #e7e7e7;
}
@media (max-width: 767px) {
  .navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > li > a {
    color: #777;
  }
  .navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > li > a:hover,
  .navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > li > a:focus {
    color: #333;
    background-color: transparent;
  }
  .navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .active > a,
  .navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .active > a:hover,
  .navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .active > a:focus {
    color: #555;
    background-color: #e7e7e7;
  }
  .navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .disabled > a,
  .navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .disabled > a:hover,
  .navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .disabled > a:focus {
    color: #ccc;
    background-color: transparent;
  }
}
.navbar-default .navbar-link {
  color: #777;
}
.navbar-default .navbar-link:hover {
  color: #333;
}
.navbar-default .btn-link {
  color: #777;
```

```
}
.navbar-default .btn-link:hover,
.navbar-default .btn-link:focus {
  color: #333;
}
.navbar-default .btn-link[disabled]:hover,
fieldset[disabled] .navbar-default .btn-link:hover,
.navbar-default .btn-link[disabled]:focus,
fieldset[disabled] .navbar-default .btn-link:focus {
  color: #ccc;
}
.navbar-inverse {
  background-color: #222;
  border-color: #080808;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-brand {
  color: #9d9d9d;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-brand:hover,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-brand:focus {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: transparent;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-text {
  color: #9d9d9d;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav > li > a {
  color: #9d9d9d;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav > li > a:hover,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav > li > a:focus {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: transparent;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav > .active > a,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav > .active > a:hover,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav > .active > a:focus {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #080808;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav > .disabled > a,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav > .disabled > a:hover,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav > .disabled > a:focus {
  color: #444;
  background-color: transparent;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-toggle {
  border-color: #333;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-toggle:hover,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-toggle:focus {
```

```
background-color: #333;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-toggle .icon-bar {
background-color: #fff;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-collapse,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-form {
border-color: #101010;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav > .open > a,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav > .open > a:hover,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav > .open > a:focus {
color: #fff;
background-color: #080808;
}
@media (max-width: 767px) {
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .dropdown-header {
border-color: #080808;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu .divider {
background-color: #080808;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > li > a {
color: #9d9d9d;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > li > a:hover,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > li > a:focus {
color: #fff;
background-color: transparent;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .active > a,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .active > a:hover,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .active > a:focus {
color: #fff;
background-color: #080808;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .disabled > a,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .disabled > a:hover,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .disabled > a:focus {
color: #444;
background-color: transparent;
}
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-link {
color: #9d9d9d;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-link:hover {
color: #fff;
}
.navbar-inverse .btn-link {
color: #9d9d9d;
```

```

}
.navbar-inverse .btn-link:hover,
.navbar-inverse .btn-link:focus {
  color: #fff;
}
.navbar-inverse .btn-link[disabled]:hover,
fieldset[disabled] .navbar-inverse .btn-link:hover,
.navbar-inverse .btn-link[disabled]:focus,
fieldset[disabled] .navbar-inverse .btn-link:focus {
  color: #444;
}
.breadcrumb {
  padding: 8px 15px;
  margin-bottom: 20px;
  list-style: none;
  background-color: #f5f5f5;
  border-radius: 4px;
}
.breadcrumb > li {
  display: inline-block;
}
.breadcrumb > li + li:before {
  padding: 0 5px;
  color: #ccc;
  content: "\00a0";
}
.breadcrumb > .active {
  color: #777;
}
.pagination {
  display: inline-block;
  padding-left: 0;
  margin: 20px 0;
  border-radius: 4px;
}
.pagination > li {
  display: inline;
}
.pagination > li > a,
.pagination > li > span {
  position: relative;
  float: left;
  padding: 6px 12px;
  margin-left: -1px;
  line-height: 1.42857143;
  color: #337ab7;
  text-decoration: none;
  background-color: #fff;
  border: 1px solid #ddd;
}
.pagination > li:first-child > a,

```

```
.pagination > li:first-child > span {
  margin-left: 0;
  border-top-left-radius: 4px;
  border-bottom-left-radius: 4px;
}
.pagination > li:last-child > a,
.pagination > li:last-child > span {
  border-top-right-radius: 4px;
  border-bottom-right-radius: 4px;
}
.pagination > li > a:hover,
.pagination > li > span:hover,
.pagination > li > a:focus,
.pagination > li > span:focus {
  z-index: 2;
  color: #23527c;
  background-color: #eee;
  border-color: #ddd;
}
.pagination > .active > a,
.pagination > .active > span,
.pagination > .active > a:hover,
.pagination > .active > span:hover,
.pagination > .active > a:focus,
.pagination > .active > span:focus {
  z-index: 3;
  color: #fff;
  cursor: default;
  background-color: #337ab7;
  border-color: #337ab7;
}
.pagination > .disabled > span,
.pagination > .disabled > span:hover,
.pagination > .disabled > span:focus,
.pagination > .disabled > a,
.pagination > .disabled > a:hover,
.pagination > .disabled > a:focus {
  color: #777;
  cursor: not-allowed;
  background-color: #fff;
  border-color: #ddd;
}
.pagination-lg > li > a,
.pagination-lg > li > span {
  padding: 10px 16px;
  font-size: 18px;
  line-height: 1.3333333;
}
.pagination-lg > li:first-child > a,
.pagination-lg > li:first-child > span {
  border-top-left-radius: 6px;
}
```

```
border-bottom-left-radius: 6px;
}
.pagination-lg > li:last-child > a,
.pagination-lg > li:last-child > span {
border-top-right-radius: 6px;
border-bottom-right-radius: 6px;
}
.pagination-sm > li > a,
.pagination-sm > li > span {
padding: 5px 10px;
font-size: 12px;
line-height: 1.5;
}
.pagination-sm > li:first-child > a,
.pagination-sm > li:first-child > span {
border-top-left-radius: 3px;
border-bottom-left-radius: 3px;
}
.pagination-sm > li:last-child > a,
.pagination-sm > li:last-child > span {
border-top-right-radius: 3px;
border-bottom-right-radius: 3px;
}
.pager {
padding-left: 0;
margin: 20px 0;
text-align: center;
list-style: none;
}
.pager li {
display: inline;
}
.pager li > a,
.pager li > span {
display: inline-block;
padding: 5px 14px;
background-color: #fff;
border: 1px solid #ddd;
border-radius: 15px;
}
.pager li > a:hover,
.pager li > a:focus {
text-decoration: none;
background-color: #eee;
}
.pager .next > a,
.pager .next > span {
float: right;
}
.pager .previous > a,
.pager .previous > span {
```

```
float: left;
}
.pager .disabled > a,
.pager .disabled > a:hover,
.pager .disabled > a:focus,
.pager .disabled > span {
  color: #777;
  cursor: not-allowed;
  background-color: #fff;
}
.label {
  display: inline;
  padding: .2em .6em .3em;
  font-size: 75%;
  font-weight: bold;
  line-height: 1;
  color: #fff;
  text-align: center;
  white-space: nowrap;
  vertical-align: baseline;
  border-radius: .25em;
}
a.label:hover,
a.label:focus {
  color: #fff;
  text-decoration: none;
  cursor: pointer;
}
.label.empty {
  display: none;
}
.btn .label {
  position: relative;
  top: -1px;
}
.label-default {
  background-color: #777;
}
.label-default[href]:hover,
.label-default[href]:focus {
  background-color: #5e5e5e;
}
.label-primary {
  background-color: #337ab7;
}
.label-primary[href]:hover,
.label-primary[href]:focus {
  background-color: #286090;
}
.label-success {
  background-color: #5cb85c;
```

```
}
.label-success[href]:hover,
.label-success[href]:focus {
  background-color: #449d44;
}
.label-info {
  background-color: #5bc0de;
}
.label-info[href]:hover,
.label-info[href]:focus {
  background-color: #31b0d5;
}
.label-warning {
  background-color: #f0ad4e;
}
.label-warning[href]:hover,
.label-warning[href]:focus {
  background-color: #ec971f;
}
.label-danger {
  background-color: #d9534f;
}
.label-danger[href]:hover,
.label-danger[href]:focus {
  background-color: #c9302c;
}
.badge {
  display: inline-block;
  min-width: 10px;
  padding: 3px 7px;
  font-size: 12px;
  font-weight: bold;
  line-height: 1;
  color: #fff;
  text-align: center;
  white-space: nowrap;
  vertical-align: middle;
  background-color: #777;
  border-radius: 10px;
}
.badge:empty {
  display: none;
}
.btn .badge {
  position: relative;
  top: -1px;
}
.btn-xs .badge,
.btn-group-xs > .btn .badge {
  top: 0;
  padding: 1px 5px;
}
```

```
}
a.badge:hover,
a.badge:focus {
  color: #fff;
  text-decoration: none;
  cursor: pointer;
}
.list-group-item.active > .badge,
.nav-pills > .active > a > .badge {
  color: #337ab7;
  background-color: #fff;
}
.list-group-item > .badge {
  float: right;
}
.list-group-item > .badge + .badge {
  margin-right: 5px;
}
.nav-pills > li > a > .badge {
  margin-left: 3px;
}
.jumbotron {
  padding-top: 30px;
  padding-bottom: 30px;
  margin-bottom: 30px;
  color: inherit;
  background-color: #eee;
}
.jumbotron h1,
.jumbotron .h1 {
  color: inherit;
}
.jumbotron p {
  margin-bottom: 15px;
  font-size: 21px;
  font-weight: 200;
}
.jumbotron > hr {
  border-top-color: #d5d5d5;
}
.container .jumbotron,
.container-fluid .jumbotron {
  padding-right: 15px;
  padding-left: 15px;
  border-radius: 6px;
}
.jumbotron .container {
  max-width: 100%;
}
@media screen and (min-width: 768px) {
  .jumbotron {
```

```
padding-top: 48px;
padding-bottom: 48px;
}
.container .jumbotron,
.container-fluid .jumbotron {
padding-right: 60px;
padding-left: 60px;
}
.jumbotron h1,
.jumbotron .h1 {
font-size: 63px;
}
}
.thumbnail {
display: block;
padding: 4px;
margin-bottom: 20px;
line-height: 1.42857143;
background-color: #fff;
border: 1px solid #ddd;
border-radius: 4px;
-webkit-transition: border .2s ease-in-out;
-o-transition: border .2s ease-in-out;
transition: border .2s ease-in-out;
}
.thumbnail > img,
.thumbnail a > img {
margin-right: auto;
margin-left: auto;
}
a.thumbnail:hover,
a.thumbnail:focus,
a.thumbnail.active {
border-color: #337ab7;
}
.thumbnail .caption {
padding: 9px;
color: #333;
}
}
.alert {
padding: 15px;
margin-bottom: 20px;
border: 1px solid transparent;
border-radius: 4px;
}
.alert h4 {
margin-top: 0;
color: inherit;
}
}
.alert .alert-link {
font-weight: bold;
```

```
}
.alert > p,
.alert > ul {
  margin-bottom: 0;
}
.alert > p + p {
  margin-top: 5px;
}
.alert-dismissable,
.alert-dismissible {
  padding-right: 35px;
}
.alert-dismissable .close,
.alert-dismissible .close {
  position: relative;
  top: -2px;
  right: -21px;
  color: inherit;
}
.alert-success {
  color: #3c763d;
  background-color: #dff0d8;
  border-color: #d6e9c6;
}
.alert-success hr {
  border-top-color: #c9e2b3;
}
.alert-success .alert-link {
  color: #2b542c;
}
.alert-info {
  color: #31708f;
  background-color: #d9edf7;
  border-color: #bce8f1;
}
.alert-info hr {
  border-top-color: #a6e1ec;
}
.alert-info .alert-link {
  color: #245269;
}
.alert-warning {
  color: #8a6d3b;
  background-color: #fcf8e3;
  border-color: #faebcc;
}
.alert-warning hr {
  border-top-color: #f7e1b5;
}
.alert-warning .alert-link {
  color: #66512c;
```

```
}
.alert-danger {
  color: #a94442;
  background-color: #f2dede;
  border-color: #ebccd1;
}
.alert-danger hr {
  border-top-color: #e4b9c0;
}
.alert-danger .alert-link {
  color: #843534;
}
@-webkit-keyframes progress-bar-stripes {
  from {
    background-position: 40px 0;
  }
  to {
    background-position: 0 0;
  }
}
@-o-keyframes progress-bar-stripes {
  from {
    background-position: 40px 0;
  }
  to {
    background-position: 0 0;
  }
}
@keyframes progress-bar-stripes {
  from {
    background-position: 40px 0;
  }
  to {
    background-position: 0 0;
  }
}
.progress {
  height: 20px;
  margin-bottom: 20px;
  overflow: hidden;
  background-color: #f5f5f5;
  border-radius: 4px;
  -webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 2px rgba(0, 0, 0, .1);
  box-shadow: inset 0 1px 2px rgba(0, 0, 0, .1);
}
.progress-bar {
  float: left;
  width: 0;
  height: 100%;
  font-size: 12px;
  line-height: 20px;
```

```

color: #fff;
text-align: center;
background-color: #337ab7;
-webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 -1px 0 rgba(0, 0, 0, .15);
    box-shadow: inset 0 -1px 0 rgba(0, 0, 0, .15);
-webkit-transition: width .6s ease;
    -o-transition: width .6s ease;
    transition: width .6s ease;
}
.progress-striped .progress-bar,
.progress-bar-striped {
    background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
    background-image: -o-linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
    background-image: linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
    -webkit-background-size: 40px 40px;
        background-size: 40px 40px;
}
.progress.active .progress-bar,
.progress-bar.active {
    -webkit-animation: progress-bar-stripes 2s linear infinite;
    -o-animation: progress-bar-stripes 2s linear infinite;
    animation: progress-bar-stripes 2s linear infinite;
}
.progress-bar-success {
    background-color: #5cb85c;
}
.progress-striped .progress-bar-success {
    background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
    background-image: -o-linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
    background-image: linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
}
.progress-bar-info {
    background-color: #5bc0de;
}
.progress-striped .progress-bar-info {
    background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
}

```

```

background-image: -o-linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
background-image: linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
}
.progress-bar-warning {
background-color: #f0ad4e;
}
.progress-striped .progress-bar-warning {
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
background-image: -o-linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
background-image: linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
}
.progress-bar-danger {
background-color: #d9534f;
}
.progress-striped .progress-bar-danger {
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
background-image: -o-linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
background-image: linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
}
.media {
margin-top: 15px;
}
.media:first-child {
margin-top: 0;
}
.media,
.media-body {
overflow: hidden;
zoom: 1;
}
.media-body {
width: 10000px;
}
}
.media-object {
display: block;

```

```
}  
.media-object.img-thumbnail {  
  max-width: none;  
}  
.media-right,  
.media > .pull-right {  
  padding-left: 10px;  
}  
.media-left,  
.media > .pull-left {  
  padding-right: 10px;  
}  
.media-left,  
.media-right,  
.media-body {  
  display: table-cell;  
  vertical-align: top;  
}  
.media-middle {  
  vertical-align: middle;  
}  
.media-bottom {  
  vertical-align: bottom;  
}  
.media-heading {  
  margin-top: 0;  
  margin-bottom: 5px;  
}  
.media-list {  
  padding-left: 0;  
  list-style: none;  
}  
.list-group {  
  padding-left: 0;  
  margin-bottom: 20px;  
}  
.list-group-item {  
  position: relative;  
  display: block;  
  padding: 10px 15px;  
  margin-bottom: -1px;  
  background-color: #fff;  
  border: 1px solid #ddd;  
}  
.list-group-item:first-child {  
  border-top-left-radius: 4px;  
  border-top-right-radius: 4px;  
}  
.list-group-item:last-child {  
  margin-bottom: 0;  
  border-bottom-right-radius: 4px;  
}
```

```
border-bottom-left-radius: 4px;
}
a.list-group-item,
button.list-group-item {
  color: #555;
}
a.list-group-item .list-group-item-heading,
button.list-group-item .list-group-item-heading {
  color: #333;
}
a.list-group-item:hover,
button.list-group-item:hover,
a.list-group-item:focus,
button.list-group-item:focus {
  color: #555;
  text-decoration: none;
  background-color: #f5f5f5;
}
button.list-group-item {
  width: 100%;
  text-align: left;
}
.list-group-item.disabled,
.list-group-item.disabled:hover,
.list-group-item.disabled:focus {
  color: #777;
  cursor: not-allowed;
  background-color: #eee;
}
.list-group-item.disabled .list-group-item-heading,
.list-group-item.disabled:hover .list-group-item-heading,
.list-group-item.disabled:focus .list-group-item-heading {
  color: inherit;
}
.list-group-item.disabled .list-group-item-text,
.list-group-item.disabled:hover .list-group-item-text,
.list-group-item.disabled:focus .list-group-item-text {
  color: #777;
}
.list-group-item.active,
.list-group-item.active:hover,
.list-group-item.active:focus {
  z-index: 2;
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #337ab7;
  border-color: #337ab7;
}
.list-group-item.active .list-group-item-heading,
.list-group-item.active:hover .list-group-item-heading,
.list-group-item.active:focus .list-group-item-heading,
.list-group-item.active .list-group-item-heading > small,
```

```
.list-group-item.active:hover .list-group-item-heading > small,  
.list-group-item.active:focus .list-group-item-heading > small,  
.list-group-item.active .list-group-item-heading > .small,  
.list-group-item.active:hover .list-group-item-heading > .small,  
.list-group-item.active:focus .list-group-item-heading > .small {  
  color: inherit;  
}  
.list-group-item.active .list-group-item-text,  
.list-group-item.active:hover .list-group-item-text,  
.list-group-item.active:focus .list-group-item-text {  
  color: #c7ddef;  
}  
.list-group-item-success {  
  color: #3c763d;  
  background-color: #dff0d8;  
}  
a.list-group-item-success,  
button.list-group-item-success {  
  color: #3c763d;  
}  
a.list-group-item-success .list-group-item-heading,  
button.list-group-item-success .list-group-item-heading {  
  color: inherit;  
}  
a.list-group-item-success:hover,  
button.list-group-item-success:hover,  
a.list-group-item-success:focus,  
button.list-group-item-success:focus {  
  color: #3c763d;  
  background-color: #d0e9c6;  
}  
a.list-group-item-success.active,  
button.list-group-item-success.active,  
a.list-group-item-success.active:hover,  
button.list-group-item-success.active:hover,  
a.list-group-item-success.active:focus,  
button.list-group-item-success.active:focus {  
  color: #fff;  
  background-color: #3c763d;  
  border-color: #3c763d;  
}  
.list-group-item-info {  
  color: #31708f;  
  background-color: #d9edf7;  
}  
a.list-group-item-info,  
button.list-group-item-info {  
  color: #31708f;  
}  
a.list-group-item-info .list-group-item-heading,  
button.list-group-item-info .list-group-item-heading {
```

```
    color: inherit;
}
a.list-group-item-info:hover,
button.list-group-item-info:hover,
a.list-group-item-info:focus,
button.list-group-item-info:focus {
    color: #31708f;
    background-color: #c4e3f3;
}
a.list-group-item-info.active,
button.list-group-item-info.active,
a.list-group-item-info.active:hover,
button.list-group-item-info.active:hover,
a.list-group-item-info.active:focus,
button.list-group-item-info.active:focus {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #31708f;
    border-color: #31708f;
}
.list-group-item-warning {
    color: #8a6d3b;
    background-color: #fcf8e3;
}
a.list-group-item-warning,
button.list-group-item-warning {
    color: #8a6d3b;
}
a.list-group-item-warning .list-group-item-heading,
button.list-group-item-warning .list-group-item-heading {
    color: inherit;
}
a.list-group-item-warning:hover,
button.list-group-item-warning:hover,
a.list-group-item-warning:focus,
button.list-group-item-warning:focus {
    color: #8a6d3b;
    background-color: #faf2cc;
}
a.list-group-item-warning.active,
button.list-group-item-warning.active,
a.list-group-item-warning.active:hover,
button.list-group-item-warning.active:hover,
a.list-group-item-warning.active:focus,
button.list-group-item-warning.active:focus {
    color: #fff;
    background-color: #8a6d3b;
    border-color: #8a6d3b;
}
.list-group-item-danger {
    color: #a94442;
    background-color: #f2dede;
```

```
}
a.list-group-item-danger,
button.list-group-item-danger {
  color: #a94442;
}
a.list-group-item-danger .list-group-item-heading,
button.list-group-item-danger .list-group-item-heading {
  color: inherit;
}
a.list-group-item-danger:hover,
button.list-group-item-danger:hover,
a.list-group-item-danger:focus,
button.list-group-item-danger:focus {
  color: #a94442;
  background-color: #ebcccc;
}
a.list-group-item-danger.active,
button.list-group-item-danger.active,
a.list-group-item-danger.active:hover,
button.list-group-item-danger.active:hover,
a.list-group-item-danger.active:focus,
button.list-group-item-danger.active:focus {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #a94442;
  border-color: #a94442;
}
.list-group-item-heading {
  margin-top: 0;
  margin-bottom: 5px;
}
.list-group-item-text {
  margin-bottom: 0;
  line-height: 1.3;
}
.panel {
  margin-bottom: 20px;
  background-color: #fff;
  border: 1px solid transparent;
  border-radius: 4px;
  -webkit-box-shadow: 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .05);
  box-shadow: 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .05);
}
.panel-body {
  padding: 15px;
}
.panel-heading {
  padding: 10px 15px;
  border-bottom: 1px solid transparent;
  border-top-left-radius: 3px;
  border-top-right-radius: 3px;
}
```

```
.panel-heading > .dropdown .dropdown-toggle {
  color: inherit;
}
.panel-title {
  margin-top: 0;
  margin-bottom: 0;
  font-size: 16px;
  color: inherit;
}
.panel-title > a,
.panel-title > small,
.panel-title > .small,
.panel-title > small > a,
.panel-title > .small > a {
  color: inherit;
}
.panel-footer {
  padding: 10px 15px;
  background-color: #f5f5f5;
  border-top: 1px solid #ddd;
  border-bottom-right-radius: 3px;
  border-bottom-left-radius: 3px;
}
.panel > .list-group,
.panel > .panel-collapse > .list-group {
  margin-bottom: 0;
}
.panel > .list-group .list-group-item,
.panel > .panel-collapse > .list-group .list-group-item {
  border-width: 1px 0;
  border-radius: 0;
}
.panel > .list-group:first-child .list-group-item:first-child,
.panel > .panel-collapse > .list-group:first-child .list-group-item:first-child {
  border-top: 0;
  border-top-left-radius: 3px;
  border-top-right-radius: 3px;
}
.panel > .list-group:last-child .list-group-item:last-child,
.panel > .panel-collapse > .list-group:last-child .list-group-item:last-child {
  border-bottom: 0;
  border-bottom-right-radius: 3px;
  border-bottom-left-radius: 3px;
}
.panel > .panel-heading + .panel-collapse > .list-group .list-group-item:first-child {
  border-top-left-radius: 0;
  border-top-right-radius: 0;
}
.panel-heading + .list-group .list-group-item:first-child {
  border-top-width: 0;
}
}
```

```

.list-group + .panel-footer {
  border-top-width: 0;
}
.panel > .table,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table,
.panel > .panel-collapse > .table {
  margin-bottom: 0;
}
.panel > .table caption,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table caption,
.panel > .panel-collapse > .table caption {
  padding-right: 15px;
  padding-left: 15px;
}
.panel > .table:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:first-child > .table:first-child {
  border-top-left-radius: 3px;
  border-top-right-radius: 3px;
}
.panel > .table:first-child > thead:first-child > tr:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:first-child > .table:first-child > thead:first-child > tr:first-child,
.panel > .table:first-child > tbody:first-child > tr:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:first-child > .table:first-child > tbody:first-child > tr:first-child {
  border-top-left-radius: 3px;
  border-top-right-radius: 3px;
}
.panel > .table:first-child > thead:first-child > tr:first-child td:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:first-child > .table:first-child > thead:first-child > tr:first-child td:first-child,
.panel > .table:first-child > tbody:first-child > tr:first-child td:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:first-child > .table:first-child > tbody:first-child > tr:first-child td:first-child,
.panel > .table:first-child > thead:first-child > tr:first-child th:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:first-child > .table:first-child > thead:first-child > tr:first-child th:first-child,
.panel > .table:first-child > tbody:first-child > tr:first-child th:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:first-child > .table:first-child > tbody:first-child > tr:first-child th:first-child {
  border-top-left-radius: 3px;
}
.panel > .table:first-child > thead:first-child > tr:first-child td:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:first-child > .table:first-child > thead:first-child > tr:first-child td:last-child,
.panel > .table:first-child > tbody:first-child > tr:first-child td:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:first-child > .table:first-child > tbody:first-child > tr:first-child td:last-child,
.panel > .table:first-child > thead:first-child > tr:first-child th:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:first-child > .table:first-child > thead:first-child > tr:first-child th:last-child,
.panel > .table:first-child > tbody:first-child > tr:first-child th:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:first-child > .table:first-child > tbody:first-child > tr:first-child th:last-child {
  border-top-right-radius: 3px;
}
.panel > .table:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:last-child > .table:last-child {
  border-bottom-right-radius: 3px;
  border-bottom-left-radius: 3px;
}

```

```

.panel > .table:last-child > tbody:last-child > tr:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:last-child > .table:last-child > tbody:last-child > tr:last-child,
.panel > .table:last-child > tfoot:last-child > tr:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:last-child > .table:last-child > tfoot:last-child > tr:last-child {
  border-bottom-right-radius: 3px;
  border-bottom-left-radius: 3px;
}
.panel > .table:last-child > tbody:last-child > tr:last-child td:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:last-child > .table:last-child > tbody:last-child > tr:last-child td:first-child,
.panel > .table:last-child > tfoot:last-child > tr:last-child td:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:last-child > .table:last-child > tfoot:last-child > tr:last-child td:first-child,
.panel > .table:last-child > tbody:last-child > tr:last-child th:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:last-child > .table:last-child > tbody:last-child > tr:last-child th:first-child,
.panel > .table:last-child > tfoot:last-child > tr:last-child th:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:last-child > .table:last-child > tfoot:last-child > tr:last-child th:first-child {
  border-bottom-left-radius: 3px;
}
.panel > .table:last-child > tbody:last-child > tr:last-child td:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:last-child > .table:last-child > tbody:last-child > tr:last-child td:last-child,
.panel > .table:last-child > tfoot:last-child > tr:last-child td:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:last-child > .table:last-child > tfoot:last-child > tr:last-child td:last-child,
.panel > .table:last-child > tbody:last-child > tr:last-child th:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:last-child > .table:last-child > tbody:last-child > tr:last-child th:last-child,
.panel > .table:last-child > tfoot:last-child > tr:last-child th:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive:last-child > .table:last-child > tfoot:last-child > tr:last-child th:last-child {
  border-bottom-right-radius: 3px;
}
.panel > .panel-body + .table,
.panel > .panel-body + .table-responsive,
.panel > .table + .panel-body,
.panel > .table-responsive + .panel-body {
  border-top: 1px solid #ddd;
}
.panel > .table > tbody:first-child > tr:first-child th,
.panel > .table > tbody:first-child > tr:first-child td {
  border-top: 0;
}
.panel > .table-bordered,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered {
  border: 0;
}
.panel > .table-bordered > thead > tr > th:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > thead > tr > th:first-child,
.panel > .table-bordered > tbody > tr > th:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tbody > tr > th:first-child,
.panel > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr > th:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr > th:first-child,
.panel > .table-bordered > thead > tr > td:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > thead > tr > td:first-child,
.panel > .table-bordered > tbody > tr > td:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tbody > tr > td:first-child,

```

```

.panel > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr > td:first-child,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr > td:first-child {
  border-left: 0;
}
.panel > .table-bordered > thead > tr > th:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > thead > tr > th:last-child,
.panel > .table-bordered > tbody > tr > th:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tbody > tr > th:last-child,
.panel > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr > th:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr > th:last-child,
.panel > .table-bordered > thead > tr > td:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > thead > tr > td:last-child,
.panel > .table-bordered > tbody > tr > td:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tbody > tr > td:last-child,
.panel > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr > td:last-child,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr > td:last-child {
  border-right: 0;
}
.panel > .table-bordered > thead > tr:first-child > td,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > thead > tr:first-child > td,
.panel > .table-bordered > tbody > tr:first-child > td,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tbody > tr:first-child > td,
.panel > .table-bordered > thead > tr:first-child > th,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > thead > tr:first-child > th,
.panel > .table-bordered > tbody > tr:first-child > th,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tbody > tr:first-child > th {
  border-bottom: 0;
}
.panel > .table-bordered > tbody > tr:last-child > td,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tbody > tr:last-child > td,
.panel > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr:last-child > td,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr:last-child > td,
.panel > .table-bordered > tbody > tr:last-child > th,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tbody > tr:last-child > th,
.panel > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr:last-child > th,
.panel > .table-responsive > .table-bordered > tfoot > tr:last-child > th {
  border-bottom: 0;
}
.panel > .table-responsive {
  margin-bottom: 0;
  border: 0;
}
.panel-group {
  margin-bottom: 20px;
}
.panel-group .panel {
  margin-bottom: 0;
  border-radius: 4px;
}
.panel-group .panel + .panel {
  margin-top: 5px;
}

```

```
}
.panel-group .panel-heading {
  border-bottom: 0;
}
.panel-group .panel-heading + .panel-collapse > .panel-body,
.panel-group .panel-heading + .panel-collapse > .list-group {
  border-top: 1px solid #ddd;
}
.panel-group .panel-footer {
  border-top: 0;
}
.panel-group .panel-footer + .panel-collapse .panel-body {
  border-bottom: 1px solid #ddd;
}
.panel-default {
  border-color: #ddd;
}
.panel-default > .panel-heading {
  color: #333;
  background-color: #f5f5f5;
  border-color: #ddd;
}
.panel-default > .panel-heading + .panel-collapse > .panel-body {
  border-top-color: #ddd;
}
.panel-default > .panel-heading .badge {
  color: #f5f5f5;
  background-color: #333;
}
.panel-default > .panel-footer + .panel-collapse > .panel-body {
  border-bottom-color: #ddd;
}
.panel-primary {
  border-color: #337ab7;
}
.panel-primary > .panel-heading {
  color: #fff;
  background-color: #337ab7;
  border-color: #337ab7;
}
.panel-primary > .panel-heading + .panel-collapse > .panel-body {
  border-top-color: #337ab7;
}
.panel-primary > .panel-heading .badge {
  color: #337ab7;
  background-color: #fff;
}
.panel-primary > .panel-footer + .panel-collapse > .panel-body {
  border-bottom-color: #337ab7;
}
.panel-success {
```

```
border-color: #d6e9c6;
}
.panel-success > .panel-heading {
color: #3c763d;
background-color: #dff0d8;
border-color: #d6e9c6;
}
.panel-success > .panel-heading + .panel-collapse > .panel-body {
border-top-color: #d6e9c6;
}
.panel-success > .panel-heading .badge {
color: #dff0d8;
background-color: #3c763d;
}
.panel-success > .panel-footer + .panel-collapse > .panel-body {
border-bottom-color: #d6e9c6;
}
.panel-info {
border-color: #eca7a7;
}
.panel-info > .panel-heading {
color: #e86060;
background-color: #fbd3d3;
border-color: #eca7a7;
}
.panel-info > .panel-heading + .panel-collapse > .panel-body {
border-top-color: #bce8f1;
}
.panel-info > .panel-heading .badge {
color: #d9edf7;
background-color: #31708f;
}
.panel-info > .panel-footer + .panel-collapse > .panel-body {
border-bottom-color: #bce8f1;
}
.panel-warning {
border-color: #faebcc;
}
.panel-warning > .panel-heading {
color: #8a6d3b;
background-color: #fcf8e3;
border-color: #faebcc;
}
.panel-warning > .panel-heading + .panel-collapse > .panel-body {
border-top-color: #faebcc;
}
.panel-warning > .panel-heading .badge {
color: #fcf8e3;
background-color: #8a6d3b;
}
.panel-warning > .panel-footer + .panel-collapse > .panel-body {
```

```
border-bottom-color: #faebcc;
}
.panel-danger {
border-color: #ebccd1;
}
.panel-danger > .panel-heading {
color: #a94442;
background-color: #f2dede;
border-color: #ebccd1;
}
.panel-danger > .panel-heading + .panel-collapse > .panel-body {
border-top-color: #ebccd1;
}
.panel-danger > .panel-heading .badge {
color: #f2dede;
background-color: #a94442;
}
.panel-danger > .panel-footer + .panel-collapse > .panel-body {
border-bottom-color: #ebccd1;
}
.embed-responsive {
position: relative;
display: block;
height: 0;
padding: 0;
overflow: hidden;
}
.embed-responsive .embed-responsive-item,
.embed-responsive iframe,
.embed-responsive embed,
.embed-responsive object,
.embed-responsive video {
position: absolute;
top: 0;
bottom: 0;
left: 0;
width: 100%;
height: 100%;
border: 0;
}
.embed-responsive-16by9 {
padding-bottom: 56.25%;
}
.embed-responsive-4by3 {
padding-bottom: 75%;
}
.well {
min-height: 20px;
padding: 19px;
margin-bottom: 20px;
background-color: #f5f5f5;
```

```
border: 1px solid #e3e3e3;
border-radius: 4px;
-webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .05);
    box-shadow: inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .05);
}
.well blockquote {
border-color: #ddd;
border-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .15);
}
.well-lg {
padding: 24px;
border-radius: 6px;
}
.well-sm {
padding: 9px;
border-radius: 3px;
}
.close {
float: right;
font-size: 21px;
font-weight: bold;
line-height: 1;
color: #000;
text-shadow: 0 1px 0 #fff;
filter: alpha(opacity=20);
opacity: .2;
}
.close:hover,
.close:focus {
color: #000;
text-decoration: none;
cursor: pointer;
filter: alpha(opacity=50);
opacity: .5;
}
button.close {
-webkit-appearance: none;
padding: 0;
cursor: pointer;
background: transparent;
border: 0;
}
.modal-open {
overflow: hidden;
}
.modal {
position: fixed;
top: 0;
right: 0;
bottom: 0;
left: 0;
```

```
z-index: 1050;
display: none;
overflow: hidden;
-webkit-overflow-scrolling: touch;
outline: 0;
}
.modal.fade .modal-dialog {
-webkit-transition: -webkit-transform .3s ease-out;
  -o-transition:    -o-transform .3s ease-out;
  transition:      transform .3s ease-out;
-webkit-transform: translate(0, -25%);
-ms-transform: translate(0, -25%);
-o-transform: translate(0, -25%);
  transform: translate(0, -25%);
}
.modal.in .modal-dialog {
-webkit-transform: translate(0, 0);
-ms-transform: translate(0, 0);
-o-transform: translate(0, 0);
  transform: translate(0, 0);
}
.modal-open .modal {
overflow-x: hidden;
overflow-y: auto;
}
.modal-dialog {
position: relative;
width: auto;
margin: 10px;
}
.modal-content {
position: relative;
background-color: #fff;
-webkit-background-clip: padding-box;
  background-clip: padding-box;
border: 1px solid #999;
border: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .2);
border-radius: 6px;
outline: 0;
-webkit-box-shadow: 0 3px 9px rgba(0, 0, 0, .5);
  box-shadow: 0 3px 9px rgba(0, 0, 0, .5);
}
.modal-backdrop {
position: fixed;
top: 0;
right: 0;
bottom: 0;
left: 0;
z-index: 1040;
background-color: #000;
}
```

```
.modal-backdrop.fade {
  filter: alpha(opacity=0);
  opacity: 0;
}
.modal-backdrop.in {
  filter: alpha(opacity=50);
  opacity: .5;
}
.modal-header {
  padding: 15px;
  border-bottom: 1px solid #e5e5e5;
}
.modal-header .close {
  margin-top: -2px;
}
.modal-title {
  margin: 0;
  line-height: 1.42857143;
}
.modal-body {
  position: relative;
  padding: 15px;
}
.modal-footer {
  padding: 15px;
  text-align: right;
  border-top: 1px solid #e5e5e5;
}
.modal-footer .btn + .btn {
  margin-bottom: 0;
  margin-left: 5px;
}
.modal-footer .btn-group .btn + .btn {
  margin-left: -1px;
}
.modal-footer .btn-block + .btn-block {
  margin-left: 0;
}
.modal-scrollbar-measure {
  position: absolute;
  top: -9999px;
  width: 50px;
  height: 50px;
  overflow: scroll;
}
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .modal-dialog {
    width: 600px;
    margin: 30px auto;
  }
  .modal-content {
```

```
-webkit-box-shadow: 0 5px 15px rgba(0, 0, 0, .5);
  box-shadow: 0 5px 15px rgba(0, 0, 0, .5);
}
.modal-sm {
  width: 300px;
}
}
@media (min-width: 992px) {
  .modal-lg {
    width: 900px;
  }
}
.tooltip {
  position: absolute;
  z-index: 1070;
  display: block;
  font-family: "Helvetica Neue", Helvetica, Arial, sans-serif;
  font-size: 12px;
  font-style: normal;
  font-weight: normal;
  line-height: 1.42857143;
  text-align: left;
  text-align: start;
  text-decoration: none;
  text-shadow: none;
  text-transform: none;
  letter-spacing: normal;
  word-break: normal;
  word-spacing: normal;
  word-wrap: normal;
  white-space: normal;
  filter: alpha(opacity=0);
  opacity: 0;

  line-break: auto;
}
.tooltip.in {
  filter: alpha(opacity=90);
  opacity: .9;
}
.tooltip.top {
  padding: 5px 0;
  margin-top: -3px;
}
.tooltip.right {
  padding: 0 5px;
  margin-left: 3px;
}
.tooltip.bottom {
  padding: 5px 0;
  margin-top: 3px;
```

```
}  
.tooltip.left {  
  padding: 0 5px;  
  margin-left: -3px;  
}  
.tooltip-inner {  
  max-width: 200px;  
  padding: 3px 8px;  
  color: #fff;  
  text-align: center;  
  background-color: #000;  
  border-radius: 4px;  
}  
.tooltip-arrow {  
  position: absolute;  
  width: 0;  
  height: 0;  
  border-color: transparent;  
  border-style: solid;  
}  
.tooltip.top .tooltip-arrow {  
  bottom: 0;  
  left: 50%;  
  margin-left: -5px;  
  border-width: 5px 5px 0;  
  border-top-color: #000;  
}  
.tooltip.top-left .tooltip-arrow {  
  right: 5px;  
  bottom: 0;  
  margin-bottom: -5px;  
  border-width: 5px 5px 0;  
  border-top-color: #000;  
}  
.tooltip.top-right .tooltip-arrow {  
  bottom: 0;  
  left: 5px;  
  margin-bottom: -5px;  
  border-width: 5px 5px 0;  
  border-top-color: #000;  
}  
.tooltip.right .tooltip-arrow {  
  top: 50%;  
  left: 0;  
  margin-top: -5px;  
  border-width: 5px 5px 5px 0;  
  border-right-color: #000;  
}  
.tooltip.left .tooltip-arrow {  
  top: 50%;  
  right: 0;
```

```
margin-top: -5px;
border-width: 5px 0 5px 5px;
border-left-color: #000;
}
.tooltip.bottom .tooltip-arrow {
top: 0;
left: 50%;
margin-left: -5px;
border-width: 0 5px 5px;
border-bottom-color: #000;
}
.tooltip.bottom-left .tooltip-arrow {
top: 0;
right: 5px;
margin-top: -5px;
border-width: 0 5px 5px;
border-bottom-color: #000;
}
.tooltip.bottom-right .tooltip-arrow {
top: 0;
left: 5px;
margin-top: -5px;
border-width: 0 5px 5px;
border-bottom-color: #000;
}
.popover {
position: absolute;
top: 0;
left: 0;
z-index: 1060;
display: none;
max-width: 276px;
padding: 1px;
font-family: "Helvetica Neue", Helvetica, Arial, sans-serif;
font-size: 14px;
font-style: normal;
font-weight: normal;
line-height: 1.42857143;
text-align: left;
text-align: start;
text-decoration: none;
text-shadow: none;
text-transform: none;
letter-spacing: normal;
word-break: normal;
word-spacing: normal;
word-wrap: normal;
white-space: normal;
background-color: #fff;
-webkit-background-clip: padding-box;
background-clip: padding-box;
```

```
border: 1px solid #ccc;
border: 1px solid rgba(0, 0, 0, .2);
border-radius: 6px;
-webkit-box-shadow: 0 5px 10px rgba(0, 0, 0, .2);
    box-shadow: 0 5px 10px rgba(0, 0, 0, .2);
```

```
    line-break: auto;
}
.popover.top {
    margin-top: -10px;
}
.popover.right {
    margin-left: 10px;
}
.popover.bottom {
    margin-top: 10px;
}
.popover.left {
    margin-left: -10px;
}
.popover-title {
    padding: 8px 14px;
    margin: 0;
    font-size: 14px;
    background-color: #f7f7f7;
    border-bottom: 1px solid #ebebeb;
    border-radius: 5px 5px 0 0;
}
.popover-content {
    padding: 9px 14px;
}
.popover > .arrow,
.popover > .arrow:after {
    position: absolute;
    display: block;
    width: 0;
    height: 0;
    border-color: transparent;
    border-style: solid;
}
.popover > .arrow {
    border-width: 11px;
}
.popover > .arrow:after {
    content: "";
    border-width: 10px;
}
.popover.top > .arrow {
    bottom: -11px;
    left: 50%;
    margin-left: -11px;
```

```
border-top-color: #999;
border-top-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .25);
border-bottom-width: 0;
}
.popover.top > .arrow:after {
  bottom: 1px;
  margin-left: -10px;
  content: " ";
  border-top-color: #fff;
  border-bottom-width: 0;
}
.popover.right > .arrow {
  top: 50%;
  left: -11px;
  margin-top: -11px;
  border-right-color: #999;
  border-right-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .25);
  border-left-width: 0;
}
.popover.right > .arrow:after {
  bottom: -10px;
  left: 1px;
  content: " ";
  border-right-color: #fff;
  border-left-width: 0;
}
.popover.bottom > .arrow {
  top: -11px;
  left: 50%;
  margin-left: -11px;
  border-top-width: 0;
  border-bottom-color: #999;
  border-bottom-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .25);
}
.popover.bottom > .arrow:after {
  top: 1px;
  margin-left: -10px;
  content: " ";
  border-top-width: 0;
  border-bottom-color: #fff;
}
.popover.left > .arrow {
  top: 50%;
  right: -11px;
  margin-top: -11px;
  border-right-width: 0;
  border-left-color: #999;
  border-left-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, .25);
}
.popover.left > .arrow:after {
  right: 1px;
```

```

bottom: -10px;
content: " ";
border-right-width: 0;
border-left-color: #fff;
}
.carousel {
position: relative;
}
.carousel-inner {
position: relative;
width: 100%;
overflow: hidden;
}
.carousel-inner > .item {
position: relative;
display: none;
-webkit-transition: .6s ease-in-out left;
-o-transition: .6s ease-in-out left;
transition: .6s ease-in-out left;
}
.carousel-inner > .item > img,
.carousel-inner > .item > a > img {
line-height: 1;
}
@media all and (transform-3d), (-webkit-transform-3d) {
.carousel-inner > .item {
-webkit-transition: -webkit-transform .6s ease-in-out;
-o-transition: -o-transform .6s ease-in-out;
transition: transform .6s ease-in-out;

-webkit-backface-visibility: hidden;
backface-visibility: hidden;
-webkit-perspective: 1000px;
perspective: 1000px;
}
.carousel-inner > .item.next,
.carousel-inner > .item.active.right {
left: 0;
-webkit-transform: translate3d(100%, 0, 0);
transform: translate3d(100%, 0, 0);
}
.carousel-inner > .item.prev,
.carousel-inner > .item.active.left {
left: 0;
-webkit-transform: translate3d(-100%, 0, 0);
transform: translate3d(-100%, 0, 0);
}
.carousel-inner > .item.next.left,
.carousel-inner > .item.prev.right,
.carousel-inner > .item.active {
left: 0;
}

```

```

    -webkit-transform: translate3d(0, 0, 0);
    transform: translate3d(0, 0, 0);
  }
}
.carousel-inner > .active,
.carousel-inner > .next,
.carousel-inner > .prev {
  display: block;
}
.carousel-inner > .active {
  left: 0;
}
.carousel-inner > .next,
.carousel-inner > .prev {
  position: absolute;
  top: 0;
  width: 100%;
}
.carousel-inner > .next {
  left: 100%;
}
.carousel-inner > .prev {
  left: -100%;
}
.carousel-inner > .next.left,
.carousel-inner > .prev.right {
  left: 0;
}
.carousel-inner > .active.left {
  left: -100%;
}
.carousel-inner > .active.right {
  left: 100%;
}
.carousel-control {
  position: absolute;
  top: 0;
  bottom: 0;
  left: 0;
  width: 15%;
  font-size: 20px;
  color: #fff;
  text-align: center;
  text-shadow: 0 1px 2px rgba(0, 0, 0, .6);
  background-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, 0);
  filter: alpha(opacity=50);
  opacity: .5;
}
.carousel-control.left {
  background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(left, rgba(0, 0, 0, .5) 0%, rgba(0, 0, 0, .0001) 100%);
  background-image: -o-linear-gradient(left, rgba(0, 0, 0, .5) 0%, rgba(0, 0, 0, .0001) 100%);
}

```

```

background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, right top, from(rgba(0, 0, 0, .5)), to(rgba(0, 0, 0, .0001)));
background-image: linear-gradient(to right, rgba(0, 0, 0, .5) 0%, rgba(0, 0, 0, .0001) 100%);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#80000000', endColorstr='#00000000', GradientType=1);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
.carousel-control.right {
right: 0;
left: auto;
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(left, rgba(0, 0, 0, .0001) 0%, rgba(0, 0, 0, .5) 100%);
background-image: -o-linear-gradient(left, rgba(0, 0, 0, .0001) 0%, rgba(0, 0, 0, .5) 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, right top, from(rgba(0, 0, 0, .0001)), to(rgba(0, 0, 0, .5)));
background-image: linear-gradient(to right, rgba(0, 0, 0, .0001) 0%, rgba(0, 0, 0, .5) 100%);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#00000000', endColorstr='#80000000', GradientType=1);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
.carousel-control:hover,
.carousel-control:focus {
color: #fff;
text-decoration: none;
filter: alpha(opacity=90);
outline: 0;
opacity: .9;
}
.carousel-control .icon-prev,
.carousel-control .icon-next,
.carousel-control .glyphicon-chevron-left,
.carousel-control .glyphicon-chevron-right {
position: absolute;
top: 50%;
z-index: 5;
display: inline-block;
margin-top: -10px;
}
.carousel-control .icon-prev,
.carousel-control .glyphicon-chevron-left {
left: 50%;
margin-left: -10px;
}
.carousel-control .icon-next,
.carousel-control .glyphicon-chevron-right {
right: 50%;
margin-right: -10px;
}
.carousel-control .icon-prev,
.carousel-control .icon-next {
width: 20px;
height: 20px;
}

```

```
font-family: serif;
line-height: 1;
}
.carousel-control .icon-prev:before {
content: '\2039';
}
.carousel-control .icon-next:before {
content: '\203a';
}
.carousel-indicators {
position: absolute;
bottom: 10px;
left: 50%;
z-index: 15;
width: 60%;
padding-left: 0;
margin-left: -30%;
text-align: center;
list-style: none;
}
.carousel-indicators li {
display: inline-block;
width: 10px;
height: 10px;
margin: 1px;
text-indent: -999px;
cursor: pointer;
background-color: #000 \9;
background-color: rgba(0, 0, 0, 0);
border: 1px solid #fff;
border-radius: 10px;
}
.carousel-indicators .active {
width: 12px;
height: 12px;
margin: 0;
background-color: #fff;
}
.carousel-caption {
position: absolute;
right: 15%;
bottom: 20px;
left: 15%;
z-index: 10;
padding-top: 20px;
padding-bottom: 20px;
color: #fff;
text-align: center;
text-shadow: 0 1px 2px rgba(0, 0, 0, .6);
}
.carousel-caption .btn {
```

```
text-shadow: none;
}
@media screen and (min-width: 768px) {
.carousel-control .glyphicon-chevron-left,
.carousel-control .glyphicon-chevron-right,
.carousel-control .icon-prev,
.carousel-control .icon-next {
width: 30px;
height: 30px;
margin-top: -10px;
font-size: 30px;
}
.carousel-control .glyphicon-chevron-left,
.carousel-control .icon-prev {
margin-left: -10px;
}
.carousel-control .glyphicon-chevron-right,
.carousel-control .icon-next {
margin-right: -10px;
}
.carousel-caption {
right: 20%;
left: 20%;
padding-bottom: 30px;
}
.carousel-indicators {
bottom: 20px;
}
}
.clearfix:before,
.clearfix:after,
.dl-horizontal dd:before,
.dl-horizontal dd:after,
.container:before,
.container:after,
.container-fluid:before,
.container-fluid:after,
.row:before,
.row:after,
.form-horizontal .form-group:before,
.form-horizontal .form-group:after,
.btn-toolbar:before,
.btn-toolbar:after,
.btn-group-vertical > .btn-group:before,
.btn-group-vertical > .btn-group:after,
.nav:before,
.nav:after,
.navbar:before,
.navbar:after,
.navbar-header:before,
.navbar-header:after,
```

```
.navbar-collapse:before,  
.navbar-collapse:after,  
.pager:before,  
.pager:after,  
.panel-body:before,  
.panel-body:after,  
.modal-header:before,  
.modal-header:after,  
.modal-footer:before,  
.modal-footer:after {  
  display: table;  
  content: " ";  
}  
.clearfix:after,  
.dl-horizontal dd:after,  
.container:after,  
.container-fluid:after,  
.row:after,  
.form-horizontal .form-group:after,  
.btn-toolbar:after,  
.btn-group-vertical > .btn-group:after,  
.nav:after,  
.navbar:after,  
.navbar-header:after,  
.navbar-collapse:after,  
.pager:after,  
.panel-body:after,  
.modal-header:after,  
.modal-footer:after {  
  clear: both;  
}  
.center-block {  
  display: block;  
  margin-right: auto;  
  margin-left: auto;  
}  
.pull-right {  
  float: right !important;  
}  
.pull-left {  
  float: left !important;  
}  
.hide {  
  display: none !important;  
}  
.show {  
  display: block !important;  
}  
.invisible {  
  visibility: hidden;  
}
```

```
.text-hide {
  font: 0/0 a;
  color: transparent;
  text-shadow: none;
  background-color: transparent;
  border: 0;
}
.hidden {
  display: none !important;
}
.affix {
  position: fixed;
}
@-ms-viewport {
  width: device-width;
}
.visible-xs,
.visible-sm,
.visible-md,
.visible-lg {
  display: none !important;
}
.visible-xs-block,
.visible-xs-inline,
.visible-xs-inline-block,
.visible-sm-block,
.visible-sm-inline,
.visible-sm-inline-block,
.visible-md-block,
.visible-md-inline,
.visible-md-inline-block,
.visible-lg-block,
.visible-lg-inline,
.visible-lg-inline-block {
  display: none !important;
}
@media (max-width: 767px) {
  .visible-xs {
    display: block !important;
  }
  table.visible-xs {
    display: table !important;
  }
  tr.visible-xs {
    display: table-row !important;
  }
  th.visible-xs,
  td.visible-xs {
    display: table-cell !important;
  }
}
```

```
@media (max-width: 767px) {
  .visible-xs-block {
    display: block !important;
  }
}
@media (max-width: 767px) {
  .visible-xs-inline {
    display: inline !important;
  }
}
@media (max-width: 767px) {
  .visible-xs-inline-block {
    display: inline-block !important;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 768px) and (max-width: 991px) {
  .visible-sm {
    display: block !important;
  }
  table.visible-sm {
    display: table !important;
  }
  tr.visible-sm {
    display: table-row !important;
  }
  th.visible-sm,
  td.visible-sm {
    display: table-cell !important;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 768px) and (max-width: 991px) {
  .visible-sm-block {
    display: block !important;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 768px) and (max-width: 991px) {
  .visible-sm-inline {
    display: inline !important;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 768px) and (max-width: 991px) {
  .visible-sm-inline-block {
    display: inline-block !important;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 992px) and (max-width: 1199px) {
  .visible-md {
    display: block !important;
  }
  table.visible-md {
    display: table !important;
  }
}
```

```
}
tr.visible-md {
  display: table-row !important;
}
th.visible-md,
td.visible-md {
  display: table-cell !important;
}
}
@media (min-width: 992px) and (max-width: 1199px) {
  .visible-md-block {
    display: block !important;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 992px) and (max-width: 1199px) {
  .visible-md-inline {
    display: inline !important;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 992px) and (max-width: 1199px) {
  .visible-md-inline-block {
    display: inline-block !important;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 1200px) {
  .visible-lg {
    display: block !important;
  }
  table.visible-lg {
    display: table !important;
  }
  tr.visible-lg {
    display: table-row !important;
  }
  th.visible-lg,
  td.visible-lg {
    display: table-cell !important;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 1200px) {
  .visible-lg-block {
    display: block !important;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 1200px) {
  .visible-lg-inline {
    display: inline !important;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 1200px) {
  .visible-lg-inline-block {
```

```
    display: inline-block !important;
  }
}
@media (max-width: 767px) {
  .hidden-xs {
    display: none !important;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 768px) and (max-width: 991px) {
  .hidden-sm {
    display: none !important;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 992px) and (max-width: 1199px) {
  .hidden-md {
    display: none !important;
  }
}
@media (min-width: 1200px) {
  .hidden-lg {
    display: none !important;
  }
}
.visible-print {
  display: none !important;
}
@media print {
  .visible-print {
    display: block !important;
  }
  table.visible-print {
    display: table !important;
  }
  tr.visible-print {
    display: table-row !important;
  }
  th.visible-print,
  td.visible-print {
    display: table-cell !important;
  }
}
.visible-print-block {
  display: none !important;
}
@media print {
  .visible-print-block {
    display: block !important;
  }
}
.visible-print-inline {
  display: none !important;
}
```

```

}
@media print {
  .visible-print-inline {
    display: inline !important;
  }
}
.visible-print-inline-block {
  display: none !important;
}
}
@media print {
  .visible-print-inline-block {
    display: inline-block !important;
  }
}
}
@media print {
  .hidden-print {
    display: none !important;
  }
}
}
/*# sourceMappingURL=bootstrap.css.map */

```

Scirpt bootstrap.min

```

/#!
* Bootstrap v3.3.7 (http://getbootstrap.com)
* Copyright 2011-2016 Twitter, Inc.
* Licensed under MIT (https://github.com/twbs/bootstrap/blob/master/LICENSE)
/*! normalize.css v3.0.3 | MIT License | github.com/necolas/normalize.css */html{font-
family:sans-serif;-webkit-text-size-adjust:100%;-ms-text-size-
adjust:100%}body{margin:0}article,aside,details,figcaption,figure,footer,header,hgroup,main,menu,
nav,section,summary{display:block}audio,canvas,progress,video{display:inline-block;vertical-
align:baseline}audio:not([controls]){display:none;height:0}[hidden],template{display:none}a{backgro-
und-color:transparent}a:active,a:hover{outline:0}abbr[title]{border-bottom:1px
dotted}b,strong{font-weight:700}dfn{font-style:italic}h1{margin:.67em 0;font-
size:2em}mark{color:#000;background:#ff0}small{font-size:80%}sub,sup{position:relative;font-
size:75%;line-height:0;vertical-align:baseline}sup{top:-.5em}sub{bottom:-
.25em}img{border:0;svg:not(:root){overflow:hidden}figure{margin:1em 40px}hr{height:0;-webkit-
box-sizing:content-box;-moz-box-sizing:content-box;box-sizing:content-
box}pre{overflow:auto}code,kbd,pre,samp{font-family:monospace,monospace;font-
size:1em}button,input,optgroup,select,textarea{margin:0;font:inherit;color:inherit}button{overflow:
visible}button,select{text-transform:none}button,html
input[type=button],input[type=reset],input[type=submit]{-webkit-
appearance:button;cursor:pointer}button[disabled],html input[disabled]{cursor:default}button::-
moz-focus-inner,input::-moz-focus-inner{padding:0;border:0}input{line-
height:normal}input[type=checkbox],input[type=radio]{-webkit-box-sizing:border-box;-moz-box-
sizing:border-box;box-sizing:border-box;padding:0}input[type=number]::-webkit-inner-spin-
button,input[type=number]::-webkit-outer-spin-button{height:auto}input[type=search]{-webkit-
box-sizing:content-box;-moz-box-sizing:content-box;box-sizing:content-box;-webkit-
appearance:textfield}input[type=search]::-webkit-search-cancel-button,input[type=search]::-webkit-
search-decoration{-webkit-appearance:none}fieldset{padding:.35em .625em .75em;margin:0
2px;border:1px solid silver}legend{padding:0;border:0}textarea{overflow:auto}optgroup{font-

```

```
weight:700}table{border-spacing:0;border-collapse:collapse}td,th{padding:0}/*!
https://github.com/h5bp/html5-boilerplate/blob/master/src/css/main.css
print{*,:after,:before{color:#000!important;text-shadow:none!important;background:0
0!important;-webkit-box-shadow:none!important;box-shadow:none!important}a,a:visited{text-
decoration:underline}a[href]:after{content:" (" attr(href) ")"}abbr[title]:after{content:" (" attr(title)
")"}a[href^="javascript:"]:after,a[href^="#"]:after{content:""}blockquote,pre{border:1px
#999;page-break-inside:avoid}thead{display:table-header-group}img,tr{page-break-
inside:avoid}img{max-width:100%!important}h2,h3,p{orphans:3;widows:3}h2,h3{page-break-
after:avoid}.navbar{display:none}.btn>.caret,.dropdown>.btn>.caret{border-top-
color:#000!important}.label{border:1px solid #000}.table{border-collapse:collapse!important}.table
td,.table th{background-color:#fff!important}.table-bordered td,.table-bordered th{border:1px solid
#ddd!important}@font-face{font-family:'Glyphicons Halflings';src:url(../fonts/glyphicons-halflings-
regular.eot);src:url(../fonts/glyphicons-halflings-regular.woff?#iefix) format('embedded-
opentype'),url(../fonts/glyphicons-halflings-regular.woff2) format('woff2'),url(../fonts/glyphicons-
halflings-regular.woff) format('woff'),url(../fonts/glyphicons-halflings-regular.ttf)
format('truetype'),url(../fonts/glyphicons-halflings-regular.svg#glyphicons_halflingsregular)
format('svg')}glyphicon{position:relative;top:1px;display:inline-block;font-family:'Glyphicons
Halflings';font-style:normal;font-weight:400;line-height:1;-webkit-font-smoothing:antialiased;-moz-
osx-font-smoothing:grayscale}.glyphicon-asterisk:before{content:"\002a"}.glyphicon-
plus:before{content:"\002b"}.glyphicon-eur:before,.glyphicon-
euro:before{content:"\20ac"}.glyphicon-minus:before{content:"\2212"}.glyphicon-
cloud:before{content:"\2601"}.glyphicon-envelope:before{content:"\2709"}.glyphicon-
pencil:before{content:"\270f"}.glyphicon-glass:before{content:"\e001"}.glyphicon-
music:before{content:"\e002"}.glyphicon-search:before{content:"\e003"}.glyphicon-
heart:before{content:"\e005"}.glyphicon-star:before{content:"\e006"}.glyphicon-star-
empty:before{content:"\e007"}.glyphicon-user:before{content:"\e008"}.glyphicon-
film:before{content:"\e009"}.glyphicon-th-large:before{content:"\e010"}.glyphicon-
th:before{content:"\e011"}.glyphicon-th-list:before{content:"\e012"}.glyphicon-
ok:before{content:"\e013"}.glyphicon-remove:before{content:"\e014"}.glyphicon-zoom-
in:before{content:"\e015"}.glyphicon-zoom-out:before{content:"\e016"}.glyphicon-
off:before{content:"\e017"}.glyphicon-signal:before{content:"\e018"}.glyphicon-
cog:before{content:"\e019"}.glyphicon-trash:before{content:"\e020"}.glyphicon-
home:before{content:"\e021"}.glyphicon-file:before{content:"\e022"}.glyphicon-
time:before{content:"\e023"}.glyphicon-road:before{content:"\e024"}.glyphicon-download-
alt:before{content:"\e025"}.glyphicon-download:before{content:"\e026"}.glyphicon-
upload:before{content:"\e027"}.glyphicon-inbox:before{content:"\e028"}.glyphicon-play-
circle:before{content:"\e029"}.glyphicon-repeat:before{content:"\e030"}.glyphicon-
refresh:before{content:"\e031"}.glyphicon-list-alt:before{content:"\e032"}.glyphicon-
lock:before{content:"\e033"}.glyphicon-flag:before{content:"\e034"}.glyphicon-
headphones:before{content:"\e035"}.glyphicon-volume-off:before{content:"\e036"}.glyphicon-
volume-down:before{content:"\e037"}.glyphicon-volume-up:before{content:"\e038"}.glyphicon-
qr-code:before{content:"\e039"}.glyphicon-barcode:before{content:"\e040"}.glyphicon-
tag:before{content:"\e041"}.glyphicon-tags:before{content:"\e042"}.glyphicon-
book:before{content:"\e043"}.glyphicon-bookmark:before{content:"\e044"}.glyphicon-
print:before{content:"\e045"}.glyphicon-camera:before{content:"\e046"}.glyphicon-
font:before{content:"\e047"}.glyphicon-bold:before{content:"\e048"}.glyphicon-
italic:before{content:"\e049"}.glyphicon-text-height:before{content:"\e050"}.glyphicon-text-
width:before{content:"\e051"}.glyphicon-align-left:before{content:"\e052"}.glyphicon-align-
center:before{content:"\e053"}.glyphicon-align-right:before{content:"\e054"}.glyphicon-align-
justify:before{content:"\e055"}.glyphicon-list:before{content:"\e056"}.glyphicon-indent-
left:before{content:"\e057"}.glyphicon-indent-right:before{content:"\e058"}.glyphicon-facetime-
```

Source:
*/@media

video:before{content:"\e059"}.glyphicon-picture:before{content:"\e060"}.glyphicon-map-marker:before{content:"\e062"}.glyphicon-adjust:before{content:"\e063"}.glyphicon-tint:before{content:"\e064"}.glyphicon-edit:before{content:"\e065"}.glyphicon-share:before{content:"\e066"}.glyphicon-check:before{content:"\e067"}.glyphicon-move:before{content:"\e068"}.glyphicon-step-backward:before{content:"\e069"}.glyphicon-fast-backward:before{content:"\e070"}.glyphicon-backward:before{content:"\e071"}.glyphicon-play:before{content:"\e072"}.glyphicon-pause:before{content:"\e073"}.glyphicon-stop:before{content:"\e074"}.glyphicon-forward:before{content:"\e075"}.glyphicon-fast-forward:before{content:"\e076"}.glyphicon-step-forward:before{content:"\e077"}.glyphicon-eject:before{content:"\e078"}.glyphicon-chevron-left:before{content:"\e079"}.glyphicon-chevron-right:before{content:"\e080"}.glyphicon-plus-sign:before{content:"\e081"}.glyphicon-minus-sign:before{content:"\e082"}.glyphicon-remove-sign:before{content:"\e083"}.glyphicon-ok-sign:before{content:"\e084"}.glyphicon-question-sign:before{content:"\e085"}.glyphicon-info-sign:before{content:"\e086"}.glyphicon-screenshot:before{content:"\e087"}.glyphicon-remove-circle:before{content:"\e088"}.glyphicon-ok-circle:before{content:"\e089"}.glyphicon-ban-circle:before{content:"\e090"}.glyphicon-arrow-left:before{content:"\e091"}.glyphicon-arrow-right:before{content:"\e092"}.glyphicon-arrow-up:before{content:"\e093"}.glyphicon-arrow-down:before{content:"\e094"}.glyphicon-share-alt:before{content:"\e095"}.glyphicon-resize-full:before{content:"\e096"}.glyphicon-resize-small:before{content:"\e097"}.glyphicon-exclamation-sign:before{content:"\e101"}.glyphicon-gift:before{content:"\e102"}.glyphicon-leaf:before{content:"\e103"}.glyphicon-fire:before{content:"\e104"}.glyphicon-eye-open:before{content:"\e105"}.glyphicon-eye-close:before{content:"\e106"}.glyphicon-warning-sign:before{content:"\e107"}.glyphicon-plane:before{content:"\e108"}.glyphicon-calendar:before{content:"\e109"}.glyphicon-random:before{content:"\e110"}.glyphicon-comment:before{content:"\e111"}.glyphicon-magnet:before{content:"\e112"}.glyphicon-chevron-up:before{content:"\e113"}.glyphicon-chevron-down:before{content:"\e114"}.glyphicon-retweet:before{content:"\e115"}.glyphicon-shopping-cart:before{content:"\e116"}.glyphicon-folder-close:before{content:"\e117"}.glyphicon-folder-open:before{content:"\e118"}.glyphicon-resize-vertical:before{content:"\e119"}.glyphicon-resize-horizontal:before{content:"\e120"}.glyphicon-hdd:before{content:"\e121"}.glyphicon-bullhorn:before{content:"\e122"}.glyphicon-bell:before{content:"\e123"}.glyphicon-certificate:before{content:"\e124"}.glyphicon-thumbs-up:before{content:"\e125"}.glyphicon-thumbs-down:before{content:"\e126"}.glyphicon-hand-right:before{content:"\e127"}.glyphicon-hand-left:before{content:"\e128"}.glyphicon-hand-up:before{content:"\e129"}.glyphicon-hand-down:before{content:"\e130"}.glyphicon-circle-arrow-right:before{content:"\e131"}.glyphicon-circle-arrow-left:before{content:"\e132"}.glyphicon-circle-arrow-up:before{content:"\e133"}.glyphicon-circle-arrow-down:before{content:"\e134"}.glyphicon-globe:before{content:"\e135"}.glyphicon-wrench:before{content:"\e136"}.glyphicon-tasks:before{content:"\e137"}.glyphicon-filter:before{content:"\e138"}.glyphicon-briefcase:before{content:"\e139"}.glyphicon-fullscreen:before{content:"\e140"}.glyphicon-dashboard:before{content:"\e141"}.glyphicon-paperclip:before{content:"\e142"}.glyphicon-heart-empty:before{content:"\e143"}.glyphicon-link:before{content:"\e144"}.glyphicon-phone:before{content:"\e145"}.glyphicon-pushpin:before{content:"\e146"}.glyphicon-usd:before{content:"\e148"}.glyphicon-gbp:before{content:"\e149"}.glyphicon-sort:before{content:"\e150"}.glyphicon-sort-by-alphabet:before{content:"\e151"}.glyphicon-sort-by-alphabet-alt:before{content:"\e152"}.glyphicon-sort-by-order:before{content:"\e153"}.glyphicon-sort-by-order-alt:before{content:"\e154"}.glyphicon-sort-by-attributes:before{content:"\e155"}.glyphicon-sort-by-attributes-alt:before{content:"\e156"}.glyphicon-unchecked:before{content:"\e157"}.glyphicon-expand:before{content:"\e158"}.glyphicon-collapse-down:before{content:"\e159"}.glyphicon-collapse-up:before{content:"\e160"}.glyphicon-log-in:before{content:"\e161"}.glyphicon-flash:before{content:"\e162"}.glyphicon-log-out:before{content:"\e163"}.glyphicon-new-

window:before{content:"\e164"}.glyphicon-record:before{content:"\e165"}.glyphicon-save:before{content:"\e166"}.glyphicon-open:before{content:"\e167"}.glyphicon-saved:before{content:"\e168"}.glyphicon-import:before{content:"\e169"}.glyphicon-export:before{content:"\e170"}.glyphicon-send:before{content:"\e171"}.glyphicon-floppy-disk:before{content:"\e172"}.glyphicon-floppy-saved:before{content:"\e173"}.glyphicon-floppy-remove:before{content:"\e174"}.glyphicon-floppy-save:before{content:"\e175"}.glyphicon-floppy-open:before{content:"\e176"}.glyphicon-credit-card:before{content:"\e177"}.glyphicon-transfer:before{content:"\e178"}.glyphicon-cutlery:before{content:"\e179"}.glyphicon-header:before{content:"\e180"}.glyphicon-compressed:before{content:"\e181"}.glyphicon-earphone:before{content:"\e182"}.glyphicon-phone-alt:before{content:"\e183"}.glyphicon-tower:before{content:"\e184"}.glyphicon-stats:before{content:"\e185"}.glyphicon-sd-video:before{content:"\e186"}.glyphicon-hd-video:before{content:"\e187"}.glyphicon-subtitles:before{content:"\e188"}.glyphicon-sound-stereo:before{content:"\e189"}.glyphicon-sound-dolby:before{content:"\e190"}.glyphicon-sound-5-1:before{content:"\e191"}.glyphicon-sound-6-1:before{content:"\e192"}.glyphicon-sound-7-1:before{content:"\e193"}.glyphicon-copyright-mark:before{content:"\e194"}.glyphicon-registration-mark:before{content:"\e195"}.glyphicon-cloud-download:before{content:"\e197"}.glyphicon-cloud-upload:before{content:"\e198"}.glyphicon-tree-conifer:before{content:"\e199"}.glyphicon-tree-deciduous:before{content:"\e200"}.glyphicon-cd:before{content:"\e201"}.glyphicon-save-file:before{content:"\e202"}.glyphicon-open-file:before{content:"\e203"}.glyphicon-level-up:before{content:"\e204"}.glyphicon-copy:before{content:"\e205"}.glyphicon-paste:before{content:"\e206"}.glyphicon-alert:before{content:"\e209"}.glyphicon-equalizer:before{content:"\e210"}.glyphicon-king:before{content:"\e211"}.glyphicon-queen:before{content:"\e212"}.glyphicon-pawn:before{content:"\e213"}.glyphicon-bishop:before{content:"\e214"}.glyphicon-knight:before{content:"\e215"}.glyphicon-baby-formula:before{content:"\e216"}.glyphicon-tent:before{content:"\26fa"}.glyphicon-blackboard:before{content:"\e218"}.glyphicon-bed:before{content:"\e219"}.glyphicon-apple:before{content:"\f8ff"}.glyphicon-erase:before{content:"\e221"}.glyphicon-hourglass:before{content:"\231b"}.glyphicon-lamp:before{content:"\e223"}.glyphicon-duplicate:before{content:"\e224"}.glyphicon-piggy-bank:before{content:"\e225"}.glyphicon-scissors:before{content:"\e226"}.glyphicon-bitcoin:before{content:"\e227"}.glyphicon-btc:before{content:"\e227"}.glyphicon-xbt:before{content:"\e227"}.glyphicon-yen:before{content:"\00a5"}.glyphicon-jpy:before{content:"\00a5"}.glyphicon-ruble:before{content:"\20bd"}.glyphicon-rub:before{content:"\20bd"}.glyphicon-scale:before{content:"\e230"}.glyphicon-ice-lolly:before{content:"\e231"}.glyphicon-ice-lolly-tasted:before{content:"\e232"}.glyphicon-education:before{content:"\e233"}.glyphicon-option-horizontal:before{content:"\e234"}.glyphicon-option-vertical:before{content:"\e235"}.glyphicon-menu-hamburger:before{content:"\e236"}.glyphicon-modal-window:before{content:"\e237"}.glyphicon-oil:before{content:"\e238"}.glyphicon-grain:before{content:"\e239"}.glyphicon-sunglasses:before{content:"\e240"}.glyphicon-text-size:before{content:"\e241"}.glyphicon-text-color:before{content:"\e242"}.glyphicon-text-background:before{content:"\e243"}.glyphicon-object-align-top:before{content:"\e244"}.glyphicon-object-align-bottom:before{content:"\e245"}.glyphicon-object-align-horizontal:before{content:"\e246"}.glyphicon-object-align-left:before{content:"\e247"}.glyphicon-object-align-vertical:before{content:"\e248"}.glyphicon-object-align-right:before{content:"\e249"}.glyphicon-triangle-right:before{content:"\e250"}.glyphicon-triangle-left:before{content:"\e251"}.glyphicon-triangle-bottom:before{content:"\e252"}.glyphicon-triangle-top:before{content:"\e253"}.glyphicon-console:before{content:"\e254"}.glyphicon-superscript:before{content:"\e255"}.glyphicon-subscript:before{content:"\e256"}.glyphicon-menu-left:before{content:"\e257"}.glyphicon-menu-right:before{content:"\e258"}.glyphicon-menu-down:before{content:"\e259"}.glyphicon-menu-up:before{content:"\e260"}*{-webkit-box-

sizing:border-box;-moz-box-sizing:border-box;box-sizing:border-box}:after,:before{-webkit-box-sizing:border-box;-moz-box-sizing:border-box;box-sizing:border-box}html{font-size:10px;-webkit-tap-highlight-color:rgba(0,0,0)}body{font-family:"Helvetica Neue",Helvetica,Arial,sans-serif;font-size:14px;line-height:1.42857143;color:#333;background-color:#fff}button,input,select,textarea{font-family:inherit;font-size:inherit;line-height:inherit}a{color:#337ab7;text-decoration:none}a:focus,a:hover{color:#23527c;text-decoration:underline}a:focus{outline:5px auto -webkit-focus-ring-color;outline-offset:-2px}figure{margin:0}img{vertical-align:middle}.carousel-inner>.item>a>img,.carousel-inner>.item>img,.img-responsive,.thumbnail a>img,.thumbnail>img{display:block;max-width:100%;height:auto}.img-rounded{border-radius:6px}.img-thumbnail{display:inline-block;max-width:100%;height:auto;padding:4px;line-height:1.42857143;background-color:#fff;border:1px solid #ddd;border-radius:4px;-webkit-transition:all .2s ease-in-out;-o-transition:all .2s ease-in-out;transition:all .2s ease-in-out}.img-circle{border-radius:50%}hr{margin-top:20px;margin-bottom:20px;border:0;border-top:1px solid #eee}.sr-only{position:absolute;width:1px;height:1px;padding:0;margin:-1px;overflow:hidden;clip:rect(0,0,0,0);border:0}.sr-only-focusable:active,.sr-only-focusable:focus{position:static;width:auto;height:auto;margin:0;overflow:visible;clip:auto}[role=button]{cursor:pointer}.h1,.h2,.h3,.h4,.h5,.h6,h1,h2,h3,h4,h5,h6{font-family:inherit;font-weight:500;line-height:1.1;color:inherit}.h1 .small,.h1 small,.h2 .small,.h2 small,.h3 .small,.h3 small,.h4 .small,.h4 small,.h5 .small,.h5 small,.h6 .small,.h6 small,h1 .small,h1 small,h2 .small,h2 small,h3 .small,h3 small,h4 .small,h4 small,h5 .small,h5 small,h6 .small,h6 small{font-weight:400;line-height:1;color:#777}.h1,.h2,.h3,h1,h2,h3{margin-top:20px;margin-bottom:10px}.h1 .small,.h1 small,.h2 .small,.h2 small,.h3 .small,.h3 small,h1 .small,h1 small,h2 .small,h2 small,h3 .small,h3 small{font-size:65%}.h4,.h5,.h6,h4,h5,h6{margin-top:10px;margin-bottom:10px}.h4 .small,.h4 small,.h5 .small,.h5 small,.h6 .small,.h6 small,h4 .small,h4 small,h5 .small,h5 small,h6 .small,h6 small{font-size:75%}.h1,h1{font-size:36px}.h2,h2{font-size:30px}.h3,h3{font-size:24px}.h4,h4{font-size:18px}.h5,h5{font-size:14px}.h6,h6{font-size:12px}p{margin:0 0 10px}.lead{margin-bottom:20px;font-size:16px;font-weight:300;line-height:1.4}@media (min-width:768px){.lead{font-size:21px}}.small,small{font-size:85%}.mark,mark{padding:.2em;background-color:#fcf8e3}.text-left{text-align:left}.text-right{text-align:right}.text-center{text-align:center}.text-justify{text-align:justify}.text-nowrap{white-space:nowrap}.text-lowercase{text-transform:lowercase}.text-uppercase{text-transform:uppercase}.text-capitalize{text-transform:capitalize}.text-muted{color:#777}.text-primary{color:#337ab7}a.text-primary:focus,a.text-primary:hover{color:#286090}.text-success{color:#3c763d}a.text-success:focus,a.text-success:hover{color:#2b542c}.text-info{color:#31708f}a.text-info:focus,a.text-info:hover{color:#245269}.text-warning{color:#8a6d3b}a.text-warning:focus,a.text-warning:hover{color:#66512c}.text-danger{color:#a94442}a.text-danger:focus,a.text-danger:hover{color:#843534}.bg-primary{color:#fff;background-color:#337ab7}a.bg-primary:focus,a.bg-primary:hover{background-color:#286090}.bg-success{background-color:#dff0d8}a.bg-success:focus,a.bg-success:hover{background-color:#c1e2b3}.bg-info{background-color:#d9edf7}a.bg-info:focus,a.bg-info:hover{background-color:#afd9ee}.bg-warning{background-color:#fcf8e3}a.bg-warning:focus,a.bg-warning:hover{background-color:#f7ecb5}.bg-danger{background-color:#f2dede}a.bg-danger:focus,a.bg-danger:hover{background-color:#e4b9b9}.page-header{padding-bottom:9px;margin:40px 0 20px;border-bottom:1px solid #eee}ol,ul{margin-top:0;margin-bottom:10px}ol ol,ol ul,ul ol,ul ul{margin-bottom:0}.list-unstyled{padding-left:0;list-style:none}.list-inline{padding-left:0;margin-left:-5px;list-style:none}.list-inline>li{display:inline-block;padding-right:5px;padding-left:5px}dl{margin-top:0;margin-bottom:20px}dd,dt{line-height:1.42857143}dt{font-weight:700}dd{margin-left:0}@media (min-width:768px){.dl-horizontal dt{float:left;width:160px;overflow:hidden;clear:left;text-align:right;text-overflow:ellipsis;white-space:nowrap}.dl-horizontal dd{margin-left:180px}}abbr[data-original-

title],abbr[title]{cursor:help;border-bottom:1px dotted #777}.initialism{font-size:90%;text-transform:uppercase}blockquote{padding:10px 20px;margin:0 0 20px;font-size:17.5px;border-left:5px solid #eee}blockquote ol:last-child,blockquote p:last-child,blockquote ul:last-child{margin-bottom:0}blockquote .small,blockquote footer,blockquote small{display:block;font-size:80%;line-height:1.42857143;color:#777}blockquote .small:before,blockquote footer:before,blockquote small:before{content:"\2014 \00A0'}.blockquote-reverse,blockquote.pull-right{padding-right:15px;padding-left:0;text-align:right;border-right:5px solid #eee;border-left:0}.blockquote-reverse .small:before,.blockquote-reverse footer:before,.blockquote-reverse small:before,blockquote.pull-right .small:before,blockquote.pull-right footer:before,blockquote.pull-right small:before{content:"'}.blockquote-reverse .small:after,.blockquote-reverse footer:after,.blockquote-reverse small:after,blockquote.pull-right .small:after,blockquote.pull-right footer:after,blockquote.pull-right small:after{content:"\00A0 \2014'}

address{margin-bottom:20px;font-style:normal;line-height:1.42857143}code,kbd,pre,samp{font-family:Menlo,Monaco,Consolas,"Courier New",monospace}code{padding:2px 4px;font-size:90%;color:#c7254e;background-color:#f9f2f4;border-radius:4px}kbd{padding:2px 4px;font-size:90%;color:#fff;background-color:#333;border-radius:3px;-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 -1px 0 rgba(0,0,0,.25);box-shadow:inset 0 -1px 0 rgba(0,0,0,.25)}kbd kbd{padding:0;font-size:100%;font-weight:700;-webkit-box-shadow:none;box-shadow:none}pre{display:block;padding:9.5px;margin:0 0 10px;font-size:13px;line-height:1.42857143;color:#333;word-break:break-all;word-wrap:break-word;background-color:#f5f5f5;border:1px solid #ccc;border-radius:4px}pre code{padding:0;font-size:inherit;color:inherit;white-space:pre-wrap;background-color:transparent;border-radius:0}.pre-scrollable{max-height:340px;overflow-y:scroll}.container{padding-right:15px;padding-left:15px;margin-right:auto;margin-left:auto}@media (min-width:768px){.container{width:750px}}@media (min-width:992px){.container{width:970px}}@media (min-width:1200px){.container{width:1170px}}.container-fluid{padding-right:15px;padding-left:15px;margin-right:auto;margin-left:auto}.row{margin-right:-15px;margin-left:-15px}.col-lg-1,.col-lg-10,.col-lg-11,.col-lg-12,.col-lg-2,.col-lg-3,.col-lg-4,.col-lg-5,.col-lg-6,.col-lg-7,.col-lg-8,.col-lg-9,.col-md-1,.col-md-10,.col-md-11,.col-md-12,.col-md-2,.col-md-3,.col-md-4,.col-md-5,.col-md-6,.col-md-7,.col-md-8,.col-md-9,.col-sm-1,.col-sm-10,.col-sm-11,.col-sm-12,.col-sm-2,.col-sm-3,.col-sm-4,.col-sm-5,.col-sm-6,.col-sm-7,.col-sm-8,.col-sm-9,.col-xs-1,.col-xs-10,.col-xs-11,.col-xs-12,.col-xs-2,.col-xs-3,.col-xs-4,.col-xs-5,.col-xs-6,.col-xs-7,.col-xs-8,.col-xs-9{position:relative;min-height:1px;padding-right:15px;padding-left:15px}.col-xs-1,.col-xs-10,.col-xs-11,.col-xs-12,.col-xs-2,.col-xs-3,.col-xs-4,.col-xs-5,.col-xs-6,.col-xs-7,.col-xs-8,.col-xs-9{float:left}.col-xs-12{width:100%}.col-xs-11{width:91.66666667%}.col-xs-10{width:83.33333333%}.col-xs-9{width:75%}.col-xs-8{width:66.66666667%}.col-xs-7{width:58.33333333%}.col-xs-6{width:50%}.col-xs-5{width:41.66666667%}.col-xs-4{width:33.33333333%}.col-xs-3{width:25%}.col-xs-2{width:16.66666667%}.col-xs-1{width:8.33333333%}.col-xs-pull-12{right:100%}.col-xs-pull-11{right:91.66666667%}.col-xs-pull-10{right:83.33333333%}.col-xs-pull-9{right:75%}.col-xs-pull-8{right:66.66666667%}.col-xs-pull-7{right:58.33333333%}.col-xs-pull-6{right:50%}.col-xs-pull-5{right:41.66666667%}.col-xs-pull-4{right:33.33333333%}.col-xs-pull-3{right:25%}.col-xs-pull-2{right:16.66666667%}.col-xs-pull-1{right:8.33333333%}.col-xs-pull-0{right:auto}.col-xs-push-12{left:100%}.col-xs-push-11{left:91.66666667%}.col-xs-push-10{left:83.33333333%}.col-xs-push-9{left:75%}.col-xs-push-8{left:66.66666667%}.col-xs-push-7{left:58.33333333%}.col-xs-push-6{left:50%}.col-xs-push-5{left:41.66666667%}.col-xs-push-4{left:33.33333333%}.col-xs-push-3{left:25%}.col-xs-push-2{left:16.66666667%}.col-xs-push-1{left:8.33333333%}.col-xs-push-0{left:auto}.col-xs-offset-12{margin-left:100%}.col-xs-offset-11{margin-left:91.66666667%}.col-xs-offset-10{margin-left:83.33333333%}.col-xs-offset-9{margin-left:75%}.col-xs-offset-8{margin-left:66.66666667%}.col-xs-offset-7{margin-left:58.33333333%}.col-xs-offset-6{margin-left:50%}.col-xs-offset-5{margin-left:41.66666667%}.col-xs-offset-4{margin-left:33.33333333%}.col-xs-offset-3{margin-left:25%}.col-xs-offset-2{margin-left:16.66666667%}.col-xs-offset-1{margin-left:8.33333333%}.col-xs-offset-0{margin-left:0}@media (min-width:768px){.col-sm-1,.col-sm-

10,.col-sm-11,.col-sm-12,.col-sm-2,.col-sm-3,.col-sm-4,.col-sm-5,.col-sm-6,.col-sm-7,.col-sm-8,.col-sm-9{float:left}.col-sm-12{width:100%}.col-sm-11{width:91.66666667%}.col-sm-10{width:83.33333333%}.col-sm-9{width:75%}.col-sm-8{width:66.66666667%}.col-sm-7{width:58.33333333%}.col-sm-6{width:50%}.col-sm-5{width:41.66666667%}.col-sm-4{width:33.33333333%}.col-sm-3{width:25%}.col-sm-2{width:16.66666667%}.col-sm-1{width:8.33333333%}.col-sm-pull-12{right:100%}.col-sm-pull-11{right:91.66666667%}.col-sm-pull-10{right:83.33333333%}.col-sm-pull-9{right:75%}.col-sm-pull-8{right:66.66666667%}.col-sm-pull-7{right:58.33333333%}.col-sm-pull-6{right:50%}.col-sm-pull-5{right:41.66666667%}.col-sm-pull-4{right:33.33333333%}.col-sm-pull-3{right:25%}.col-sm-pull-2{right:16.66666667%}.col-sm-pull-1{right:8.33333333%}.col-sm-pull-0{right:auto}.col-sm-push-12{left:100%}.col-sm-push-11{left:91.66666667%}.col-sm-push-10{left:83.33333333%}.col-sm-push-9{left:75%}.col-sm-push-8{left:66.66666667%}.col-sm-push-7{left:58.33333333%}.col-sm-push-6{left:50%}.col-sm-push-5{left:41.66666667%}.col-sm-push-4{left:33.33333333%}.col-sm-push-3{left:25%}.col-sm-push-2{left:16.66666667%}.col-sm-push-1{left:8.33333333%}.col-sm-push-0{left:auto}.col-sm-offset-12{margin-left:100%}.col-sm-offset-11{margin-left:91.66666667%}.col-sm-offset-10{margin-left:83.33333333%}.col-sm-offset-9{margin-left:75%}.col-sm-offset-8{margin-left:66.66666667%}.col-sm-offset-7{margin-left:58.33333333%}.col-sm-offset-6{margin-left:50%}.col-sm-offset-5{margin-left:41.66666667%}.col-sm-offset-4{margin-left:33.33333333%}.col-sm-offset-3{margin-left:25%}.col-sm-offset-2{margin-left:16.66666667%}.col-sm-offset-1{margin-left:8.33333333%}.col-sm-offset-0{margin-left:0}}@media (min-width:992px){.col-md-1,.col-md-10,.col-md-11,.col-md-12,.col-md-2,.col-md-3,.col-md-4,.col-md-5,.col-md-6,.col-md-7,.col-md-8,.col-md-9{float:left}.col-md-12{width:100%}.col-md-11{width:91.66666667%}.col-md-10{width:83.33333333%}.col-md-9{width:75%}.col-md-8{width:66.66666667%}.col-md-7{width:58.33333333%}.col-md-6{width:50%}.col-md-5{width:41.66666667%}.col-md-4{width:33.33333333%}.col-md-3{width:25%}.col-md-2{width:16.66666667%}.col-md-1{width:8.33333333%}.col-md-pull-12{right:100%}.col-md-pull-11{right:91.66666667%}.col-md-pull-10{right:83.33333333%}.col-md-pull-9{right:75%}.col-md-pull-8{right:66.66666667%}.col-md-pull-7{right:58.33333333%}.col-md-pull-6{right:50%}.col-md-pull-5{right:41.66666667%}.col-md-pull-4{right:33.33333333%}.col-md-pull-3{right:25%}.col-md-pull-2{right:16.66666667%}.col-md-pull-1{right:8.33333333%}.col-md-pull-0{right:auto}.col-md-push-12{left:100%}.col-md-push-11{left:91.66666667%}.col-md-push-10{left:83.33333333%}.col-md-push-9{left:75%}.col-md-push-8{left:66.66666667%}.col-md-push-7{left:58.33333333%}.col-md-push-6{left:50%}.col-md-push-5{left:41.66666667%}.col-md-push-4{left:33.33333333%}.col-md-push-3{left:25%}.col-md-push-2{left:16.66666667%}.col-md-push-1{left:8.33333333%}.col-md-push-0{left:auto}.col-md-offset-12{margin-left:100%}.col-md-offset-11{margin-left:91.66666667%}.col-md-offset-10{margin-left:83.33333333%}.col-md-offset-9{margin-left:75%}.col-md-offset-8{margin-left:66.66666667%}.col-md-offset-7{margin-left:58.33333333%}.col-md-offset-6{margin-left:50%}.col-md-offset-5{margin-left:41.66666667%}.col-md-offset-4{margin-left:33.33333333%}.col-md-offset-3{margin-left:25%}.col-md-offset-2{margin-left:16.66666667%}.col-md-offset-1{margin-left:8.33333333%}.col-md-offset-0{margin-left:0}}@media (min-width:1200px){.col-lg-1,.col-lg-10,.col-lg-11,.col-lg-12,.col-lg-2,.col-lg-3,.col-lg-4,.col-lg-5,.col-lg-6,.col-lg-7,.col-lg-8,.col-lg-9{float:left}.col-lg-12{width:100%}.col-lg-11{width:91.66666667%}.col-lg-10{width:83.33333333%}.col-lg-9{width:75%}.col-lg-8{width:66.66666667%}.col-lg-7{width:58.33333333%}.col-lg-6{width:50%}.col-lg-5{width:41.66666667%}.col-lg-4{width:33.33333333%}.col-lg-3{width:25%}.col-lg-2{width:16.66666667%}.col-lg-1{width:8.33333333%}.col-lg-pull-12{right:100%}.col-lg-pull-11{right:91.66666667%}.col-lg-pull-10{right:83.33333333%}.col-lg-pull-9{right:75%}.col-lg-pull-8{right:66.66666667%}.col-lg-pull-7{right:58.33333333%}.col-lg-pull-6{right:50%}.col-lg-pull-5{right:41.66666667%}.col-lg-pull-4{right:33.33333333%}.col-lg-pull-3{right:25%}.col-lg-pull-2{right:16.66666667%}.col-lg-pull-1{right:8.33333333%}.col-lg-pull-0{right:auto}.col-lg-push-12{left:100%}.col-lg-push-11{left:91.66666667%}.col-lg-push-10{left:83.33333333%}.col-lg-push-

9{left:75%}.col-lg-push-8{left:66.66666667%}.col-lg-push-7{left:58.33333333%}.col-lg-push-6{left:50%}.col-lg-push-5{left:41.66666667%}.col-lg-push-4{left:33.33333333%}.col-lg-push-3{left:25%}.col-lg-push-2{left:16.66666667%}.col-lg-push-1{left:8.33333333%}.col-lg-push-0{left:auto}.col-lg-offset-12{margin-left:100%}.col-lg-offset-11{margin-left:91.66666667%}.col-lg-offset-10{margin-left:83.33333333%}.col-lg-offset-9{margin-left:75%}.col-lg-offset-8{margin-left:66.66666667%}.col-lg-offset-7{margin-left:58.33333333%}.col-lg-offset-6{margin-left:50%}.col-lg-offset-5{margin-left:41.66666667%}.col-lg-offset-4{margin-left:33.33333333%}.col-lg-offset-3{margin-left:25%}.col-lg-offset-2{margin-left:16.66666667%}.col-lg-offset-1{margin-left:8.33333333%}.col-lg-offset-0{margin-left:0}}table{background-color:transparent}caption{padding-top:8px;padding-bottom:8px;color:#777;text-align:left}th{text-align:left}.table{width:100%;max-width:100%;margin-bottom:20px}.table>tbody>tr>td,.table>tbody>tr>th,.table>tfoot>tr>td,.table>tfoot>tr>th,.table>thead>tr>td,.table>thead>tr>th{padding:8px;line-height:1.42857143;vertical-align:top;border-top:1px solid #ddd}.table>thead>tr>th{vertical-align:bottom;border-bottom:2px solid #ddd}.table>caption+thead>tr:first-child>td,.table>caption+thead>tr:first-child>th,.table>colgroup+thead>tr:first-child>td,.table>colgroup+thead>tr:first-child>th,.table>thead:first-child>tr:first-child>td,.table>thead:first-child>tr:first-child>th{border-top:0}.table>tbody+tbody{border-top:2px solid #ddd}.table .table{background-color:#fff}.table-condensed>tbody>tr>td,.table-condensed>tbody>tr>th,.table-condensed>tfoot>tr>td,.table-condensed>tfoot>tr>th,.table-condensed>thead>tr>td,.table-condensed>thead>tr>th{padding:5px}.table-bordered{border:1px solid #ddd}.table-bordered>tbody>tr>td,.table-bordered>tbody>tr>th,.table-bordered>tfoot>tr>td,.table-bordered>tfoot>tr>th,.table-bordered>thead>tr>td,.table-bordered>thead>tr>th{border:1px solid #ddd}.table-bordered>thead>tr>td,.table-bordered>thead>tr>th{border-bottom-width:2px}.table-striped>tbody>tr:nth-of-type(odd){background-color:#f9f9f9}.table-hover>tbody>tr:active{background-color:#f5f5f5}table col[class*=col-]{position:static;display:table-column;float:none}table td[class*=col-],table th[class*=col-]{position:static;display:table-cell;float:none}.table>tbody>tr.active>td,.table>tbody>tr.active>th,.table>tbody>tr>td.active,.table>tbody>tr>th.active,.table>tfoot>tr.active>td,.table>tfoot>tr.active>th,.table>tfoot>tr>td.active,.table>tfoot>tr>th.active,.table>thead>tr.active>td,.table>thead>tr.active>th,.table>thead>tr>td.active,.table>thead>tr>th.active{background-color:#f5f5f5}.table-hover>tbody>tr.active:active>td,.table-hover>tbody>tr.active:active>th,.table-hover>tbody>tr:active:active>td,.table-hover>tbody>tr:active:active>th,.table-hover>tbody>tr>td.active:active,.table-hover>tbody>tr>th.active:active{background-color:#e8e8e8}.table>tbody>tr.success>td,.table>tbody>tr.success>th,.table>tbody>tr>td.success,.table>tbody>tr>th.success,.table>tfoot>tr.success>td,.table>tfoot>tr.success>th,.table>tfoot>tr>td.success,.table>tfoot>tr>th.success,.table>thead>tr.success>td,.table>thead>tr.success>th,.table>thead>tr>td.success,.table>thead>tr>th.success{background-color:#dff0d8}.table-hover>tbody>tr.success:active>td,.table-hover>tbody>tr.success:active>th,.table-hover>tbody>tr:active>td.success:active,.table-hover>tbody>tr:active>th.success:active{background-color:#d0e9c6}.table>tbody>tr.info>td,.table>tbody>tr.info>th,.table>tbody>tr>td.info,.table>tbody>tr>th.info,.table>tfoot>tr.info>td,.table>tfoot>tr.info>th,.table>tfoot>tr>td.info,.table>tfoot>tr>th.info,.table>thead>tr.info>td,.table>thead>tr.info>th,.table>thead>tr>td.info,.table>thead>tr>th.info{background-color:#d9edf7}.table-hover>tbody>tr.info:active>td,.table-hover>tbody>tr.info:active>th,.table-hover>tbody>tr:active>td.info:active,.table-hover>tbody>tr:active>th.info:active{background-color:#c4e3f3}.table>tbody>tr.warning>td,.table>tbody>tr.warning>th,.table>tbody>tr>td.warning,.table>tbody>tr>th.warning,.table>tfoot>tr.warning>td,.table>tfoot>tr.warning>th,.table>tfoot>tr>td.warning,.table>tfoot>tr>th.warning,.table>thead>tr.warning>td,.table>thead>tr.warning>th,.table>thead>tr>td.warning,.table>thead>tr>th.warning{background-color:#fcf8e3}.table-hover>tbody>tr.warning:active>td,.table-hover>tbody>tr.warning:active>th,.table-

hover>tbody>tr: hover>.warning,.table-hover>tbody>tr>td.warning: hover,.table-
hover>tbody>tr>th.warning: hover{background-
color:#faf2cc}.table>tbody>tr.danger>td,.table>tbody>tr.danger>th,.table>tbody>tr>td.danger,.tabl
e>tbody>tr>th.danger,.table>tfoot>tr.danger>td,.table>tfoot>tr.danger>th,.table>tfoot>tr>td.dange
r,.table>tfoot>tr>th.danger,.table>thead>tr.danger>td,.table>thead>tr.danger>th,.table>thead>tr>t
d.danger,.table>thead>tr>th.danger{background-color:#f2dede}.table-
hover>tbody>tr.danger: hover>td,.table-hover>tbody>tr.danger: hover>th,.table-
hover>tbody>tr: hover>.danger,.table-hover>tbody>tr>td.danger: hover,.table-
hover>tbody>tr>th.danger: hover{background-color:#ebcccc}.table-responsive{min-
height:.01%;overflow-x:auto}@media screen and (max-width:767px){.table-
responsive{width:100%;margin-bottom:15px;overflow-y:hidden;-ms-overflow-style:-ms-autohiding-
scrollbar;border:1px solid #ddd}.table-responsive>.table{margin-bottom:0}.table-
responsive>.table>tbody>tr>td,.table-responsive>.table>tbody>tr>th,.table-
responsive>.table>tfoot>tr>td,.table-responsive>.table>tfoot>tr>th,.table-
responsive>.table>thead>tr>td,.table-responsive>.table>thead>tr>th{white-space:nowrap}.table-
responsive>.table-bordered{border:0}.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tbody>tr>td:first-
child,.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tbody>tr>th:first-child,.table-responsive>.table-
bordered>tfoot>tr>td:first-child,.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tfoot>tr>th:first-child,.table-
responsive>.table-bordered>thead>tr>td:first-child,.table-responsive>.table-
bordered>thead>tr>th:first-child{border-left:0}.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tbody>tr>td:last-
child,.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tbody>tr>th:last-child,.table-responsive>.table-
bordered>tfoot>tr>td:last-child,.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tfoot>tr>th:last-child,.table-
responsive>.table-bordered>thead>tr>td:last-child,.table-responsive>.table-
bordered>thead>tr>th:last-child{border-right:0}.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tbody>tr:last-
child>td,.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tbody>tr:last-child>th,.table-responsive>.table-
bordered>tfoot>tr:last-child>td,.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tfoot>tr:last-child>th{border-
bottom:0}}fieldset{min-
width:0;padding:0;margin:0;border:0}legend{display:block;width:100%;padding:0;margin-
bottom:20px;font-size:21px;line-height:inherit;color:#333;border:0;border-bottom:1px solid
#e5e5e5}label{display:inline-block;max-width:100%;margin-bottom:5px;font-
weight:700}input[type=search]{-webkit-box-sizing:border-box;-moz-box-sizing:border-box;box-
sizing:border-box}input[type=checkbox],input[type=radio]{margin:4px 0 0;margin-top:1px}input[type=range]{display:block;width:100%}select[mul
tiple],select[size]{height:auto}input[type=file]:focus,input[type=checkbox]:focus,input[type=radio]:f
ocus{outline:5px auto -webkit-focus-ring-color;outline-offset:-2px}output{display:block;padding-
top:7px;font-size:14px;line-height:1.42857143;color:#555}.form-
control{display:block;width:100%;height:34px;padding:6px 12px;font-size:14px;line-
height:1.42857143;color:#555;background-color:#fff;background-image:none;border:1px solid
#ccc;border-radius:4px;-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075);box-shadow:inset 0 1px
1px rgba(0,0,0,.075);-webkit-transition:border-color ease-in-out .15s,-webkit-box-shadow ease-in-
out .15s,-o-transition:border-color ease-in-out .15s,box-shadow ease-in-out .15s;transition:border-
color ease-in-out .15s,box-shadow ease-in-out .15s}.form-control:focus{border-
color:#66afe9;outline:0;-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075),0 0 8px
rgba(102,175,233,.6);box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075),0 0 8px
rgba(102,175,233,.6)}.form-control::-moz-placeholder{color:#999;opacity:1}.form-control::-ms-
input-placeholder{color:#999}.form-control::-webkit-input-placeholder{color:#999}.form-control::-ms-
expand{background-color:transparent;border:0}.form-control[disabled],.form-
control[readonly],fieldset[disabled] .form-control{background-color:#eee;opacity:1}.form-
control[disabled],fieldset[disabled] .form-control{cursor:not-allowed}textarea.form-
control{height:auto}input[type=search]{-webkit-appearance:none}@media screen and (-webkit-min-
device-pixel-ratio:0){input[type=date].form-control,input[type=time].form-

control,input[type=datetime-local].form-control,input[type=month].form-control{line-height:34px}.input-group-sm input[type=date],.input-group-sm input[type=time],.input-group-sm input[type=datetime-local],.input-group-sm input[type=month],input[type=date].input-sm,input[type=time].input-sm,input[type=datetime-local].input-sm,input[type=month].input-sm{line-height:30px}.input-group-lg input[type=date],.input-group-lg input[type=time],.input-group-lg input[type=datetime-local],.input-group-lg input[type=month],input[type=date].input-lg,input[type=time].input-lg,input[type=datetime-local].input-lg,input[type=month].input-lg{line-height:46px}}.form-group{margin-bottom:15px}.checkbox,.radio{position:relative;display:block;margin-top:10px;margin-bottom:10px}.checkbox label,.radio label{min-height:20px;padding-left:20px;margin-bottom:0;font-weight:400;cursor:pointer}.checkbox input[type=checkbox],.checkbox-inline input[type=checkbox],.radio input[type=radio],.radio-inline input[type=radio]{position:absolute;margin-top:4px\9;margin-left:-20px}.checkbox+.checkbox,.radio+.radio{margin-top:-5px}.checkbox-inline,.radio-inline{position:relative;display:inline-block;padding-left:20px;margin-bottom:0;font-weight:400;vertical-align:middle;cursor:pointer}.checkbox-inline+.checkbox-inline,.radio-inline+.radio-inline{margin-top:0;margin-left:10px}fieldset[disabled] input[type=checkbox],fieldset[disabled] input[type=radio],input[type=checkbox].disabled,input[type=checkbox][disabled],input[type=radio].disabled,input[type=radio][disabled]{cursor:not-allowed}.checkbox-inline.disabled,.radio-inline.disabled,fieldset[disabled] .checkbox-inline,fieldset[disabled] .radio-inline{cursor:not-allowed}.checkbox.disabled label,.radio.disabled label,fieldset[disabled] .checkbox label,fieldset[disabled] .radio label{cursor:not-allowed}.form-control-static{min-height:34px;padding-top:7px;padding-bottom:7px;margin-bottom:0}.form-control-static.input-lg,.form-control-static.input-sm{padding-right:0;padding-left:0}.input-sm{height:30px;padding:5px 10px;font-size:12px;line-height:1.5;border-radius:3px}select.input-sm{height:30px;line-height:30px}select[multiple].input-sm,textarea.input-sm{height:auto}.form-group-sm .form-control{height:30px;padding:5px 10px;font-size:12px;line-height:1.5;border-radius:3px}.form-group-sm select.form-control{height:30px;line-height:30px}.form-group-sm select[multiple].form-control,.form-group-sm textarea.form-control{height:auto}.form-group-sm .form-control-static{height:30px;min-height:32px;padding:6px 10px;font-size:12px;line-height:1.5}.input-lg{height:46px;padding:10px 16px;font-size:18px;line-height:1.3333333;border-radius:6px}select.input-lg{height:46px;line-height:46px}select[multiple].input-lg,textarea.input-lg{height:auto}.form-group-lg .form-control{height:46px;padding:10px 16px;font-size:18px;line-height:1.3333333;border-radius:6px}.form-group-lg select.form-control{height:46px;line-height:46px}.form-group-lg select[multiple].form-control,.form-group-lg textarea.form-control{height:auto}.form-group-lg .form-control-static{height:46px;min-height:38px;padding:11px 16px;font-size:18px;line-height:1.3333333}.has-feedback{position:relative}.has-feedback .form-control{padding-right:42.5px}.form-control-feedback{position:absolute;top:0;right:0;z-index:2;display:block;width:34px;height:34px;line-height:34px;text-align:center;pointer-events:none}.form-group-lg .form-control+.form-control-feedback,.input-group-lg+.form-control-feedback,.input-lg+.form-control-feedback{width:46px;height:46px;line-height:46px}.form-group-sm .form-control+.form-control-feedback,.input-group-sm+.form-control-feedback,.input-sm+.form-control-feedback{width:30px;height:30px;line-height:30px}.has-success .checkbox,.has-success .checkbox-inline,.has-success .control-label,.has-success .help-block,.has-success .radio,.has-success .radio-inline,.has-success.checkbox label,.has-success.checkbox-inline label,.has-success.radio label,.has-success.radio-inline label{color:#3c763d}.has-success .form-control{border-color:#3c763d;-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075);box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075)}.has-success .form-control:focus{border-color:#2b542c;-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075),0 0 6px #67b168;box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075),0 0 6px #67b168}.has-success .input-group-addon{color:#3c763d;background-color:#dff0d8;border-

color:#3c763d}.has-success .form-control-feedback{color:#3c763d}.has-warning .checkbox,.has-warning .checkbox-inline,.has-warning .control-label,.has-warning .help-block,.has-warning .radio,.has-warning .radio-inline,.has-warning.checkbox label,.has-warning.checkbox-inline label,.has-warning.radio label,.has-warning.radio-inline label{color:#8a6d3b}.has-warning .form-control{border-color:#8a6d3b;-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075);box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075)}.has-warning .form-control:focus{border-color:#66512c;-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075),0 0 6px #c0a16b;box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075),0 0 6px #c0a16b}.has-warning .input-group-addon{color:#8a6d3b;background-color:#fcf8e3;border-color:#8a6d3b}.has-warning .form-control-feedback{color:#8a6d3b}.has-error .checkbox,.has-error .checkbox-inline,.has-error .control-label,.has-error .help-block,.has-error .radio,.has-error .radio-inline,.has-error.checkbox label,.has-error.checkbox-inline label,.has-error.radio label,.has-error.radio-inline label{color:#a94442}.has-error .form-control{border-color:#a94442;-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075);box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075)}.has-error .form-control:focus{border-color:#843534;-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075),0 0 6px #ce8483;box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075),0 0 6px #ce8483}.has-error .input-group-addon{color:#a94442;background-color:#f2dede;border-color:#a94442}.has-error .form-control-feedback{color:#a94442}.has-feedback label~.form-control-feedback{top:25px}.has-feedback label.sr-only~.form-control-feedback{top:0}.help-block{display:block;margin-top:5px;margin-bottom:10px;color:#737373}@media (min-width:768px){.form-inline .form-group{display:inline-block;margin-bottom:0;vertical-align:middle}.form-inline .form-control{display:inline-block;width:auto;vertical-align:middle}.form-inline .form-control-static{display:inline-block}.form-inline .input-group{display:inline-table;vertical-align:middle}.form-inline .input-group .form-control,.form-inline .input-group .input-group-addon,.form-inline .input-group .input-group-btn{width:auto}.form-inline .input-group>.form-control{width:100%}.form-inline .control-label{margin-bottom:0;vertical-align:middle}.form-inline .checkbox,.form-inline .radio{display:inline-block;margin-top:0;margin-bottom:0;vertical-align:middle}.form-inline .checkbox label,.form-inline .radio label{padding-left:0}.form-inline .checkbox input[type=checkbox],.form-inline .radio input[type=radio]{position:relative;margin-left:0}.form-inline .has-feedback .form-control-feedback{top:0}.form-horizontal .checkbox,.form-horizontal .checkbox-inline,.form-horizontal .radio,.form-horizontal .radio-inline{padding-top:7px;margin-top:0;margin-bottom:0}.form-horizontal .checkbox,.form-horizontal .radio{min-height:27px}.form-horizontal .form-group{margin-right:-15px;margin-left:-15px}@media (min-width:768px){.form-horizontal .control-label{padding-top:7px;margin-bottom:0;text-align:right}}.form-horizontal .has-feedback .form-control-feedback{right:15px}@media (min-width:768px){.form-horizontal .form-group-lg .control-label{padding-top:11px;font-size:18px}}@media (min-width:768px){.form-horizontal .form-group-sm .control-label{padding-top:6px;font-size:12px}}.btn{display:inline-block;padding:6px 12px;margin-bottom:0;font-size:14px;font-weight:400;line-height:1.42857143;text-align:center;white-space:nowrap;vertical-align:middle;-ms-touch-action:manipulation;touch-action:manipulation;cursor:pointer;-webkit-user-select:none;-moz-user-select:none;-ms-user-select:none;user-select:none;background-image:none;border:1px solid transparent;border-radius:4px}.btn.active.focus,.btn.active:focus,.btn.focus,.btn.active.focus,.btn.active:focus,.btn.focus{outline:5px auto -webkit-focus-ring-color;outline-offset:-2px}.btn.focus,.btn:focus,.btn:hover{color:#333;text-decoration:none}.btn.active,.btn.active{background-image:none;outline:0;-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 3px 5px rgba(0,0,0,.125);box-shadow:inset 0 3px 5px rgba(0,0,0,.125)}.btn.disabled,.btn[disabled],fieldset[disabled] .btn{cursor:not-allowed;filter:alpha(opacity=65);-webkit-box-shadow:none;box-shadow:none;opacity:.65}a.btn.disabled,fieldset[disabled] a.btn{pointer-events:none}.btn-default{color:#333;background-color:#fff;border-color:#ccc}.btn-default.focus,.btn-default:focus{color:#333;background-color:#e6e6e6;border-color:#8c8c8c}.btn-

default:hover{color:#333;background-color:#e6e6e6;border-color:#adadad}.btn-default.active,.btn-default:active,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-default{color:#333;background-color:#e6e6e6;border-color:#adadad}.btn-default.active.focus,.btn-default.active:focus,.btn-default.active:hover,.btn-default:active.focus,.btn-default:active:focus,.btn-default:active:hover,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-default.focus,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-default:focus,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-default:hover{color:#333;background-color:#d4d4d4;border-color:#8c8c8c}.btn-default.active,.btn-default:active,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-default{background-image:none}.btn-default.disabled.focus,.btn-default.disabled:focus,.btn-default.disabled:hover,.btn-default[disabled].focus,.btn-default[disabled]:focus,.btn-default[disabled]:hover,fieldset[disabled].btn-default.focus,fieldset[disabled].btn-default:focus,fieldset[disabled].btn-default:hover{background-color:#fff;border-color:#ccc}.btn-default .badge{color:#fff;background-color:#333}.btn-primary{color:#fff;background-color:#337ab7;border-color:#2e6da4}.btn-primary.focus,.btn-primary:focus{color:#fff;background-color:#286090;border-color:#122b40}.btn-primary:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#286090;border-color:#204d74}.btn-primary.active,.btn-primary:active,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-primary{color:#fff;background-color:#286090;border-color:#204d74}.btn-primary.active.focus,.btn-primary.active:focus,.btn-primary.active:hover,.btn-primary:active.focus,.btn-primary:active:focus,.btn-primary:active:hover,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-primary.focus,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-primary:focus,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-primary:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#204d74;border-color:#122b40}.btn-primary.active,.btn-primary:active,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-primary{background-image:none}.btn-primary.disabled.focus,.btn-primary.disabled:focus,.btn-primary.disabled:hover,.btn-primary[disabled].focus,.btn-primary[disabled]:focus,.btn-primary[disabled]:hover,fieldset[disabled].btn-primary.focus,fieldset[disabled].btn-primary:focus,fieldset[disabled].btn-primary:hover{background-color:#337ab7;border-color:#2e6da4}.btn-primary .badge{color:#337ab7;background-color:#fff}.btn-success{color:#fff;background-color:#5cb85c;border-color:#4cae4c}.btn-success.focus,.btn-success:focus{color:#fff;background-color:#449d44;border-color:#255625}.btn-success:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#449d44;border-color:#398439}.btn-success.active,.btn-success:active,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-success{color:#fff;background-color:#449d44;border-color:#398439}.btn-success.active.focus,.btn-success.active:focus,.btn-success.active:hover,.btn-success:active.focus,.btn-success:active:focus,.btn-success:active:hover,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-success.focus,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-success:focus,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-success:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#398439;border-color:#255625}.btn-success.active,.btn-success:active,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-success{background-image:none}.btn-success.disabled.focus,.btn-success.disabled:focus,.btn-success.disabled:hover,.btn-success[disabled].focus,.btn-success[disabled]:focus,.btn-success[disabled]:hover,fieldset[disabled].btn-success.focus,fieldset[disabled].btn-success:focus,fieldset[disabled].btn-success:hover{background-color:#5cb85c;border-color:#4cae4c}.btn-success .badge{color:#5cb85c;background-color:#fff}.btn-info{color:#fff;background-color:#5bc0de;border-color:#46b8da}.btn-info.focus,.btn-info:focus{color:#fff;background-color:#31b0d5;border-color:#1b6d85}.btn-info:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#31b0d5;border-color:#269abc}.btn-info.active,.btn-info:active,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-info{color:#fff;background-color:#31b0d5;border-color:#269abc}.btn-info.active.focus,.btn-info.active:focus,.btn-info:active.focus,.btn-info:active:focus,.btn-info:active:hover,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-info.focus,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-info:focus,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-info:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#269abc;border-color:#1b6d85}.btn-info.active,.btn-info:active,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-info{background-image:none}.btn-info.disabled.focus,.btn-info.disabled:focus,.btn-info.disabled:hover,.btn-info[disabled].focus,.btn-info[disabled]:focus,.btn-info[disabled]:hover,fieldset[disabled].btn-info.focus,fieldset[disabled].btn-info:focus,fieldset[disabled].btn-info:hover{background-color:#5bc0de;border-color:#46b8da}.btn-info .badge{color:#5bc0de;background-color:#fff}.btn-

warning{color:#fff;background-color:#f0ad4e;border-color:#eea236}.btn-warning.focus,.btn-warning:warning:focus{color:#fff;background-color:#ec971f;border-color:#985f0d}.btn-warning:warning:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#ec971f;border-color:#d58512}.btn-warning.active,.btn-warning:active,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-warning{color:#fff;background-color:#ec971f;border-color:#d58512}.btn-warning.active.focus,.btn-warning.active:focus,.btn-warning.active:hover,.btn-warning:active.focus,.btn-warning:active:focus,.btn-warning:active:hover,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-warning.focus,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-warning:focus,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-warning:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#d58512;border-color:#985f0d}.btn-warning.active,.btn-warning:active,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-warning{background-image:none}.btn-warning.disabled.focus,.btn-warning.disabled:focus,.btn-warning.disabled:hover,.btn-warning[disabled].focus,.btn-warning[disabled]:focus,.btn-warning[disabled]:hover,fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning.focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning:focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning:hover{background-color:#f0ad4e;border-color:#eea236}.btn-warning .badge{color:#f0ad4e;background-color:#fff}.btn-danger{color:#fff;background-color:#d9534f;border-color:#d43f3a}.btn-danger.focus,.btn-danger:focus{color:#fff;background-color:#c9302c;border-color:#761c19}.btn-danger:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#c9302c;border-color:#ac2925}.btn-danger.active,.btn-danger:active,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-danger{color:#fff;background-color:#c9302c;border-color:#ac2925}.btn-danger.active.focus,.btn-danger.active:focus,.btn-danger.active:hover,.btn-danger:active.focus,.btn-danger:active:focus,.btn-danger:active:hover,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-danger.focus,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-danger:focus,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-danger:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#ac2925;border-color:#761c19}.btn-danger.active,.btn-danger:active,.open>.dropdown-toggle.btn-danger{background-image:none}.btn-danger.disabled.focus,.btn-danger.disabled:focus,.btn-danger.disabled:hover,.btn-danger[disabled].focus,.btn-danger[disabled]:focus,.btn-danger[disabled]:hover,fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger.focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger:focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger:hover{background-color:#d9534f;border-color:#d43f3a}.btn-danger .badge{color:#d9534f;background-color:#fff}.btn-link{font-weight:400;color:#337ab7;border-radius:0}.btn-link,.btn-link.active,.btn-link:active,.btn-link[disabled],fieldset[disabled] .btn-link{background-color:transparent;-webkit-box-shadow:none;box-shadow:none}.btn-link,.btn-link:active,.btn-link:focus,.btn-link:hover{border-color:transparent}.btn-link:focus,.btn-link:hover{color:#23527c;text-decoration:underline;background-color:transparent}.btn-link[disabled]:focus,.btn-link[disabled]:hover,fieldset[disabled] .btn-link:focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-link:hover{color:#777;text-decoration:none}.btn-group-lg>.btn,.btn-lg{padding:10px 16px;font-size:18px;line-height:1.33333333;border-radius:6px}.btn-group-sm>.btn,.btn-sm{padding:5px 10px;font-size:12px;line-height:1.5;border-radius:3px}.btn-group-xs>.btn,.btn-xs{padding:1px 5px;font-size:12px;line-height:1.5;border-radius:3px}.btn-block{display:block;width:100%}.btn-block+.btn-block{margin-top:5px}input[type=button].btn-block,input[type=reset].btn-block,input[type=submit].btn-block{width:100%}.fade{opacity:0;-webkit-transition:opacity .15s linear;-o-transition:opacity .15s linear;transition:opacity .15s linear}.fade.in{opacity:1}.collapse{display:none}.collapse.in{display:table-row}tbody.collapse.in{display:table-row-group}.collapsing{position:relative;height:0;overflow:hidden;-webkit-transition-timing-function:ease;-o-transition-timing-function:ease;transition-timing-function:ease;-webkit-transition-duration:.35s;-o-transition-duration:.35s;transition-duration:.35s;-webkit-transition-property:height,visibility;-o-transition-property:height,visibility;transition-property:height,visibility}.caret{display:inline-block;width:0;height:0;margin-left:2px;vertical-align:middle;border-top:4px dashed;border-top:4px solid 9;border-right:4px solid transparent;border-left:4px solid transparent}.dropdown,.dropdown{position:relative}.dropdown-toggle:focus{outline:0}.dropdown-menu{position:absolute;top:100%;left:0;z-index:1000;display:none;float:left;min-width:160px;padding:5px 0;margin:2px 0 0 0;font-

size:14px;text-align:left;list-style:none;background-color:#fff;-webkit-background-clip:padding-box;background-clip:padding-box;border:1px solid #ccc;border:1px solid rgba(0,0,0,.15);border-radius:4px;-webkit-box-shadow:0 6px 12px rgba(0,0,0,.175);box-shadow:0 6px 12px rgba(0,0,0,.175)}.dropdown-menu.pull-right{right:0;left:auto}.dropdown-menu .divider{height:1px;margin:9px 0;overflow:hidden;background-color:#e5e5e5}.dropdown-menu>li>a{display:block;padding:3px 20px;clear:both;font-weight:400;line-height:1.42857143;color:#333;white-space:nowrap}.dropdown-menu>li>a:focus,.dropdown-menu>li>a:hover{color:#262626;text-decoration:none;background-color:#f5f5f5}.dropdown-menu>.active>a,.dropdown-menu>.active>a:focus,.dropdown-menu>.active>a:hover{color:#fff;text-decoration:none;background-color:#337ab7;outline:0}.dropdown-menu>.disabled>a,.dropdown-menu>.disabled>a:focus,.dropdown-menu>.disabled>a:hover{color:#777}.dropdown-menu>.disabled>a:focus,.dropdown-menu>.disabled>a:hover{text-decoration:none;cursor:not-allowed;background-color:transparent;background-image:none;filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled=false)}.open>.dropdown-menu{display:block}.open>a{outline:0}.dropdown-menu-right{right:0;left:auto}.dropdown-menu-left{right:auto;left:0}.dropdown-header{display:block;padding:3px 20px;font-size:12px;line-height:1.42857143;color:#777;white-space:nowrap}.dropdown-backdrop{position:fixed;top:0;right:0;bottom:0;left:0;z-index:990}.pull-right>.dropdown-menu{right:0;left:auto}.dropdown .caret,.navbar-fixed-bottom .dropdown .caret{content:"";border-top:0;border-bottom:4px dashed;border-bottom:4px solid\9}.dropdown .dropdown-menu,.navbar-fixed-bottom .dropdown .dropdown-menu{top:auto;bottom:100%;margin-bottom:2px}@media (min-width:768px){.navbar-right .dropdown-menu{right:0;left:auto}.navbar-right .dropdown-menu-left{right:auto;left:0}}.btn-group,.btn-group-vertical{position:relative;display:inline-block;vertical-align:middle}.btn-group-vertical>.btn,.btn-group>.btn{position:relative;float:left}.btn-group-vertical>.btn.active,.btn-group-vertical>.btn.active,.btn-group-vertical>.btn:focus,.btn-group-vertical>.btn:hover,.btn-group>.btn.active,.btn-group>.btn.active,.btn-group>.btn:focus,.btn-group>.btn:hover{z-index:2}.btn-group .btn+.btn,.btn-group .btn+.btn-group,.btn-group .btn-group+.btn,.btn-group .btn-group+.btn-group{margin-left:-1px}.btn-toolbar{margin-left:-5px}.btn-toolbar .btn,.btn-toolbar .btn-group,.btn-toolbar .input-group{float:left}.btn-toolbar>.btn,.btn-toolbar>.btn-group,.btn-toolbar>.input-group{margin-left:5px}.btn-group>.btn:not(:first-child):not(:last-child):not(.dropdown-toggle){border-radius:0}.btn-group>.btn:first-child{margin-left:0}.btn-group>.btn:first-child:not(:last-child):not(.dropdown-toggle){border-top-right-radius:0;border-bottom-right-radius:0}.btn-group>.btn:last-child:not(:first-child),.btn-group>.dropdown-toggle:not(:first-child){border-top-left-radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.btn-group>.btn-group{float:left}.btn-group>.btn-group:not(:first-child):not(:last-child)>.btn{border-radius:0}.btn-group>.btn-group:first-child:not(:last-child)>.btn:last-child,.btn-group>.btn-group:first-child:not(:last-child)>.dropdown-toggle{border-top-right-radius:0;border-bottom-right-radius:0}.btn-group>.btn-group:last-child:not(:first-child)>.btn:first-child{border-top-left-radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.btn-group .dropdown-toggle.active,.btn-group.open .dropdown-toggle{outline:0}.btn-group>.btn+.dropdown-toggle{padding-right:8px;padding-left:8px}.btn-group>.btn-lg+.dropdown-toggle{padding-right:12px;padding-left:12px}.btn-group.open .dropdown-toggle{-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 3px 5px rgba(0,0,0,.125);box-shadow:inset 0 3px 5px rgba(0,0,0,.125)}.btn-group.open .dropdown-toggle.btn-link{-webkit-box-shadow:none;box-shadow:none}.btn .caret{margin-left:0}.btn-lg .caret{border-width:5px 5px 0;border-bottom-width:0}.dropdown .btn-lg .caret{border-width:0 5px 5px}.btn-group-vertical>.btn,.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group,.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group>.btn{display:block;float:none;width:100%;max-width:100%}.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group>.btn{float:none}.btn-group-vertical>.btn+.btn,.btn-group-vertical>.btn+.btn-group,.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group+.btn,.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group+.btn-group{margin-top:1px;margin-left:0}.btn-group-vertical>.btn:not(:first-child):not(:last-child){border-radius:0}.btn-group-vertical>.btn:first-child:not(:last-child){border-top-left-radius:4px;border-top-right-radius:4px;border-bottom-right-radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.btn-group-vertical>.btn:last-

child:not(:first-child){border-top-left-radius:0;border-top-right-radius:0;border-bottom-right-radius:4px;border-bottom-left-radius:4px}.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group:not(:first-child):not(:last-child)>.btn{border-radius:0}.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group:first-child:not(:last-child)>.btn:last-child,.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group:first-child:not(:last-child)>.dropdown-toggle{border-bottom-right-radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group:last-child:not(:first-child)>.btn:first-child{border-top-left-radius:0;border-top-right-radius:0}.btn-group-justified{display:table;width:100%;table-layout:fixed;border-collapse:separate}.btn-group-justified>.btn,.btn-group-justified>.btn-group{display:table-cell;float:none;width:1%}.btn-group-justified>.btn-group .btn{width:100%}.btn-group-justified>.btn-group .dropdown-menu{left:auto}[data-toggle=buttons]>.btn input[type=checkbox],[data-toggle=buttons]>.btn input[type=radio],[data-toggle=buttons]>.btn-group>.btn input[type=checkbox],[data-toggle=buttons]>.btn-group>.btn input[type=radio]{position:absolute;clip:rect(0,0,0,0);pointer-events:none}.input-group{position:relative;display:table;border-collapse:separate}.input-group[class*=col-]{float:none;padding-right:0;padding-left:0}.input-group .form-control{position:relative;z-index:2;float:left;width:100%;margin-bottom:0}.input-group .form-control:focus{z-index:3}.input-group-lg>.form-control,.input-group-lg>.input-group-addon,.input-group-lg>.input-group-btn>.btn{height:46px;padding:10px 16px;font-size:18px;line-height:1.333333;border-radius:6px}select.input-group-lg>.form-control,select.input-group-lg>.input-group-addon,select.input-group-lg>.input-group-btn>.btn{height:46px;line-height:46px}select[multiple].input-group-lg>.form-control,select[multiple].input-group-lg>.input-group-addon,select[multiple].input-group-lg>.input-group-btn>.btn,textarea.input-group-lg>.form-control,textarea.input-group-lg>.input-group-addon,textarea.input-group-lg>.input-group-btn>.btn{height:auto}.input-group-sm>.form-control,.input-group-sm>.input-group-addon,.input-group-sm>.input-group-btn>.btn{height:30px;padding:5px 10px;font-size:12px;line-height:1.5;border-radius:3px}select.input-group-sm>.form-control,select.input-group-sm>.input-group-addon,select.input-group-sm>.input-group-btn>.btn{height:30px;line-height:30px}select[multiple].input-group-sm>.form-control,select[multiple].input-group-sm>.input-group-addon,select[multiple].input-group-sm>.input-group-btn>.btn,textarea.input-group-sm>.form-control,textarea.input-group-sm>.input-group-addon,textarea.input-group-sm>.input-group-btn>.btn{height:auto}.input-group .form-control,.input-group-addon,.input-group-btn{display:table-cell}.input-group .form-control:not(:first-child):not(:last-child),.input-group-addon:not(:first-child):not(:last-child),.input-group-btn:not(:first-child):not(:last-child){border-radius:0}.input-group-addon,.input-group-btn{width:1%;white-space:nowrap;vertical-align:middle}.input-group-addon{padding:6px 12px;font-size:14px;font-weight:400;line-height:1;color:#555;text-align:center;background-color:#eee;border:1px solid #ccc;border-radius:4px}.input-group-addon.input-sm{padding:5px 10px;font-size:12px;border-radius:3px}.input-group-addon.input-lg{padding:10px 16px;font-size:18px;border-radius:6px}.input-group-addon input[type=checkbox],.input-group-addon input[type=radio]{margin-top:0}.input-group .form-control:first-child,.input-group-addon:first-child,.input-group-btn:first-child>.btn,.input-group-btn:first-child>.btn-group>.btn,.input-group-btn:first-child>.dropdown-toggle,.input-group-btn:last-child>.btn-group:not(:last-child)>.btn,.input-group-btn:last-child>.btn:not(:last-child):not(.dropdown-toggle){border-top-right-radius:0;border-bottom-right-radius:0}.input-group-addon:first-child{border-right:0}.input-group .form-control:last-child,.input-group-addon:last-child,.input-group-btn:first-child>.btn-group:not(:first-child)>.btn,.input-group-btn:first-child>.btn:not(:first-child),.input-group-btn:last-child>.btn,.input-group-btn:last-child>.btn-group>.btn,.input-group-btn:last-child>.dropdown-toggle{border-top-left-radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.input-group-addon:last-child{border-left:0}.input-group-btn{position:relative;font-size:0;white-space:nowrap}.input-group-btn>.btn{position:relative}.input-group-btn>.btn+.btn{margin-left:-1px}.input-group-btn>.btn:active,.input-group-btn>.btn:focus,.input-group-btn>.btn:hover{z-index:2}.input-group-btn:first-child>.btn,.input-group-btn:first-child>.btn-group{margin-right:-1px}.input-group-btn:last-child>.btn,.input-group-btn:last-child>.btn-group{z-

index:2;margin-left:-1px}.nav{padding-left:0;margin-bottom:0;list-style:none}.nav>li{position:relative;display:block}.nav>li>a{position:relative;display:block;padding:10px 15px}.nav>li>a:focus,.nav>li>a:hover{text-decoration:none;background-color:#eee}.nav>li.disabled>a{color:#777}.nav>li.disabled>a:focus,.nav>li.disabled>a:hover{color:#777;text-decoration:none;cursor:not-allowed;background-color:transparent}.nav .open>a,.nav .open>a:focus,.nav .open>a:hover{background-color:#eee;border-color:#337ab7}.nav .nav-divider{height:1px;margin:9px 0;overflow:hidden;background-color:#e5e5e5}.nav>li>a>img{max-width:none}.nav-tabs{border-bottom:1px solid #ddd}.nav-tabs>li{float:left;margin-bottom:-1px}.nav-tabs>li>a{margin-right:2px;line-height:1.42857143;border:1px solid transparent;border-radius:4px 4px 0 0}.nav-tabs>li>a:hover{border-color:#eee #eee #ddd}.nav-tabs>li.active>a,.nav-tabs>li.active>a:focus,.nav-tabs>li.active>a:hover{color:#555;cursor:default;background-color:#fff;border:1px solid #ddd;border-bottom-color:transparent}.nav-tabs.nav-justified{width:100%;border-bottom:0}.nav-tabs.nav-justified>li{float:none}.nav-tabs.nav-justified>li>a{margin-bottom:5px;text-align:center}.nav-tabs.nav-justified>.dropdown .dropdown-menu{top:auto;left:auto}@media (min-width:768px){.nav-tabs.nav-justified>li{display:table-cell;width:1%}.nav-tabs.nav-justified>li>a{margin-bottom:0}.nav-tabs.nav-justified>li>a{margin-right:0;border-radius:4px}.nav-tabs.nav-justified>.active>a,.nav-tabs.nav-justified>.active>a:focus,.nav-tabs.nav-justified>.active>a:hover{border:1px solid #ddd}@media (min-width:768px){.nav-tabs.nav-justified>li>a{border-bottom:1px solid #ddd;border-radius:4px 4px 0 0}.nav-tabs.nav-justified>.active>a,.nav-tabs.nav-justified>.active>a:focus,.nav-tabs.nav-justified>.active>a:hover{border-bottom-color:#fff}}.nav-pills>li{float:left}.nav-pills>li>a{border-radius:4px}.nav-pills>li+li{margin-left:2px}.nav-pills>li.active>a,.nav-pills>li.active>a:focus,.nav-pills>li.active>a:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#337ab7}.nav-stacked>li{float:none}.nav-stacked>li+li{margin-top:2px;margin-left:0}.nav-justified{width:100%}.nav-justified>li{float:none}.nav-justified>li>a{margin-bottom:5px;text-align:center}.nav-justified>.dropdown .dropdown-menu{top:auto;left:auto}@media (min-width:768px){.nav-justified>li{display:table-cell;width:1%}.nav-justified>li>a{margin-bottom:0}.nav-tabs-justified{border-bottom:0}.nav-tabs-justified>li>a{margin-right:0;border-radius:4px}.nav-tabs-justified>.active>a,.nav-tabs-justified>.active>a:focus,.nav-tabs-justified>.active>a:hover{border:1px solid #ddd}@media (min-width:768px){.nav-tabs-justified>li>a{border-bottom:1px solid #ddd;border-radius:4px 4px 0 0}.nav-tabs-justified>.active>a,.nav-tabs-justified>.active>a:focus,.nav-tabs-justified>.active>a:hover{border-bottom-color:#fff}}.tab-content>.tab-pane{display:none}.tab-content>.active{display:block}.nav-tabs .dropdown-menu{margin-top:-1px;border-top-left-radius:0;border-top-right-radius:0}.navbar{position:relative;min-height:50px;margin-bottom:20px;border:1px solid transparent}@media (min-width:768px){.navbar{border-radius:4px}}@media (min-width:768px){.navbar-header{float:left}.navbar-collapse{padding-right:15px;padding-left:15px;overflow-x:visible;-webkit-overflow-scrolling:touch;border-top:1px solid transparent;-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255,255,255,.1);box-shadow:inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255,255,255,.1)}.navbar-collapse.in{overflow-y:auto}@media (min-width:768px){.navbar-collapse{width:auto;border-top:0;-webkit-box-shadow:none;box-shadow:none}.navbar-collapse.collapse{display:block!important;height:auto!important;padding-bottom:0;overflow:visible!important}.navbar-collapse.in{overflow-y:visible}.navbar-fixed-bottom .navbar-collapse,.navbar-fixed-top .navbar-collapse,.navbar-static-top .navbar-collapse{padding-right:0;padding-left:0}}.navbar-fixed-bottom .navbar-collapse,.navbar-fixed-top .navbar-collapse{max-height:340px}@media (max-device-width:480px) and (orientation:landscape){.navbar-fixed-bottom .navbar-collapse,.navbar-fixed-top .navbar-collapse{max-height:200px}}.container-fluid>.navbar-collapse,.container-fluid>.navbar-header,.container>.navbar-collapse,.container>.navbar-header{margin-right:-15px;margin-left:-15px}@media (min-width:768px){.container-fluid>.navbar-collapse,.container-fluid>.navbar-header,.container>.navbar-collapse,.container>.navbar-header{margin-right:0;margin-left:0}}.navbar-static-top{z-index:1000;border-width:0 0 1px}@media (min-width:768px){.navbar-static-top{border-

radius:0}}.navbar-fixed-bottom,.navbar-fixed-top{position:fixed;right:0;left:0;z-index:1030}@media (min-width:768px){.navbar-fixed-bottom,.navbar-fixed-top{border-radius:0}}.navbar-fixed-top{top:0;border-width:0 0 1px}.navbar-fixed-bottom{bottom:0;margin-bottom:0;border-width:1px 0 0}.navbar-brand{float:left;height:50px;padding:15px 15px;font-size:18px;line-height:20px}.navbar-brand:focus,.navbar-brand:hover{text-decoration:none}.navbar-brand>img{display:block}@media (min-width:768px){.navbar>.container .navbar-brand,.navbar>.container-fluid .navbar-brand{margin-left:-15px}}.navbar-toggle{position:relative;float:right;padding:9px 10px;margin-top:8px;margin-right:15px;margin-bottom:8px;background-color:transparent;background-image:none;border:1px solid transparent;border-radius:4px}.navbar-toggle:focus{outline:0}.navbar-toggle .icon-bar{display:block;width:22px;height:2px;border-radius:1px}.navbar-toggle .icon-bar+.icon-bar{margin-top:4px}@media (min-width:768px){.navbar-toggle{display:none}}.navbar-nav{margin:7.5px -15px}.navbar-nav>li>a{padding-top:10px;padding-bottom:10px;line-height:20px}@media (max-width:767px){.navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu{position:static;float:none;width:auto;margin-top:0;background-color:transparent;border:0;-webkit-box-shadow:none;box-shadow:none}.navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu .dropdown-header,.navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>li>a{padding:5px 15px 5px 25px}.navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>li>a{line-height:20px}.navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>li>a:focus,.navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>li>a:hover{background-image:none}}@media (min-width:768px){.navbar-nav{float:left;margin:0}.navbar-nav>li{float:left}.navbar-nav>li>a{padding-top:15px;padding-bottom:15px}}.navbar-form{padding:10px 15px;margin-top:8px;margin-right:-15px;margin-bottom:8px;margin-left:-15px;border-top:1px solid transparent;border-bottom:1px solid transparent;-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255,255,255,.1),0 1px 0 rgba(255,255,255,.1);box-shadow:inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255,255,255,.1),0 1px 0 rgba(255,255,255,.1)}@media (min-width:768px){.navbar-form .form-group{display:inline-block;margin-bottom:0;vertical-align:middle}.navbar-form .form-control{display:inline-block;width:auto;vertical-align:middle}.navbar-form .form-control-static{display:inline-block}.navbar-form .input-group{display:inline-table;vertical-align:middle}.navbar-form .input-group .form-control,.navbar-form .input-group .input-group-addon,.navbar-form .input-group .input-group-btn{width:auto}.navbar-form .input-group>.form-control{width:100%}.navbar-form .control-label{margin-bottom:0;vertical-align:middle}.navbar-form .checkbox,.navbar-form .radio{display:inline-block;margin-top:0;margin-bottom:0;vertical-align:middle}.navbar-form .checkbox label,.navbar-form .radio label{padding-left:0}.navbar-form .checkbox input[type=checkbox],.navbar-form .radio input[type=radio]{position:relative;margin-left:0}.navbar-form .has-feedback .form-control-feedback{top:0}}@media (max-width:767px){.navbar-form .form-group{margin-bottom:5px}.navbar-form .form-group:last-child{margin-bottom:0}}@media (min-width:768px){.navbar-form{width:auto;padding-top:0;padding-bottom:0;margin-right:0;margin-left:0;border:0;-webkit-box-shadow:none;box-shadow:none}}.navbar-nav>li>.dropdown-menu{margin-top:0;border-top-left-radius:0;border-top-right-radius:0}.navbar-fixed-bottom .navbar-nav>li>.dropdown-menu{margin-bottom:0;border-top-left-radius:4px;border-top-right-radius:4px;border-bottom-right-radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.navbar-btn{margin-top:8px;margin-bottom:8px}.navbar-btn.btn-sm{margin-top:10px;margin-bottom:10px}.navbar-btn.btn-xs{margin-top:14px;margin-bottom:14px}.navbar-text{margin-top:15px;margin-bottom:15px}@media (min-width:768px){.navbar-text{float:left;margin-right:15px;margin-left:15px}}@media (min-width:768px){.navbar-left{float:left!important}.navbar-right{float:right!important;margin-right:-15px}.navbar-right~.navbar-right{margin-right:0}}.navbar-default{background-color:#f8f8f8;border-color:#e7e7e7}.navbar-default .navbar-brand{color:#777}.navbar-default .navbar-brand:focus,.navbar-default .navbar-brand:hover{color:#5e5e5e;background-color:transparent}.navbar-default .navbar-text{color:#777}.navbar-default .navbar-nav>li>a{color:#777}.navbar-default .navbar-nav>li>a:focus,.navbar-default .navbar-nav>li>a:hover{color:#333;background-color:transparent}.navbar-default .navbar-nav>.active>a,.navbar-default .navbar

nav>.active>a:focus,.navbar-default .navbar-nav>.active>a:hover{color:#555;background-color:#e7e7e7}.navbar-default .navbar-nav>.disabled>a,.navbar-default .navbar-nav>.disabled>a:focus,.navbar-default .navbar-nav>.disabled>a:hover{color:#ccc;background-color:transparent}.navbar-default .navbar-toggle{border-color:#ddd}.navbar-default .navbar-toggle:focus,.navbar-default .navbar-toggle:hover{background-color:#ddd}.navbar-default .navbar-toggle .icon-bar{background-color:#888}.navbar-default .navbar-collapse,.navbar-default .navbar-form{border-color:#e7e7e7}.navbar-default .navbar-nav>.open>a,.navbar-default .navbar-nav>.open>a:focus,.navbar-default .navbar-nav>.open>a:hover{color:#555;background-color:#e7e7e7}@media (max-width:767px){.navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>li>a{color:#777}.navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>li>a:focus,.navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>li>a:hover{color:#333;background-color:transparent}.navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>.active>a,.navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>.active>a:focus,.navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>.active>a:hover{color:#555;background-color:#e7e7e7}.navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>.disabled>a,.navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>.disabled>a:focus,.navbar-default .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>.disabled>a:hover{color:#ccc;background-color:transparent}}.navbar-default .navbar-link{color:#777}.navbar-default .navbar-link:hover{color:#333}.navbar-default .btn-link{color:#777}.navbar-default .btn-link:focus,.navbar-default .btn-link:hover{color:#333}.navbar-default .btn-link[disabled]:focus,.navbar-default .btn-link[disabled]:hover,fieldset[disabled] .navbar-default .btn-link:focus,fieldset[disabled] .navbar-default .btn-link:hover{color:#ccc}.navbar-inverse{background-color:#222;border-color:#080808}.navbar-inverse .navbar-brand{color:#9d9d9d}.navbar-inverse .navbar-brand:focus,.navbar-inverse .navbar-brand:hover{color:#fff;background-color:transparent}.navbar-inverse .navbar-text{color:#9d9d9d}.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav>li>a{color:#9d9d9d}.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav>li>a:focus,.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav>li>a:hover{color:#fff;background-color:transparent}.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav>.active>a,.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav>.active>a:focus,.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav>.active>a:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#080808}.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav>.disabled>a,.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav>.disabled>a:focus,.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav>.disabled>a:hover{color:#444;background-color:transparent}.navbar-inverse .navbar-toggle{border-color:#333}.navbar-inverse .navbar-toggle:focus,.navbar-inverse .navbar-toggle:hover{background-color:#333}.navbar-inverse .navbar-toggle .icon-bar{background-color:#fff}.navbar-inverse .navbar-collapse,.navbar-inverse .navbar-form{border-color:#101010}.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav>.open>a,.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav>.open>a:focus,.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav>.open>a:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#080808}@media (max-width:767px){.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>.dropdown-header{border-color:#080808}.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu .divider{background-color:#080808}.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>li>a{color:#9d9d9d}.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>li>a:focus,.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>li>a:hover{color:#fff;background-color:transparent}.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>.active>a,.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>.active>a:focus,.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>.active>a:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#080808}.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>.disabled>a,.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>.disabled>a:focus,.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu>.disabled>a:hover{color:#444;background-color:transparent}}.navbar-inverse .navbar-link{color:#9d9d9d}.navbar-inverse .navbar-link:hover{color:#fff}.navbar-inverse .btn-link{color:#9d9d9d}.navbar-inverse .btn-link:focus,.navbar-inverse .btn-link:hover{color:#fff}.navbar-inverse .btn-link[disabled]:focus,.navbar-inverse .btn-link[disabled]:hover,fieldset[disabled] .navbar-inverse .btn-link:focus,fieldset[disabled] .navbar-inverse .btn-link:hover{color:#444}.breadcrumb{padding:8px 15px;margin-bottom:20px;list-

style:none;background-color:#f5f5f5;border-radius:4px}.breadcrumb>li{display:inline-block}.breadcrumb>li+li:before{padding:0 5px;color:#ccc;content:"\00a0"}.breadcrumb>.active{color:#777}.pagination{display:inline-block;padding-left:0;margin:20px 0;border-radius:4px}.pagination>li{display:inline}.pagination>li>a,.pagination>li>span{position:relative;float:left;padding:6px 12px;margin-left:-1px;line-height:1.42857143;color:#337ab7;text-decoration:none;background-color:#fff;border:1px solid #ddd}.pagination>li:first-child>a,.pagination>li:first-child>span{margin-left:0;border-top-left-radius:4px;border-bottom-left-radius:4px}.pagination>li:last-child>a,.pagination>li:last-child>span{border-top-right-radius:4px;border-bottom-right-radius:4px}.pagination>li>a:focus,.pagination>li>a:hover,.pagination>li>span:focus,.pagination>li>span:hover{z-index:2;color:#23527c;background-color:#eee;border-color:#ddd}.pagination>.active>a,.pagination>.active>a:focus,.pagination>.active>a:hover,.pagination>.active>span,.pagination>.active>span:focus,.pagination>.active>span:hover{z-index:3;color:#fff;cursor:default;background-color:#337ab7;border-color:#337ab7}.pagination>.disabled>a,.pagination>.disabled>a:focus,.pagination>.disabled>a:hover,.pagination>.disabled>span,.pagination>.disabled>span:focus,.pagination>.disabled>span:hover{color:#777;cursor:not-allowed;background-color:#fff;border-color:#ddd}.pagination-lg>li>a,.pagination-lg>li>span{padding:10px 16px;font-size:18px;line-height:1.3333333}.pagination-lg>li:first-child>a,.pagination-lg>li:first-child>span{border-top-left-radius:6px;border-bottom-left-radius:6px}.pagination-lg>li:last-child>a,.pagination-lg>li:last-child>span{border-top-right-radius:6px;border-bottom-right-radius:6px}.pagination-sm>li>a,.pagination-sm>li>span{padding:5px 10px;font-size:12px;line-height:1.5}.pagination-sm>li:first-child>a,.pagination-sm>li:first-child>span{border-top-left-radius:3px;border-bottom-left-radius:3px}.pagination-sm>li:last-child>a,.pagination-sm>li:last-child>span{border-top-right-radius:3px;border-bottom-right-radius:3px}.pager{padding-left:0;margin:20px 0;text-align:center;list-style:none}.pager li{display:inline}.pager li>a,.pager li>span{display:inline-block;padding:5px 14px;background-color:#fff;border:1px solid #ddd;border-radius:15px}.pager li>a:focus,.pager li>a:hover{text-decoration:none;background-color:#eee}.pager .next>a,.pager .next>span{float:right}.pager .previous>a,.pager .previous>span{float:left}.pager .disabled>a,.pager .disabled>a:focus,.pager .disabled>a:hover,.pager .disabled>span{color:#777;cursor:not-allowed;background-color:#fff}.label{display:inline;padding:.2em .6em .3em;font-size:75%;font-weight:700;line-height:1;color:#fff;text-align:center;white-space:nowrap;vertical-align:baseline;border-radius:.25em}.label:focus,.label:hover{color:#fff;text-decoration:none;cursor:pointer}.label.empty{display:none}.btn .label{position:relative;top:-1px}.label-default{background-color:#777}.label-default[href]:focus,.label-default[href]:hover{background-color:#5e5e5e}.label-primary{background-color:#337ab7}.label-primary[href]:focus,.label-primary[href]:hover{background-color:#286090}.label-success{background-color:#5cb85c}.label-success[href]:focus,.label-success[href]:hover{background-color:#449d44}.label-info{background-color:#5bc0de}.label-info[href]:focus,.label-info[href]:hover{background-color:#31b0d5}.label-warning{background-color:#f0ad4e}.label-warning[href]:focus,.label-warning[href]:hover{background-color:#ec971f}.label-danger{background-color:#d9534f}.label-danger[href]:focus,.label-danger[href]:hover{background-color:#c9302c}.badge{display:inline-block;min-width:10px;padding:3px 7px;font-size:12px;font-weight:700;line-height:1;color:#fff;text-align:center;white-space:nowrap;vertical-align:middle;background-color:#777;border-radius:10px}.badge.empty{display:none}.btn .badge{position:relative;top:-1px}.btn-group-xs>.btn .badge,.btn-xs .badge{top:0;padding:1px 5px}.a.badge:focus,.a.badge:hover{color:#fff;text-decoration:none;cursor:pointer}.list-group-item.active>.badge,.nav-pills>.active>a>.badge{color:#337ab7;background-color:#fff}.list-group-item>.badge{float:right}.list-group-item>.badge+.badge{margin-right:5px}.nav-pills>li>a>.badge{margin-left:3px}.jumbotron{padding-top:30px;padding-bottom:30px;margin-

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bottom:30px;color:inherit;background-color:#eee}.jumbotron
h1{color:inherit}.jumbotron
p{margin-bottom:15px;font-size:21px;font-
weight:200}.jumbotron>hr{border-top-color:#d5d5d5}.container
.jumbotron{padding-right:15px;padding-left:15px;border-radius:6px}.jumbotron
.container{max-
width:100%}@media screen and (min-width:768px){.jumbotron{padding-top:48px;padding-
bottom:48px}.container
.jumbotron,.container-fluid
.jumbotron{padding-right:60px;padding-
left:60px}.jumbotron
.h1,.jumbotron
h1{font-
size:63px}}.thumbnail{display:block;padding:4px;margin-bottom:20px;line-
height:1.42857143;background-color:#fff;border:1px solid #ddd;border-radius:4px;-webkit-
transition:border .2s ease-in-out;-o-transition:border .2s ease-in-out;transition:border .2s ease-in-
out}.thumbnail
a>img,.thumbnail>img{margin-right:auto;margin-
left:auto}a.thumbnail.active,a.thumbnail:focus,a.thumbnail:hover{border-color:#337ab7}.thumbnail
.caption{padding:9px;color:#333}.alert{padding:15px;margin-bottom:20px;border:1px solid
transparent;border-radius:4px}.alert
h4{margin-top:0;color:inherit}.alert
.alert-link{font-
weight:700}.alert>p,.alert>ul{margin-bottom:0}.alert>p+p{margin-top:5px}.alert-dismissible,.alert-
dismissible{padding-right:35px}.alert-dismissible
.close,.alert-dismissible
.close{position:relative;top:-2px;right:-21px;color:inherit}.alert-success{color:#3c763d;background-
color:#dff0d8;border-color:#d6e9c6}.alert-success
hr{border-top-color:#c9e2b3}.alert-success
.alert-
link{color:#2b542c}.alert-info{color:#31708f;background-color:#d9edf7;border-color:#bce8f1}.alert-
info
hr{border-top-color:#a6e1ec}.alert-info
.alert-link{color:#245269}.alert-
warning{color:#8a6d3b;background-color:#fcf8e3;border-color:#faebcc}.alert-warning
hr{border-
top-color:#f7e1b5}.alert-warning
.alert-link{color:#66512c}.alert-danger{color:#a94442;background-
color:#f2dede;border-color:#ebccd1}.alert-danger
hr{border-top-color:#e4b9c0}.alert-danger
.alert-
link{color:#843534}@-webkit-keyframes
progress-bar-stripes{from{background-position:40px
0}to{background-position:0
0}}@-o-keyframes
progress-bar-stripes{from{background-position:40px
0}to{background-position:0
0}}@keyframes
progress-bar-stripes{from{background-position:40px
0}to{background-position:0
0}}.progress{height:20px;margin-
bottom:20px;overflow:hidden;background-color:#f5f5f5;border-radius:4px;-webkit-box-
shadow:inset 0 1px 2px rgba(0,0,0,.1);box-shadow:inset 0 1px 2px rgba(0,0,0,.1)}.progress-
bar{float:left;width:0;height:100%;font-size:12px;line-height:20px;color:#fff;text-
align:center;background-color:#337ab7;-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 -1px 0 rgba(0,0,0,.15);box-
shadow:inset 0 -1px 0 rgba(0,0,0,.15);-webkit-transition:width .6s ease;-o-transition:width .6s
ease;transition:width .6s ease}.progress-bar-striped,.progress-striped
.progress-bar{background-
image:-webkit-linear-gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 25%,transparent 25%,transparent
50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 75%,transparent
75%,transparent);background-image:-o-linear-gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
75%,transparent 75%,transparent);background-image:linear-gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
75%,transparent 75%,transparent);background-image:linear-gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
75%,transparent 75%,transparent)}-webkit-background-size:40px 40px;background-size:40px
40px}.progress-bar.active,.progress.active
.progress-bar{-webkit-animation:progress-bar-stripes 2s
linear infinite;-o-animation:progress-bar-stripes 2s linear infinite;animation:progress-bar-stripes 2s
linear infinite}.progress-bar-success{background-color:#5cb85c}.progress-striped
.progress-bar-
success{background-image:-webkit-linear-gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 25%,transparent
25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 75%,transparent
75%,transparent);background-image:-o-linear-gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
75%,transparent 75%,transparent);background-image:linear-gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
75%,transparent 75%,transparent)}-webkit-background-size:40px 40px;background-size:40px
40px}.progress-bar-info{background-color:#5bc0de}.progress-striped
.progress-bar-
info{background-image:-webkit-linear-gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15)

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25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
75%,transparent 75%,transparent);background-image:-o-linear-
gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 75%,transparent 75%,transparent);background-image:linear-
gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 75%,transparent 75%,transparent)}.progress-bar-warning{background-
color:#f0ad4e}.progress-striped .progress-bar-warning{background-image:-webkit-linear-
gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 75%,transparent 75%,transparent);background-image:-o-linear-
gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 75%,transparent 75%,transparent);background-image:linear-
gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 75%,transparent 75%,transparent)}.progress-bar-danger{background-
color:#d9534f}.progress-striped .progress-bar-danger{background-image:-webkit-linear-
gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 75%,transparent 75%,transparent);background-image:-o-linear-
gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 75%,transparent 75%,transparent);background-image:linear-
gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15)
50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 75%,transparent 75%,transparent)}.media{margin-top:15px}.media:first-
child{margin-top:0}.media,.media-body{overflow:hidden;zoom:1}.media-
body{width:1000px}.media-object{display:block}.media-object.img-thumbnail{max-
width:none}.media-right,.media>.pull-right{padding-left:10px}.media-left,.media>.pull-left{padding-
right:10px}.media-body,.media-left,.media-right{display:table-cell;vertical-align:top}.media-
middle{vertical-align:middle}.media-bottom{vertical-align:bottom}.media-heading{margin-
top:0;margin-bottom:5px}.media-list{padding-left:0;list-style:none}.list-group{padding-left:0;margin-
bottom:20px}.list-group-item{position:relative;display:block;padding:10px 15px;margin-bottom:-
1px;background-color:#fff;border:1px solid #ddd}.list-group-item:first-child{border-top-left-
radius:4px;border-top-right-radius:4px}.list-group-item:last-child{margin-bottom:0;border-bottom-
right-radius:4px;border-bottom-left-radius:4px}.list-group-item>a.list-group-item-
item{color:#555}.list-group-item .list-group-item-heading,button.list-group-item .list-group-item-
heading{color:#333}.list-group-item:focus,.list-group-item:hover,button.list-group-
item:focus,button.list-group-item:hover{color:#555;text-decoration:none;background-
color:#f5f5f5}button.list-group-item{width:100%;text-align:left}.list-group-item.disabled,.list-group-
item.disabled:focus,.list-group-item.disabled:hover{color:#777;cursor:not-allowed;background-
color:#eee}.list-group-item.disabled .list-group-item-heading,.list-group-item.disabled:focus .list-
group-item-heading,.list-group-item.disabled:hover .list-group-item-heading{color:inherit}.list-
group-item.disabled .list-group-item-text,.list-group-item.disabled:focus .list-group-item-text,.list-
group-item.disabled:hover .list-group-item-text{color:#777}.list-group-item.active,.list-group-
item.active:focus,.list-group-item.active:hover{z-index:2;color:#fff;background-
color:#337ab7;border-color:#337ab7}.list-group-item.active .list-group-item-heading,.list-group-
item.active .list-group-item-heading>small,.list-group-item.active .list-group-item-
heading>small,.list-group-item.active:focus .list-group-item-heading,.list-group-item.active:focus
.list-group-item-heading>small,.list-group-item.active:focus .list-group-item-heading>small,.list-
group-item.active:hover .list-group-item-heading,.list-group-item.active:hover .list-group-item-
heading>small,.list-group-item.active:hover .list-group-item-heading>small{color:inherit}.list-group-
item.active .list-group-item-text,.list-group-item.active:focus .list-group-item-text,.list-group-
item.active:hover .list-group-item-text{color:#c7ddef}.list-group-item-
success{color:#3c763d;background-color:#dff0d8}.list-group-item-success,button.list-group-item-
success{color:#3c763d}.list-group-item-success .list-group-item-heading,button.list-group-item-
success .list-group-item-heading{color:inherit}.list-group-item-success:focus,.list-group-item-

success:hover,button.list-group-item-success:focus,button.list-group-item-success:hover{color:#3c763d;background-color:#d0e9c6}a.list-group-item-success.active,a.list-group-item-success.active:focus,a.list-group-item-success.active:hover,button.list-group-item-success.active,button.list-group-item-success.active:focus,button.list-group-item-success.active:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#3c763d;border-color:#3c763d}.list-group-item-info{color:#31708f;background-color:#d9edf7}a.list-group-item-info,button.list-group-item-info{color:#31708f}a.list-group-item-info .list-group-item-heading,button.list-group-item-info .list-group-item-heading{color:inherit}a.list-group-item-info:focus,a.list-group-item-info:hover,button.list-group-item-info:focus,button.list-group-item-info:hover{color:#31708f;background-color:#c4e3f3}a.list-group-item-info.active,a.list-group-item-info.active:focus,a.list-group-item-info.active:hover,button.list-group-item-info.active,button.list-group-item-info.active:focus,button.list-group-item-info.active:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#31708f;border-color:#31708f}.list-group-item-warning{color:#8a6d3b;background-color:#fcf8e3}a.list-group-item-warning,button.list-group-item-warning{color:#8a6d3b}a.list-group-item-warning .list-group-item-heading,button.list-group-item-warning .list-group-item-heading{color:inherit}a.list-group-item-warning:focus,a.list-group-item-warning:hover,button.list-group-item-warning:focus,button.list-group-item-warning:hover{color:#8a6d3b;background-color:#faf2cc}a.list-group-item-warning.active,a.list-group-item-warning.active:focus,a.list-group-item-warning.active:hover,button.list-group-item-warning.active,button.list-group-item-warning.active:focus,button.list-group-item-warning.active:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#8a6d3b;border-color:#8a6d3b}.list-group-item-danger{color:#a94442;background-color:#f2dede}a.list-group-item-danger,button.list-group-item-danger{color:#a94442}a.list-group-item-danger .list-group-item-heading,button.list-group-item-danger .list-group-item-heading{color:inherit}a.list-group-item-danger:focus,a.list-group-item-danger:hover,button.list-group-item-danger:focus,button.list-group-item-danger:hover{color:#a94442;background-color:#ebcccc}a.list-group-item-danger.active,a.list-group-item-danger.active:focus,a.list-group-item-danger.active:hover,button.list-group-item-danger.active,button.list-group-item-danger.active:focus,button.list-group-item-danger.active:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#a94442;border-color:#a94442}.list-group-item-heading{margin-top:0;margin-bottom:5px}.list-group-item-text{margin-bottom:0;line-height:1.3}.panel{margin-bottom:20px;background-color:#fff;border:1px solid transparent;border-radius:4px;-webkit-box-shadow:0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.05);box-shadow:0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.05)}.panel-body{padding:15px}.panel-heading{padding:10px 15px;border-bottom:1px solid transparent;border-top-left-radius:3px;border-top-right-radius:3px}.panel-heading>.dropdown .dropdown-toggle{color:inherit}.panel-title{margin-top:0;margin-bottom:0;font-size:16px;color:inherit}.panel-title>.small,.panel-title>.small>a,.panel-title>a,.panel-title>small,.panel-title>small>a{color:inherit}.panel-footer{padding:10px 15px;background-color:#f5f5f5;border-top:1px solid #ddd;border-bottom-right-radius:3px;border-bottom-left-radius:3px}.panel>.list-group,.panel>.panel-collapse>.list-group{margin-bottom:0}.panel>.list-group .list-group-item,.panel>.panel-collapse>.list-group .list-group-item{border-width:1px 0;border-radius:0}.panel>.list-group:first-child .list-group-item:first-child,.panel>.panel-collapse>.list-group:first-child .list-group-item:first-child{border-top:0;border-top-left-radius:3px;border-top-right-radius:3px}.panel>.list-group:last-child .list-group-item:last-child,.panel>.panel-collapse>.list-group:last-child .list-group-item:last-child{border-bottom:0;border-bottom-right-radius:3px;border-bottom-left-radius:3px}.panel>.panel-heading+.panel-collapse>.list-group .list-group-item:first-child{border-top-left-radius:0;border-top-right-radius:0}.panel-heading+.list-group .list-group-item:first-child{border-top-width:0}.list-group+.panel-footer{border-top-width:0}.panel>.panel-collapse>.table,.panel>.table,.panel>.table-responsive>.table{margin-bottom:0}.panel>.panel-collapse>.table caption,.panel>.table caption,.panel>.table-responsive>.table caption{padding-right:15px;padding-left:15px}.panel>.table-responsive:first-child>.table:first-child,.panel>.table:first-child{border-top-left-radius:3px;border-top-right-radius:3px}.panel>.table-responsive:first-

child>.table:first-child>tbody:first-child>tr:first-child,.panel>.table-responsive:first-child>.table:first-child>thead:first-child>tr:first-child,.panel>.table:first-child>tbody:first-child>tr:first-child,.panel>.table-responsive:first-child>.table:first-child>tbody:first-child>tr:first-child

bordered>tbody>tr>td:last-child,.panel>.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tbody>tr>th:last-child,.panel>.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tfoot>tr>td:last-child,.panel>.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tfoot>tr>th:last-child,.panel>.table-responsive>.table-bordered>thead>tr>td:last-child,.panel>.table-responsive>.table-bordered>thead>tr>th:last-child{border-right:0}.panel>.table-bordered>tbody>tr:first-child>td,.panel>.table-bordered>tbody>tr:first-child>th,.panel>.table-bordered>thead>tr:first-child>td,.panel>.table-bordered>thead>tr:first-child>th,.panel>.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tbody>tr:first-child>td,.panel>.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tbody>tr:first-child>th,.panel>.table-responsive>.table-bordered>thead>tr:first-child>td,.panel>.table-responsive>.table-bordered>thead>tr:first-child>th{border-bottom:0}.panel>.table-bordered>tbody>tr:last-child>td,.panel>.table-bordered>tbody>tr:last-child>th,.panel>.table-bordered>tfoot>tr:last-child>td,.panel>.table-bordered>tfoot>tr:last-child>th,.panel>.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tbody>tr:last-child>td,.panel>.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tbody>tr:last-child>th,.panel>.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tfoot>tr:last-child>td,.panel>.table-responsive>.table-bordered>tfoot>tr:last-child>th{border-bottom:0}.panel>.table-responsive{margin-bottom:0;border:0}.panel-group{margin-bottom:20px}.panel-group .panel{margin-bottom:0;border-radius:4px}.panel-group .panel+.panel{margin-top:5px}.panel-group .panel-heading{border-bottom:0}.panel-group .panel-heading+.panel-collapse>.list-group,.panel-group .panel-heading+.panel-collapse>.panel-body{border-top:1px solid #ddd}.panel-group .panel-footer{border-top:0}.panel-group .panel-footer+.panel-collapse .panel-body{border-bottom:1px solid #ddd}.panel-default{border-color:#ddd}.panel-default>.panel-heading{color:#333;background-color:#f5f5f5;border-color:#ddd}.panel-default>.panel-heading+.panel-collapse>.panel-body{border-top-color:#ddd}.panel-default>.panel-heading .badge{color:#f5f5f5;background-color:#333}.panel-default>.panel-footer+.panel-collapse>.panel-body{border-bottom-color:#ddd}.panel-primary{border-color:#337ab7}.panel-primary>.panel-heading{color:#fff;background-color:#337ab7;border-color:#337ab7}.panel-primary>.panel-heading+.panel-collapse>.panel-body{border-top-color:#337ab7}.panel-primary>.panel-heading .badge{color:#337ab7;background-color:#fff}.panel-primary>.panel-footer+.panel-collapse>.panel-body{border-bottom-color:#337ab7}.panel-success{border-color:#d6e9c6}.panel-success>.panel-heading{color:#3c763d;background-color:#dff0d8;border-color:#d6e9c6}.panel-success>.panel-heading+.panel-collapse>.panel-body{border-top-color:#d6e9c6}.panel-success>.panel-heading .badge{color:#dff0d8;background-color:#3c763d}.panel-success>.panel-footer+.panel-collapse>.panel-body{border-bottom-color:#d6e9c6}.panel-info{border-color:#bce8f1}.panel-info>.panel-heading{color:#31708f;background-color:#d9edf7;border-color:#bce8f1}.panel-info>.panel-heading+.panel-collapse>.panel-body{border-top-color:#bce8f1}.panel-info>.panel-heading .badge{color:#d9edf7;background-color:#31708f}.panel-info>.panel-footer+.panel-collapse>.panel-body{border-bottom-color:#bce8f1}.panel-warning{border-color:#faebcc}.panel-warning>.panel-heading{color:#8a6d3b;background-color:#fcf8e3;border-color:#faebcc}.panel-warning>.panel-heading+.panel-collapse>.panel-body{border-top-color:#faebcc}.panel-warning>.panel-heading .badge{color:#fcf8e3;background-color:#8a6d3b}.panel-warning>.panel-footer+.panel-collapse>.panel-body{border-bottom-color:#faebcc}.panel-danger{border-color:#ebccd1}.panel-danger>.panel-heading{color:#a94442;background-color:#f2dede;border-color:#ebccd1}.panel-danger>.panel-heading+.panel-collapse>.panel-body{border-top-color:#ebccd1}.panel-danger>.panel-heading .badge{color:#f2dede;background-color:#a94442}.panel-danger>.panel-footer+.panel-collapse>.panel-body{border-bottom-color:#ebccd1}.embed-responsive{position:relative;display:block;height:0;padding:0;overflow:hidden}.embed-responsive .embed-responsive-item,.embed-responsive embed,.embed-responsive iframe,.embed-responsive object,.embed-responsive video{position:absolute;top:0;bottom:0;left:0;right:0;width:100%;height:100%;border:0}.embed-responsive-16by9{padding-bottom:56.25%}.embed-responsive-4by3{padding-

bottom:75%}.well{min-height:20px;padding:19px;margin-bottom:20px;background-color:#f5f5f5;border:1px solid #e3e3e3;border-radius:4px;-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.05);box-shadow:inset 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.05)}.well blockquote{border-color:#ddd;border-color:rgba(0,0,0,.15)}.well-lg{padding:24px;border-radius:6px}.well-sm{padding:9px;border-radius:3px}.close{float:right;font-size:21px;font-weight:700;line-height:1;color:#000;text-shadow:0 1px 0 #fff;filter:alpha(opacity=20);opacity:.2}.close:focus,.close:hover{color:#000;text-decoration:none;cursor:pointer;filter:alpha(opacity=50);opacity:.5}button.close{-webkit-appearance:none;padding:0;cursor:pointer;background:0 0 0 0;border:0}.modal-open{overflow:hidden}.modal{position:fixed;top:0;right:0;bottom:0;left:0;z-index:1050;display:none;overflow:hidden;-webkit-overflow-scrolling:touch;outline:0}.modal.fade .modal-dialog{-webkit-transition:-webkit-transform .3s ease-out;-o-transition:-o-transform .3s ease-out;transition:transform .3s ease-out;-webkit-transform:translate(0,-25%);-ms-transform:translate(0,-25%);-o-transform:translate(0,-25%);transform:translate(0,-25%)}.modal.in .modal-dialog{-webkit-transform:translate(0,0);-ms-transform:translate(0,0);-o-transform:translate(0,0);transform:translate(0,0)}.modal-open .modal{overflow-x:hidden;overflow-y:auto}.modal-dialog{position:relative;width:auto;margin:10px}.modal-content{position:relative;background-color:#fff;-webkit-background-clip:padding-box;background-clip:padding-box;border:1px solid #999;border:1px solid rgba(0,0,0,.2);border-radius:6px;outline:0;-webkit-box-shadow:0 3px 9px rgba(0,0,0,.5);box-shadow:0 3px 9px rgba(0,0,0,.5)}.modal-backdrop{position:fixed;top:0;right:0;bottom:0;left:0;z-index:1040;background-color:#000}.modal-backdrop.fade{filter:alpha(opacity=0);opacity:0}.modal-backdrop.in{filter:alpha(opacity=50);opacity:.5}.modal-header{padding:15px;border-bottom:1px solid #e5e5e5}.modal-header .close{margin-top:-2px}.modal-title{margin:0;line-height:1.42857143}.modal-body{position:relative;padding:15px}.modal-footer{padding:15px;text-align:right;border-top:1px solid #e5e5e5}.modal-footer .btn+.btn{margin-bottom:0;margin-left:5px}.modal-footer .btn-group .btn+.btn{margin-left:-1px}.modal-footer .btn-block+.btn-block{margin-left:0}.modal-scrollbar-measure{position:absolute;top:-9999px;width:50px;height:50px;overflow:scroll}@media (min-width:768px){.modal-dialog{width:600px;margin:30px auto}.modal-content{-webkit-box-shadow:0 5px 15px rgba(0,0,0,.5);box-shadow:0 5px 15px rgba(0,0,0,.5)}.modal-sm{width:300px}}@media (min-width:992px){.modal-lg{width:900px}}.tooltip{position:absolute;z-index:1070;display:block;font-family:"Helvetica Neue",Helvetica,Arial,sans-serif;font-size:12px;font-style:normal;font-weight:400;line-height:1.42857143;text-align:left;text-align:start;text-decoration:none;text-shadow:none;text-transform:none;letter-spacing:normal;word-break:normal;word-spacing:normal;word-wrap:normal;white-space:normal;filter:alpha(opacity=0);opacity:0;line-break:auto}.tooltip.in{filter:alpha(opacity=90);opacity:.9}.tooltip.top{padding:5px 0;margin-top:-3px}.tooltip.right{padding:0 5px;margin-left:3px}.tooltip.bottom{padding:5px 0;margin-top:3px}.tooltip.left{padding:0 5px;margin-left:-3px}.tooltip-inner{max-width:200px;padding:3px 8px;color:#fff;text-align:center;background-color:#000;border-radius:4px}.tooltip-arrow{position:absolute;width:0;height:0;border-color:transparent;border-style:solid}.tooltip.top .tooltip-arrow{bottom:0;left:50%;margin-left:-5px;border-width:5px 5px 0;border-top-color:#000}.tooltip.top-left .tooltip-arrow{right:5px;bottom:0;margin-bottom:-5px;border-width:5px 5px 0;border-top-color:#000}.tooltip.top-right .tooltip-arrow{bottom:0;left:5px;margin-bottom:-5px;border-width:5px 5px 0;border-top-color:#000}.tooltip.right .tooltip-arrow{top:50%;left:0;margin-top:-5px;border-width:5px 5px 5px 0;border-right-color:#000}.tooltip.left .tooltip-arrow{top:50%;right:0;margin-top:-5px;border-width:5px 0 5px 5px;border-left-color:#000}.tooltip.bottom .tooltip-arrow{top:0;left:50%;margin-left:-5px;border-width:0 5px 5px 5px;border-bottom-color:#000}.tooltip.bottom-left .tooltip-arrow{top:0;right:5px;margin-top:-5px;border-width:0 5px 5px 5px;border-bottom-color:#000}.tooltip.bottom-right .tooltip-arrow{top:0;left:5px;margin-top:-5px;border-width:0 5px

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5px;border-bottom-color:#000}.popover{position:absolute;top:0;left:0;z-
index:1060;display:none;max-width:276px;padding:1px;font-family:"Helvetica
Neue",Helvetica,Arial,sans-serif;font-size:14px;font-style:normal;font-weight:400;line-
height:1.42857143;text-align:left;text-align:start;text-decoration:none;text-shadow:none;text-
transform:none;letter-spacing:normal;word-break:normal;word-spacing:normal;word-
wrap:normal;white-space:normal;background-color:#fff;-webkit-background-clip:padding-
box;background-clip:padding-box;border:1px solid #ccc;border:1px solid rgba(0,0,0,.2);border-
radius:6px;-webkit-box-shadow:0 5px 10px rgba(0,0,0,.2);box-shadow:0 5px 10px rgba(0,0,0,.2);line-
break:auto}.popover.top{margin-top:-10px}.popover.right{margin-
left:10px}.popover.bottom{margin-top:10px}.popover.left{margin-left:-10px}.popover-
title{padding:8px 14px;margin:0;font-size:14px;background-color:#f7f7f7;border-bottom:1px solid
#ebeb;border-radius:5px 5px 0 0}.popover-content{padding:9px
14px}.popover>.arrow,.popover>.arrow:after{position:absolute;display:block;width:0;height:0;borde
r-color:transparent;border-style:solid}.popover>.arrow{border-
width:11px}.popover>.arrow:after{content:"";border-width:10px}.popover.top>.arrow{bottom:-
11px;left:50%;margin-left:-11px;border-top-color:#999;border-top-color:rgba(0,0,0,.25);border-
bottom-width:0}.popover.top>.arrow:after{bottom:1px;margin-left:-10px;content:" ";border-top-
color:#fff;border-bottom-width:0}.popover.right>.arrow{top:50%;left:-11px;margin-top:-
11px;border-right-color:#999;border-right-color:rgba(0,0,0,.25);border-left-
width:0}.popover.right>.arrow:after{bottom:-10px;left:1px;content:" ";border-right-
color:#fff;border-left-width:0}.popover.bottom>.arrow{top:-11px;left:50%;margin-left:-11px;border-
top-width:0;border-bottom-color:#999;border-bottom-
color:rgba(0,0,0,.25)}.popover.bottom>.arrow:after{top:1px;margin-left:-10px;content:" ";border-
top-width:0;border-bottom-color:#fff}.popover.left>.arrow{top:50%;right:-11px;margin-top:-
11px;border-right-width:0;border-left-color:#999;border-left-
color:rgba(0,0,0,.25)}.popover.left>.arrow:after{right:1px;bottom:-10px;content:" ";border-right-
width:0;border-left-color:#fff}.carousel{position:relative}.carousel-
inner{position:relative;width:100%;overflow:hidden}.carousel-
inner>.item{position:relative;display:none;-webkit-transition:.6s ease-in-out left;-o-transition:.6s
ease-in-out left;transition:.6s ease-in-out left}.carousel-inner>.item>a>img,.carousel-
inner>.item>img{line-height:1}@media all and (transform-3d),(-webkit-transform-3d){.carousel-
inner>.item{-webkit-transition:-webkit-transform .6s ease-in-out;-o-transition:-o-transform .6s ease-
in-out;transition:transform .6s ease-in-out;-webkit-backface-visibility:hidden;backface-
visibility:hidden;-webkit-perspective:1000px;perspective:1000px}.carousel-
inner>.item.active.right,.carousel-inner>.item.next{left:0;-webkit-
transform:translate3d(100%,0,0);transform:translate3d(100%,0,0)}.carousel-
inner>.item.active.left,.carousel-inner>.item.prev{left:0;-webkit-transform:translate3d(-
100%,0,0);transform:translate3d(-100%,0,0)}.carousel-inner>.item.active,.carousel-
inner>.item.next.left,.carousel-inner>.item.prev.right{left:0;-webkit-
transform:translate3d(0,0,0);transform:translate3d(0,0,0)}.carousel-inner>.active,.carousel-
inner>.next,.carousel-inner>.prev{display:block}.carousel-inner>.active{left:0}.carousel-
inner>.next,.carousel-inner>.prev{position:absolute;top:0;width:100%}.carousel-
inner>.next{left:100%}.carousel-inner>.prev{left:-100%}.carousel-inner>.next.left,.carousel-
inner>.prev.right{left:0}.carousel-inner>.active.left{left:-100%}.carousel-
inner>.active.right{left:100%}.carousel-
control{position:absolute;top:0;bottom:0;left:0;width:15%;font-size:20px;color:#fff;text-
align:center;text-shadow:0 1px 2px rgba(0,0,0,.6);background-
color:rgba(0,0,0,0);filter:alpha(opacity=50);opacity:.5}.carousel-control.left{background-image:-
webkit-linear-gradient(left,rgba(0,0,0,.5) 0,rgba(0,0,0,.0001) 100%);background-image:-o-linear-
gradient(left,rgba(0,0,0,.5) 0,rgba(0,0,0,.0001) 100%);background-image:-webkit-gradient(linear,left
top,right top,from(rgba(0,0,0,.5)),to(rgba(0,0,0,.0001)));background-image:linear-gradient(to
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right,rgba(0,0,0,.5) 0,rgba(0,0,0,.0001)
100%);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#80000000',
endColorstr='#00000000', GradientType=1);background-repeat:repeat-x}.carousel-
control.right{right:0;left:auto;background-image:-webkit-linear-gradient(left,rgba(0,0,0,.0001)
0,rgba(0,0,0,.5) 100%);background-image:-o-linear-gradient(left,rgba(0,0,0,.0001) 0,rgba(0,0,0,.5)
100%);background-image:-webkit-gradient(linear,left top,right
top,from(rgba(0,0,0,.0001)),to(rgba(0,0,0,.5)));background-image:linear-gradient(to
right,rgba(0,0,0,.0001) 0,rgba(0,0,0,.5)
100%);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#00000000',
endColorstr='#80000000', GradientType=1);background-repeat:repeat-x}.carousel-
control:focus,.carousel-control:hover{color:#fff;text-
decoration:none;filter:alpha(opacity=90);outline:0;opacity:.9}.carousel-control .glyphicon-chevron-
left,.carousel-control .glyphicon-chevron-right,.carousel-control .icon-next,.carousel-control .icon-
prev{position:absolute;top:50%;z-index:5;display:inline-block;margin-top:-10px}.carousel-control
.glyphicon-chevron-left,.carousel-control .icon-prev{left:50%;margin-left:-10px}.carousel-control
.glyphicon-chevron-right,.carousel-control .icon-next{right:50%;margin-right:-10px}.carousel-control
.icon-next,.carousel-control .icon-prev{width:20px;height:20px;font-family:serif;line-
height:1}.carousel-control .icon-prev:before{content:'\2039'}.carousel-control .icon-
next:before{content:'\203a'}.carousel-indicators{position:absolute;bottom:10px;left:50%;z-
index:15;width:60%;padding-left:0;margin-left:-30%;text-align:center;list-style:none}.carousel-
indicators li{display:inline-block;width:10px;height:10px;margin:1px;text-indent:-
999px;cursor:pointer;background-color:#000\9;background-color:rgba(0,0,0,0);border:1px solid
#fff;border-radius:10px}.carousel-indicators .active{width:12px;height:12px;margin:0;background-
color:#fff}.carousel-caption{position:absolute;right:15%;bottom:20px;left:15%;z-index:10;padding-
top:20px;padding-bottom:20px;color:#fff;text-align:center;text-shadow:0 1px 2px
rgba(0,0,0,.6)}.carousel-caption .btn{text-shadow:none}@media screen and (min-
width:768px){.carousel-control .glyphicon-chevron-left,.carousel-control .glyphicon-chevron-
right,.carousel-control .icon-next,.carousel-control .icon-prev{width:30px;height:30px;margin-top:-
10px;font-size:30px}.carousel-control .glyphicon-chevron-left,.carousel-control .icon-prev{margin-
left:-10px}.carousel-control .glyphicon-chevron-right,.carousel-control .icon-next{margin-right:-
10px}.carousel-caption{right:20%;left:20%;padding-bottom:30px}.carousel-
indicators{bottom:20px}}.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group:after,.btn-group-vertical>.btn-
group:before,.btn-toolbar:after,.btn-toolbar:before,.clearfix:after,.clearfix:before,.container-
fluid:after,.container-fluid:before,.container:after,.container:before,.dl-horizontal
dd:after,.dl-
horizontal dd:before,.form-horizontal .form-group:after,.form-horizontal
.form-
group:before,.modal-footer:after,.modal-footer:before,.modal-header:after,.modal-
header:before,.nav:after,.nav:before,.navbar-collapse:after,.navbar-collapse:before,.navbar-
header:after,.navbar-header:before,.navbar:after,.navbar:before,.pager:after,.pager:before,.panel-
body:after,.panel-body:before,.row:after,.row:before{display:table;content:"
"}.btn-group-
vertical>.btn-group:after,.btn-toolbar:after,.clearfix:after,.container-fluid:after,.container:after,.dl-
horizontal
dd:after,.form-horizontal
.form-
group:after,.modal-footer:after,.modal-
header:after,.nav:after,.navbar-collapse:after,.navbar-header:after,.navbar:after,.pager:after,.panel-
body:after,.row:after{clear:both}.center-block{display:block;margin-right:auto;margin-
left:auto}.pull-right{float:right!important}.pull-
left{float:left!important}.hide{display:none!important}.show{display:block!important}.invisible{visibi-
lity:hidden}.text-hide{font:0/0
a;color:transparent;text-shadow:none;background-
color:transparent;border:0}.hidden{display:none!important}.affix{position:fixed}@-ms-
viewport{width:device-width}.visible-lg,.visible-md,.visible-sm,.visible-
xs{display:none!important}.visible-lg-block,.visible-lg-inline,.visible-lg-inline-block,.visible-md-
block,.visible-md-inline,.visible-md-inline-block,.visible-sm-block,.visible-sm-inline,.visible-sm-inline-
block,.visible-xs-block,.visible-xs-inline,.visible-xs-inline-block{display:none!important}@media (max-
```

```

width:767px){.visible-xs{display:block!important}table.visible-xs{display:table!important}tr.visible-
xs{display:table-row!important}td.visible-xs,th.visible-xs{display:table-cell!important}}@media (max-
width:767px){.visible-xs-block{display:block!important}}@media (max-width:767px){.visible-xs-
inline{display:inline!important}}@media (max-width:767px){.visible-xs-inline-block{display:inline-
block!important}}@media (min-width:768px) and (max-width:991px){.visible-
sm{display:block!important}table.visible-sm{display:table!important}tr.visible-sm{display:table-
row!important}td.visible-sm,th.visible-sm{display:table-cell!important}}@media (min-width:768px)
and (max-width:991px){.visible-sm-block{display:block!important}}@media (min-width:768px) and
(max-width:991px){.visible-sm-inline{display:inline!important}}@media (min-width:768px) and
(max-width:991px){.visible-sm-inline-block{display:inline-block!important}}@media (min-
width:992px) and (max-width:1199px){.visible-md{display:block!important}table.visible-
md{display:table!important}tr.visible-md{display:table-row!important}td.visible-md,th.visible-
md{display:table-cell!important}}@media (min-width:992px) and (max-width:1199px){.visible-md-
block{display:block!important}}@media (min-width:992px) and (max-width:1199px){.visible-md-
inline{display:inline!important}}@media (min-width:992px) and (max-width:1199px){.visible-md-
inline-block{display:inline-block!important}}@media (min-width:1200px){.visible-
lg{display:block!important}table.visible-lg{display:table!important}tr.visible-lg{display:table-
row!important}td.visible-lg,th.visible-lg{display:table-cell!important}}@media (min-
width:1200px){.visible-lg-block{display:block!important}}@media (min-width:1200px){.visible-lg-
inline{display:inline!important}}@media (min-width:1200px){.visible-lg-inline-block{display:inline-
block!important}}@media (max-width:767px){.hidden-xs{display:none!important}}@media (min-
width:768px) and (max-width:991px){.hidden-sm{display:none!important}}@media (min-
width:992px) and (max-width:1199px){.hidden-md{display:none!important}}@media (min-
width:1200px){.hidden-lg{display:none!important}}.visible-print{display:none!important}@media
print{.visible-print{display:block!important}table.visible-print{display:table!important}tr.visible-
print{display:table-row!important}td.visible-print,th.visible-print{display:table-
cell!important}}.visible-print-block{display:none!important}@media print{.visible-print-
block{display:block!important}}.visible-print-inline{display:none!important}@media print{.visible-
print-inline{display:inline!important}}.visible-print-inline-block{display:none!important}@media
print{.visible-print-inline-block{display:inline-block!important}}@media print{.hidden-
print{display:none!important}}
/*# sourceMappingURL=bootstrap.min.css.map */

```

Script bootstrap4.min

```

/*!
* Bootstrap v4.0.0 (https://getbootstrap.com)
* Copyright 2011-2018 The Bootstrap Authors
* Copyright 2011-2018 Twitter, Inc.
* Licensed under MIT (https://github.com/twbs/bootstrap/blob/master/LICENSE)
*/:root{--blue:#007bff;--indigo:#6610f2;--purple:#6f42c1;--pink:#e83e8c;--red:#dc3545;--
orange:#fd7e14;--yellow:#ffc107;--green:#28a745;--teal:#20c997;--cyan:#17a2b8;--white:#fff;--
gray:#6c757d;--gray-dark:#343a40;--primary:#007bff;--secondary:#6c757d;--success:#28a745;--
info:#17a2b8;--warning:#ffc107;--danger:#dc3545;--light:#f8f9fa;--dark:#343a40;--breakpoint-xs:0;--
breakpoint-sm:576px;--breakpoint-md:768px;--breakpoint-lg:992px;--breakpoint-xl:1200px;--font-
family-sans-serif:-apple-system,BlinkMacSystemFont,"Segoe UI",Roboto,"Helvetica Neue",Arial,sans-
serif,"Apple Color Emoji","Segoe UI Emoji","Segoe UI Symbol";--font-family-monospace:SFMono-
Regular,Menlo,Monaco,Consolas,"Liberation Mono","Courier
New",monospace}*,:after,:before{box-sizing:border-box}html{font-family:sans-serif;line-
height:1.15;-webkit-text-size-adjust:100%;-ms-text-size-adjust:100%;-ms-overflow-style:scrollbar;-
webkit-tap-highlight-color:transparent}@-ms-viewpoint{width:device-

```

width}article,aside,dialog,figcaption,figure,footer,header,hgroup,main,nav,section{display:block}body{margin:0;font-family:-apple-system,BlinkMacSystemFont,"Segoe UI",Roboto,"Helvetica Neue",Arial,sans-serif,"Apple Color Emoji","Segoe UI Emoji","Segoe UI Symbol";font-size:1rem;font-weight:400;line-height:1.5;color:#212529;text-align:left;background-color:#fff}[tabindex="-1"]:focus{outline:0!important}hr{box-sizing:content-box;height:0;overflow:visible}h1,h2,h3,h4,h5,h6{margin-top:0;margin-bottom:.5rem}p{margin-top:0;margin-bottom:1rem}abbr[data-original-title],abbr[title]{text-decoration:underline;-webkit-text-decoration:underline dotted;text-decoration:underline dotted;cursor:help;border-bottom:0}address{margin-bottom:1rem;font-style:normal;line-height:inherit}dl,ol,ul{margin-top:0;margin-bottom:1rem}ol ol,ol ul,ul ol,ul ul{margin-bottom:0}dt{font-weight:700}dd{margin-bottom:.5rem;margin-left:0}blockquote{margin:0 0 1rem}dfn{font-style:italic}b,strong{font-weight:bolder}small{font-size:80%}sub,sup{position:relative;font-size:75%;line-height:0;vertical-align:baseline}sub{bottom:-.25em}sup{top:-.5em}a{color:#007bff;text-decoration:none;background-color:transparent;-webkit-text-decoration-skip:objects}a:hover{color:#0056b3;text-decoration:underline}a:not([href]):not([tabindex]){color:inherit;text-decoration:none}a:not([href]):not([tabindex]):focus,a:not([href]):not([tabindex]):hover{color:inherit;text-decoration:none}a:not([href]):not([tabindex]):focus{outline:0}code,kbd,pre,samp{font-family:monospace,monospace;font-size:1em}pre{margin-top:0;margin-bottom:1rem;overflow:auto;-ms-overflow-style:scrollbar}figure{margin:0 0 1rem}img{vertical-align:middle;border-style:none}svg:not(:root){overflow:hidden}table{border-collapse:collapse}caption{padding-top:.75rem;padding-bottom:.75rem;color:#6c757d;text-align:left;caption-side:bottom}th{text-align:inherit}label{display:inline-block;margin-bottom:.5rem}button{border-radius:0}button:focus{outline:1px dotted;outline:5px auto -webkit-focus-ring-color}button,input,optgroup,select,textarea{margin:0;font-family:inherit;font-size:inherit;line-height:inherit}button,input{overflow:visible}button,select{text-transform:none}[type=reset],[type=submit],button,html [type=button]{-webkit-appearance:button}[type=button]:::-moz-focus-inner,[type=reset]:::-moz-focus-inner,[type=submit]:::-moz-focus-inner,button:::-moz-focus-inner{padding:0;border-style:none}input[type=checkbox],input[type=radio]{box-sizing:border-box;padding:0}input[type=date],input[type=datetime-local],input[type=month],input[type=time]{-webkit-appearance:listbox}textarea{overflow:auto;resize:vertical}fieldset{min-width:0;padding:0;margin:0;border:0}legend{display:block;width:100%;max-width:100%;padding:0;margin-bottom:.5rem;font-size:1.5rem;line-height:inherit;color:inherit;white-space:normal}progress{vertical-align:baseline}[type=number]:::-webkit-inner-spin-button,[type=number]:::-webkit-outer-spin-button{height:auto}[type=search]{outline-offset:-2px;-webkit-appearance:none}[type=search]:::-webkit-search-cancel-button,[type=search]:::-webkit-search-decoration{-webkit-appearance:none}:::-webkit-file-upload-button{font:inherit;-webkit-appearance:button}output{display:inline-block}summary{display:list-item;cursor:pointer}template{display:none}[hidden]{display:none!important}.h1,.h2,.h3,.h4,.h5,.h6,.h1,h2,h3,h4,h5,h6{margin-bottom:.5rem;font-family:inherit;font-weight:500;line-height:1.2;color:inherit}.h1,h1{font-size:2.5rem}.h2,h2{font-size:2rem}.h3,h3{font-size:1.75rem}.h4,h4{font-size:1.5rem}.h5,h5{font-size:1.25rem}.h6,h6{font-size:1rem}.lead{font-size:1.25rem;font-weight:300}.display-1{font-size:6rem;font-weight:300;line-height:1.2}.display-2{font-size:5.5rem;font-weight:300;line-height:1.2}.display-3{font-size:4.5rem;font-weight:300;line-height:1.2}.display-4{font-size:3.5rem;font-weight:300;line-height:1.2}hr{margin-top:1rem;margin-bottom:1rem;border:0;border-top:1px solid rgba(0,0,0,.1)}.small,small{font-size:80%;font-weight:400}.mark,mark{padding:.2em;background-color:#fcf8e3}.list-unstyled{padding-left:0;list-style:none}.list-inline{padding-left:0;list-style:none}.list-inline-item{display:inline-block}.list-inline-item:not(:last-child){margin-right:.5rem}.initialism{font-size:90%;text-transform:uppercase}.blockquote{margin-bottom:1rem;font-size:1.25rem}.blockquote-footer{display:block;font-size:80%;color:#6c757d}.blockquote-footer::before{content:"\2014"}

\00A0").img-fluid{max-width:100%;height:auto}.img-thumbnail{padding:.25rem;background-color:#fff;border:1px solid #dee2e6;border-radius:.25rem;max-width:100%;height:auto}.figure{display:inline-block}.figure-img{margin-bottom:.5rem;line-height:1}.figure-caption{font-size:90%;color:#6c757d}code,kbd,pre,samp{font-family:SFMono-Regular,Menlo,Monaco,Consolas,"Liberation Mono","Courier New",monospace}code{font-size:87.5%;color:#e83e8c;word-break:break-word}a>code{color:inherit}kbd{padding:.2rem .4rem;font-size:87.5%;color:#fff;background-color:#212529;border-radius:.2rem}kbd kbd{padding:0;font-size:100%;font-weight:700}pre{display:block;font-size:87.5%;color:#212529}pre code{font-size:inherit;color:inherit;word-break:normal}.pre-scrollable{max-height:340px;overflow-y:scroll}.container{width:100%;padding-right:15px;padding-left:15px;margin-right:auto;margin-left:auto}@media (min-width:576px){.container{max-width:540px}}@media (min-width:768px){.container{max-width:720px}}@media (min-width:992px){.container{max-width:960px}}@media (min-width:1200px){.container{max-width:1140px}}.container-fluid{width:100%;padding-right:15px;padding-left:15px;margin-right:auto;margin-left:auto}.row{margin-right:-15px;margin-left:-15px}.no-gutters{margin-right:0;margin-left:0}.no-gutters>.col,.no-gutters>[class*=col-]{padding-right:0;padding-left:0}.col,.col-1,.col-10,.col-11,.col-12,.col-2,.col-3,.col-4,.col-5,.col-6,.col-7,.col-8,.col-9,.col-auto,.col-lg,.col-lg-1,.col-lg-10,.col-lg-11,.col-lg-12,.col-lg-2,.col-lg-3,.col-lg-4,.col-lg-5,.col-lg-6,.col-lg-7,.col-lg-8,.col-lg-9,.col-lg-auto,.col-md,.col-md-1,.col-md-10,.col-md-11,.col-md-12,.col-md-2,.col-md-3,.col-md-4,.col-md-5,.col-md-6,.col-md-7,.col-md-8,.col-md-9,.col-md-auto,.col-sm,.col-sm-1,.col-sm-10,.col-sm-11,.col-sm-12,.col-sm-2,.col-sm-3,.col-sm-4,.col-sm-5,.col-sm-6,.col-sm-7,.col-sm-8,.col-sm-9,.col-sm-auto,.col-xl,.col-xl-1,.col-xl-10,.col-xl-11,.col-xl-12,.col-xl-2,.col-xl-3,.col-xl-4,.col-xl-5,.col-xl-6,.col-xl-7,.col-xl-8,.col-xl-9,.col-xl-auto{position:relative;width:100%;min-height:1px;padding-right:15px;padding-left:15px}.col{-ms-flex-preferred-size:0;flex-basis:0;-webkit-box-flex:1;-ms-flex-positive:1;flex-grow:1;max-width:100%}.col-auto{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 auto;flex:0 0 auto;width:auto;max-width:none}.col-1{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 8.333333%;flex:0 0 8.333333%;max-width:8.333333%}.col-2{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 16.666667%;flex:0 0 16.666667%;max-width:16.666667%}.col-3{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 25%;flex:0 0 25%;max-width:25%}.col-4{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 33.333333%;flex:0 0 33.333333%;max-width:33.333333%}.col-5{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 41.666667%;flex:0 0 41.666667%;max-width:41.666667%}.col-6{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 50%;flex:0 0 50%;max-width:50%}.col-7{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 58.333333%;flex:0 0 58.333333%;max-width:58.333333%}.col-8{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 66.666667%;flex:0 0 66.666667%;max-width:66.666667%}.col-9{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 75%;flex:0 0 75%;max-width:75%}.col-10{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 83.333333%;flex:0 0 83.333333%;max-width:83.333333%}.col-11{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 91.666667%;flex:0 0 91.666667%;max-width:91.666667%}.col-12{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 100%;flex:0 0 100%;max-width:100%}.order-first{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:0;-ms-flex-order:-1;order:-1}.order-last{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:14;-ms-flex-order:13;order:13}.order-0{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:1;-ms-flex-order:0;order:0}.order-1{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:2;-ms-flex-order:1;order:1}.order-2{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:3;-ms-flex-order:2;order:2}.order-3{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:4;-ms-flex-order:3;order:3}.order-4{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:5;-ms-flex-order:4;order:4}.order-5{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:6;-ms-flex-order:5;order:5}.order-6{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:7;-ms-flex-order:6;order:6}.order-7{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:8;-ms-flex-order:7;order:7}.order-8{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:9;-ms-flex-order:8;order:8}.order-9{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:10;-ms-flex-order:9;order:9}.order-10{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:11;-ms-flex-order:10;order:10}.order-11{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:12;-ms-flex-order:11;order:11}.order-12{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:13;-ms-flex-order:12;order:12}.offset-1{margin-left:8.333333%}.offset-2{margin-left:16.666667%}.offset-3{margin-left:25%}.offset-4{margin-left:33.333333%}.offset-5{margin-left:41.666667%}.offset-6{margin-left:50%}.offset-7{margin-left:58.333333%}.offset-8{margin-left:66.666667%}.offset-9{margin-left:75%}.offset-10{margin-left:83.333333%}.offset-11{margin-left:91.666667%}@media (min-width:576px){.col-sm{-ms-flex-preferred-size:0;flex-basis:0;-webkit-

box-flex:1;-ms-flex-positive:1;flex-grow:1;max-width:100%}.col-sm-auto{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 auto;flex:0 0 auto;width:auto;max-width:none}.col-sm-1{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 8.333333%;flex:0 0 8.333333%;max-width:8.333333%}.col-sm-2{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 16.666667%;flex:0 0 16.666667%;max-width:16.666667%}.col-sm-3{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 25%;flex:0 0 25%;max-width:25%}.col-sm-4{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 33.333333%;flex:0 0 33.333333%;max-width:33.333333%}.col-sm-5{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 41.666667%;flex:0 0 41.666667%;max-width:41.666667%}.col-sm-6{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 50%;flex:0 0 50%;max-width:50%}.col-sm-7{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 58.333333%;flex:0 0 58.333333%;max-width:58.333333%}.col-sm-8{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 66.666667%;flex:0 0 66.666667%;max-width:66.666667%}.col-sm-9{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 75%;flex:0 0 75%;max-width:75%}.col-sm-10{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 83.333333%;flex:0 0 83.333333%;max-width:83.333333%}.col-sm-11{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 91.666667%;flex:0 0 91.666667%;max-width:91.666667%}.col-sm-12{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 100%;flex:0 0 100%;max-width:100%}.order-sm-first{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:0;-ms-flex-order:-1;order:-1}.order-sm-last{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:14;-ms-flex-order:13;order:13}.order-sm-0{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:1;-ms-flex-order:0;order:0}.order-sm-1{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:2;-ms-flex-order:1;order:1}.order-sm-2{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:3;-ms-flex-order:2;order:2}.order-sm-3{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:4;-ms-flex-order:3;order:3}.order-sm-4{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:5;-ms-flex-order:4;order:4}.order-sm-5{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:6;-ms-flex-order:5;order:5}.order-sm-6{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:7;-ms-flex-order:6;order:6}.order-sm-7{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:8;-ms-flex-order:7;order:7}.order-sm-8{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:9;-ms-flex-order:8;order:8}.order-sm-9{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:10;-ms-flex-order:9;order:9}.order-sm-10{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:11;-ms-flex-order:10;order:10}.order-sm-11{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:12;-ms-flex-order:11;order:11}.order-sm-12{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:13;-ms-flex-order:12;order:12}.offset-sm-0{margin-left:0}.offset-sm-1{margin-left:8.333333%}.offset-sm-2{margin-left:16.666667%}.offset-sm-3{margin-left:25%}.offset-sm-4{margin-left:33.333333%}.offset-sm-5{margin-left:41.666667%}.offset-sm-6{margin-left:50%}.offset-sm-7{margin-left:58.333333%}.offset-sm-8{margin-left:66.666667%}.offset-sm-9{margin-left:75%}.offset-sm-10{margin-left:83.333333%}.offset-sm-11{margin-left:91.666667%}}@media (min-width:768px){.col-md{-ms-flex-preferred-size:0;flex-basis:0;-webkit-box-flex:1;-ms-flex-positive:1;flex-grow:1;max-width:100%}.col-md-auto{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 auto;flex:0 0 auto;width:auto;max-width:none}.col-md-1{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 8.333333%;flex:0 0 8.333333%;max-width:8.333333%}.col-md-2{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 16.666667%;flex:0 0 16.666667%;max-width:16.666667%}.col-md-3{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 25%;flex:0 0 25%;max-width:25%}.col-md-4{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 33.333333%;flex:0 0 33.333333%;max-width:33.333333%}.col-md-5{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 41.666667%;flex:0 0 41.666667%;max-width:41.666667%}.col-md-6{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 50%;flex:0 0 50%;max-width:50%}.col-md-7{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 58.333333%;flex:0 0 58.333333%;max-width:58.333333%}.col-md-8{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 66.666667%;flex:0 0 66.666667%;max-width:66.666667%}.col-md-9{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 75%;flex:0 0 75%;max-width:75%}.col-md-10{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 83.333333%;flex:0 0 83.333333%;max-width:83.333333%}.col-md-11{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 91.666667%;flex:0 0 91.666667%;max-width:91.666667%}.col-md-12{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 100%;flex:0 0 100%;max-width:100%}.order-md-first{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:0;-ms-flex-order:-1;order:-1}.order-md-last{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:14;-ms-flex-order:13;order:13}.order-md-0{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:1;-ms-flex-order:0;order:0}.order-md-1{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:2;-ms-flex-order:1;order:1}.order-md-2{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:3;-ms-flex-order:2;order:2}.order-md-3{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:4;-ms-flex-order:3;order:3}.order-md-4{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:5;-ms-flex-order:4;order:4}.order-md-5{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:6;-ms-flex-order:5;order:5}.order-md-6{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:7;-ms-flex-order:6;order:6}.order-md-7{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:8;-ms-flex-order:7;order:7}.order-md-8{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:9;-ms-flex-order:8;order:8}.order-md-9{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:10;-ms-flex-order:9;order:9}.order-md-10{-

webkit-box-ordinal-group:11;-ms-flex-order:10;order:10}.order-md-11{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:12;-ms-flex-order:11;order:11}.order-md-12{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:13;-ms-flex-order:12;order:12}.offset-md-0{margin-left:0}.offset-md-1{margin-left:8.333333%}.offset-md-2{margin-left:16.666667%}.offset-md-3{margin-left:25%}.offset-md-4{margin-left:33.333333%}.offset-md-5{margin-left:41.666667%}.offset-md-6{margin-left:50%}.offset-md-7{margin-left:58.333333%}.offset-md-8{margin-left:66.666667%}.offset-md-9{margin-left:75%}.offset-md-10{margin-left:83.333333%}.offset-md-11{margin-left:91.666667%}}@media (min-width:992px){.col-lg{-ms-flex-preferred-size:0;flex-basis:0;-webkit-box-flex:1;-ms-flex-positive:1;flex-grow:1;max-width:100%}.col-lg-auto{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 auto;flex:0 0 auto;width:auto;max-width:none}.col-lg-1{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 8.333333%;flex:0 0 8.333333%;max-width:8.333333%}.col-lg-2{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 16.666667%;flex:0 0 16.666667%;max-width:16.666667%}.col-lg-3{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 25%;flex:0 0 25%;max-width:25%}.col-lg-4{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 33.333333%;flex:0 0 33.333333%;max-width:33.333333%}.col-lg-5{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 41.666667%;flex:0 0 41.666667%;max-width:41.666667%}.col-lg-6{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 50%;flex:0 0 50%;max-width:50%}.col-lg-7{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 58.333333%;flex:0 0 58.333333%;max-width:58.333333%}.col-lg-8{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 66.666667%;flex:0 0 66.666667%;max-width:66.666667%}.col-lg-9{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 75%;flex:0 0 75%;max-width:75%}.col-lg-10{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 83.333333%;flex:0 0 83.333333%;max-width:83.333333%}.col-lg-11{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 91.666667%;flex:0 0 91.666667%;max-width:91.666667%}.col-lg-12{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 100%;flex:0 0 100%;max-width:100%}.order-lg-first{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:0;-ms-flex-order:-1;order:-1}.order-lg-last{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:14;-ms-flex-order:13;order:13}.order-lg-0{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:1;-ms-flex-order:0;order:0}.order-lg-1{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:2;-ms-flex-order:1;order:1}.order-lg-2{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:3;-ms-flex-order:2;order:2}.order-lg-3{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:4;-ms-flex-order:3;order:3}.order-lg-4{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:5;-ms-flex-order:4;order:4}.order-lg-5{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:6;-ms-flex-order:5;order:5}.order-lg-6{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:7;-ms-flex-order:6;order:6}.order-lg-7{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:8;-ms-flex-order:7;order:7}.order-lg-8{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:9;-ms-flex-order:8;order:8}.order-lg-9{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:10;-ms-flex-order:9;order:9}.order-lg-10{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:11;-ms-flex-order:10;order:10}.order-lg-11{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:12;-ms-flex-order:11;order:11}.order-lg-12{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:13;-ms-flex-order:12;order:12}.offset-lg-0{margin-left:0}.offset-lg-1{margin-left:8.333333%}.offset-lg-2{margin-left:16.666667%}.offset-lg-3{margin-left:25%}.offset-lg-4{margin-left:33.333333%}.offset-lg-5{margin-left:41.666667%}.offset-lg-6{margin-left:50%}.offset-lg-7{margin-left:58.333333%}.offset-lg-8{margin-left:66.666667%}.offset-lg-9{margin-left:75%}.offset-lg-10{margin-left:83.333333%}.offset-lg-11{margin-left:91.666667%}}@media (min-width:1200px){.col-xl{-ms-flex-preferred-size:0;flex-basis:0;-webkit-box-flex:1;-ms-flex-positive:1;flex-grow:1;max-width:100%}.col-xl-auto{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 auto;flex:0 0 auto;width:auto;max-width:none}.col-xl-1{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 8.333333%;flex:0 0 8.333333%;max-width:8.333333%}.col-xl-2{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 16.666667%;flex:0 0 16.666667%;max-width:16.666667%}.col-xl-3{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 25%;flex:0 0 25%;max-width:25%}.col-xl-4{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 33.333333%;flex:0 0 33.333333%;max-width:33.333333%}.col-xl-5{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 41.666667%;flex:0 0 41.666667%;max-width:41.666667%}.col-xl-6{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 50%;flex:0 0 50%;max-width:50%}.col-xl-7{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 58.333333%;flex:0 0 58.333333%;max-width:58.333333%}.col-xl-8{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 66.666667%;flex:0 0 66.666667%;max-width:66.666667%}.col-xl-9{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 75%;flex:0 0 75%;max-width:75%}.col-xl-10{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 83.333333%;flex:0 0 83.333333%;max-width:83.333333%}.col-xl-11{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 91.666667%;flex:0 0 91.666667%;max-width:91.666667%}.col-xl-12{-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 100%;flex:0 0 100%;max-width:100%}.order-xl-first{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:0;-ms-flex-order:-1;order:-1}.order-xl-last{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:14;-ms-flex-order:13;order:13}.order-xl-0{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:1;-ms-flex-order:0;order:0}.order-xl-1{-

webkit-box-ordinal-group:2;-ms-flex-order:1;order:1}.order-xl-2{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:3;-ms-flex-order:2;order:2}.order-xl-3{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:4;-ms-flex-order:3;order:3}.order-xl-4{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:5;-ms-flex-order:4;order:4}.order-xl-5{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:6;-ms-flex-order:5;order:5}.order-xl-6{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:7;-ms-flex-order:6;order:6}.order-xl-7{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:8;-ms-flex-order:7;order:7}.order-xl-8{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:9;-ms-flex-order:8;order:8}.order-xl-9{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:10;-ms-flex-order:9;order:9}.order-xl-10{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:11;-ms-flex-order:10;order:10}.order-xl-11{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:12;-ms-flex-order:11;order:11}.order-xl-12{-webkit-box-ordinal-group:13;-ms-flex-order:12;order:12}.offset-xl-0{margin-left:0}.offset-xl-1{margin-left:8.333333%}.offset-xl-2{margin-left:16.666667%}.offset-xl-3{margin-left:25%}.offset-xl-4{margin-left:33.333333%}.offset-xl-5{margin-left:41.666667%}.offset-xl-6{margin-left:50%}.offset-xl-7{margin-left:58.333333%}.offset-xl-8{margin-left:66.666667%}.offset-xl-9{margin-left:75%}.offset-xl-10{margin-left:83.333333%}.offset-xl-11{margin-left:91.666667%}}.table{width:100%;max-width:100%;margin-bottom:1rem;background-color:transparent}.table td,.table th{padding:.75rem;vertical-align:top;border-top:1px solid #dee2e6}.table thead th{vertical-align:bottom;border-bottom:2px solid #dee2e6}.table tbody+tbody{border-top:2px solid #dee2e6}.table .table{background-color:#fff}.table-sm td,.table-sm th{padding:.3rem}.table-bordered{border:1px solid #dee2e6}.table-bordered td,.table-bordered th{border:1px solid #dee2e6}.table-bordered thead td,.table-bordered thead th{border-bottom-width:2px}.table-striped tbody tr:nth-of-type(odd){background-color:rgba(0,0,0,.05)}.table-hover tbody tr:hover{background-color:rgba(0,0,0,.075)}.table-primary,.table-primary>td,.table-primary>th{background-color:#b8daff}.table-primary .table-primary:hover{background-color:#9fcdfc}.table-primary .table-primary>td,.table-primary .table-primary>th{background-color:#9fcdfc}.table-secondary,.table-secondary>td,.table-secondary>th{background-color:#d6d8db}.table-secondary .table-secondary:hover{background-color:#c8cbcf}.table-secondary .table-secondary>td,.table-secondary .table-secondary>th{background-color:#c8cbcf}.table-success,.table-success>td,.table-success>th{background-color:#c3e6cb}.table-success .table-success:hover{background-color:#b1dfbb}.table-success .table-success>td,.table-success .table-success>th{background-color:#b1dfbb}.table-info,.table-info>td,.table-info>th{background-color:#bee5eb}.table-info .table-info:hover{background-color:#abdde5}.table-info .table-info>td,.table-info .table-info>th{background-color:#abdde5}.table-warning,.table-warning>td,.table-warning>th{background-color:#ffeeba}.table-warning .table-warning:hover{background-color:#ffe8a1}.table-warning .table-warning>td,.table-warning .table-warning>th{background-color:#ffe8a1}.table-danger,.table-danger>td,.table-danger>th{background-color:#f5c6cb}.table-danger .table-danger:hover{background-color:#f1b0b7}.table-danger .table-danger>td,.table-danger .table-danger>th{background-color:#f1b0b7}.table-light,.table-light>td,.table-light>th{background-color:#fdfdfe}.table-light .table-light:hover{background-color:#ececfc}.table-light .table-light>td,.table-light .table-light>th{background-color:#ececfc}.table-dark,.table-dark>td,.table-dark>th{background-color:#c6c8ca}.table-dark .table-dark:hover{background-color:#b9bbbe}.table-dark .table-dark>td,.table-dark .table-dark>th{background-color:#b9bbbe}.table-active,.table-active>td,.table-active>th{background-color:rgba(0,0,0,.075)}.table-active .table-active:hover{background-color:rgba(0,0,0,.075)}.table-active .table-active>td,.table-active .table-active>th{background-color:rgba(0,0,0,.075)}.table .thead-dark th{color:#fff;background-color:#212529;border-color:#32383e}.table .thead-light th{color:#495057;background-color:#e9ecef;border-color:#dee2e6}.table-dark{color:#fff;background-color:#212529}.table-dark td,.table-dark th,.table-dark thead th{border-color:#32383e}.table-dark.table-bordered{border:0}.table-dark.table-striped tbody tr:nth-of-type(odd){background-color:rgba(255,255,255,.05)}.table-dark.table-hover tbody tr:hover{background-color:rgba(255,255,255,.075)}@media (max-width:575.98px){table-responsive-sm{display:block;width:100%;overflow-x:auto;-webkit-overflow-scrolling:touch;-ms-

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overflow-style:-ms-autohiding-scrollbar}.table-responsive-sm>.table-bordered{border:0}}@media
(max-width:767.98px){.table-responsive-md{display:block;width:100%;overflow-x:auto;-webkit-
overflow-scrolling:touch;-ms-overflow-style:-ms-autohiding-scrollbar}.table-responsive-md>.table-
bordered{border:0}}@media (max-width:991.98px){.table-responsive-
lg{display:block;width:100%;overflow-x:auto;-webkit-overflow-scrolling:touch;-ms-overflow-style:-
ms-autohiding-scrollbar}.table-responsive-lg>.table-bordered{border:0}}@media (max-
width:1199.98px){.table-responsive-xl{display:block;width:100%;overflow-x:auto;-webkit-overflow-
scrolling:touch;-ms-overflow-style:-ms-autohiding-scrollbar}.table-responsive-xl>.table-
bordered{border:0}}.table-responsive{display:block;width:100%;overflow-x:auto;-webkit-overflow-
scrolling:touch;-ms-overflow-style:-ms-autohiding-scrollbar}.table-responsive>.table-
bordered{border:0}.form-control{display:block;width:100%;padding:.375rem .75rem;font-
size:1rem;line-height:1.5;color:#495057;background-color:#fff;background-clip:padding-
box;border:1px solid #ced4da;border-radius:.25rem;transition:border-color .15s ease-in-out,box-
shadow .15s ease-in-out}.form-control:-ms-expand{background-color:transparent;border:0}.form-
control:focus{color:#495057;background-color:#fff;border-color:#80bdff;outline:0;box-shadow:0 0 0
.2rem rgba(0,123,255,.25)}.form-control::-webkit-input-placeholder{color:#6c757d;opacity:1}.form-
control::-moz-placeholder{color:#6c757d;opacity:1}.form-control:-ms-input-
placeholder{color:#6c757d;opacity:1}.form-control:-ms-input-
placeholder{color:#6c757d;opacity:1}.form-control::placeholder{color:#6c757d;opacity:1}.form-
control:disabled,.form-control[readonly]{background-color:#e9ecef;opacity:1}select.form-
control:not([size]):not([multiple]){height:calc(2.25rem + 2px)}select.form-control:focus::-ms-
value{color:#495057;background-color:#fff}.form-control-file,.form-control-
range{display:block;width:100%}.col-form-label{padding-top:calc(.375rem + 1px);padding-
bottom:calc(.375rem + 1px);margin-bottom:0;font-size:inherit;line-height:1.5}.col-form-label-
lg{padding-top:calc(.5rem + 1px);padding-bottom:calc(.5rem + 1px);font-size:1.25rem;line-
height:1.5}.col-form-label-sm{padding-top:calc(.25rem + 1px);padding-bottom:calc(.25rem +
1px);font-size:.875rem;line-height:1.5}.form-control-plaintext{display:block;width:100%;padding-
top:.375rem;padding-bottom:.375rem;margin-bottom:0;line-height:1.5;background-
color:transparent;border:solid transparent;border-width:1px 0}.form-control-plaintext.form-control-
lg,.form-control-plaintext.form-control-sm,.input-group-lg>.form-control-plaintext.form-
control,.input-group-lg>.input-group-append>.form-control-plaintext.btn,.input-group-lg>.input-
group-append>.form-control-plaintext.input-group-text,.input-group-lg>.input-group-
prepend>.form-control-plaintext.btn,.input-group-lg>.input-group-prepend>.form-control-
plaintext.input-group-text,.input-group-sm>.form-control-plaintext.form-control,.input-group-
sm>.input-group-append>.form-control-plaintext.btn,.input-group-sm>.input-group-append>.form-
control-plaintext.input-group-text,.input-group-sm>.input-group-prepend>.form-control-
plaintext.btn,.input-group-sm>.input-group-prepend>.form-control-plaintext.input-group-
text{padding-right:0;padding-left:0}.form-control-sm,.input-group-sm>.form-control,.input-group-
sm>.input-group-append>.btn,.input-group-sm>.input-group-append>.input-group-text,.input-
group-sm>.input-group-prepend>.btn,.input-group-sm>.input-group-prepend>.input-group-
text{padding:.25rem .5rem;font-size:.875rem;line-height:1.5;border-radius:.25rem}.input-group-
sm>.input-group-append>select.btn:not([size]):not([multiple]),.input-group-sm>.input-group-
append>select.input-group-text:not([size]):not([multiple]),.input-group-sm>.input-group-
prepend>select.btn:not([size]):not([multiple]),.input-group-sm>.input-group-prepend>select.input-
group-text:not([size]):not([multiple]),.input-group-sm>select.form-
control:not([size]):not([multiple]),select.form-control-
sm:not([size]):not([multiple]){height:calc(1.8125rem + 2px)}.form-control-lg,.input-group-lg>.form-
control,.input-group-lg>.input-group-append>.btn,.input-group-lg>.input-group-append>.input-
group-text,.input-group-lg>.input-group-prepend>.btn,.input-group-lg>.input-group-
prepend>.input-group-text{padding:.5rem 1rem;font-size:1.25rem;line-height:1.5;border-
radius:.375rem}.input-group-lg>.input-group-append>select.btn:not([size]):not([multiple]),.input-
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group-lg>.input-group-append>select.input-group-text:not([size]):not([multiple]),.input-group-
lg>.input-group-prepend>select.btn:not([size]):not([multiple]),.input-group-lg>.input-group-
prepend>select.input-group-text:not([size]):not([multiple]),.input-group-lg>select.form-
control:not([size]):not([multiple]),select.form-control-
lg:not([size]):not([multiple]){height:calc(2.875rem + 2px)}.form-group{margin-bottom:1rem}.form-
text{display:block;margin-top:.25rem}.form-row{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-
flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-wrap:wrap;flex-wrap:wrap;margin-right:-5px;margin-left:-5px}.form-
row>.col,.form-row>[class*=col-]{padding-right:5px;padding-left:5px}.form-
check{position:relative;display:block;padding-left:1.25rem}.form-check-
input{position:absolute;margin-top:.3rem;margin-left:-1.25rem}.form-check-input:disabled~.form-
check-label{color:#6c757d}.form-check-label{margin-bottom:0}.form-check-inline{display:-webkit-
inline-block;display:-ms-inline-flexbox;display:inline-flex;-webkit-box-align:center;-ms-flex-
align:center;align-items:center;padding-left:0;margin-right:.75rem}.form-check-inline .form-check-
input{position:static;margin-top:0;margin-right:.3125rem;margin-left:0}.valid-
feedback{display:none;width:100%;margin-top:.25rem;font-size:80%;color:#28a745}.valid-
tooltip{position:absolute;top:100%;z-index:5;display:none;max-width:100%;padding:.5rem;margin-
top:.1rem;font-size:.875rem;line-height:1;color:#fff;background-color:rgba(40,167,69,.8);border-
radius:.2rem}.custom-select.is-valid,.form-control.is-valid,.was-validated .custom-select.valid,.was-
validated .form-control.valid{border-color:#28a745}.custom-select.is-valid:focus,.form-control.is-
valid:focus,.was-validated .custom-select.valid:focus,.was-validated .form-
control.valid:focus{border-color:#28a745;box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(40,167,69,.25)}.custom-
select.is-valid~.valid-feedback,.custom-select.is-valid~.valid-tooltip,.form-control.is-valid~.valid-
feedback,.form-control.is-valid~.valid-tooltip,.was-validated .custom-select.valid~.valid-
feedback,.was-validated .form-control.valid~.valid-feedback,.was-validated .custom-select.valid~.valid-
feedback,.was-validated .form-control.valid~.valid-feedback{display:block}.form-check-input.is-
valid~.form-check-label,.was-validated .form-check-input.valid~.form-check-
label{color:#28a745}.form-check-input.is-valid~.valid-feedback,.form-check-input.is-valid~.valid-
tooltip,.was-validated .form-check-input.valid~.valid-feedback,.was-validated .form-check-
input.valid~.valid-tooltip{display:block}.custom-control-input.is-valid~.custom-control-label,.was-
validated .custom-control-input.valid~.custom-control-label{color:#28a745}.custom-control-input.is-
valid~.custom-control-label::before,.was-validated .custom-control-input.valid~.custom-control-
label::before{background-color:#71dd8a}.custom-control-input.is-valid~.valid-feedback,.custom-
control-input.is-valid~.valid-tooltip,.was-validated .custom-control-input.valid~.valid-feedback,.was-
validated .custom-control-input.valid~.valid-tooltip{display:block}.custom-control-input.is-
valid:checked~.custom-control-label::before,.was-validated .custom-control-input.valid:checked~.custom-control-
label::before{background-color:#34ce57}.custom-control-
input.is-valid:focus~.custom-control-label::before,.was-validated .custom-control-
input.valid:focus~.custom-control-label::before{box-shadow:0 0 0 1px #fff,0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(40,167,69,.25)}.custom-file-input.is-valid~.custom-file-label,.was-validated .custom-file-
input.valid~.custom-file-label{border-color:#28a745}.custom-file-input.is-valid~.custom-file-
label::before,.was-validated .custom-file-input.valid~.custom-file-label::before{border-
color:inherit}.custom-file-input.is-valid~.valid-feedback,.custom-file-input.is-valid~.valid-
tooltip,.was-validated .custom-file-input.valid~.valid-feedback,.was-validated .custom-file-
input.valid~.valid-tooltip{display:block}.custom-file-input.is-valid:focus~.custom-file-label,.was-
validated .custom-file-input.valid:focus~.custom-file-label{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(40,167,69,.25)}.invalid-feedback{display:none;width:100%;margin-top:.25rem;font-
size:80%;color:#dc3545}.invalid-tooltip{position:absolute;top:100%;z-index:5;display:none;max-
width:100%;padding:.5rem;margin-top:.1rem;font-size:.875rem;line-height:1;color:#fff;background-
color:rgba(220,53,69,.8);border-radius:.2rem}.custom-select.is-invalid,.form-control.is-invalid,.was-
validated .custom-select.invalid,.was-validated .form-control.invalid{border-color:#dc3545}.custom-
select.is-invalid:focus,.form-control.is-invalid:focus,.was-validated .custom-select.invalid:focus,.was-

validated .form-control:invalid:focus{border-color:#dc3545;box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(220,53,69,.25)}.custom-select.is-invalid~.invalid-feedback,.custom-select.is-invalid~.invalid-
tooltip,.form-control.is-invalid~.invalid-feedback,.form-control.is-invalid~.invalid-tooltip,.was-
validated .custom-select:invalid~.invalid-feedback,.was-validated .custom-select:invalid~.invalid-
tooltip,.was-validated .form-control:invalid~.invalid-feedback,.was-validated .form-
control:invalid~.invalid-tooltip{display:block}.form-check-input.is-invalid~.form-check-label,.was-
validated .form-check-input:invalid~.form-check-label{color:#dc3545}.form-check-input.is-
invalid~.invalid-feedback,.form-check-input.is-invalid~.invalid-tooltip,.was-validated .form-check-
input:invalid~.invalid-feedback,.was-validated .form-check-input:invalid~.invalid-
tooltip{display:block}.custom-control-input.is-invalid~.custom-control-label,.was-validated .custom-
control-input:invalid~.custom-control-label{color:#dc3545}.custom-control-input.is-invalid~.custom-
control-label::before,.was-validated .custom-control-input:invalid~.custom-control-
label::before{background-color:#efa2a9}.custom-control-input.is-invalid~.invalid-feedback,.custom-
control-input.is-invalid~.invalid-tooltip,.was-validated .custom-control-input:invalid~.invalid-
feedback,.was-validated .custom-control-input:invalid~.invalid-tooltip{display:block}.custom-
control-input.is-invalid:checked~.custom-control-label::before,.was-validated .custom-control-
input:invalid:checked~.custom-control-label::before{background-color:#e4606d}.custom-control-
input.is-invalid:focus~.custom-control-label::before,.was-validated .custom-control-
input:invalid:focus~.custom-control-label::before{box-shadow:0 0 0 1px #fff,0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(220,53,69,.25)}.custom-file-input.is-invalid~.custom-file-label,.was-validated .custom-file-
input:invalid~.custom-file-label{border-color:#dc3545}.custom-file-input.is-invalid~.custom-file-
label::before,.was-validated .custom-file-input:invalid~.custom-file-label::before{border-
color:inherit}.custom-file-input.is-invalid~.invalid-feedback,.custom-file-input.is-invalid~.invalid-
tooltip,.was-validated .custom-file-input:invalid~.invalid-feedback,.was-validated .custom-file-
input:invalid~.invalid-tooltip{display:block}.custom-file-input.is-invalid:focus~.custom-file-label,.was-
validated .custom-file-input:invalid:focus~.custom-file-label{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(220,53,69,.25)}.form-inline{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-
orient:horizontal;-webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-flex-flow:row wrap;flex-flow:row wrap;-webkit-
box-align:center;-ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center}.form-inline .form-
check{width:100%}@media (min-width:576px){.form-inline label{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-
flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-align:center;-ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center;-webkit-box-
pack:center;-ms-flex-pack:center;justify-content:center;margin-bottom:0}.form-inline .form-
group{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 0 auto;flex:0
0 auto;-webkit-box-orient:horizontal;-webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-flex-flow:row wrap;flex-
flow:row wrap;-webkit-box-align:center;-ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center;margin-
bottom:0}.form-inline .form-control{display:inline-block;width:auto;vertical-align:middle}.form-
inline .form-control-plaintext{display:inline-block}.form-inline .input-group{width:auto}.form-inline
.form-check{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-align:center;-ms-flex-
align:center;align-items:center;-webkit-box-pack:center;-ms-flex-pack:center;justify-
content:center;width:auto;padding-left:0}.form-inline .form-check-input{position:relative;margin-
top:0;margin-right:.25rem;margin-left:0}.form-inline .custom-control{-webkit-box-align:center;-ms-
flex-align:center;align-items:center;-webkit-box-pack:center;-ms-flex-pack:center;justify-
content:center}.form-inline .custom-control-label{margin-bottom:0}.btn{display:inline-block;font-
weight:400;text-align:center;white-space:nowrap;vertical-align:middle;-webkit-user-select:none;-
moz-user-select:none;-ms-user-select:none;user-select:none;border:1px solid
transparent;padding:.375rem .75rem;font-size:1rem;line-height:1.5;border-
radius:.25rem;transition:color .15s ease-in-out;background-color .15s ease-in-out,border-color .15s
ease-in-out,box-shadow .15s ease-in-out}.btn:focus,.btn:hover{text-
decoration:none}.btn:focus,.btn:focus{outline:0;box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(0,123,255,.25)}.btn.disabled,.btn:disabled{opacity:.65}.btn:not(:disabled):not(.disabled){cursor:
pointer}.btn:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active{background

-image:none}a.btn.disabled,fieldset:disabled a.btn{pointer-events:none}.btn-primary{color:#fff;background-color:#007bff;border-color:#007bff}.btn-primary:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#0069d9;border-color:#0062cc}.btn-primary.focus,.btn-primary:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(0,123,255,.5)}.btn-primary.disabled,.btn-primary:disabled{color:#fff;background-color:#007bff;border-color:#007bff}.btn-primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-primary.dropdown-toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#0062cc;border-color:#005cbf}.btn-primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-primary.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(0,123,255,.5)}.btn-secondary{color:#fff;background-color:#6c757d;border-color:#6c757d}.btn-secondary:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#5a6268;border-color:#545b62}.btn-secondary.focus,.btn-secondary:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(108,117,125,.5)}.btn-secondary.disabled,.btn-secondary:disabled{color:#fff;background-color:#6c757d;border-color:#6c757d}.btn-secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-secondary.dropdown-toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#545b62;border-color:#4e555b}.btn-secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-secondary.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(108,117,125,.5)}.btn-success{color:#fff;background-color:#28a745;border-color:#28a745}.btn-success:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#218838;border-color:#1e7e34}.btn-success.focus,.btn-success:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(40,167,69,.5)}.btn-success.disabled,.btn-success:disabled{color:#fff;background-color:#28a745;border-color:#28a745}.btn-success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-success.dropdown-toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#1e7e34;border-color:#1c7430}.btn-success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-success.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(40,167,69,.5)}.btn-info{color:#fff;background-color:#17a2b8;border-color:#17a2b8}.btn-info:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#138496;border-color:#117a8b}.btn-info.focus,.btn-info:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(23,162,184,.5)}.btn-info.disabled,.btn-info:disabled{color:#fff;background-color:#17a2b8;border-color:#17a2b8}.btn-info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-info.dropdown-toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#117a8b;border-color:#10707f}.btn-info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-info.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(23,162,184,.5)}.btn-warning{color:#212529;background-color:#ffc107;border-color:#ffc107}.btn-warning:hover{color:#212529;background-color:#e0a800;border-color:#d39e00}.btn-warning.focus,.btn-warning:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(255,193,7,.5)}.btn-warning.disabled,.btn-warning:disabled{color:#212529;background-color:#ffc107;border-color:#ffc107}.btn-warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-warning.dropdown-toggle{color:#212529;background-color:#d39e00;border-color:#c69500}.btn-warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-warning.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(255,193,7,.5)}.btn-danger{color:#fff;background-color:#dc3545;border-color:#dc3545}.btn-danger:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#c82333;border-color:#bd2130}.btn-danger.focus,.btn-danger:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(220,53,69,.5)}.btn-danger.disabled,.btn-danger:disabled{color:#fff;background-color:#dc3545;border-color:#dc3545}.btn-danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-danger.dropdown-

toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#bd2130;border-color:#b21f2d}.btn-danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-danger.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(220,53,69,.5)}.btn-light{color:#212529;background-color:#f8f9fa;border-color:#f8f9fa}.btn-light:hover{color:#212529;background-color:#e2e6ea;border-color:#dae0e5}.btn-light:focus,.btn-light:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(248,249,250,.5)}.btn-light.disabled,.btn-light:disabled{color:#212529;background-color:#f8f9fa;border-color:#f8f9fa}.btn-light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-light.dropdown-toggle{color:#212529;background-color:#dae0e5;border-color:#d3d9df}.btn-light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-light.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(248,249,250,.5)}.btn-dark{color:#fff;background-color:#343a40;border-color:#343a40}.btn-dark:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#23272b;border-color:#1d2124}.btn-dark:focus,.btn-dark:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(52,58,64,.5)}.btn-dark.disabled,.btn-dark:disabled{color:#fff;background-color:#343a40;border-color:#343a40}.btn-dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-dark.dropdown-toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#1d2124;border-color:#171a1d}.btn-dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-dark.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(52,58,64,.5)}.btn-outline-primary{color:#007bff;background-color:transparent;background-image:none;border-color:#007bff}.btn-outline-primary:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#007bff;border-color:#007bff}.btn-outline-primary:focus,.btn-outline-primary:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(0,123,255,.5)}.btn-outline-primary.disabled,.btn-outline-primary:disabled{color:#007bff;background-color:transparent}.btn-outline-primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-primary.dropdown-toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#007bff;border-color:#007bff}.btn-outline-primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-primary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-primary.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(0,123,255,.5)}.btn-outline-secondary{color:#6c757d;background-color:transparent;background-image:none;border-color:#6c757d}.btn-outline-secondary:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#6c757d;border-color:#6c757d}.btn-outline-secondary:focus,.btn-outline-secondary:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(108,117,125,.5)}.btn-outline-secondary.disabled,.btn-outline-secondary:disabled{color:#6c757d;background-color:transparent}.btn-outline-secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-secondary.dropdown-toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#6c757d;border-color:#6c757d}.btn-outline-secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-secondary:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-secondary.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(108,117,125,.5)}.btn-outline-success{color:#28a745;background-color:transparent;background-image:none;border-color:#28a745}.btn-outline-success:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#28a745;border-color:#28a745}.btn-outline-success:focus,.btn-outline-success:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(40,167,69,.5)}.btn-outline-success.disabled,.btn-outline-success:disabled{color:#28a745;background-color:transparent}.btn-outline-success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-success.dropdown-toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#28a745;border-color:#28a745}.btn-outline-success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-success:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-success.dropdown-

toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(40,167,69,.5)}.btn-outline-info{color:#17a2b8;background-color:transparent;background-image:none;border-color:#17a2b8}.btn-outline-info:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#17a2b8;border-color:#17a2b8}.btn-outline-info.focus,.btn-outline-info:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(23,162,184,.5)}.btn-outline-info.disabled,.btn-outline-info:disabled{color:#17a2b8;background-color:transparent}.btn-outline-info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-info.dropdown-toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#17a2b8;border-color:#17a2b8}.btn-outline-info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-info:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-info.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(23,162,184,.5)}.btn-outline-warning{color:#ffc107;background-color:transparent;background-image:none;border-color:#ffc107}.btn-outline-warning:hover{color:#212529;background-color:#ffc107;border-color:#ffc107}.btn-outline-warning.focus,.btn-outline-warning:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(255,193,7,.5)}.btn-outline-warning.disabled,.btn-outline-warning:disabled{color:#ffc107;background-color:transparent}.btn-outline-warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-warning.dropdown-toggle{color:#212529;background-color:#ffc107;border-color:#ffc107}.btn-outline-warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-warning:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-warning.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(255,193,7,.5)}.btn-outline-danger{color:#dc3545;background-color:transparent;background-image:none;border-color:#dc3545}.btn-outline-danger:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#dc3545;border-color:#dc3545}.btn-outline-danger.focus,.btn-outline-danger:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(220,53,69,.5)}.btn-outline-danger.disabled,.btn-outline-danger:disabled{color:#dc3545;background-color:transparent}.btn-outline-danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-danger.dropdown-toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#dc3545;border-color:#dc3545}.btn-outline-danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-danger:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-danger.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(220,53,69,.5)}.btn-outline-light{color:#f8f9fa;background-color:transparent;background-image:none;border-color:#f8f9fa}.btn-outline-light:hover{color:#212529;background-color:#f8f9fa;border-color:#f8f9fa}.btn-outline-light.focus,.btn-outline-light:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(248,249,250,.5)}.btn-outline-light.disabled,.btn-outline-light:disabled{color:#f8f9fa;background-color:transparent}.btn-outline-light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-light.dropdown-toggle{color:#212529;background-color:#f8f9fa;border-color:#f8f9fa}.btn-outline-light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-light:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-light.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(248,249,250,.5)}.btn-outline-dark{color:#343a40;background-color:transparent;background-image:none;border-color:#343a40}.btn-outline-dark:hover{color:#fff;background-color:#343a40;border-color:#343a40}.btn-outline-dark.focus,.btn-outline-dark:focus{box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(52,58,64,.5)}.btn-outline-dark.disabled,.btn-outline-dark:disabled{color:#343a40;background-color:transparent}.btn-outline-dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active,.btn-outline-dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active,.show>.btn-outline-dark.dropdown-toggle{color:#fff;background-color:#343a40;border-color:#343a40}.btn-outline-dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled).active:focus,.btn-outline-dark:not(:disabled):not(.disabled):active:focus,.show>.btn-outline-dark.dropdown-toggle:focus{box-

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shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(52,58,64,.5)}.btn-link{font-weight:400;color:#007bff;background-color:transparent}.btn-link:hover{color:#0056b3;text-decoration:underline;background-color:transparent;border-color:transparent}.btn-link:focus,.btn-link:focus{text-decoration:underline;border-color:transparent;box-shadow:none}.btn-link.disabled,.btn-link:disabled{color:#6c757d}.btn-group-lg>.btn,.btn-lg{padding:.5rem 1rem;font-size:1.25rem;line-height:1.5;border-radius:.3rem}.btn-group-sm>.btn,.btn-sm{padding:.25rem .5rem;font-size:.875rem;line-height:1.5;border-radius:.2rem}.btn-block{display:block;width:100%}.btn-block+.btn-block{margin-top:.5rem}input[type=button].btn-block,input[type=reset].btn-block,input[type=submit].btn-block{width:100%}.fade{opacity:0;transition:opacity .15s linear}.fade.show{opacity:1}.collapse{display:none}.collapse.show{display:block}tr.collapse.show{display:table-row}tbody.collapse.show{display:table-row-group}.collapsing{position:relative;height:0;overflow:hidden;transition:height .35s ease}.dropdown,.dropup{position:relative}.dropdown-toggle::after{display:inline-block;width:0;height:0;margin-left:.255em;vertical-align:.255em;content:"";border-top:.3em solid transparent;border-right:.3em solid transparent;border-bottom:0;border-left:.3em solid transparent}.dropdown-toggle:empty::after{margin-left:0}.dropdown-menu{position:absolute;top:100%;left:0;z-index:1000;display:none;float:left;min-width:10rem;padding:.5rem 0;margin:.125rem 0 0;font-size:1rem;color:#212529;text-align:left;list-style:none;background-color:#fff;background-clip:padding-box;border:1px solid rgba(0,0,0,.15);border-radius:.25rem}.dropdown .dropdown-menu{margin-top:0;margin-bottom:.125rem}.dropup .dropdown-toggle::after{display:inline-block;width:0;height:0;margin-left:.255em;vertical-align:.255em;content:"";border-top:0;border-right:.3em solid transparent;border-bottom:.3em solid transparent;border-left:.3em solid transparent}.dropup .dropdown-toggle:empty::after{margin-left:0}.dropright .dropdown-menu{margin-top:0;margin-left:.125rem}.dropright .dropdown-toggle::after{display:inline-block;width:0;height:0;margin-left:.255em;vertical-align:.255em;content:"";border-top:.3em solid transparent;border-bottom:.3em solid transparent;border-left:.3em solid}.dropright .dropdown-toggle:empty::after{margin-left:0}.dropright .dropdown-toggle::after{vertical-align:0}.dropleft .dropdown-menu{margin-top:0;margin-right:.125rem}.dropleft .dropdown-toggle::after{display:inline-block;width:0;height:0;margin-left:.255em;vertical-align:.255em;content:""}.dropleft .dropdown-toggle:empty::after{display:none}.dropleft .dropdown-toggle::before{display:inline-block;width:0;height:0;margin-right:.255em;vertical-align:.255em;content:"";border-top:.3em solid transparent;border-right:.3em solid;border-bottom:.3em solid transparent}.dropleft .dropdown-toggle:empty::after{margin-left:0}.dropleft .dropdown-toggle::before{vertical-align:0}.dropdown-divider{height:0;margin:.5rem 0;overflow:hidden;border-top:1px solid #e9ecef}.dropdown-item{display:block;width:100%;padding:.25rem 1.5rem;clear:both;font-weight:400;color:#212529;text-align:inherit;white-space:nowrap;background-color:transparent;border:0}.dropdown-item:focus,.dropdown-item:hover{color:#16181b;text-decoration:none;background-color:#f8f9fa}.dropdown-item.active,.dropdown-item:active{color:#fff;text-decoration:none;background-color:#007bff}.dropdown-item.disabled,.dropdown-item:disabled{color:#6c757d;background-color:transparent}.dropdown-menu.show{display:block}.dropdown-header{display:block;padding:.5rem 1.5rem;margin-bottom:0;font-size:.875rem;color:#6c757d;white-space:nowrap}.btn-group,.btn-group-vertical{position:relative;display:-webkit-inline-block;display:-ms-inline-flexbox;display:inline-flex;vertical-align:middle}.btn-group-vertical>.btn,.btn-group>.btn{position:relative;-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 1 auto;flex:0 1 auto}.btn-group-vertical>.btn:hover,.btn-group>.btn:hover{z-index:1}.btn-group-vertical>.btn.active,.btn-group-vertical>.btn:active,.btn-group-vertical>.btn:focus,.btn-group>.btn.active,.btn-group>.btn:active,.btn-group>.btn:focus{z-index:1}.btn-group .btn+.btn,.btn-group .btn+.btn-group,.btn-group .btn-group+.btn,.btn-group .btn-group+.btn-group,.btn-group-vertical .btn+.btn,.btn-group-vertical .btn+.btn-group,.btn-group-vertical .btn-group+.btn,.btn-group-vertical .btn-group+.btn-group{margin-left:-1px}.btn-
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toolbar{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-wrap:wrap;flex-wrap:wrap;-
webkit-box-pack:start;-ms-flex-pack:start;justify-content:flex-start}.btn-toolbar
.input-
group{width:auto}.btn-group>.btn:first-child{margin-left:0}.btn-group>.btn-group:not(:last-
child)>.btn,.btn-group>.btn:not(:last-child):not(.dropdown-toggle){border-top-right-radius:0;border-
bottom-right-radius:0}.btn-group>.btn-group:not(:first-child)>.btn,.btn-group>.btn:not(:first-
child){border-top-left-radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.dropdown-toggle-split{padding-
right:.5625rem;padding-left:.5625rem}.dropdown-toggle-split::after{margin-left:0}.btn-group-
sm>.btn+.dropdown-toggle-split,.btn-sm+.dropdown-toggle-split{padding-right:.375rem;padding-
left:.375rem}.btn-group-lg>.btn+.dropdown-toggle-split,.btn-lg+.dropdown-toggle-split{padding-
right:.75rem;padding-left:.75rem}.btn-group-vertical{-webkit-box-orient:vertical;-webkit-box-
direction:normal;-ms-flex-direction:column;flex-direction:column;-webkit-box-align:start;-ms-flex-
align:start;align-items:flex-start;-webkit-box-pack:center;-ms-flex-pack:center;justify-
content:center}.btn-group-vertical .btn,.btn-group-vertical .btn-group{width:100%}.btn-group-
vertical>.btn+.btn,.btn-group-vertical>.btn+.btn-group,.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group+.btn,.btn-
group-vertical>.btn-group+.btn-group{margin-top:-1px;margin-left:0}.btn-group-vertical>.btn-
group:not(:last-child)>.btn,.btn-group-vertical>.btn:not(:last-child):not(.dropdown-toggle){border-
bottom-right-radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.btn-group-vertical>.btn-group:not(:first-
child)>.btn,.btn-group-vertical>.btn:not(:first-child){border-top-left-radius:0;border-top-right-
radius:0}.btn-group-toggle>.btn,.btn-group-toggle>.btn-group>.btn{margin-bottom:0}.btn-group-
toggle>.btn input[type=checkbox],.btn-group-toggle>.btn input[type=radio],.btn-group-toggle>.btn-
group>.btn
input[type=checkbox],.btn-group-toggle>.btn-group>.btn
input[type=radio]{position:absolute;clip:rect(0,0,0,0);pointer-events:none}.input-
group{position:relative;display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-wrap:wrap;flex-
wrap:wrap;-webkit-box-align:stretch;-ms-flex-align:stretch;align-items:stretch;width:100%}.input-
group>.custom-file,.input-group>.custom-select,.input-group>.form-control{position:relative;-
webkit-box-flex:1;-ms-flex:1 1 auto;flex:1 1 auto;width:1%;margin-bottom:0}.input-group>.custom-
file:focus,.input-group>.custom-select:focus,.input-group>.form-control:focus{z-index:3}.input-
group>.custom-file+.custom-file,.input-group>.custom-file+.custom-select,.input-group>.custom-
file+.form-control,.input-group>.custom-select+.custom-file,.input-group>.custom-select+.custom-
select,.input-group>.custom-select+.form-control,.input-group>.form-control+.custom-file,.input-
group>.form-control+.custom-select,.input-group>.form-control+.form-control{margin-left:-
1px}.input-group>.custom-select:not(:last-child),.input-group>.form-control:not(:last-child){border-
top-right-radius:0;border-bottom-right-radius:0}.input-group>.custom-select:not(:first-child),.input-
group>.form-control:not(:first-child){border-top-left-radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.input-
group>.custom-file{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-align:center;-
ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center}.input-group>.custom-file:not(:last-child)
.custom-file-
label,.input-group>.custom-file:not(:last-child)
.custom-file-label::before{border-top-right-
radius:0;border-bottom-right-radius:0}.input-group>.custom-file:not(:first-child)
.custom-file-
label,.input-group>.custom-file:not(:first-child)
.custom-file-label::before{border-top-left-
radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.input-group-append,.input-group-prepend{display:-webkit-
box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex}.input-group-append
.btn,.input-group-prepend
.btn{position:relative;z-index:2}.input-group-append .btn+.btn,.input-group-append .btn+.input-
group-text,.input-group-append
.input-group-text+.btn,.input-group-append
.input-group-
text+.input-group-text,.input-group-prepend .btn+.btn,.input-group-prepend .btn+.input-group-
text,.input-group-prepend
.input-group-text+.btn,.input-group-prepend
.input-group-text+.input-
group-text{margin-left:-1px}.input-group-prepend{margin-right:-1px}.input-group-append{margin-
left:-1px}.input-group-text{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-
align:center;-ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center;padding:.375rem
.75rem;margin-
bottom:0;font-size:1rem;font-weight:400;line-height:1.5;color:#495057;text-align:center;white-
space:nowrap;background-color:#e9ecef;border:1px solid #ced4da;border-radius:.25rem}.input-
group-text
input[type=checkbox],.input-group-text
input[type=radio]{margin-top:0}.input-
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group>.input-group-append:last-child>.btn:not(:last-child):not(.dropdown-toggle),.input-
group>.input-group-append:last-child>.input-group-text:not(:last-child),.input-group>.input-group-
append:not(:last-child)>.btn,.input-group>.input-group-append:not(:last-child)>.input-group-
text,.input-group>.input-group-prepend>.btn,.input-group>.input-group-prepend>.input-group-
text{border-top-right-radius:0;border-bottom-right-radius:0}.input-group>.input-group-
append>.btn,.input-group>.input-group-append>.input-group-text,.input-group>.input-group-
prepend:first-child>.btn:not(:first-child),.input-group>.input-group-prepend:first-child>.input-group-
text:not(:first-child),.input-group>.input-group-prepend:not(:first-child)>.btn,.input-group>.input-
group-prepend:not(:first-child)>.input-group-text{border-top-left-radius:0;border-bottom-left-
radius:0}.custom-control{position:relative;display:block;min-height:1.5rem;padding-
left:1.5rem}.custom-control-inline{display:-webkit-inline-box;display:-ms-inline-
flexbox;display:inline-flex;margin-right:1rem}.custom-control-input{position:absolute;z-index:-
1;opacity:0}.custom-control-input:checked~.custom-control-label::before{color:#fff;background-
color:#007bff}.custom-control-input:focus~.custom-control-label::before{box-shadow:0 0 0 1px
#fff,0 0 0 .2rem rgba(0,123,255,.25)}.custom-control-input:active~.custom-control-
label::before{color:#fff;background-color:#b3d7ff}.custom-control-input:disabled~.custom-control-
label{color:#6c757d}.custom-control-input:disabled~.custom-control-label::before{background-
color:#e9ecef}.custom-control-label{margin-bottom:0}.custom-control-
label::before{position:absolute;top:.25rem;left:0;display:block;width:1rem;height:1rem;pointer-
events:none;content:"";-webkit-user-select:none;-moz-user-select:none;-ms-user-select:none;user-
select:none;background-color:#dee2e6}.custom-control-
label::after{position:absolute;top:.25rem;left:0;display:block;width:1rem;height:1rem;content:"";ba
ckground-repeat:no-repeat;background-position:center center;background-size:50% 50%}.custom-
checkbox .custom-control-label::before{border-radius:.25rem}.custom-checkbox .custom-control-
input:checked~.custom-control-label::before{background-color:#007bff}.custom-checkbox .custom-
control-input:checked~.custom-control-label::after{background-
image:url("data:image/svg+xml;charset=utf8,%3Csvg xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg'
viewBox='0 0 8 8'%3E%3Cpath fill='%23fff' d='M6.564.75l-3.59 3.612-1.538-1.55L0 4.26 2.974 7.25 8
2.193z'%3E%3C/svg%3E")}.custom-checkbox .custom-control-input:indeterminate~.custom-
control-label::before{background-color:#007bff}.custom-checkbox .custom-control-
input:indeterminate~.custom-control-label::after{background-
image:url("data:image/svg+xml;charset=utf8,%3Csvg xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg'
viewBox='0 0 4 4'%3E%3Cpath stroke='%23fff' d='M0 2h4'%3E%3C/svg%3E")}.custom-checkbox
.custom-control-input:disabled:checked~.custom-control-label::before{background-
color:rgba(0,123,255,.5)}.custom-checkbox .custom-control-input:disabled:indeterminate~.custom-
control-label::before{background-color:rgba(0,123,255,.5)}.custom-radio .custom-control-
label::before{border-radius:50%}.custom-radio .custom-control-input:checked~.custom-control-
label::before{background-color:#007bff}.custom-radio .custom-control-input:checked~.custom-
control-label::after{background-image:url("data:image/svg+xml;charset=utf8,%3Csvg
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='-4 -4 8 8'%3E%3Ccircle r='3'
fill='%23fff'%3E%3C/svg%3E")}.custom-radio .custom-control-input:disabled:checked~.custom-
control-label::before{background-color:rgba(0,123,255,.5)}.custom-select{display:inline-
block;width:100%;height:calc(2.25rem + 2px);padding:.375rem 1.75rem .375rem .75rem;line-
height:1.5;color:#495057;vertical-align:middle;background:#fff
url("data:image/svg+xml;charset=utf8,%3Csvg xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' viewBox='0 0 4
5'%3E%3Cpath fill='%23343a40' d='M2 0L0 2h4zm0 5L0 3h4z'%3E%3C/svg%3E") no-repeat right
.75rem center;background-size:8px 10px;border:1px solid #ced4da;border-radius:.25rem;-webkit-
appearance:none;-moz-appearance:none;appearance:none}.custom-select:focus{border-
color:#80bdff;outline:0;box-shadow:inset 0 1px 2px rgba(0,0,0,.075),0 0 5px
rgba(128,189,255,.5)}.custom-select:focus::-ms-value{color:#495057;background-color:#fff}.custom-
select[multiple],.custom-select[size]:not([size="1"]){height:auto;padding-right:.75rem;background-
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image:none}.custom-select:disabled{color:#6c757d;background-color:#e9ecef}.custom-select::-ms-expand{opacity:0}.custom-select-sm{height:calc(1.8125rem + 2px);padding-top:.375rem;padding-bottom:.375rem;font-size:75%}.custom-select-lg{height:calc(2.875rem + 2px);padding-top:.375rem;padding-bottom:.375rem;font-size:125%}.custom-file{position:relative;display:inline-block;width:100%;height:calc(2.25rem + 2px);margin-bottom:0}.custom-file-input{position:relative;z-index:2;width:100%;height:calc(2.25rem + 2px);margin:0;opacity:0}.custom-file-input:focus~.custom-file-control{border-color:#80bdff;box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem rgba(0,123,255,.25)}.custom-file-input:focus~.custom-file-control::before{border-color:#80bdff}.custom-file-input:lang(en)~.custom-file-label::after{content:"Browse"}.custom-file-label{position:absolute;top:0;right:0;left:0;z-index:1;height:calc(2.25rem + 2px);padding:.375rem .75rem;line-height:1.5;color:#495057;background-color:#fff;border:1px solid #ced4da;border-radius:.25rem}.custom-file-label::after{position:absolute;top:0;right:0;bottom:0;z-index:3;display:block;height:calc(calc(2.25rem + 2px) - 1px * 2);padding:.375rem .75rem;line-height:1.5;color:#495057;content:"Browse";background-color:#e9ecef;border-left:1px solid #ced4da;border-radius:0 .25rem .25rem 0}.nav{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-wrap:wrap;flex-wrap:wrap;padding-left:0;margin-bottom:0;list-style:none}.nav-link{display:block;padding:.5rem 1rem}.nav-link:focus,.nav-link:hover{text-decoration:none}.nav-link.disabled{color:#6c757d}.nav-tabs{border-bottom:1px solid #dee2e6}.nav-tabs .nav-item{margin-bottom:-1px}.nav-tabs .nav-link{border:1px solid transparent;border-top-left-radius:.25rem;border-top-right-radius:.25rem}.nav-tabs .nav-link:focus,.nav-tabs .nav-link:hover{border-color:#e9ecef #e9ecef #dee2e6}.nav-tabs .nav-link.disabled{color:#6c757d;background-color:transparent;border-color:transparent}.nav-tabs .nav-item.show .nav-link,.nav-tabs .nav-link.active{color:#495057;background-color:#fff;border-color:#dee2e6 #dee2e6 #fff}.nav-tabs .dropdown-menu{margin-top:-1px;border-top-left-radius:0;border-top-right-radius:0}.nav-pills .nav-link{border-radius:.25rem}.nav-pills .nav-link.active,.nav-pills .show>.nav-link{color:#fff;background-color:#007bff}.nav-fill .nav-item{-webkit-box-flex:1;-ms-flex:1 1 auto;flex:1 1 auto;text-align:center}.nav-justified .nav-item{-ms-flex-preferred-size:0;flex-basis:0;-webkit-box-flex:1;-ms-flex-positive:1;flex-grow:1;text-align:center}.tab-content>.tab-pane{display:none}.tab-content>.active{display:block}.navbar{position:relative;display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-wrap:wrap;flex-wrap:wrap;-webkit-box-align:center;-ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center;-webkit-box-pack:justify;-ms-flex-pack:justify;justify-content:space-between;padding:.5rem 1rem}.navbar>.container,.navbar>.container-fluid{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-wrap:wrap;flex-wrap:wrap;-webkit-box-align:center;-ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center;-webkit-box-pack:justify;-ms-flex-pack:justify;justify-content:space-between}.navbar-brand{display:inline-block;padding-top:.3125rem;padding-bottom:.3125rem;margin-right:1rem;font-size:1.25rem;line-height:inherit;white-space:nowrap}.navbar-brand:focus,.navbar-brand:hover{text-decoration:none}.navbar-nav{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-orient:vertical;-webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-flex-direction:column;flex-direction:column;padding-left:0;margin-bottom:0;list-style:none}.navbar-nav .nav-link{padding-right:0;padding-left:0}.navbar-nav .dropdown-menu{position:static;float:none}.navbar-text{display:inline-block;padding-top:.5rem;padding-bottom:.5rem}.navbar-collapse{-ms-flex-preferred-size:100%;flex-basis:100%;-webkit-box-flex:1;-ms-flex-positive:1;flex-grow:1;-webkit-box-align:center;-ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center}.navbar-toggler{padding:.25rem .75rem;font-size:1.25rem;line-height:1;background-color:transparent;border:1px solid transparent;border-radius:.25rem}.navbar-toggler:focus,.navbar-toggler:hover{text-decoration:none}.navbar-toggler:not(:disabled):not(.disabled){cursor:pointer}.navbar-toggler-icon{display:inline-block;width:1.5em;height:1.5em;vertical-align:middle;content:"";background:no-repeat center center;background-size:100% 100%}@media (max-width:575.98px){.navbar-expand-sm>.container,.navbar-expand-sm>.container-fluid{padding-right:0;padding-left:0}}@media (min-

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width:576px){.navbar-expand-sm{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal;-webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-
flex-flow:row nowrap;flex-flow:row nowrap;-webkit-box-pack:start;-ms-flex-pack:start;justify-
content:flex-start}.navbar-expand-sm .navbar-nav{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal;-webkit-box-
direction:normal;-ms-flex-direction:row;flex-direction:row}.navbar-expand-sm .navbar-nav
.dropdown-menu{position:absolute}.navbar-expand-sm .navbar-nav .dropdown-menu-
right{right:0;left:auto}.navbar-expand-sm .navbar-nav .nav-link{padding-right:.5rem;padding-
left:.5rem}.navbar-expand-sm>.container,.navbar-expand-sm>.container-fluid{-ms-flex-
wrap:nowrap;flex-wrap:nowrap}.navbar-expand-sm .navbar-collapse{display:-webkit-
box!important;display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important;-ms-flex-preferred-
size:auto;flex-basis:auto}.navbar-expand-sm .navbar-toggler{display:none}.navbar-expand-sm
.dropdown .dropdown-menu{top:auto;bottom:100%}}@media (max-width:767.98px){.navbar-expand-
md>.container,.navbar-expand-md>.container-fluid{padding-right:0;padding-left:0}}@media (min-
width:768px){.navbar-expand-md{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal;-webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-
flex-flow:row nowrap;flex-flow:row nowrap;-webkit-box-pack:start;-ms-flex-pack:start;justify-
content:flex-start}.navbar-expand-md .navbar-nav{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal;-webkit-box-
direction:normal;-ms-flex-direction:row;flex-direction:row}.navbar-expand-md .navbar-nav
.dropdown-menu{position:absolute}.navbar-expand-md .navbar-nav .dropdown-menu-
right{right:0;left:auto}.navbar-expand-md .navbar-nav .nav-link{padding-right:.5rem;padding-
left:.5rem}.navbar-expand-md>.container,.navbar-expand-md>.container-fluid{-ms-flex-
wrap:nowrap;flex-wrap:nowrap}.navbar-expand-md .navbar-collapse{display:-webkit-
box!important;display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important;-ms-flex-preferred-
size:auto;flex-basis:auto}.navbar-expand-md .navbar-toggler{display:none}.navbar-expand-md
.dropdown .dropdown-menu{top:auto;bottom:100%}}@media (max-width:991.98px){.navbar-expand-
lg>.container,.navbar-expand-lg>.container-fluid{padding-right:0;padding-left:0}}@media (min-
width:992px){.navbar-expand-lg{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal;-webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-
flex-flow:row nowrap;flex-flow:row nowrap;-webkit-box-pack:start;-ms-flex-pack:start;justify-
content:flex-start}.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-nav{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal;-webkit-box-
direction:normal;-ms-flex-direction:row;flex-direction:row}.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-nav
.dropdown-menu{position:absolute}.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-nav .dropdown-menu-
right{right:0;left:auto}.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-nav .nav-link{padding-right:.5rem;padding-
left:.5rem}.navbar-expand-lg>.container,.navbar-expand-lg>.container-fluid{-ms-flex-
wrap:nowrap;flex-wrap:nowrap}.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-collapse{display:-webkit-
box!important;display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important;-ms-flex-preferred-
size:auto;flex-basis:auto}.navbar-expand-lg .navbar-toggler{display:none}.navbar-expand-lg .dropdown
.dropdown-menu{top:auto;bottom:100%}}@media (max-width:1199.98px){.navbar-expand-
xl>.container,.navbar-expand-xl>.container-fluid{padding-right:0;padding-left:0}}@media (min-
width:1200px){.navbar-expand-xl{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal;-webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-
flex-flow:row nowrap;flex-flow:row nowrap;-webkit-box-pack:start;-ms-flex-pack:start;justify-
content:flex-start}.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-nav{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal;-webkit-box-
direction:normal;-ms-flex-direction:row;flex-direction:row}.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-nav
.dropdown-menu{position:absolute}.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-nav .dropdown-menu-
right{right:0;left:auto}.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-nav .nav-link{padding-right:.5rem;padding-
left:.5rem}.navbar-expand-xl>.container,.navbar-expand-xl>.container-fluid{-ms-flex-
wrap:nowrap;flex-wrap:nowrap}.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-collapse{display:-webkit-
box!important;display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important;-ms-flex-preferred-
size:auto;flex-basis:auto}.navbar-expand-xl .navbar-toggler{display:none}.navbar-expand-xl .dropdown
.dropdown-menu{top:auto;bottom:100%}}.navbar-expand{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal;-webkit-
box-direction:normal;-ms-flex-flow:row nowrap;flex-flow:row nowrap;-webkit-box-pack:start;-ms-
flex-pack:start;justify-content:flex-start}.navbar-expand>.container,.navbar-expand>.container-
fluid{padding-right:0;padding-left:0}.navbar-expand .navbar-nav{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal;-
webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-flex-direction:row;flex-direction:row}.navbar-expand .navbar-nav
```

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.dropdown-menu{position:absolute}.navbar-expand
right{right:0;left:auto}.navbar-expand
.navbar-nav
.dropdown-menu-
left{left:5rem}.navbar-expand>.container,.navbar-expand>.container-fluid{-ms-flex-wrap:nowrap;flex-
wrap:nowrap}.navbar-expand
.navbar-collapse{display:-webkit-box!important;display:-ms-
flexbox!important;display:flex!important;-ms-flex-preferred-size:auto;flex-basis:auto}.navbar-
expand
.navbar-toggler{display:none}.navbar-expand
.dropdown-
menu{top:auto;bottom:100%}.navbar-light
.navbar-brand{color:rgba(0,0,0,.9)}.navbar-light
.navbar-
brand:focus,.navbar-light
.navbar-brand: hover{color:rgba(0,0,0,.9)}.navbar-light
.navbar-nav
.nav-
link{color:rgba(0,0,0,.5)}.navbar-light
.navbar-nav
.nav-link:focus,.navbar-light
.navbar-nav
.nav-
link: hover{color:rgba(0,0,0,.7)}.navbar-light
.navbar-nav
.nav-
link.disabled{color:rgba(0,0,0,.3)}.navbar-light
.navbar-nav
.active>.nav-link,.navbar-light
.navbar-nav
.nav-link.active,.navbar-light
.navbar-nav
.nav-link.show,.navbar-light
.navbar-nav
.show>.nav-
link{color:rgba(0,0,0,.9)}.navbar-light
.navbar-toggler{color:rgba(0,0,0,.5);border-
color:rgba(0,0,0,.1)}.navbar-light
.navbar-toggler-icon{background-
image:url("data:image/svg+xml;charset=utf8,%3Csvg
viewBox='0 0 30 30'
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg'%3E%3Cpath stroke='rgba(0, 0, 0, 0.5)' stroke-width='2'
stroke-linecap='round' stroke-miterlimit='10' d='M4 7h22M4 15h22M4
23h22'/%3E%3C/svg%3E")}.navbar-light
.navbar-text{color:rgba(0,0,0,.5)}.navbar-light
.navbar-text
a{color:rgba(0,0,0,.9)}.navbar-light
.navbar-text
a:focus,.navbar-light
.navbar-text
a: hover{color:rgba(0,0,0,.9)}.navbar-dark
.navbar-brand{color:#fff}.navbar-dark
.navbar-
brand:focus,.navbar-dark
.navbar-brand: hover{color:#fff}.navbar-dark
.navbar-nav
.nav-
link{color:rgba(255,255,255,.5)}.navbar-dark
.navbar-nav
.nav-link:focus,.navbar-dark
.navbar-nav
.nav-link: hover{color:rgba(255,255,255,.75)}.navbar-dark
.navbar-nav
.nav-
link.disabled{color:rgba(255,255,255,.25)}.navbar-dark
.navbar-nav
.active>.nav-link,.navbar-dark
.navbar-nav
.nav-link.active,.navbar-dark
.navbar-nav
.nav-link.show,.navbar-dark
.navbar-nav
.show>.nav-link{color:#fff}.navbar-dark
.navbar-toggler{color:rgba(255,255,255,.5);border-
color:rgba(255,255,255,.1)}.navbar-dark
.navbar-toggler-icon{background-
image:url("data:image/svg+xml;charset=utf8,%3Csvg
viewBox='0 0 30 30'
xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg'%3E%3Cpath stroke='rgba(255, 255, 255, 0.5)' stroke-width='2'
stroke-linecap='round' stroke-miterlimit='10' d='M4 7h22M4 15h22M4
23h22'/%3E%3C/svg%3E")}.navbar-dark
.navbar-text{color:rgba(255,255,255,.5)}.navbar-dark
.navbar-text
a{color:#fff}.navbar-dark
.navbar-text
a:focus,.navbar-dark
.navbar-text
a: hover{color:#fff}.card{position:relative;display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-
webkit-box-orient:vertical;-webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-flex-direction:column;flex-
direction:column;min-width:0;word-wrap:break-word;background-color:#fff;background-
clip:border-box;border:1px solid rgba(0,0,0,.125);border-radius:.25rem}.card>hr{margin-
right:0;margin-left:0}.card>.list-group:first-child
.list-group-item:first-child{border-top-left-
radius:.25rem;border-top-right-radius:.25rem}.card>.list-group:last-child
.list-group-item:last-
child{border-bottom-right-radius:.25rem;border-bottom-left-radius:.25rem}.card-body{-webkit-box-
flex:1;-ms-flex:1 1 auto;flex:1 1 auto;padding:1.25rem}.card-title{margin-bottom:.75rem}.card-
subtitle{margin-top:-.375rem;margin-bottom:0}.card-text:last-child{margin-bottom:0}.card-
link: hover{text-decoration:none}.card-link+.card-link{margin-left:1.25rem}.card-
header{padding:.75rem 1.25rem;margin-bottom:0;background-color:rgba(0,0,0,.03);border-
bottom:1px solid rgba(0,0,0,.125)}.card-header:first-child{border-radius:calc(.25rem - 1px)
calc(.25rem - 1px) 0 0}.card-header+.list-group
.list-group-item:first-child{border-top:0}.card-
footer{padding:.75rem 1.25rem;background-color:rgba(0,0,0,.03);border-top:1px solid
rgba(0,0,0,.125)}.card-footer:last-child{border-radius:0 0 calc(.25rem - 1px) calc(.25rem - 1px)}.card-
header-tabs{margin-right:-.625rem;margin-bottom:-.75rem;margin-left:-.625rem;border-
bottom:0}.card-header-pills{margin-right:-.625rem;margin-left:-.625rem}.card-img-
overlay{position:absolute;top:0;right:0;bottom:0;left:0;padding:1.25rem}.card-
img{width:100%;border-radius:calc(.25rem - 1px)}.card-img-top{width:100%;border-top-left-
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radius:calc(.25rem - 1px);border-top-right-radius:calc(.25rem - 1px)}.card-img-
bottom{width:100%;border-bottom-right-radius:calc(.25rem - 1px);border-bottom-left-
radius:calc(.25rem - 1px)}.card-deck{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-
box-orient:vertical;-webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-flex-direction:column;flex-
direction:column}.card-deck .card{margin-bottom:15px}@media (min-width:576px){.card-deck{-
webkit-box-orient:horizontal;-webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-flex-flow:row wrap;flex-flow:row
wrap;margin-right:-15px;margin-left:-15px}.card-deck .card{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-
flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-flex:1;-ms-flex:1 0 0%;flex:1 0 0%;-webkit-box-orient:vertical;-
webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-flex-direction:column;flex-direction:column;margin-
right:15px;margin-bottom:0;margin-left:15px}}.card-group{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-
flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-orient:vertical;-webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-flex-
direction:column;flex-direction:column}.card-group>.card{margin-bottom:15px}@media (min-
width:576px){.card-group{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal;-webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-flex-
flow:row wrap;flex-flow:row wrap}.card-group>.card{-webkit-box-flex:1;-ms-flex:1 0 0%;flex:1 0
0%;margin-bottom:0}.card-group>.card+.card{margin-left:0;border-left:0}.card-group>.card:first-
child{border-top-right-radius:0;border-bottom-right-radius:0}.card-group>.card:first-child .card-
header,.card-group>.card:first-child .card-img-top{border-top-right-radius:0}.card-group>.card:first-
child .card-footer,.card-group>.card:first-child .card-img-bottom{border-bottom-right-radius:0}.card-
group>.card:last-child{border-top-left-radius:0;border-bottom-left-radius:0}.card-group>.card:last-
child .card-header,.card-group>.card:last-child .card-img-top{border-top-left-radius:0}.card-
group>.card:last-child .card-footer,.card-group>.card:last-child .card-img-bottom{border-bottom-
left-radius:0}.card-group>.card:only-child{border-radius:.25rem}.card-group>.card:only-child .card-
header,.card-group>.card:only-child .card-img-top{border-top-left-radius:.25rem;border-top-right-
radius:.25rem}.card-group>.card:only-child .card-footer,.card-group>.card:only-child .card-img-
bottom{border-bottom-right-radius:.25rem;border-bottom-left-radius:.25rem}.card-
group>.card:not(:first-child):not(:last-child):not(:only-child){border-radius:0}.card-
group>.card:not(:first-child):not(:last-child):not(:only-child) .card-footer,.card-group>.card:not(:first-
child):not(:last-child):not(:only-child) .card-header,.card-group>.card:not(:first-child):not(:last-
child):not(:only-child) .card-img-bottom,.card-group>.card:not(:first-child):not(:last-child):not(:only-
child) .card-img-top{border-radius:0}}.card-columns .card{margin-bottom:.75rem}@media (min-
width:576px){.card-columns{-webkit-column-count:3;-moz-column-count:3;column-count:3;-webkit-
column-gap:1.25rem;-moz-column-gap:1.25rem;column-gap:1.25rem}.card-columns
.card{display:inline-block;width:100%}}.breadcrumb{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-
flexbox;display:flex;-ms-flex-wrap:wrap;flex-wrap:wrap;padding:.75rem 1rem;margin-
bottom:1rem;list-style:none;background-color:#e9ecef;border-radius:.25rem}.breadcrumb-
item+.breadcrumb-item::before{display:inline-block;padding-right:.5rem;padding-
left:.5rem;color:#6c757d;content:"/"}.breadcrumb-item+.breadcrumb-item:hover::before{text-
decoration:underline}.breadcrumb-item+.breadcrumb-item:hover::before{text-
decoration:none}.breadcrumb-item.active{color:#6c757d}.pagination{display:-webkit-box;display:-
ms-flexbox;display:flex;padding-left:0;list-style:none;border-radius:.25rem}.page-
link{position:relative;display:block;padding:.5rem .75rem;margin-left:-1px;line-
height:1.25;color:#007bff;background-color:#fff;border:1px solid #dee2e6}.page-
link:hover{color:#0056b3;text-decoration:none;background-color:#e9ecef;border-
color:#dee2e6}.page-link:focus{z-index:2;outline:0;box-shadow:0 0 0 .2rem
rgba(0,123,255,.25)}.page-link:not(:disabled):not(.disabled){cursor:pointer}.page-item:first-child
.page-link{margin-left:0;border-top-left-radius:.25rem;border-bottom-left-radius:.25rem}.page-
item:last-child .page-link{border-top-right-radius:.25rem;border-bottom-right-radius:.25rem}.page-
item.active .page-link{z-index:1;color:#fff;background-color:#007bff;border-color:#007bff}.page-
item.disabled .page-link{color:#6c757d;pointer-events:none;cursor:auto;background-
color:#fff;border-color:#dee2e6}.pagination-lg .page-link{padding:.75rem 1.5rem;font-
size:1.25rem;line-height:1.5}.pagination-lg .page-item:first-child .page-link{border-top-left-
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radius:.3rem;border-bottom-left-radius:.3rem}.pagination-lg .page-item:last-child .page-link{border-top-right-radius:.3rem;border-bottom-right-radius:.3rem}.pagination-sm .page-link{padding:.25rem .5rem;font-size:.875rem;line-height:1.5}.pagination-sm .page-item:first-child .page-link{border-top-left-radius:.2rem;border-bottom-left-radius:.2rem}.pagination-sm .page-item:last-child .page-link{border-top-right-radius:.2rem;border-bottom-right-radius:.2rem}.badge{display:inline-block;padding:.25em .4em;font-size:75%;font-weight:700;line-height:1;text-align:center;white-space:nowrap;vertical-align:baseline;border-radius:.25rem}.badge:empty{display:none}.btn .badge{position:relative;top:-1px}.badge-pill{padding-right:.6em;padding-left:.6em;border-radius:10rem}.badge-primary{color:#fff;background-color:#007bff}.badge-primary[href]:focus,.badge-primary[href]:hover{color:#fff;text-decoration:none;background-color:#0062cc}.badge-secondary{color:#fff;background-color:#6c757d}.badge-secondary[href]:focus,.badge-secondary[href]:hover{color:#fff;text-decoration:none;background-color:#545b62}.badge-success{color:#fff;background-color:#28a745}.badge-success[href]:focus,.badge-success[href]:hover{color:#fff;text-decoration:none;background-color:#1e7e34}.badge-info{color:#fff;background-color:#17a2b8}.badge-info[href]:focus,.badge-info[href]:hover{color:#fff;text-decoration:none;background-color:#117a8b}.badge-warning{color:#212529;background-color:#ffc107}.badge-warning[href]:focus,.badge-warning[href]:hover{color:#212529;text-decoration:none;background-color:#d39e00}.badge-danger{color:#fff;background-color:#dc3545}.badge-danger[href]:focus,.badge-danger[href]:hover{color:#fff;text-decoration:none;background-color:#bd2130}.badge-light{color:#212529;background-color:#f8f9fa}.badge-light[href]:focus,.badge-light[href]:hover{color:#212529;text-decoration:none;background-color:#dae0e5}.badge-dark{color:#fff;background-color:#343a40}.badge-dark[href]:focus,.badge-dark[href]:hover{color:#fff;text-decoration:none;background-color:#1d2124}.jumbotron{padding:2rem 1rem;margin-bottom:2rem;background-color:#e9ecef;border-radius:.3rem}@media (min-width:576px){.jumbotron{padding:4rem 2rem}}.jumbotron-fluid{padding-right:0;padding-left:0;border-radius:0}.alert{position:relative;padding:.75rem 1.25rem;margin-bottom:1rem;border:1px solid transparent;border-radius:.25rem}.alert-heading{color:inherit}.alert-link{font-weight:700}.alert-dismissible{padding-right:4rem}.alert-dismissible .close{position:absolute;top:0;right:0;padding:.75rem 1.25rem;color:inherit}.alert-primary{color:#004085;background-color:#cce5ff;border-color:#b8daff}.alert-primary hr{border-top-color:#9fcdff}.alert-primary .alert-link{color:#002752}.alert-secondary{color:#383d41;background-color:#e2e3e5;border-color:#d6d8db}.alert-secondary hr{border-top-color:#c8cbcf}.alert-secondary .alert-link{color:#202326}.alert-success{color:#155724;background-color:#d4edda;border-color:#c3e6cb}.alert-success hr{border-top-color:#b1dfbb}.alert-success .alert-link{color:#0b2e13}.alert-info{color:#0c5460;background-color:#d1ecf1;border-color:#bee5eb}.alert-info hr{border-top-color:#abdde5}.alert-info .alert-link{color:#062c33}.alert-warning{color:#856404;background-color:#fff3cd;border-color:#ffeeba}.alert-warning hr{border-top-color:#ffe8a1}.alert-warning .alert-link{color:#533f03}.alert-danger{color:#721c24;background-color:#f8d7da;border-color:#f5c6cb}.alert-danger hr{border-top-color:#f1b0b7}.alert-danger .alert-link{color:#491217}.alert-light{color:#818182;background-color:#fefefe;border-color:#fdfdfe}.alert-light hr{border-top-color:#ececfc}.alert-light .alert-link{color:#686868}.alert-dark{color:#1b1e21;background-color:#d6d8d9;border-color:#c6c8ca}.alert-dark hr{border-top-color:#b9bbbe}.alert-dark .alert-link{color:#040505}@-webkit-keyframes progress-bar-stripes{from{background-position:1rem 0}to{background-position:0 0}}@keyframes progress-bar-stripes{from{background-position:1rem 0}to{background-position:0 0}}.progress{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;height:1rem;overflow:hidden;font-size:.75rem;background-color:#e9ecef;border-radius:.25rem}.progress-bar{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-orient:vertical;-webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-flex-direction:column;flex-direction:column;-webkit-box-pack:center;-ms-flex-pack:center;justify-

content:center;color:#fff;text-align:center;background-color:#007bff;transition:width .6s ease).progress-bar-striped{background-image:linear-gradient(45deg,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 25%,transparent 25%,transparent 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 50%,rgba(255,255,255,.15) 75%,transparent 75%,transparent);background-size:1rem 1rem}.progress-bar-animated{-webkit-animation:progress-bar-stripes 1s linear infinite;animation:progress-bar-stripes 1s linear infinite}.media{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-align:start;-ms-flex-align:start;align-items:flex-start}.media-body{-webkit-box-flex:1;-ms-flex:1;flex:1}.list-group{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-orient:vertical;-webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-flex-direction:column;flex-direction:column;padding-left:0;margin-bottom:0}.list-group-item-action{width:100%;color:#495057;text-align:inherit}.list-group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-action:hover{color:#495057;text-decoration:none;background-color:#f8f9fa}.list-group-item-action:active{color:#212529;background-color:#e9ecef}.list-group-item{position:relative;display:block;padding:.75rem 1.25rem;margin-bottom:-1px;background-color:#fff;border:1px solid rgba(0,0,0,.125)}.list-group-item:first-child{border-top-left-radius:.25rem;border-top-right-radius:.25rem}.list-group-item:last-child{margin-bottom:0;border-bottom-right-radius:.25rem;border-bottom-left-radius:.25rem}.list-group-item:focus,.list-group-item:hover{z-index:1;text-decoration:none}.list-group-item.disabled,.list-group-item:disabled{color:#6c757d;background-color:#fff}.list-group-item.active{z-index:2;color:#fff;background-color:#007bff;border-color:#007bff}.list-group-flush .list-group-item{border-right:0;border-left:0;border-radius:0}.list-group-flush:first-child .list-group-item:first-child{border-top:0}.list-group-flush:last-child .list-group-item:last-child{border-bottom:0}.list-group-item-primary{color:#004085;background-color:#b8daff}.list-group-item-primary.list-group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-primary.list-group-item-action:hover{color:#004085;background-color:#9fcdff}.list-group-item-primary.list-group-item-action:active{color:#fff;background-color:#004085;border-color:#004085}.list-group-item-secondary{color:#383d41;background-color:#d6d8db}.list-group-item-secondary.list-group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-secondary.list-group-item-action:hover{color:#383d41;background-color:#c8cbcf}.list-group-item-secondary.list-group-item-action:active{color:#fff;background-color:#383d41;border-color:#383d41}.list-group-item-success{color:#155724;background-color:#c3e6cb}.list-group-item-success.list-group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-success.list-group-item-action:hover{color:#155724;background-color:#b1dfbb}.list-group-item-success.list-group-item-action:active{color:#fff;background-color:#155724;border-color:#155724}.list-group-item-info{color:#0c5460;background-color:#bee5eb}.list-group-item-info.list-group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-info.list-group-item-action:hover{color:#0c5460;background-color:#abdde5}.list-group-item-info.list-group-item-action:active{color:#fff;background-color:#0c5460;border-color:#0c5460}.list-group-item-warning{color:#856404;background-color:#ffeeba}.list-group-item-warning.list-group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-warning.list-group-item-action:hover{color:#856404;background-color:#ffe8a1}.list-group-item-warning.list-group-item-action:active{color:#fff;background-color:#856404;border-color:#856404}.list-group-item-danger{color:#721c24;background-color:#f5c6cb}.list-group-item-danger.list-group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-danger.list-group-item-action:hover{color:#721c24;background-color:#f1b0b7}.list-group-item-danger.list-group-item-action:active{color:#fff;background-color:#721c24;border-color:#721c24}.list-group-item-light{color:#818182;background-color:#fdfdfe}.list-group-item-light.list-group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-light.list-group-item-action:hover{color:#818182;background-color:#e9ecef}.list-group-item-light.list-group-item-action:active{color:#fff;background-color:#818182;border-color:#818182}.list-group-item-dark{color:#1b1e21;background-color:#c6c8ca}.list-group-item-dark.list-group-item-action:focus,.list-group-item-dark.list-group-item-action:hover{color:#1b1e21;background-color:#b9bbbe}.list-group-item-dark.list-group-item-action:active{color:#fff;background-color:#1b1e21;border-color:#1b1e21}.close{float:right;font-size:1.5rem;font-weight:700;line-height:1;color:#000;text-shadow:0 1px 0 #fff;opacity:.5}.close:focus,.close:hover{color:#000;text-

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decoration:none;opacity:.75}.close:not(:disabled):not(.disabled){cursor:pointer}button.close{padding:0;background-color:transparent;border:0;-webkit-appearance:none}.modal-open{overflow:hidden}.modal{position:fixed;top:0;right:0;bottom:0;left:0;z-index:1050;display:none;overflow:hidden;outline:0}.modal-open .modal{overflow-x:hidden;overflow-y:auto}.modal-dialog{position:relative;width:auto;margin:.5rem;pointer-events:none}.modal.fade .modal-dialog{transition:-webkit-transform .3s ease-out;transition:transform .3s ease-out;-webkit-transform:translate(0,-25%);transform:translate(0,-25%)}.modal.show .modal-dialog{-webkit-transform:translate(0,0);transform:translate(0,0)}.modal-dialog-centered{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-align:center;-ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center;min-height:calc(100% - (.5rem * 2))}.modal-content{position:relative;display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-orient:vertical;-webkit-box-direction:normal;-ms-flex-direction:column;flex-direction:column;width:100%;pointer-events:auto;background-color:#fff;background-clip:padding-box;border:1px solid rgba(0,0,0,.2);border-radius:.3rem;outline:0}.modal-backdrop{position:fixed;top:0;right:0;bottom:0;left:0;z-index:1040;background-color:#000}.modal-backdrop.fade{opacity:0}.modal-backdrop.show{opacity:.5}.modal-header{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-align:start;-ms-flex-align:start;align-items:flex-start;-webkit-box-pack:justify;-ms-flex-pack:justify;justify-content:space-between;padding:1rem;border-bottom:1px solid #e9ecef;border-top-left-radius:.3rem;border-top-right-radius:.3rem}.modal-header .close{padding:1rem 1rem 1rem auto}.modal-title{margin-bottom:0;line-height:1.5}.modal-body{position:relative;-webkit-box-flex:1;-ms-flex:1 1 auto;flex:1 1 auto;padding:1rem}.modal-footer{display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-align:center;-ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center;-webkit-box-pack:end;-ms-flex-pack:end;justify-content:flex-end;padding:1rem;border-top:1px solid #e9ecef}.modal-footer>:not(:first-child){margin-left:.25rem}.modal-footer>:not(:last-child){margin-right:.25rem}.modal-scrollbar-measure{position:absolute;top:-9999px;width:50px;height:50px;overflow:scroll}@media (min-width:576px){.modal-dialog{max-width:500px;margin:1.75rem auto}.modal-dialog-centered{min-height:calc(100% - (1.75rem * 2))}.modal-sm{max-width:300px}}@media (min-width:992px){.modal-lg{max-width:800px}}.tooltip{position:absolute;z-index:1070;display:block;margin:0;font-family:-apple-system,BlinkMacSystemFont,"Segoe UI",Roboto,"Helvetica Neue",Arial,sans-serif,"Apple Color Emoji","Segoe UI Emoji","Segoe UI Symbol";font-style:normal;font-weight:400;line-height:1.5;text-align:left;text-align:start;text-decoration:none;text-shadow:none;text-transform:none;letter-spacing:normal;word-break:normal;word-spacing:normal;white-space:normal;line-break:auto;font-size:.875rem;word-wrap:break-word;opacity:0}.tooltip.show{opacity:.9}.tooltip .arrow{position:absolute;display:block;width:.8rem;height:.4rem}.tooltip .arrow::before{position:absolute;content:"";border-color:transparent;border-style:solid}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=top],.bs-tooltip-top{padding:.4rem 0}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=top] .arrow,.bs-tooltip-top .arrow{bottom:0}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=top] .arrow::before,.bs-tooltip-top .arrow::before{top:0;border-width:.4rem .4rem 0;border-top-color:#000}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=right],.bs-tooltip-right{padding:0 .4rem}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=right] .arrow,.bs-tooltip-right .arrow{left:0;width:.4rem;height:.8rem}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=right] .arrow::before,.bs-tooltip-right .arrow::before{right:0;border-width:.4rem .4rem .4rem 0;border-right-color:#000}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=bottom],.bs-tooltip-bottom{padding:.4rem 0}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=bottom] .arrow,.bs-tooltip-bottom .arrow{top:0}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=bottom] .arrow::before,.bs-tooltip-bottom .arrow::before{bottom:0;border-width:0 .4rem .4rem 0;border-bottom-color:#000}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=left],.bs-tooltip-left{padding:0 .4rem}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=left] .arrow,.bs-tooltip-left .arrow{right:0;width:.4rem;height:.8rem}.bs-tooltip-auto[x-placement^=left] .arrow::before,.bs-tooltip-left .arrow::before{left:0;border-width:.4rem 0 .4rem .4rem;border-left-color:#000}.tooltip-inner{max-width:200px;padding:.25rem .5rem;color:#fff;text-align:center;background-
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color:#000;border-radius:.25rem}.popover{position:absolute;top:0;left:0;z-
index:1060;display:block;max-width:276px;font-family:-apple-system,BlinkMacSystemFont,"Segoe
UI",Roboto,"Helvetica Neue",Arial,sans-serif,"Apple Color Emoji","Segoe UI Emoji","Segoe UI
Symbol";font-style:normal;font-weight:400;line-height:1.5;text-align:left;text-align:start;text-
decoration:none;text-shadow:none;text-transform:none;letter-spacing:normal;word-
break:normal;word-spacing:normal;white-space:normal;line-break:auto;font-size:.875rem;word-
wrap:break-word;background-color:#fff;background-clip:padding-box;border:1px solid
rgba(0,0,0,.2);border-radius:.3rem}.popover
.arrow{position:absolute;display:block;width:1rem;height:.5rem;margin:0 .3rem}.popover
.arrow::after,.popover .arrow::before{position:absolute;display:block;content:"";border-
color:transparent;border-style:solid}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=top],.bs-popover-top{margin-
bottom:.5rem}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=top] .arrow,.bs-popover-top
.arrow{bottom:calc((.5rem + 1px) * -1)}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=top] .arrow::after,.bs-
popover-auto[x-placement^=top] .arrow::before,.bs-popover-top .arrow::after,.bs-popover-top
.arrow::before{border-width:.5rem .5rem 0}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=top] .arrow::before,.bs-
popover-top .arrow::before{bottom:0;border-top-color:rgba(0,0,0,.25)}.bs-popover-auto[x-
placement^=top] .arrow::after,.bs-popover-top .arrow::after{bottom:1px;border-top-color:#fff}.bs-
popover-auto[x-placement^=right],.bs-popover-right{margin-left:.5rem}.bs-popover-auto[x-
placement^=right] .arrow,.bs-popover-right .arrow{left:calc((.5rem + 1px) * -
1);width:.5rem;height:1rem;margin:.3rem 0}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=right] .arrow::after,.bs-
popover-auto[x-placement^=right] .arrow::before,.bs-popover-right .arrow::after,.bs-popover-right
.arrow::before{border-width:.5rem .5rem .5rem 0}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=right]
.arrow::before,.bs-popover-right .arrow::before{left:0;border-right-color:rgba(0,0,0,.25)}.bs-
popover-auto[x-placement^=right] .arrow::after,.bs-popover-right .arrow::after{left:1px;border-
right-color:#fff}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=bottom],.bs-popover-bottom{margin-top:.5rem}.bs-
popover-auto[x-placement^=bottom] .arrow,.bs-popover-bottom .arrow{top:calc((.5rem + 1px) * -
1)}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=bottom] .arrow::after,.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=bottom]
.arrow::before,.bs-popover-bottom .arrow::after,.bs-popover-bottom .arrow::before{border-width:0
.5rem .5rem .5rem}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=bottom] .arrow::before,.bs-popover-bottom
.arrow::before{top:0;border-bottom-color:rgba(0,0,0,.25)}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=bottom]
.arrow::after,.bs-popover-bottom .arrow::after{top:1px;border-bottom-color:#fff}.bs-popover-
auto[x-placement^=bottom] .popover-header::before,.bs-popover-bottom .popover-
header::before{position:absolute;top:0;left:50%;display:block;width:1rem;margin-left:-
.5rem;content:"";border-bottom:1px solid #f7f7f7}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=left],.bs-
popover-left{margin-right:.5rem}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=left] .arrow,.bs-popover-left
.arrow{right:calc((.5rem + 1px) * -1);width:.5rem;height:1rem;margin:.3rem 0}.bs-popover-auto[x-
placement^=left] .arrow::after,.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=left] .arrow::before,.bs-popover-left
.arrow::after,.bs-popover-left .arrow::before{border-width:.5rem 0 .5rem .5rem}.bs-popover-auto[x-
placement^=left] .arrow::before,.bs-popover-left .arrow::before{right:0;border-left-
color:rgba(0,0,0,.25)}.bs-popover-auto[x-placement^=left] .arrow::after,.bs-popover-left
.arrow::after{right:1px;border-left-color:#fff}.popover-header{padding:.5rem .75rem;margin-
bottom:0;font-size:1rem;color:inherit;background-color:#f7f7f7;border-bottom:1px solid
#ebebcb;border-top-left-radius:calc(.3rem - 1px);border-top-right-radius:calc(.3rem - 1px)}.popover-
header:empty{display:none}.popover-body{padding:.5rem .75rem;color:#212529}.carousel{position:relative}.carousel-
inner{position:relative;width:100%;overflow:hidden}.carousel-item{position:relative;display:none;-
webkit-box-align:center;-ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center;width:100%;transition:-webkit-
transform .6s ease;transition:transform .6s ease;transition:transform .6s ease,-webkit-transform .6s
ease;-webkit-backface-visibility:hidden;backface-visibility:hidden;-webkit-
perspective:1000px;perspective:1000px}.carousel-item-next,.carousel-item-prev,.carousel-
item.active{display:block}.carousel-item-next,.carousel-item-prev{position:absolute;top:0}carousel-
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item-next.carousel-item-left,.carousel-item-prev.carousel-item-right{-webkit-transform:translateX(0);transform:translateX(0)}@supports ((-webkit-transform-style:preserve-3d) or (transform-style:preserve-3d)){.carousel-item-next.carousel-item-left,.carousel-item-prev.carousel-item-right{-webkit-transform:translate3d(0,0,0);transform:translate3d(0,0,0)}}.active.carousel-item-right,.carousel-item-next{-webkit-transform:translateX(100%);transform:translateX(100%)}@supports ((-webkit-transform-style:preserve-3d) or (transform-style:preserve-3d)){.active.carousel-item-right,.carousel-item-next{-webkit-transform:translate3d(100%,0,0);transform:translate3d(100%,0,0)}}.active.carousel-item-left,.carousel-item-prev{-webkit-transform:translateX(-100%);transform:translateX(-100%)}@supports ((-webkit-transform-style:preserve-3d) or (transform-style:preserve-3d)){.active.carousel-item-left,.carousel-item-prev{-webkit-transform:translate3d(-100%,0,0);transform:translate3d(-100%,0,0)}}.carousel-control-next,.carousel-control-prev{position:absolute;top:0;bottom:0;display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-align:center;-ms-flex-align:center;align-items:center;-webkit-box-pack:center;-ms-flex-pack:center;justify-content:center;width:15%;color:#fff;text-align:center;opacity:.5}.carousel-control-next:focus,.carousel-control-next:hover,.carousel-control-prev:focus,.carousel-control-prev:hover{color:#fff;text-decoration:none;outline:0;opacity:.9}.carousel-control-prev{left:0}.carousel-control-next{right:0}.carousel-control-next-icon,.carousel-control-prev-icon{display:inline-block;width:20px;height:20px;background:transparent no-repeat center center;background-size:100% 100%}.carousel-control-prev-icon{background-image:url("data:image/svg+xml;charset=utf8,%3Csvg xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' fill='%23fff' viewBox='0 0 8 8'%3E%3Cpath d='M5.25 0l-4 4 4 4 1.5-1.5-2.5-2.5 2.5-2.5-1.5-1.5z'/%3E%3C/svg%3E")}.carousel-control-next-icon{background-image:url("data:image/svg+xml;charset=utf8,%3Csvg xmlns='http://www.w3.org/2000/svg' fill='%23fff' viewBox='0 0 8 8'%3E%3Cpath d='M2.75 0l1.5 1.5 2.5 2.5 2.5 2.5 1.5 1.5 4-4-4z'/%3E%3C/svg%3E")}.carousel-indicators{position:absolute;right:0;bottom:10px;left:0;z-index:15;display:-webkit-box;display:-ms-flexbox;display:flex;-webkit-box-pack:center;-ms-flex-pack:center;justify-content:center;padding-left:0;margin-right:15%;margin-left:15%;list-style:none}.carousel-indicators li{position:relative;-webkit-box-flex:0;-ms-flex:0 1 auto;flex:0 1 auto;width:30px;height:3px;margin-right:3px;margin-left:3px;text-indent:-999px;background-color:rgba(255,255,255,.5)}.carousel-indicators li::before{position:absolute;top:-10px;left:0;display:inline-block;width:100%;height:10px;content:""}.carousel-indicators li::after{position:absolute;bottom:-10px;left:0;display:inline-block;width:100%;height:10px;content:""}.carousel-indicators .active{background-color:#fff}.carousel-caption{position:absolute;right:15%;bottom:20px;left:15%;z-index:10;padding-top:20px;padding-bottom:20px;color:#fff;text-align:center}.align-baseline{vertical-align:baseline!important}.align-top{vertical-align:top!important}.align-middle{vertical-align:middle!important}.align-bottom{vertical-align:bottom!important}.align-text-bottom{vertical-align:text-bottom!important}.align-text-top{vertical-align:text-top!important}.bg-primary{background-color:#007bff!important}.a.bg-primary:focus,.a.bg-primary:hover,.button.bg-primary:focus,.button.bg-primary:hover{background-color:#0062cc!important}.bg-secondary{background-color:#6c757d!important}.a.bg-secondary:focus,.a.bg-secondary:hover,.button.bg-secondary:focus,.button.bg-secondary:hover{background-color:#545b62!important}.bg-success{background-color:#28a745!important}.a.bg-success:focus,.a.bg-success:hover,.button.bg-success:focus,.button.bg-success:hover{background-color:#1e7e34!important}.bg-info{background-color:#17a2b8!important}.a.bg-info:focus,.a.bg-info:hover,.button.bg-info:focus,.button.bg-info:hover{background-color:#117a8b!important}.bg-warning{background-color:#ffc107!important}.a.bg-warning:focus,.a.bg-warning:hover,.button.bg-warning:focus,.button.bg-warning:hover{background-color:#d39e00!important}.bg-danger{background-color:#dc3545!important}.a.bg-danger:focus,.a.bg-danger:hover,.button.bg-

danger:focus,button.bg-danger:hover{background-color:#bd2130!important}.bg-light{background-color:#f8f9fa!important}a.bg-light:focus,a.bg-light:hover,button.bg-light:focus,button.bg-light:hover{background-color:#dae0e5!important}.bg-dark{background-color:#343a40!important}a.bg-dark:focus,a.bg-dark:hover,button.bg-dark:focus,button.bg-dark:hover{background-color:#1d2124!important}.bg-white{background-color:#fff!important}.bg-transparent{background-color:transparent!important}.border{border:1px solid #dee2e6!important}.border-top{border-top:1px solid #dee2e6!important}.border-right{border-right:1px solid #dee2e6!important}.border-bottom{border-bottom:1px solid #dee2e6!important}.border-left{border-left:1px solid #dee2e6!important}.border-0{border:0!important}.border-top-0{border-top:0!important}.border-right-0{border-right:0!important}.border-bottom-0{border-bottom:0!important}.border-left-0{border-left:0!important}.border-primary{border-color:#007bff!important}.border-secondary{border-color:#6c757d!important}.border-success{border-color:#28a745!important}.border-info{border-color:#17a2b8!important}.border-warning{border-color:#ffc107!important}.border-danger{border-color:#dc3545!important}.border-light{border-color:#f8f9fa!important}.border-dark{border-color:#343a40!important}.border-white{border-color:#fff!important}.rounded{border-radius:.25rem!important}.rounded-top{border-top-left-radius:.25rem!important;border-top-right-radius:.25rem!important}.rounded-right{border-top-right-radius:.25rem!important;border-bottom-right-radius:.25rem!important}.rounded-bottom{border-bottom-right-radius:.25rem!important;border-bottom-left-radius:.25rem!important}.rounded-left{border-top-left-radius:.25rem!important;border-bottom-left-radius:.25rem!important}.rounded-circle{border-radius:50%!important}.rounded-0{border-radius:0!important}.clearfix::after{display:block;clear:both;content:""}.d-none{display:none!important}.d-inline{display:inline!important}.d-inline-block{display:inline-block!important}.d-block{display:block!important}.d-table{display:table!important}.d-table-row{display:table-row!important}.d-table-cell{display:table-cell!important}.d-flex{display:-webkit-box!important;display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important}.d-inline-flex{display:-webkit-inline-box!important;display:-ms-inline-flexbox!important;display:inline-flex!important}@media (min-width:576px){.d-sm-none{display:none!important}.d-sm-inline{display:inline!important}.d-sm-inline-block{display:inline-block!important}.d-sm-block{display:block!important}.d-sm-table{display:table!important}.d-sm-table-row{display:table-row!important}.d-sm-table-cell{display:table-cell!important}.d-sm-flex{display:-webkit-box!important;display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important}.d-sm-inline-flex{display:-webkit-inline-box!important;display:-ms-inline-flexbox!important;display:inline-flex!important}}@media (min-width:768px){.d-md-none{display:none!important}.d-md-inline{display:inline!important}.d-md-inline-block{display:inline-block!important}.d-md-block{display:block!important}.d-md-table{display:table!important}.d-md-table-row{display:table-row!important}.d-md-table-cell{display:table-cell!important}.d-md-flex{display:-webkit-box!important;display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important}.d-md-inline-flex{display:-webkit-inline-box!important;display:-ms-inline-flexbox!important;display:inline-flex!important}}@media (min-width:992px){.d-lg-none{display:none!important}.d-lg-inline{display:inline!important}.d-lg-inline-block{display:inline-block!important}.d-lg-block{display:block!important}.d-lg-table{display:table!important}.d-lg-table-row{display:table-row!important}.d-lg-table-cell{display:table-cell!important}.d-lg-flex{display:-webkit-box!important;display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important}.d-lg-inline-flex{display:-webkit-inline-box!important;display:-ms-inline-flexbox!important;display:inline-flex!important}}@media (min-width:1200px){.d-xl-none{display:none!important}.d-xl-inline{display:inline!important}.d-xl-inline-block{display:inline-block!important}.d-xl-block{display:block!important}.d-xl-table{display:table!important}.d-xl-table-row{display:table-row!important}.d-xl-table-cell{display:table-cell!important}.d-xl-flex{display:-webkit-box!important;display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important}.d-xl-inline-flex{display:-webkit-inline-

box!important;display:-ms-inline-flexbox!important;display:inline-flex!important}}@media print{.d-print-none{display:none!important}.d-print-inline{display:inline!important}.d-print-inline-block{display:inline-block!important}.d-print-block{display:block!important}.d-print-table{display:table!important}.d-print-table-row{display:table-row!important}.d-print-table-cell{display:table-cell!important}.d-print-flex{display:-webkit-box!important;display:-ms-flexbox!important;display:flex!important}.d-print-inline-flex{display:-webkit-inline-box!important;display:-ms-inline-flexbox!important;display:inline-flex!important}}.embed-responsive{position:relative;display:block;width:100%;padding:0;overflow:hidden}.embed-responsive::before{display:block;content:""}.embed-responsive .embed-responsive-item,.embed-responsive embed,.embed-responsive iframe,.embed-responsive object,.embed-responsive video{position:absolute;top:0;bottom:0;left:0;width:100%;height:100%;border:0}.embed-responsive-21by9::before{padding-top:42.857143%}.embed-responsive-16by9::before{padding-top:56.25%}.embed-responsive-4by3::before{padding-top:75%}.embed-responsive-1by1::before{padding-top:100%}.flex-row{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal!important;-webkit-box-direction:normal!important;-ms-flex-direction:row!important;flex-direction:row!important}.flex-column{-webkit-box-orient:vertical!important;-webkit-box-direction:normal!important;-ms-flex-direction:column!important;flex-direction:column!important}.flex-row-reverse{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal!important;-webkit-box-direction:reverse!important;-ms-flex-direction:row-reverse!important;flex-direction:row-reverse!important}.flex-column-reverse{-webkit-box-orient:vertical!important;-webkit-box-direction:reverse!important;-ms-flex-direction:column-reverse!important;flex-direction:column-reverse!important}.flex-wrap{-ms-flex-wrap:wrap!important;flex-wrap:wrap!important}.flex-nowrap{-ms-flex-wrap:nowrap!important;flex-wrap:nowrap!important}.flex-wrap-reverse{-ms-flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important;flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important}.justify-content-start{-webkit-box-pack:start!important;-ms-flex-pack:start!important;justify-content:flex-start!important}.justify-content-end{-webkit-box-pack:end!important;-ms-flex-pack:end!important;justify-content:flex-end!important}.justify-content-center{-webkit-box-pack:center!important;-ms-flex-pack:center!important;justify-content:center!important}.justify-content-between{-webkit-box-pack:justify!important;-ms-flex-pack:justify!important;justify-content:space-between!important}.justify-content-around{-ms-flex-pack:distribute!important;justify-content:space-around!important}.align-items-start{-webkit-box-align:start!important;-ms-flex-align:start!important;align-items:flex-start!important}.align-items-end{-webkit-box-align:end!important;-ms-flex-align:end!important;align-items:flex-end!important}.align-items-center{-webkit-box-align:center!important;-ms-flex-align:center!important;align-items:center!important}.align-items-baseline{-webkit-box-align:baseline!important;-ms-flex-align:baseline!important;align-items:baseline!important}.align-items-stretch{-webkit-box-align:stretch!important;-ms-flex-align:stretch!important;align-items:stretch!important}.align-content-start{-ms-flex-line-pack:start!important;align-content:flex-start!important}.align-content-end{-ms-flex-line-pack:end!important;align-content:flex-end!important}.align-content-center{-ms-flex-line-pack:center!important;align-content:center!important}.align-content-between{-ms-flex-line-pack:justify!important;align-content:space-between!important}.align-content-around{-ms-flex-line-pack:distribute!important;align-content:space-around!important}.align-content-stretch{-ms-flex-line-pack:stretch!important;align-content:stretch!important}.align-self-auto{-ms-flex-item-align:auto!important;align-self:auto!important}.align-self-start{-ms-flex-item-align:start!important;align-self:flex-start!important}.align-self-end{-ms-flex-item-align:end!important;align-self:flex-end!important}.align-self-center{-ms-flex-item-align:center!important;align-self:center!important}.align-self-baseline{-ms-flex-item-align:baseline!important;align-self:baseline!important}.align-self-stretch{-ms-flex-item-align:stretch!important;align-self:stretch!important}@media (min-width:576px){.flex-sm-row{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal!important;-webkit-box-direction:normal!important;-ms-flex-direction:row!important;flex-direction:row!important}.flex-sm-column{-webkit-box-

orient:vertical!important;-webkit-box-direction:normal!important;-ms-flex-direction:column!important;flex-direction:column!important}.flex-sm-row-reverse{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal!important;-webkit-box-direction:reverse!important;-ms-flex-direction:row-reverse!important;flex-direction:row-reverse!important}.flex-sm-column-reverse{-webkit-box-orient:vertical!important;-webkit-box-direction:reverse!important;-ms-flex-direction:column-reverse!important;flex-direction:column-reverse!important}.flex-sm-wrap{-ms-flex-wrap:wrap!important;flex-wrap:wrap!important}.flex-sm-nowrap{-ms-flex-wrap:nowrap!important;flex-wrap:nowrap!important}.flex-sm-wrap-reverse{-ms-flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important;flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important}.justify-content-sm-start{-webkit-box-pack:start!important;-ms-flex-pack:start!important;justify-content:flex-start!important}.justify-content-sm-end{-webkit-box-pack:end!important;-ms-flex-pack:end!important;justify-content:flex-end!important}.justify-content-sm-center{-webkit-box-pack:center!important;-ms-flex-pack:center!important;justify-content:center!important}.justify-content-sm-between{-webkit-box-pack:justify!important;-ms-flex-pack:justify!important;justify-content:space-between!important}.justify-content-sm-around{-ms-flex-pack:distribute!important;justify-content:space-around!important}.align-items-sm-start{-webkit-box-align:start!important;-ms-flex-align:start!important;align-items:flex-start!important}.align-items-sm-end{-webkit-box-align:end!important;-ms-flex-align:end!important;align-items:flex-end!important}.align-items-sm-center{-webkit-box-align:center!important;-ms-flex-align:center!important;align-items:center!important}.align-items-sm-baseline{-webkit-box-align:baseline!important;-ms-flex-align:baseline!important;align-items:baseline!important}.align-items-sm-stretch{-webkit-box-align:stretch!important;-ms-flex-align:stretch!important;align-items:stretch!important}.align-content-sm-start{-ms-flex-line-pack:start!important;align-content:flex-start!important}.align-content-sm-end{-ms-flex-line-pack:end!important;align-content:flex-end!important}.align-content-sm-center{-ms-flex-line-pack:center!important;align-content:center!important}.align-content-sm-between{-ms-flex-line-pack:justify!important;align-content:space-between!important}.align-content-sm-around{-ms-flex-line-pack:distribute!important;align-content:space-around!important}.align-content-sm-stretch{-ms-flex-line-pack:stretch!important;align-content:stretch!important}.align-self-sm-auto{-ms-flex-item-align:auto!important;align-self:auto!important}.align-self-sm-start{-ms-flex-item-align:start!important;align-self:flex-start!important}.align-self-sm-end{-ms-flex-item-align:end!important;align-self:flex-end!important}.align-self-sm-center{-ms-flex-item-align:center!important;align-self:center!important}.align-self-sm-baseline{-ms-flex-item-align:baseline!important;align-self:baseline!important}.align-self-sm-stretch{-ms-flex-item-align:stretch!important;align-self:stretch!important}}@media (min-width:768px){.flex-md-row{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal!important;-webkit-box-direction:normal!important;-ms-flex-direction:row!important;flex-direction:row!important}.flex-md-column{-webkit-box-orient:vertical!important;-webkit-box-direction:normal!important;-ms-flex-direction:column!important;flex-direction:column!important}.flex-md-row-reverse{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal!important;-webkit-box-direction:reverse!important;-ms-flex-direction:row-reverse!important;flex-direction:row-reverse!important}.flex-md-column-reverse{-webkit-box-orient:vertical!important;-webkit-box-direction:reverse!important;-ms-flex-direction:column-reverse!important;flex-direction:column-reverse!important}.flex-md-wrap{-ms-flex-wrap:wrap!important;flex-wrap:wrap!important}.flex-md-nowrap{-ms-flex-wrap:nowrap!important;flex-wrap:nowrap!important}.flex-md-wrap-reverse{-ms-flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important;flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important}.justify-content-md-start{-webkit-box-pack:start!important;-ms-flex-pack:start!important;justify-content:flex-start!important}.justify-content-md-end{-webkit-box-pack:end!important;-ms-flex-pack:end!important;justify-content:flex-end!important}.justify-content-md-center{-webkit-box-pack:center!important;-ms-flex-pack:center!important;justify-content:center!important}.justify-content-md-between{-webkit-box-pack:justify!important;-ms-flex-pack:justify!important;justify-content:space-

between!important}.justify-content-md-around{-ms-flex-pack:distribute!important;justify-content:space-around!important}.align-items-md-start{-webkit-box-align:start!important;-ms-flex-align:start!important;align-items:flex-start!important}.align-items-md-end{-webkit-box-align:end!important;-ms-flex-align:end!important;align-items:flex-end!important}.align-items-md-center{-webkit-box-align:center!important;-ms-flex-align:center!important;align-items:center!important}.align-items-md-baseline{-webkit-box-align:baseline!important;-ms-flex-align:baseline!important;align-items:baseline!important}.align-items-md-stretch{-webkit-box-align:stretch!important;-ms-flex-align:stretch!important;align-items:stretch!important}.align-content-md-start{-ms-flex-line-pack:start!important;align-content:flex-start!important}.align-content-md-end{-ms-flex-line-pack:end!important;align-content:flex-end!important}.align-content-md-center{-ms-flex-line-pack:center!important;align-content:center!important}.align-content-md-between{-ms-flex-line-pack:justify!important;align-content:space-between!important}.align-content-md-around{-ms-flex-line-pack:distribute!important;align-content:space-around!important}.align-content-md-stretch{-ms-flex-line-pack:stretch!important;align-content:stretch!important}.align-self-md-auto{-ms-flex-item-align:auto!important;align-self:auto!important}.align-self-md-start{-ms-flex-item-align:start!important;align-self:flex-start!important}.align-self-md-end{-ms-flex-item-align:end!important;align-self:flex-end!important}.align-self-md-center{-ms-flex-item-align:center!important;align-self:center!important}.align-self-md-baseline{-ms-flex-item-align:baseline!important;align-self:baseline!important}.align-self-md-stretch{-ms-flex-item-align:stretch!important;align-self:stretch!important}}@media (min-width:992px){.flex-lg-row{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal!important;-webkit-box-direction:normal!important;-ms-flex-direction:row!important;flex-direction:row!important}.flex-lg-column{-webkit-box-orient:vertical!important;-webkit-box-direction:normal!important;-ms-flex-direction:column!important;flex-direction:column!important}.flex-lg-row-reverse{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal!important;-webkit-box-direction:reverse!important;-ms-flex-direction:row-reverse!important;flex-direction:row-reverse!important}.flex-lg-column-reverse{-webkit-box-orient:vertical!important;-webkit-box-direction:reverse!important;-ms-flex-direction:column-reverse!important;flex-direction:column-reverse!important}.flex-lg-wrap{-ms-flex-wrap:wrap!important;flex-wrap:wrap!important}.flex-lg-nowrap{-ms-flex-wrap:nowrap!important;flex-wrap:nowrap!important}.flex-lg-wrap-reverse{-ms-flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important;flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important}.justify-content-lg-start{-webkit-box-pack:start!important;-ms-flex-pack:start!important;justify-content:flex-start!important}.justify-content-lg-end{-webkit-box-pack:end!important;-ms-flex-pack:end!important;justify-content:flex-end!important}.justify-content-lg-center{-webkit-box-pack:center!important;-ms-flex-pack:center!important;justify-content:center!important}.justify-content-lg-between{-webkit-box-pack:justify!important;-ms-flex-pack:justify!important;justify-content:space-between!important}.justify-content-lg-around{-ms-flex-pack:distribute!important;justify-content:space-around!important}.align-items-lg-start{-webkit-box-align:start!important;-ms-flex-align:start!important;align-items:flex-start!important}.align-items-lg-end{-webkit-box-align:end!important;-ms-flex-align:end!important;align-items:flex-end!important}.align-items-lg-center{-webkit-box-align:center!important;-ms-flex-align:center!important;align-items:center!important}.align-items-lg-baseline{-webkit-box-align:baseline!important;-ms-flex-align:baseline!important;align-items:baseline!important}.align-items-lg-stretch{-webkit-box-align:stretch!important;-ms-flex-align:stretch!important;align-items:stretch!important}.align-content-lg-start{-ms-flex-line-pack:start!important;align-content:flex-start!important}.align-content-lg-end{-ms-flex-line-pack:end!important;align-content:flex-end!important}.align-content-lg-center{-ms-flex-line-pack:center!important;align-content:center!important}.align-content-lg-between{-ms-flex-line-pack:justify!important;align-content:space-between!important}.align-content-lg-around{-ms-flex-line-pack:distribute!important;align-content:space-around!important}.align-content-lg-stretch{-ms-flex-line-pack:stretch!important;align-content:stretch!important}.align-self-lg-auto{-ms-

flex-item-align:auto!important;align-self:auto!important}.align-self-lg-start{-ms-flex-item-align:start!important;align-self:flex-start!important}.align-self-lg-end{-ms-flex-item-align:end!important;align-self:flex-end!important}.align-self-lg-center{-ms-flex-item-align:center!important;align-self:center!important}.align-self-lg-baseline{-ms-flex-item-align:baseline!important;align-self:baseline!important}.align-self-lg-stretch{-ms-flex-item-align:stretch!important;align-self:stretch!important}}@media (min-width:1200px){.flex-xl-row{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal!important;-webkit-box-direction:normal!important;-ms-flex-direction:row!important;flex-direction:row!important}.flex-xl-column{-webkit-box-orient:vertical!important;-webkit-box-direction:normal!important;-ms-flex-direction:column!important;flex-direction:column!important}.flex-xl-row-reverse{-webkit-box-orient:horizontal!important;-webkit-box-direction:reverse!important;-ms-flex-direction:row-reverse!important;flex-direction:row-reverse!important}.flex-xl-column-reverse{-webkit-box-orient:vertical!important;-webkit-box-direction:reverse!important;-ms-flex-direction:column-reverse!important;flex-direction:column-reverse!important}.flex-xl-wrap{-ms-flex-wrap:wrap!important;flex-wrap:wrap!important}.flex-xl-nowrap{-ms-flex-wrap:nowrap!important;flex-wrap:nowrap!important}.flex-xl-wrap-reverse{-ms-flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important;flex-wrap:wrap-reverse!important}.justify-content-xl-start{-webkit-box-pack:start!important;-ms-flex-pack:start!important;justify-content:flex-start!important}.justify-content-xl-end{-webkit-box-pack:end!important;-ms-flex-pack:end!important;justify-content:flex-end!important}.justify-content-xl-center{-webkit-box-pack:center!important;-ms-flex-pack:center!important;justify-content:center!important}.justify-content-xl-between{-webkit-box-pack:justify!important;-ms-flex-pack:justify!important;justify-content:space-between!important}.justify-content-xl-around{-ms-flex-pack:distribute!important;justify-content:space-around!important}.align-items-xl-start{-webkit-box-align:start!important;-ms-flex-align:start!important;align-items:flex-start!important}.align-items-xl-end{-webkit-box-align:end!important;-ms-flex-align:end!important;align-items:flex-end!important}.align-items-xl-center{-webkit-box-align:center!important;-ms-flex-align:center!important;align-items:center!important}.align-items-xl-baseline{-webkit-box-align:baseline!important;-ms-flex-align:baseline!important;align-items:baseline!important}.align-items-xl-stretch{-webkit-box-align:stretch!important;-ms-flex-align:stretch!important;align-items:stretch!important}.align-content-xl-start{-ms-flex-line-pack:start!important;align-content:flex-start!important}.align-content-xl-end{-ms-flex-line-pack:end!important;align-content:flex-end!important}.align-content-xl-center{-ms-flex-line-pack:center!important;align-content:center!important}.align-content-xl-between{-ms-flex-line-pack:justify!important;align-content:space-between!important}.align-content-xl-around{-ms-flex-line-pack:distribute!important;align-content:space-around!important}.align-content-xl-stretch{-ms-flex-line-pack:stretch!important;align-content:stretch!important}.align-self-xl-auto{-ms-flex-item-align:auto!important;align-self:auto!important}.align-self-xl-start{-ms-flex-item-align:start!important;align-self:flex-start!important}.align-self-xl-end{-ms-flex-item-align:end!important;align-self:flex-end!important}.align-self-xl-center{-ms-flex-item-align:center!important;align-self:center!important}.align-self-xl-baseline{-ms-flex-item-align:baseline!important;align-self:baseline!important}.align-self-xl-stretch{-ms-flex-item-align:stretch!important;align-self:stretch!important}}.float-left{float:left!important}.float-right{float:right!important}.float-none{float:none!important}@media (min-width:576px){.float-sm-left{float:left!important}.float-sm-right{float:right!important}.float-sm-none{float:none!important}}@media (min-width:768px){.float-md-left{float:left!important}.float-md-right{float:right!important}.float-md-none{float:none!important}}@media (min-width:992px){.float-lg-left{float:left!important}.float-lg-right{float:right!important}.float-lg-none{float:none!important}}@media (min-width:1200px){.float-xl-left{float:left!important}.float-xl-right{float:right!important}.float-xl-none{float:none!important}}.position-static{position:static!important}.position-relative{position:relative!important}.position-absolute{position:absolute!important}.position-fixed{position:fixed!important}.position-

sticky{position:-webkit-sticky!important;position:sticky!important}.fixed-top{position:fixed;top:0;right:0;left:0;z-index:1030}.fixed-bottom{position:fixed;right:0;bottom:0;left:0;z-index:1030}@supports ((position:-webkit-sticky) or (position:sticky)){.sticky-top{position:-webkit-sticky;position:sticky;top:0;z-index:1020}}.sr-only{position:absolute;width:1px;height:1px;padding:0;overflow:hidden;clip:rect(0,0,0,0);white-space:nowrap;-webkit-clip-path:inset(50%);clip-path:inset(50%);border:0}.sr-only-focusable:active,.sr-only-focusable:focus{position:static;width:auto;height:auto;overflow:visible;clip:auto;white-space:normal;-webkit-clip-path:none;clip-path:none}.w-25{width:25%!important}.w-50{width:50%!important}.w-75{width:75%!important}.w-100{width:100%!important}.h-25{height:25%!important}.h-50{height:50%!important}.h-75{height:75%!important}.h-100{height:100%!important}.mw-100{max-width:100%!important}.mh-100{max-height:100%!important}.m-0{margin:0!important}.mt-0,.my-0{margin-top:0!important}.mr-0,.mx-0{margin-right:0!important}.mb-0,.my-0{margin-bottom:0!important}.ml-0,.mx-0{margin-left:0!important}.m-1{margin:.25rem!important}.mt-1,.my-1{margin-top:.25rem!important}.mr-1,.mx-1{margin-right:.25rem!important}.mb-1,.my-1{margin-bottom:.25rem!important}.ml-1,.mx-1{margin-left:.25rem!important}.m-2{margin:.5rem!important}.mt-2,.my-2{margin-top:.5rem!important}.mr-2,.mx-2{margin-right:.5rem!important}.mb-2,.my-2{margin-bottom:.5rem!important}.ml-2,.mx-2{margin-left:.5rem!important}.m-3{margin:1rem!important}.mt-3,.my-3{margin-top:1rem!important}.mr-3,.mx-3{margin-right:1rem!important}.mb-3,.my-3{margin-bottom:1rem!important}.ml-3,.mx-3{margin-left:1rem!important}.m-4{margin:1.5rem!important}.mt-4,.my-4{margin-top:1.5rem!important}.mr-4,.mx-4{margin-right:1.5rem!important}.mb-4,.my-4{margin-bottom:1.5rem!important}.ml-4,.mx-4{margin-left:1.5rem!important}.m-5{margin:3rem!important}.mt-5,.my-5{margin-top:3rem!important}.mr-5,.mx-5{margin-right:3rem!important}.mb-5,.my-5{margin-bottom:3rem!important}.ml-5,.mx-5{margin-left:3rem!important}.p-0{padding:0!important}.pt-0,.py-0{padding-top:0!important}.pr-0,.px-0{padding-right:0!important}.pb-0,.py-0{padding-bottom:0!important}.pl-0,.px-0{padding-left:0!important}.p-1{padding:.25rem!important}.pt-1,.py-1{padding-top:.25rem!important}.pr-1,.px-1{padding-right:.25rem!important}.pb-1,.py-1{padding-bottom:.25rem!important}.pl-1,.px-1{padding-left:.25rem!important}.p-2{padding:.5rem!important}.pt-2,.py-2{padding-top:.5rem!important}.pr-2,.px-2{padding-right:.5rem!important}.pb-2,.py-2{padding-bottom:.5rem!important}.pl-2,.px-2{padding-left:.5rem!important}.p-3{padding:1rem!important}.pt-3,.py-3{padding-top:1rem!important}.pr-3,.px-3{padding-right:1rem!important}.pb-3,.py-3{padding-bottom:1rem!important}.pl-3,.px-3{padding-left:1rem!important}.p-4{padding:1.5rem!important}.pt-4,.py-4{padding-top:1.5rem!important}.pr-4,.px-4{padding-right:1.5rem!important}.pb-4,.py-4{padding-bottom:1.5rem!important}.pl-4,.px-4{padding-left:1.5rem!important}.p-5{padding:3rem!important}.pt-5,.py-5{padding-top:3rem!important}.pr-5,.px-5{padding-right:3rem!important}.pb-5,.py-5{padding-bottom:3rem!important}.pl-5,.px-5{padding-left:3rem!important}.m-auto{margin:auto!important}.mt-auto,.my-auto{margin-top:auto!important}.mr-auto,.mx-auto{margin-right:auto!important}.mb-auto,.my-auto{margin-bottom:auto!important}.ml-auto,.mx-auto{margin-left:auto!important}@media (min-width:576px){.m-sm-0{margin:0!important}.mt-sm-0,.my-sm-0{margin-top:0!important}.mr-sm-0,.mx-sm-0{margin-right:0!important}.mb-sm-0,.my-sm-0{margin-bottom:0!important}.ml-sm-0,.mx-sm-0{margin-left:0!important}.m-sm-1{margin:.25rem!important}.mt-sm-1,.my-sm-1{margin-top:.25rem!important}.mr-sm-1,.mx-sm-1{margin-right:.25rem!important}.mb-sm-1,.my-sm-1{margin-bottom:.25rem!important}.ml-sm-1,.mx-sm-1{margin-left:.25rem!important}.m-sm-2{margin:.5rem!important}.mt-sm-2,.my-sm-2{margin-top:.5rem!important}.mr-sm-2,.mx-sm-2{margin-right:.5rem!important}.mb-sm-2,.my-sm-2{margin-bottom:.5rem!important}.ml-sm-2,.mx-sm-2{margin-left:.5rem!important}.m-sm-3{margin:1rem!important}.mt-sm-3,.my-sm-3{margin-top:1rem!important}.mr-sm-3,.mx-sm-3{margin-right:1rem!important}.mb-sm-3,.my-sm-3{margin-

bottom:1rem!important}.ml-sm-3,.mx-sm-3{margin-left:1rem!important}.m-sm-4{margin:1.5rem!important}.mt-sm-4,.my-sm-4{margin-top:1.5rem!important}.mr-sm-4,.mx-sm-4{margin-right:1.5rem!important}.mb-sm-4,.my-sm-4{margin-bottom:1.5rem!important}.ml-sm-4,.mx-sm-4{margin-left:1.5rem!important}.m-sm-5{margin:3rem!important}.mt-sm-5,.my-sm-5{margin-top:3rem!important}.mr-sm-5,.mx-sm-5{margin-right:3rem!important}.mb-sm-5,.my-sm-5{margin-bottom:3rem!important}.ml-sm-5,.mx-sm-5{margin-left:3rem!important}.p-sm-0{padding:0!important}.pt-sm-0,.py-sm-0{padding-top:0!important}.pr-sm-0,.px-sm-0{padding-right:0!important}.pb-sm-0,.py-sm-0{padding-bottom:0!important}.pl-sm-0,.px-sm-0{padding-left:0!important}.p-sm-1{padding:.25rem!important}.pt-sm-1,.py-sm-1{padding-top:.25rem!important}.pr-sm-1,.px-sm-1{padding-right:.25rem!important}.pb-sm-1,.py-sm-1{padding-bottom:.25rem!important}.pl-sm-1,.px-sm-1{padding-left:.25rem!important}.p-sm-2{padding:.5rem!important}.pt-sm-2,.py-sm-2{padding-top:.5rem!important}.pr-sm-2,.px-sm-2{padding-right:.5rem!important}.pb-sm-2,.py-sm-2{padding-bottom:.5rem!important}.pl-sm-2,.px-sm-2{padding-left:.5rem!important}.p-sm-3{padding:1rem!important}.pt-sm-3,.py-sm-3{padding-top:1rem!important}.pr-sm-3,.px-sm-3{padding-right:1rem!important}.pb-sm-3,.py-sm-3{padding-bottom:1rem!important}.pl-sm-3,.px-sm-3{padding-left:1rem!important}.p-sm-4{padding:1.5rem!important}.pt-sm-4,.py-sm-4{padding-top:1.5rem!important}.pr-sm-4,.px-sm-4{padding-right:1.5rem!important}.pb-sm-4,.py-sm-4{padding-bottom:1.5rem!important}.pl-sm-4,.px-sm-4{padding-left:1.5rem!important}.p-sm-5{padding:3rem!important}.pt-sm-5,.py-sm-5{padding-top:3rem!important}.pr-sm-5,.px-sm-5{padding-right:3rem!important}.pb-sm-5,.py-sm-5{padding-bottom:3rem!important}.pl-sm-5,.px-sm-5{padding-left:3rem!important}.m-sm-auto{margin:auto!important}.mt-sm-auto,.my-sm-auto{margin-top:auto!important}.mr-sm-auto,.mx-sm-auto{margin-right:auto!important}.mb-sm-auto,.my-sm-auto{margin-bottom:auto!important}.ml-sm-auto,.mx-sm-auto{margin-left:auto!important}}@media (min-width:768px){.m-md-0{margin:0!important}.mt-md-0,.my-md-0{margin-top:0!important}.mr-md-0,.mx-md-0{margin-right:0!important}.mb-md-0,.my-md-0{margin-bottom:0!important}.ml-md-0,.mx-md-0{margin-left:0!important}.m-md-1{margin:.25rem!important}.mt-md-1,.my-md-1{margin-top:.25rem!important}.mr-md-1,.mx-md-1{margin-right:.25rem!important}.mb-md-1,.my-md-1{margin-bottom:.25rem!important}.ml-md-1,.mx-md-1{margin-left:.25rem!important}.m-md-2{margin:.5rem!important}.mt-md-2,.my-md-2{margin-top:.5rem!important}.mr-md-2,.mx-md-2{margin-right:.5rem!important}.mb-md-2,.my-md-2{margin-bottom:.5rem!important}.ml-md-2,.mx-md-2{margin-left:.5rem!important}.m-md-3{margin:1rem!important}.mt-md-3,.my-md-3{margin-top:1rem!important}.mr-md-3,.mx-md-3{margin-right:1rem!important}.mb-md-3,.my-md-3{margin-bottom:1rem!important}.ml-md-3,.mx-md-3{margin-left:1rem!important}.m-md-4{margin:1.5rem!important}.mt-md-4,.my-md-4{margin-top:1.5rem!important}.mr-md-4,.mx-md-4{margin-right:1.5rem!important}.mb-md-4,.my-md-4{margin-bottom:1.5rem!important}.ml-md-4,.mx-md-4{margin-left:1.5rem!important}.m-md-5{margin:3rem!important}.mt-md-5,.my-md-5{margin-top:3rem!important}.mr-md-5,.mx-md-5{margin-right:3rem!important}.mb-md-5,.my-md-5{margin-bottom:3rem!important}.ml-md-5,.mx-md-5{margin-left:3rem!important}.p-md-0{padding:0!important}.pt-md-0,.py-md-0{padding-top:0!important}.pr-md-0,.px-md-0{padding-right:0!important}.pb-md-0,.py-md-0{padding-bottom:0!important}.pl-md-0,.px-md-0{padding-left:0!important}.p-md-1{padding:.25rem!important}.pt-md-1,.py-md-1{padding-top:.25rem!important}.pr-md-1,.px-md-1{padding-right:.25rem!important}.pb-md-1,.py-md-1{padding-bottom:.25rem!important}.pl-md-1,.px-md-1{padding-left:.25rem!important}.p-md-2{padding:.5rem!important}.pt-md-2,.py-md-2{padding-top:.5rem!important}.pr-md-2,.px-md-2{padding-right:.5rem!important}.pb-md-2,.py-md-2{padding-bottom:.5rem!important}.pl-md-2,.px-md-2{padding-left:.5rem!important}.p-md-3{padding:1rem!important}.pt-md-3,.py-md-3{padding-top:1rem!important}.pr-md-3,.px-md-3{padding-right:1rem!important}.pb-md-3,.py-md-3{padding-bottom:1rem!important}.pl-md-3,.px-md-3{padding-left:1rem!important}.p-md-4{padding:1.5rem!important}.pt-md-4,.py-md-4{padding-top:1.5rem!important}.pr-md-4,.px-md-4{padding-right:1.5rem!important}.pb-md-4,.py-md-4{padding-bottom:1.5rem!important}.pl-md-4

4,.px-md-4{padding-left:1.5rem!important}.p-md-5{padding:3rem!important}.pt-md-5,.py-md-5{padding-top:3rem!important}.pr-md-5,.px-md-5{padding-right:3rem!important}.pb-md-5,.py-md-5{padding-bottom:3rem!important}.pl-md-5,.px-md-5{padding-left:3rem!important}.m-md-auto{margin:auto!important}.mt-md-auto,.my-md-auto{margin-top:auto!important}.mr-md-auto,.mx-md-auto{margin-right:auto!important}.mb-md-auto,.my-md-auto{margin-bottom:auto!important}.ml-md-auto,.mx-md-auto{margin-left:auto!important}}@media (min-width:992px){.m-lg-0{margin:0!important}.mt-lg-0,.my-lg-0{margin-top:0!important}.mr-lg-0,.mx-lg-0{margin-right:0!important}.mb-lg-0,.my-lg-0{margin-bottom:0!important}.ml-lg-0,.mx-lg-0{margin-left:0!important}.m-lg-1{margin:.25rem!important}.mt-lg-1,.my-lg-1{margin-top:.25rem!important}.mr-lg-1,.mx-lg-1{margin-right:.25rem!important}.mb-lg-1,.my-lg-1{margin-bottom:.25rem!important}.ml-lg-1,.mx-lg-1{margin-left:.25rem!important}.m-lg-2{margin:.5rem!important}.mt-lg-2,.my-lg-2{margin-top:.5rem!important}.mr-lg-2,.mx-lg-2{margin-right:.5rem!important}.mb-lg-2,.my-lg-2{margin-bottom:.5rem!important}.ml-lg-2,.mx-lg-2{margin-left:.5rem!important}.m-lg-3{margin:1rem!important}.mt-lg-3,.my-lg-3{margin-top:1rem!important}.mr-lg-3,.mx-lg-3{margin-right:1rem!important}.mb-lg-3,.my-lg-3{margin-bottom:1rem!important}.ml-lg-3,.mx-lg-3{margin-left:1rem!important}.m-lg-4{margin:1.5rem!important}.mt-lg-4,.my-lg-4{margin-top:1.5rem!important}.mr-lg-4,.mx-lg-4{margin-right:1.5rem!important}.mb-lg-4,.my-lg-4{margin-bottom:1.5rem!important}.ml-lg-4,.mx-lg-4{margin-left:1.5rem!important}.m-lg-5{margin:3rem!important}.mt-lg-5,.my-lg-5{margin-top:3rem!important}.mr-lg-5,.mx-lg-5{margin-right:3rem!important}.mb-lg-5,.my-lg-5{margin-bottom:3rem!important}.ml-lg-5,.mx-lg-5{margin-left:3rem!important}.p-lg-0{padding:0!important}.pt-lg-0,.py-lg-0{padding-top:0!important}.pr-lg-0,.px-lg-0{padding-right:0!important}.pb-lg-0,.py-lg-0{padding-bottom:0!important}.pl-lg-0,.px-lg-0{padding-left:0!important}.p-lg-1{padding:.25rem!important}.pt-lg-1,.py-lg-1{padding-top:.25rem!important}.pr-lg-1,.px-lg-1{padding-right:.25rem!important}.pb-lg-1,.py-lg-1{padding-bottom:.25rem!important}.pl-lg-1,.px-lg-1{padding-left:.25rem!important}.p-lg-2{padding:.5rem!important}.pt-lg-2,.py-lg-2{padding-top:.5rem!important}.pr-lg-2,.px-lg-2{padding-right:.5rem!important}.pb-lg-2,.py-lg-2{padding-bottom:.5rem!important}.pl-lg-2,.px-lg-2{padding-left:.5rem!important}.p-lg-3{padding:1rem!important}.pt-lg-3,.py-lg-3{padding-top:1rem!important}.pr-lg-3,.px-lg-3{padding-right:1rem!important}.pb-lg-3,.py-lg-3{padding-bottom:1rem!important}.pl-lg-3,.px-lg-3{padding-left:1rem!important}.p-lg-4{padding:1.5rem!important}.pt-lg-4,.py-lg-4{padding-top:1.5rem!important}.pr-lg-4,.px-lg-4{padding-right:1.5rem!important}.pb-lg-4,.py-lg-4{padding-bottom:1.5rem!important}.pl-lg-4,.px-lg-4{padding-left:1.5rem!important}.p-lg-5{padding:3rem!important}.pt-lg-5,.py-lg-5{padding-top:3rem!important}.pr-lg-5,.px-lg-5{padding-right:3rem!important}.pb-lg-5,.py-lg-5{padding-bottom:3rem!important}.pl-lg-5,.px-lg-5{padding-left:3rem!important}.m-lg-auto{margin:auto!important}.mt-lg-auto,.my-lg-auto{margin-top:auto!important}.mr-lg-auto,.mx-lg-auto{margin-right:auto!important}.mb-lg-auto,.my-lg-auto{margin-bottom:auto!important}.ml-lg-auto,.mx-lg-auto{margin-left:auto!important}}@media (min-width:1200px){.m-xl-0{margin:0!important}.mt-xl-0,.my-xl-0{margin-top:0!important}.mr-xl-0,.mx-xl-0{margin-right:0!important}.mb-xl-0,.my-xl-0{margin-bottom:0!important}.ml-xl-0,.mx-xl-0{margin-left:0!important}.m-xl-1{margin:.25rem!important}.mt-xl-1,.my-xl-1{margin-top:.25rem!important}.mr-xl-1,.mx-xl-1{margin-right:.25rem!important}.mb-xl-1,.my-xl-1{margin-bottom:.25rem!important}.ml-xl-1,.mx-xl-1{margin-left:.25rem!important}.m-xl-2{margin:.5rem!important}.mt-xl-2,.my-xl-2{margin-top:.5rem!important}.mr-xl-2,.mx-xl-2{margin-right:.5rem!important}.mb-xl-2,.my-xl-2{margin-bottom:.5rem!important}.ml-xl-2,.mx-xl-2{margin-left:.5rem!important}.m-xl-3{margin:1rem!important}.mt-xl-3,.my-xl-3{margin-top:1rem!important}.mr-xl-3,.mx-xl-3{margin-right:1rem!important}.mb-xl-3,.my-xl-3{margin-bottom:1rem!important}.ml-xl-3,.mx-xl-3{margin-left:1rem!important}.m-xl-4{margin:1.5rem!important}.mt-xl-4,.my-xl-4{margin-top:1.5rem!important}.mr-xl-4,.mx-xl-4{margin-right:1.5rem!important}.mb-xl-4,.my-xl-4{margin-bottom:1.5rem!important}.ml-xl-4,.mx-

xl-4{margin-left:1.5rem!important}.m-xl-5{margin:3rem!important}.mt-xl-5,.my-xl-5{margin-top:3rem!important}.mr-xl-5,.mx-xl-5{margin-right:3rem!important}.mb-xl-5,.my-xl-5{margin-bottom:3rem!important}.ml-xl-5,.mx-xl-5{margin-left:3rem!important}.p-xl-0{padding:0!important}.pt-xl-0,.py-xl-0{padding-top:0!important}.pr-xl-0,.px-xl-0{padding-right:0!important}.pb-xl-0,.py-xl-0{padding-bottom:0!important}.pl-xl-0,.px-xl-0{padding-left:0!important}.p-xl-1{padding:.25rem!important}.pt-xl-1,.py-xl-1{padding-top:.25rem!important}.pr-xl-1,.px-xl-1{padding-right:.25rem!important}.pb-xl-1,.py-xl-1{padding-bottom:.25rem!important}.pl-xl-1,.px-xl-1{padding-left:.25rem!important}.p-xl-2{padding:.5rem!important}.pt-xl-2,.py-xl-2{padding-top:.5rem!important}.pr-xl-2,.px-xl-2{padding-right:.5rem!important}.pb-xl-2,.py-xl-2{padding-bottom:.5rem!important}.pl-xl-2,.px-xl-2{padding-left:.5rem!important}.p-xl-3{padding:1rem!important}.pt-xl-3,.py-xl-3{padding-top:1rem!important}.pr-xl-3,.px-xl-3{padding-right:1rem!important}.pb-xl-3,.py-xl-3{padding-bottom:1rem!important}.pl-xl-3,.px-xl-3{padding-left:1rem!important}.p-xl-4{padding:1.5rem!important}.pt-xl-4,.py-xl-4{padding-top:1.5rem!important}.pr-xl-4,.px-xl-4{padding-right:1.5rem!important}.pb-xl-4,.py-xl-4{padding-bottom:1.5rem!important}.pl-xl-4,.px-xl-4{padding-left:1.5rem!important}.p-xl-5{padding:3rem!important}.pt-xl-5,.py-xl-5{padding-top:3rem!important}.pr-xl-5,.px-xl-5{padding-right:3rem!important}.pb-xl-5,.py-xl-5{padding-bottom:3rem!important}.pl-xl-5,.px-xl-5{padding-left:3rem!important}.m-xl-auto{margin:auto!important}.mt-xl-auto,.my-xl-auto{margin-top:auto!important}.mr-xl-auto,.mx-xl-auto{margin-right:auto!important}.mb-xl-auto,.my-xl-auto{margin-bottom:auto!important}.ml-xl-auto,.mx-xl-auto{margin-left:auto!important}.text-justify{text-align:justify!important}.text-nowrap{white-space:nowrap!important}.text-truncate{overflow:hidden;text-overflow:ellipsis;white-space:nowrap}.text-left{text-align:left!important}.text-right{text-align:right!important}.text-center{text-align:center!important}@media (min-width:576px){.text-sm-left{text-align:left!important}.text-sm-right{text-align:right!important}.text-sm-center{text-align:center!important}}@media (min-width:768px){.text-md-left{text-align:left!important}.text-md-right{text-align:right!important}.text-md-center{text-align:center!important}}@media (min-width:992px){.text-lg-left{text-align:left!important}.text-lg-right{text-align:right!important}.text-lg-center{text-align:center!important}}@media (min-width:1200px){.text-xl-left{text-align:left!important}.text-xl-right{text-align:right!important}.text-xl-center{text-align:center!important}}.text-lowercase{text-transform:lowercase!important}.text-uppercase{text-transform:uppercase!important}.text-capitalize{text-transform:capitalize!important}.font-weight-light{font-weight:300!important}.font-weight-normal{font-weight:400!important}.font-weight-bold{font-weight:700!important}.font-italic{font-style:italic!important}.text-white{color:#fff!important}.text-primary{color:#007bff!important}a.text-primary:focus,a.text-primary:hover{color:#0062cc!important}.text-secondary{color:#6c757d!important}a.text-secondary:focus,a.text-secondary:hover{color:#545b62!important}.text-success{color:#28a745!important}a.text-success:focus,a.text-success:hover{color:#1e7e34!important}.text-info{color:#17a2b8!important}a.text-info:focus,a.text-info:hover{color:#117a8b!important}.text-warning{color:#ffc107!important}a.text-warning:focus,a.text-warning:hover{color:#d39e00!important}.text-danger{color:#dc3545!important}a.text-danger:focus,a.text-danger:hover{color:#bd2130!important}.text-light{color:#f8f9fa!important}a.text-light:focus,a.text-light:hover{color:#dae0e5!important}.text-dark{color:#343a40!important}a.text-dark:focus,a.text-dark:hover{color:#1d2124!important}.text-muted{color:#6c757d!important}.text-hide{font:0/0 a;color:transparent;text-shadow:none;background-color:transparent;border:0}.visible{visibility:visible!important}.invisible{visibility:hidden!important}@media print{*,:after,:before{text-shadow:none!important;box-shadow:none!important}a:not(.btn){text-decoration:underline}abbr[title]::after{content:" attr(title) "}}pre{white-space:pre-wrap!important}blockquote,pre{border:1px solid #999;page-break-inside:avoid}thead{display:table-header-group}img,tr{page-break-

```
inside:avoid}h2,h3,p{orphans:3;widows:3}h2,h3{page-break-after:avoid}@page{size:a3}body{min-
width:992px!important}.container{min-
width:992px!important}.navbar{display:none}.badge{border:1px solid #000}.table{border-
collapse:collapse!important}.table td,.table th{background-color:#fff!important}.table-bordered
td,.table-bordered th{border:1px solid #ddd!important}}
/*# sourceMappingURL=bootstrap.min.css.map */
```

Script bootstrap theme

```
/*!
 * Bootstrap v3.3.7 (http://getbootstrap.com)
 * Copyright 2011-2016 Twitter, Inc.
 * Licensed under MIT (https://github.com/twbs/bootstrap/blob/master/LICENSE)
 */
.btn-default,
.btn-primary,
.btn-success,
.btn-info,
.btn-warning,
.btn-danger {
  text-shadow: 0 -1px 0 rgba(0, 0, 0, .2);
  -webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .15), 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
  box-shadow: inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .15), 0 1px 1px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
}
.btn-default:active,
.btn-primary:active,
.btn-success:active,
.btn-info:active,
.btn-warning:active,
.btn-danger:active,
.btn-default.active,
.btn-primary.active,
.btn-success.active,
.btn-info.active,
.btn-warning.active,
.btn-danger.active {
  -webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 3px 5px rgba(0, 0, 0, .125);
  box-shadow: inset 0 3px 5px rgba(0, 0, 0, .125);
}
.btn-default.disabled,
.btn-primary.disabled,
.btn-success.disabled,
.btn-info.disabled,
.btn-warning.disabled,
.btn-danger.disabled,
.btn-default[disabled],
.btn-primary[disabled],
.btn-success[disabled],
.btn-info[disabled],
.btn-warning[disabled],
.btn-danger[disabled],
```

```

fieldset[disabled] .btn-default,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-success,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-info,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger {
  -webkit-box-shadow: none;
  box-shadow: none;
}
.btn-default .badge,
.btn-primary .badge,
.btn-success .badge,
.btn-info .badge,
.btn-warning .badge,
.btn-danger .badge {
  text-shadow: none;
}
.btn:active,
.btn.active {
  background-image: none;
}
.btn-default {
  text-shadow: 0 1px 0 #fff;
  background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #fff 0%, #e0e0e0 100%);
  background-image:      -o-linear-gradient(top, #fff 0%, #e0e0e0 100%);
  background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#fff), to(#e0e0e0));
  background-image:      linear-gradient(to bottom, #fff 0%, #e0e0e0 100%);
  filter:                progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ffffff',
endColorstr='#ffe0e0', GradientType=0);
  filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled = false);
  background-repeat: repeat-x;
  border-color: #dbdbdb;
  border-color: #ccc;
}
.btn-default:hover,
.btn-default:focus {
  background-color: #e0e0e0;
  background-position: 0 -15px;
}
.btn-default:active,
.btn-default.active {
  background-color: #e0e0e0;
  border-color: #dbdbdb;
}
.btn-default.disabled,
.btn-default[disabled],
fieldset[disabled] .btn-default,
.btn-default.disabled:hover,
.btn-default[disabled]:hover,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-default:hover,
.btn-default.disabled:focus,

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.btn-default[disabled]:focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-default:focus,
.btn-default.disabled:focus,
.btn-default[disabled].focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-default.focus,
.btn-default.disabled:active,
.btn-default[disabled]:active,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-default:active,
.btn-default.disabled.active,
.btn-default[disabled].active,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-default.active {
  background-color: #e0e0e0;
  background-image: none;
}
.btn-primary {
  background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #337ab7 0%, #265a88 100%);
  background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #337ab7 0%, #265a88 100%);
  background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#337ab7), to(#265a88));
  background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #337ab7 0%, #265a88 100%);
  filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff337ab7',
endColorstr='#ff265a88', GradientType=0);
  filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled = false);
  background-repeat: repeat-x;
  border-color: #245580;
}
.btn-primary:hover,
.btn-primary:focus {
  background-color: #265a88;
  background-position: 0 -15px;
}
.btn-primary:active,
.btn-primary.active {
  background-color: #265a88;
  border-color: #245580;
}
.btn-primary.disabled,
.btn-primary[disabled],
fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary,
.btn-primary.disabled:hover,
.btn-primary[disabled]:hover,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary:hover,
.btn-primary.disabled:focus,
.btn-primary[disabled]:focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary:focus,
.btn-primary.disabled.focus,
.btn-primary[disabled].focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary.focus,
.btn-primary.disabled:active,
.btn-primary[disabled]:active,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary:active,
.btn-primary.disabled.active,

```

```

.btn-primary[disabled].active,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary.active {
  background-color: #265a88;
  background-image: none;
}
.btn-success {
  background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #5cb85c 0%, #419641 100%);
  background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #5cb85c 0%, #419641 100%);
  background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#5cb85c), to(#419641));
  background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #5cb85c 0%, #419641 100%);
  filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff5cb85c',
endColorstr='#ff419641', GradientType=0);
  filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled = false);
  background-repeat: repeat-x;
  border-color: #3e8f3e;
}
.btn-success:hover,
.btn-success:focus {
  background-color: #419641;
  background-position: 0 -15px;
}
.btn-success:active,
.btn-success.active {
  background-color: #419641;
  border-color: #3e8f3e;
}
.btn-success.disabled,
.btn-success[disabled],
fieldset[disabled] .btn-success,
.btn-success.disabled:hover,
.btn-success[disabled]:hover,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-success:hover,
.btn-success.disabled:focus,
.btn-success[disabled]:focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-success:focus,
.btn-success.disabled.focus,
.btn-success[disabled].focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-success.focus,
.btn-success.disabled:active,
.btn-success[disabled]:active,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-success:active,
.btn-success.disabled.active,
.btn-success[disabled].active,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-success.active {
  background-color: #419641;
  background-image: none;
}
.btn-info {
  background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #5bc0de 0%, #2aabd2 100%);
  background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #5bc0de 0%, #2aabd2 100%);
  background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#5bc0de), to(#2aabd2));
}

```

```

background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #5bc0de 0%, #2aabd2 100%);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff5bc0de',
endColorstr='#ff2aabd2', GradientType=0);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled = false);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
border-color: #28a4c9;
}
.btn-info:hover,
.btn-info:focus {
background-color: #2aabd2;
background-position: 0 -15px;
}
.btn-info:active,
.btn-info.active {
background-color: #2aabd2;
border-color: #28a4c9;
}
.btn-info.disabled,
.btn-info[disabled],
fieldset[disabled] .btn-info,
.btn-info.disabled:hover,
.btn-info[disabled]:hover,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-info:hover,
.btn-info.disabled:focus,
.btn-info[disabled]:focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-info:focus,
.btn-info.disabled.focus,
.btn-info[disabled].focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-info.focus,
.btn-info.disabled:active,
.btn-info[disabled]:active,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-info:active,
.btn-info.disabled.active,
.btn-info[disabled].active,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-info.active {
background-color: #2aabd2;
background-image: none;
}
.btn-warning {
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #f0ad4e 0%, #eb9316 100%);
background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #f0ad4e 0%, #eb9316 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#f0ad4e), to(#eb9316));
background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #f0ad4e 0%, #eb9316 100%);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#fff0ad4e',
endColorstr='#ffeb9316', GradientType=0);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled = false);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
border-color: #e38d13;
}
.btn-warning:hover,
.btn-warning:focus {

```

```

    background-color: #eb9316;
    background-position: 0 -15px;
}
.btn-warning:active,
.btn-warning.active {
    background-color: #eb9316;
    border-color: #e38d13;
}
.btn-warning.disabled,
.btn-warning[disabled],
fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning,
.btn-warning.disabled:hover,
.btn-warning[disabled]:hover,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning:hover,
.btn-warning.disabled:focus,
.btn-warning[disabled]:focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning:focus,
.btn-warning.disabled.focus,
.btn-warning[disabled].focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning.focus,
.btn-warning.disabled.active,
.btn-warning[disabled]:active,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning.active,
.btn-warning.disabled.active,
.btn-warning[disabled].active,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning.active {
    background-color: #eb9316;
    background-image: none;
}
.btn-danger {
    background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #d9534f 0%, #c12e2a 100%);
    background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #d9534f 0%, #c12e2a 100%);
    background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#d9534f), to(#c12e2a));
    background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #d9534f 0%, #c12e2a 100%);
    filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ffd9534f',
endColorstr='#ffc12e2a', GradientType=0);
    filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled = false);
    background-repeat: repeat-x;
    border-color: #b92c28;
}
.btn-danger:hover,
.btn-danger:focus {
    background-color: #c12e2a;
    background-position: 0 -15px;
}
.btn-danger:active,
.btn-danger.active {
    background-color: #c12e2a;
    border-color: #b92c28;
}
.btn-danger.disabled,

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.btn-danger[disabled],
fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger,
.btn-danger.disabled:hover,
.btn-danger[disabled]:hover,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger:hover,
.btn-danger.disabled:focus,
.btn-danger[disabled]:focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger:focus,
.btn-danger.disabled.focus,
.btn-danger[disabled].focus,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger.focus,
.btn-danger.disabled:active,
.btn-danger[disabled]:active,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger:active,
.btn-danger.disabled.active,
.btn-danger[disabled].active,
fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger.active {
    background-color: #c12e2a;
    background-image: none;
}
.thumbnail,
img-thumbnail {
    -webkit-box-shadow: 0 1px 2px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
    box-shadow: 0 1px 2px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
}
.dropdown-menu > li > a:hover,
.dropdown-menu > li > a:focus {
    background-color: #e8e8e8;
    background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #f5f5f5 0%, #e8e8e8 100%);
    background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #f5f5f5 0%, #e8e8e8 100%);
    background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#f5f5f5), to(#e8e8e8));
    background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #f5f5f5 0%, #e8e8e8 100%);
    filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#fff5f5f5',
endColorstr='#ffe8e8e8', GradientType=0);
    background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
.dropdown-menu > .active > a,
.dropdown-menu > .active > a:hover,
.dropdown-menu > .active > a:focus {
    background-color: #2e6da4;
    background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #337ab7 0%, #2e6da4 100%);
    background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #337ab7 0%, #2e6da4 100%);
    background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#337ab7), to(#2e6da4));
    background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #337ab7 0%, #2e6da4 100%);
    filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff337ab7',
endColorstr='#ff2e6da4', GradientType=0);
    background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
.navbar-default {
    background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #fff 0%, #f8f8f8 100%);
    background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #fff 0%, #f8f8f8 100%);

```

```

background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#fff), to(#f8f8f8));
background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #fff 0%, #f8f8f8 100%);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ffffff', endColorstr='#fff8f8f8', GradientType=0);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled = false);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
border-radius: 4px;
-webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .15), 0 1px 5px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
    box-shadow: inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .15), 0 1px 5px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
}
.navbar-default .navbar-nav > .open > a,
.navbar-default .navbar-nav > .active > a {
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #dbdbdb 0%, #e2e2e2 100%);
background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #dbdbdb 0%, #e2e2e2 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#dbdbdb), to(#e2e2e2));
background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #dbdbdb 0%, #e2e2e2 100%);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#f8dbdbdb', endColorstr='#ffe2e2e2', GradientType=0);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
-webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 3px 9px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
    box-shadow: inset 0 3px 9px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
}
.navbar-brand,
.navbar-nav > li > a {
text-shadow: 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .25);
}
.navbar-inverse {
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #3c3c3c 0%, #222 100%);
background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #3c3c3c 0%, #222 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#3c3c3c), to(#222));
background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #3c3c3c 0%, #222 100%);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff3c3c3c', endColorstr='#ff222222', GradientType=0);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled = false);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
border-radius: 4px;
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav > .open > a,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav > .active > a {
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #080808 0%, #0f0f0f 100%);
background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #080808 0%, #0f0f0f 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#080808), to(#0f0f0f));
background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #080808 0%, #0f0f0f 100%);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff080808', endColorstr='#ff0f0f0f', GradientType=0);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
-webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 3px 9px rgba(0, 0, 0, .25);
    box-shadow: inset 0 3px 9px rgba(0, 0, 0, .25);
}
.navbar-inverse .navbar-brand,
.navbar-inverse .navbar-nav > li > a {

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text-shadow: 0 -1px 0 rgba(0, 0, 0, .25);
}
.navbar-static-top,
.navbar-fixed-top,
.navbar-fixed-bottom {
border-radius: 0;
}
@media (max-width: 767px) {
.navbar .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .active > a,
.navbar .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .active > a:hover,
.navbar .navbar-nav .open .dropdown-menu > .active > a:focus {
color: #fff;
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #337ab7 0%, #2e6da4 100%);
background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #337ab7 0%, #2e6da4 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#337ab7), to(#2e6da4));
background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #337ab7 0%, #2e6da4 100%);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff337ab7',
endColorstr='#ff2e6da4', GradientType=0);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
}
.alert {
text-shadow: 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .2);
-webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .25), 0 1px 2px rgba(0, 0, 0, .05);
box-shadow: inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .25), 0 1px 2px rgba(0, 0, 0, .05);
}
.alert-success {
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #dff0d8 0%, #c8e5bc 100%);
background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #dff0d8 0%, #c8e5bc 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#dff0d8), to(#c8e5bc));
background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #dff0d8 0%, #c8e5bc 100%);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ffdff0d8',
endColorstr='#ffc8e5bc', GradientType=0);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
border-color: #b2dba1;
}
.alert-info {
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #d9edf7 0%, #b9def0 100%);
background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #d9edf7 0%, #b9def0 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#d9edf7), to(#b9def0));
background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #d9edf7 0%, #b9def0 100%);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ffd9edf7',
endColorstr='#ffb9def0', GradientType=0);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
border-color: #9acfea;
}
.alert-warning {
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #fcf8e3 0%, #f8efc0 100%);
background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #fcf8e3 0%, #f8efc0 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#fcf8e3), to(#f8efc0));
background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #fcf8e3 0%, #f8efc0 100%);
}

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filter:                progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ffcf8e3',
endColorstr='#ff8efc0', GradientType=0);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
border-color: #f5e79e;
}
.alert-danger {
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #f2dede 0%, #e7c3c3 100%);
background-image:    -o-linear-gradient(top, #f2dede 0%, #e7c3c3 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#f2dede), to(#e7c3c3));
background-image:    linear-gradient(to bottom, #f2dede 0%, #e7c3c3 100%);
filter:                progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#fff2dede',
endColorstr='#ffe7c3c3', GradientType=0);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
border-color: #dca7a7;
}
.progress {
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #ebebeb 0%, #5f5f5f 100%);
background-image:    -o-linear-gradient(top, #ebebeb 0%, #5f5f5f 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#ebebeb), to(#5f5f5f));
background-image:    linear-gradient(to bottom, #ebebeb 0%, #5f5f5f 100%);
filter:                progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ffebebeb',
endColorstr='#fff5f5f5', GradientType=0);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
.progress-bar {
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #337ab7 0%, #286090 100%);
background-image:    -o-linear-gradient(top, #337ab7 0%, #286090 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#337ab7), to(#286090));
background-image:    linear-gradient(to bottom, #337ab7 0%, #286090 100%);
filter:                progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff337ab7',
endColorstr='#ff286090', GradientType=0);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
.progress-bar-success {
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #5cb85c 0%, #449d44 100%);
background-image:    -o-linear-gradient(top, #5cb85c 0%, #449d44 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#5cb85c), to(#449d44));
background-image:    linear-gradient(to bottom, #5cb85c 0%, #449d44 100%);
filter:                progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff5cb85c',
endColorstr='#ff449d44', GradientType=0);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
.progress-bar-info {
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #5bc0de 0%, #31b0d5 100%);
background-image:    -o-linear-gradient(top, #5bc0de 0%, #31b0d5 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#5bc0de), to(#31b0d5));
background-image:    linear-gradient(to bottom, #5bc0de 0%, #31b0d5 100%);
filter:                progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff5bc0de',
endColorstr='#ff31b0d5', GradientType=0);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
}

```

```

.progress-bar-warning {
  background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #f0ad4e 0%, #ec971f 100%);
  background-image:    -o-linear-gradient(top, #f0ad4e 0%, #ec971f 100%);
  background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#f0ad4e), to(#ec971f));
  background-image:    linear-gradient(to bottom, #f0ad4e 0%, #ec971f 100%);
  filter:              progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#fff0ad4e',
endColorstr='#ffec971f', GradientType=0);
  background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
.progress-bar-danger {
  background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #d9534f 0%, #c9302c 100%);
  background-image:    -o-linear-gradient(top, #d9534f 0%, #c9302c 100%);
  background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#d9534f), to(#c9302c));
  background-image:    linear-gradient(to bottom, #d9534f 0%, #c9302c 100%);
  filter:              progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ffd9534f',
endColorstr='#ffc9302c', GradientType=0);
  background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
.progress-bar-striped {
  background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
  background-image:    -o-linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
  background-image:    linear-gradient(45deg, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 25%, transparent 25%,
transparent 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 50%, rgba(255, 255, 255, .15) 75%, transparent 75%,
transparent);
}
.list-group {
  border-radius: 4px;
  -webkit-box-shadow: 0 1px 2px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
  box-shadow: 0 1px 2px rgba(0, 0, 0, .075);
}
.list-group-item.active,
.list-group-item.active:hover,
.list-group-item.active:focus {
  text-shadow: 0 -1px 0 #286090;
  background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #337ab7 0%, #2b669a 100%);
  background-image:    -o-linear-gradient(top, #337ab7 0%, #2b669a 100%);
  background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#337ab7), to(#2b669a));
  background-image:    linear-gradient(to bottom, #337ab7 0%, #2b669a 100%);
  filter:              progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff337ab7',
endColorstr='#ff2b669a', GradientType=0);
  background-repeat: repeat-x;
  border-color: #2b669a;
}
.list-group-item.active .badge,
.list-group-item.active:hover .badge,
.list-group-item.active:focus .badge {
  text-shadow: none;
}

```

```

}
.panel {
  -webkit-box-shadow: 0 1px 2px rgba(0, 0, 0, .05);
  box-shadow: 0 1px 2px rgba(0, 0, 0, .05);
}
.panel-default > .panel-heading {
  background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #f5f5f5 0%, #e8e8e8 100%);
  background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #f5f5f5 0%, #e8e8e8 100%);
  background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#f5f5f5), to(#e8e8e8));
  background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #f5f5f5 0%, #e8e8e8 100%);
  filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#fff5f5f5',
endColorstr='#ffe8e8e8', GradientType=0);
  background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
.panel-primary > .panel-heading {
  background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #337ab7 0%, #2e6da4 100%);
  background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #337ab7 0%, #2e6da4 100%);
  background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#337ab7), to(#2e6da4));
  background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #337ab7 0%, #2e6da4 100%);
  filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff337ab7',
endColorstr='#ff2e6da4', GradientType=0);
  background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
.panel-success > .panel-heading {
  background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #dff0d8 0%, #d0e9c6 100%);
  background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #dff0d8 0%, #d0e9c6 100%);
  background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#dff0d8), to(#d0e9c6));
  background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #dff0d8 0%, #d0e9c6 100%);
  filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ffdff0d8',
endColorstr='#ffd0e9c6', GradientType=0);
  background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
.panel-info > .panel-heading {
  background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #d9edf7 0%, #c4e3f3 100%);
  background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #d9edf7 0%, #c4e3f3 100%);
  background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#d9edf7), to(#c4e3f3));
  background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #d9edf7 0%, #c4e3f3 100%);
  filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ffd9edf7',
endColorstr='#ffc4e3f3', GradientType=0);
  background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
.panel-warning > .panel-heading {
  background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #fcf8e3 0%, #faf2cc 100%);
  background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #fcf8e3 0%, #faf2cc 100%);
  background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#fcf8e3), to(#faf2cc));
  background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #fcf8e3 0%, #faf2cc 100%);
  filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#fff8e3',
endColorstr='#fffaf2cc', GradientType=0);
  background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
.panel-danger > .panel-heading {

```

```

background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #f2dede 0%, #ebcccc 100%);
background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #f2dede 0%, #ebcccc 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#f2dede), to(#ebcccc));
background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #f2dede 0%, #ebcccc 100%);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#fff2dede',
endColorstr='#ffe8e8', GradientType=0);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
}
.well {
background-image: -webkit-linear-gradient(top, #e8e8e8 0%, #f5f5f5 100%);
background-image: -o-linear-gradient(top, #e8e8e8 0%, #f5f5f5 100%);
background-image: -webkit-gradient(linear, left top, left bottom, from(#e8e8e8), to(#f5f5f5));
background-image: linear-gradient(to bottom, #e8e8e8 0%, #f5f5f5 100%);
filter: progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ffe8e8e8',
endColorstr='#fff5f5f5', GradientType=0);
background-repeat: repeat-x;
border-color: #dcdcdc;
-webkit-box-shadow: inset 0 1px 3px rgba(0, 0, 0, .05), 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .1);
box-shadow: inset 0 1px 3px rgba(0, 0, 0, .05), 0 1px 0 rgba(255, 255, 255, .1);
}
/*# sourceMappingURL=bootstrap-theme.css.map */

```

Script bootstrap-theme.min

```

/*!
 * Bootstrap v3.3.7 (http://getbootstrap.com)
 * Copyright 2011-2016 Twitter, Inc.
 * Licensed under MIT (https://github.com/twbs/bootstrap/blob/master/LICENSE)
 */
.btn-danger,.btn-default,.btn-info,.btn-primary,.btn-success,.btn-warning{text-shadow:0 -1px 0
rgba(0,0,0,.2);-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255,255,255,.15),0 1px 1px
rgba(0,0,0,.075);box-shadow:inset 0 1px 0 rgba(255,255,255,.15),0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.075)}.btn-
danger.active,.btn-danger:active,.btn-default.active,.btn-default:active,.btn-info.active,.btn-
info:active,.btn-primary.active,.btn-primary:active,.btn-success.active,.btn-success:active,.btn-
warning.active,.btn-warning:active{-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 3px 5px rgba(0,0,0,.125);box-
shadow:inset 0 3px 5px rgba(0,0,0,.125)}.btn-danger.disabled,.btn-danger[disabled],.btn-
default.disabled,.btn-default[disabled],.btn-info.disabled,.btn-info[disabled],.btn-
primary.disabled,.btn-primary[disabled],.btn-success.disabled,.btn-success[disabled],.btn-
warning.disabled,.btn-warning[disabled],fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger,fieldset[disabled] .btn-
default,fieldset[disabled] .btn-info,fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary,fieldset[disabled] .btn-
success,fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning{-webkit-box-shadow:none;box-shadow:none}.btn-danger
.badge,.btn-default .badge,.btn-info .badge,.btn-primary .badge,.btn-success .badge,.btn-warning
.badge{text-shadow:none}.btn.active,.btn:active{background-image:none}.btn-default{text-
shadow:0 1px 0 #fff;background-image:-webkit-linear-gradient(top,#fff 0,#e0e0e0
100%);background-image:-o-linear-gradient(top,#fff 0,#e0e0e0 100%);background-image:-webkit-
gradient(linear,left top,left bottom,from(#fff),to(#e0e0e0));background-image:linear-gradient(to
bottom,#fff 0,#e0e0e0
100%);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ffffff',
endColorstr='#ffe0e0',
GradientType=0);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled=false);background-
repeat:repeat-x;border-color:#dbdbdb;border-color:#ccc}.btn-default:focus,.btn-
default:hover{background-color:#e0e0e0;background-position:0 -15px}.btn-default.active,.btn-

```

default:active{background-color:#e0e0e0;border-color:#dbbdbd}.btn-default.disabled,.btn-default.disabled.active,.btn-default.disabled.focus,.btn-default.disabled:active,.btn-default.disabled:focus,.btn-default.disabled:hover,.btn-default[disabled],.btn-default[disabled].active,.btn-default[disabled].focus,.btn-default[disabled]:active,.btn-default[disabled]:focus,.btn-default[disabled]:hover,fieldset[disabled] .btn-default,fieldset[disabled] .btn-default.active,fieldset[disabled] .btn-default.focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-default:active,fieldset[disabled] .btn-default:focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-default:hover{background-color:#e0e0e0;background-image:none}.btn-primary{background-image:-webkit-linear-gradient(top,#337ab7 0,#265a88 100%);background-image:-o-linear-gradient(top,#337ab7 0,#265a88 100%);background-image:-webkit-gradient(linear,left top,left bottom,from(#337ab7),to(#265a88));background-image:linear-gradient(to bottom,#337ab7 0,#265a88 100%);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff337ab7',endColorstr='#ff265a88',GradientType=0);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled=false);background-repeat:repeat-x;border-color:#245580}.btn-primary:focus,.btn-primary:hover{background-color:#265a88;background-position:0 -15px}.btn-primary.active,.btn-primary:active{background-color:#265a88;border-color:#245580}.btn-primary.disabled,.btn-primary.disabled.active,.btn-primary.disabled.focus,.btn-primary.disabled:active,.btn-primary.disabled:focus,.btn-primary.disabled:hover,.btn-primary[disabled],.btn-primary[disabled].active,.btn-primary[disabled].focus,.btn-primary[disabled]:active,.btn-primary[disabled]:focus,.btn-primary[disabled]:hover,fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary,fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary.active,fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary.focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary:active,fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary:focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-primary:hover{background-color:#265a88;background-image:none}.btn-success{background-image:-webkit-linear-gradient(top,#5cb85c 0,#419641 100%);background-image:-o-linear-gradient(top,#5cb85c 0,#419641 100%);background-image:-webkit-gradient(linear,left top,left bottom,from(#5cb85c),to(#419641));background-image:linear-gradient(to bottom,#5cb85c 0,#419641 100%);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff5cb85c',endColorstr='#ff419641',GradientType=0);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled=false);background-repeat:repeat-x;border-color:#3e8f3e}.btn-success:focus,.btn-success:hover{background-color:#419641;background-position:0 -15px}.btn-success.active,.btn-success:active{background-color:#419641;border-color:#3e8f3e}.btn-success.disabled,.btn-success.disabled.active,.btn-success.disabled.focus,.btn-success.disabled:active,.btn-success.disabled:focus,.btn-success.disabled:hover,.btn-success[disabled],.btn-success[disabled].active,.btn-success[disabled].focus,.btn-success[disabled]:active,.btn-success[disabled]:focus,.btn-success[disabled]:hover,fieldset[disabled] .btn-success,fieldset[disabled] .btn-success.active,fieldset[disabled] .btn-success.focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-success:active,fieldset[disabled] .btn-success:focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-success:hover{background-color:#419641;background-image:none}.btn-info{background-image:-webkit-linear-gradient(top,#5bc0de 0,#2aabd2 100%);background-image:-o-linear-gradient(top,#5bc0de 0,#2aabd2 100%);background-image:-webkit-gradient(linear,left top,left bottom,from(#5bc0de),to(#2aabd2));background-image:linear-gradient(to bottom,#5bc0de 0,#2aabd2 100%);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff5bc0de',endColorstr='#ff2aabd2',GradientType=0);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled=false);background-repeat:repeat-x;border-color:#28a4c9}.btn-info:focus,.btn-info:hover{background-color:#2aabd2;background-position:0 -15px}.btn-info.active,.btn-info:active{background-color:#2aabd2;border-color:#28a4c9}.btn-info.disabled,.btn-info.disabled.active,.btn-info.disabled.focus,.btn-info.disabled:active,.btn-info.disabled:focus,.btn-info.disabled:hover,.btn-info[disabled],.btn-info[disabled].active,.btn-info[disabled].focus,.btn-info[disabled]:active,.btn-

info[disabled]:focus,.btn-info[disabled]:hover,fieldset[disabled] .btn-info,fieldset[disabled] .btn-info.active,fieldset[disabled] .btn-info.focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-info:active,fieldset[disabled] .btn-info:focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-info:hover{background-color:#2aab2;background-image:none}.btn-warning{background-image:-webkit-linear-gradient(top,#f0ad4e 0,#eb9316 100%);background-image:-o-linear-gradient(top,#f0ad4e 0,#eb9316 100%);background-image:-webkit-gradient(linear,left top,left bottom,from(#f0ad4e),to(#eb9316));background-image:linear-gradient(to bottom,#f0ad4e 0,#eb9316 100%);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#fff0ad4e',endColorstr='#ffeb9316',GradientType=0);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled=false);background-repeat:repeat-x;border-color:#e38d13}.btn-warning:focus,.btn-warning:active{background-color:#eb9316;border-color:#e38d13}.btn-warning.disabled,.btn-warning.disabled.active,.btn-warning.disabled:focus,.btn-warning.disabled:active,.btn-warning.disabled:focus,.btn-warning.disabled:hover,.btn-warning[disabled].active,.btn-warning[disabled].focus,.btn-warning[disabled]:hover,fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning,fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning.active,fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning.focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning:active,fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning:focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-warning:hover{background-color:#eb9316;background-image:none}.btn-danger{background-image:-webkit-linear-gradient(top,#d9534f 0,#c12e2a 100%);background-image:-o-linear-gradient(top,#d9534f 0,#c12e2a 100%);background-image:-webkit-gradient(linear,left top,left bottom,from(#d9534f),to(#c12e2a));background-image:linear-gradient(to bottom,#d9534f 0,#c12e2a 100%);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ffd9534f',endColorstr='#ffc12e2a',GradientType=0);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(enabled=false);background-repeat:repeat-x;border-color:#b92c28}.btn-danger:focus,.btn-danger:active{background-color:#c12e2a;background-position:0 -15px}.btn-danger.active,.btn-danger:active{background-color:#c12e2a;border-color:#b92c28}.btn-danger.disabled,.btn-danger.disabled.active,.btn-danger.disabled:focus,.btn-danger.disabled:active,.btn-danger.disabled:focus,.btn-danger.disabled:hover,.btn-danger[disabled].active,.btn-danger[disabled].focus,.btn-danger[disabled]:hover,fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger,fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger.active,fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger.focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger:active,fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger:focus,fieldset[disabled] .btn-danger:hover{background-color:#c12e2a;background-image:none}.img-thumbnail,.thumbnail{-webkit-box-shadow:0 1px 2px rgba(0,0,0,.075);box-shadow:0 1px 2px rgba(0,0,0,.075)}.dropdown-menu>li>a:focus,.dropdown-menu>li>a:active{background-color:#e8e8e8;background-image:-webkit-linear-gradient(top,#f5f5f5 0,#e8e8e8 100%);background-image:-o-linear-gradient(top,#f5f5f5 0,#e8e8e8 100%);background-image:-webkit-gradient(linear,left top,left bottom,from(#f5f5f5),to(#e8e8e8));background-image:linear-gradient(to bottom,#f5f5f5 0,#e8e8e8 100%);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#fff5f5f5',endColorstr='#ffe8e8e8',GradientType=0);background-repeat:repeat-x}.dropdown-menu>.active>a,.dropdown-menu>.active>a:focus,.dropdown-menu>.active>a:active{background-color:#2e6da4;background-image:-webkit-linear-gradient(top,#337ab7 0,#2e6da4 100%);background-image:-o-linear-gradient(top,#337ab7 0,#2e6da4 100%);background-image:-webkit-gradient(linear,left top,left bottom,from(#337ab7),to(#2e6da4));background-image:linear-gradient(to bottom,#337ab7 0,#2e6da4 100%);filter:progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.gradient(startColorstr='#ff337ab7',endColorstr='#ff2e6da4',GradientType=0);background-repeat:repeat-x}.navbar-default{background-image:-webkit-linear-gradient(top,fff 0,#f8f8f8 100%);background-image:-o-linear-gradient(top,fff


```
endColorstr='#fff5f5f5', GradientType=0);background-repeat:repeat-x;border-color:#dcdcdc;-webkit-box-shadow:inset 0 1px 3px rgba(0,0,0,.05),0 1px 0 rgba(255,255,255,.1);box-shadow:inset 0 1px 3px rgba(0,0,0,.05),0 1px 0 rgba(255,255,255,.1)}  
/*# sourceMappingURL=bootstrap-theme.min.css.map */
```

Script dataTable.bootstrap4

```
table.dataTable {  
  clear: both;  
  margin-top: 6px !important;  
  margin-bottom: 6px !important;  
  max-width: none !important;  
  border-collapse: separate !important;  
}  
table.dataTable td,  
table.dataTable th {  
  -webkit-box-sizing: content-box;  
  box-sizing: content-box;  
}  
table.dataTable td.dataTables_empty,  
table.dataTable th.dataTables_empty {  
  text-align: center;  
}  
table.dataTable.nowrap th,  
table.dataTable.nowrap td {  
  white-space: nowrap;  
}  
  
div.dataTables_wrapper div.dataTables_length label {  
  font-weight: normal;  
  text-align: left;  
  white-space: nowrap;  
}  
div.dataTables_wrapper div.dataTables_length select {  
  width: 75px;  
  display: inline-block;  
}  
div.dataTables_wrapper div.dataTables_filter {  
  text-align: right;  
}  
div.dataTables_wrapper div.dataTables_filter label {  
  font-weight: normal;  
  white-space: nowrap;  
  text-align: left;  
}  
div.dataTables_wrapper div.dataTables_filter input {  
  margin-left: 0.5em;  
  display: inline-block;  
  width: auto;  
}  
div.dataTables_wrapper div.dataTables_info {
```

```

padding-top: 0.85em;
white-space: nowrap;
}
div.dataTables_wrapper div.dataTables_paginate {
margin: 0;
white-space: nowrap;
text-align: right;
}
div.dataTables_wrapper div.dataTables_paginate ul.pagination {
margin: 2px 0;
white-space: nowrap;
justify-content: flex-end;
}
div.dataTables_wrapper div.dataTables_processing {
position: absolute;
top: 50%;
left: 50%;
width: 200px;
margin-left: -100px;
margin-top: -26px;
text-align: center;
padding: 1em 0;
}

```

```

table.dataTable thead > tr > th.sorting_asc, table.dataTable thead > tr > th.sorting_desc,
table.dataTable thead > tr > th.sorting,
table.dataTable thead > tr > td.sorting_asc,
table.dataTable thead > tr > td.sorting_desc,
table.dataTable thead > tr > td.sorting {
padding-right: 30px;
}
table.dataTable thead > tr > th:active,
table.dataTable thead > tr > td:active {
outline: none;
}
table.dataTable thead .sorting,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_asc,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_desc,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_asc_disabled,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_desc_disabled {
cursor: pointer;
position: relative;
}
table.dataTable thead .sorting:before, table.dataTable thead .sorting:after,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_asc:before,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_asc:after,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_desc:before,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_desc:after,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_asc_disabled:before,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_asc_disabled:after,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_desc_disabled:before,

```

```

table.dataTable thead .sorting_desc_disabled:after {
  position: absolute;
  bottom: 0.9em;
  display: block;
  opacity: 0.3;
}
table.dataTable thead .sorting:before,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_asc:before,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_desc:before,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_asc_disabled:before,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_desc_disabled:before {
  right: 1em;
  content: "\2191";
}
table.dataTable thead .sorting:after,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_asc:after,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_desc:after,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_asc_disabled:after,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_desc_disabled:after {
  right: 0.5em;
  content: "\2193";
}
table.dataTable thead .sorting_asc:before,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_desc:after {
  opacity: 1;
}
table.dataTable thead .sorting_asc_disabled:before,
table.dataTable thead .sorting_desc_disabled:after {
  opacity: 0;
}

div.dataTables_scrollHead table.dataTable {
  margin-bottom: 0 !important;
}

div.dataTables_scrollBody table {
  border-top: none;
  margin-top: 0 !important;
  margin-bottom: 0 !important;
}
div.dataTables_scrollBody table thead .sorting:after,
div.dataTables_scrollBody table thead .sorting_asc:after,
div.dataTables_scrollBody table thead .sorting_desc:after {
  display: none;
}
div.dataTables_scrollBody table tbody tr:first-child th,
div.dataTables_scrollBody table tbody tr:first-child td {
  border-top: none;
}

div.dataTables_scrollFoot > .dataTables_scrollFootInner {

```

```

    box-sizing: content-box;
}
div.dataTables_scrollFoot > .dataTables_scrollFootInner > table {
    margin-top: 0 !important;
    border-top: none;
}

@media screen and (max-width: 767px) {
    div.dataTables_wrapper div.dataTables_length,
    div.dataTables_wrapper div.dataTables_filter,
    div.dataTables_wrapper div.dataTables_info,
    div.dataTables_wrapper div.dataTables_paginate {
        text-align: center;
    }
}
table.dataTable.table-sm > thead > tr > th {
    padding-right: 20px;
}
table.dataTable.table-sm .sorting:before,
table.dataTable.table-sm .sorting_asc:before,
table.dataTable.table-sm .sorting_desc:before {
    top: 5px;
    right: 0.85em;
}
table.dataTable.table-sm .sorting:after,
table.dataTable.table-sm .sorting_asc:after,
table.dataTable.table-sm .sorting_desc:after {
    top: 5px;
}

table.table-bordered.dataTable th,
table.table-bordered.dataTable td {
    border-left-width: 0;
}
table.table-bordered.dataTable th:last-child, table.table-bordered.dataTable th:last-child,
table.table-bordered.dataTable td:last-child,
table.table-bordered.dataTable td:last-child {
    border-right-width: 0;
}
table.table-bordered.dataTable tbody th,
table.table-bordered.dataTable tbody td {
    border-bottom-width: 0;
}

div.dataTables_scrollHead table.table-bordered {
    border-bottom-width: 0;
}

div.table-responsive > div.dataTables_wrapper > div.row {
    margin: 0;
}

```

```
div.table-responsive > div.dataTables_wrapper > div.row > div[class^="col-"]:first-child {
  padding-left: 0;
}
```

```
div.table-responsive > div.dataTables_wrapper > div.row > div[class^="col-"]:last-child {
  padding-right: 0;
}
```

```
div#example_length {
  position: absolute;
}
```

Script font-awesome.min

```
/*!
 * Font Awesome 4.7.0 by @davegandy - http://fontawesome.io - @fontawesome
 * License - http://fontawesome.io/license (Font: SIL OFL 1.1, CSS: MIT License)
 */@font-face{font-family:'FontAwesome';src:url('../fonts/fontawesome-
webfont.eot?v=4.7.0');src:url('../fonts/fontawesome-webfont.eot?#iefix&v=4.7.0')
format('embedded-opentype'),url('../fonts/fontawesome-webfont.woff?v=4.7.0')
format('woff2'),url('../fonts/fontawesome-webfont.woff?v=4.7.0')
format('woff'),url('../fonts/fontawesome-webfont.ttf?v=4.7.0')
format('truetype'),url('../fonts/fontawesome-webfont.svg?v=4.7.0#fontawesomeregular')
format('svg');font-weight:normal;font-style:normal}.fa{display:inline-block;font:normal
normal 14px/1 FontAwesome;font-size:inherit;text-rendering:auto;-webkit-font-
smoothing:antialiased;-moz-osx-font-smoothing:grayscale}.fa-lg{font-size:1.33333333em;line-
height:.75em;vertical-align:-15%}.fa-2x{font-size:2em}.fa-3x{font-size:3em}.fa-4x{font-size:4em}.fa-
5x{font-size:5em}.fa-fw{width:1.28571429em;text-align:center}.fa-ul{padding-left:0;margin-
left:2.14285714em;list-style-type:none}.fa-ul>li{position:relative}.fa-li{position:absolute;left:-
2.14285714em;width:2.14285714em;top:.14285714em;text-align:center}.fa-li.fa-lg{left:-
1.85714286em}.fa-border{padding:.2em .25em .15em;border:solid .08em #eee;border-
radius:.1em}.fa-pull-left{float:left}.fa-pull-right{float:right}.fa.fa-pull-left{margin-right:.3em}.fa.fa-
pull-right{margin-left:.3em}.pull-right{float:right}.pull-left{float:left}.fa.pull-left{margin-
right:.3em}.fa.pull-right{margin-left:.3em}.fa-spin{-webkit-animation:fa-spin 2s infinite
linear;animation:fa-spin 2s infinite linear}.fa-pulse{-webkit-animation:fa-spin 1s infinite
steps(8);animation:fa-spin 1s infinite steps(8)}@-webkit-keyframes fa-spin{0%{-webkit-
transform:rotate(0deg);transform:rotate(0deg)}100%{-webkit-
transform:rotate(359deg);transform:rotate(359deg)}}@keyframes fa-spin{0%{-webkit-
transform:rotate(0deg);transform:rotate(0deg)}100%{-webkit-
transform:rotate(359deg);transform:rotate(359deg)}}.fa-rotate-90{-ms-
filter:"progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.BasicImage(rotation=1)";-webkit-
transform:rotate(90deg);-ms-transform:rotate(90deg);transform:rotate(90deg)}.fa-rotate-180{-ms-
filter:"progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.BasicImage(rotation=2)";-webkit-
transform:rotate(180deg);-ms-transform:rotate(180deg);transform:rotate(180deg)}.fa-rotate-270{-
ms-filter:"progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.BasicImage(rotation=3)";-webkit-
transform:rotate(270deg);-ms-transform:rotate(270deg);transform:rotate(270deg)}.fa-flip-
horizontal{-ms-filter:"progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.BasicImage(rotation=0, mirror=1)";-
webkit-transform:scale(-1, 1);-ms-transform:scale(-1, 1);transform:scale(-1, 1)}.fa-flip-vertical{-ms-
filter:"progid:DXImageTransform.Microsoft.BasicImage(rotation=2, mirror=1)";-webkit-
transform:scale(1, -1);-ms-transform:scale(1, -1);transform:scale(1, -1)}:root .fa-rotate-90,:root .fa-
rotate-180,:root .fa-rotate-270,:root .fa-flip-horizontal,:root .fa-flip-vertical{filter:none}.fa-
stack{position:relative;display:inline-block;width:2em;height:2em;line-height:2em;vertical-
```

align:middle}.fa-stack-1x,.fa-stack-2x{position:absolute;left:0;width:100%;text-align:center}.fa-stack-1x{line-height:inherit}.fa-stack-2x{font-size:2em}.fa-inverse{color:#fff}.fa-glass:before{content:"\f000"}.fa-music:before{content:"\f001"}.fa-search:before{content:"\f002"}.fa-envelope-o:before{content:"\f003"}.fa-heart:before{content:"\f004"}.fa-star:before{content:"\f005"}.fa-star-o:before{content:"\f006"}.fa-user:before{content:"\f007"}.fa-film:before{content:"\f008"}.fa-th-large:before{content:"\f009"}.fa-th:before{content:"\f00a"}.fa-th-list:before{content:"\f00b"}.fa-check:before{content:"\f00c"}.fa-remove:before,.fa-close:before,.fa-times:before{content:"\f00d"}.fa-search-plus:before{content:"\f00e"}.fa-search-minus:before{content:"\f010"}.fa-power-off:before{content:"\f011"}.fa-signal:before{content:"\f012"}.fa-gear:before,.fa-cog:before{content:"\f013"}.fa-trash-o:before{content:"\f014"}.fa-home:before{content:"\f015"}.fa-file-o:before{content:"\f016"}.fa-clock-o:before{content:"\f017"}.fa-road:before{content:"\f018"}.fa-download:before{content:"\f019"}.fa-arrow-circle-o-down:before{content:"\f01a"}.fa-arrow-circle-o-up:before{content:"\f01b"}.fa-inbox:before{content:"\f01c"}.fa-play-circle-o:before{content:"\f01d"}.fa-rotate-right:before,.fa-repeat:before{content:"\f01e"}.fa-refresh:before{content:"\f021"}.fa-list-alt:before{content:"\f022"}.fa-lock:before{content:"\f023"}.fa-flag:before{content:"\f024"}.fa-headphones:before{content:"\f025"}.fa-volume-off:before{content:"\f026"}.fa-volume-down:before{content:"\f027"}.fa-volume-up:before{content:"\f028"}.fa-qr-code:before{content:"\f029"}.fa-barcode:before{content:"\f02a"}.fa-tag:before{content:"\f02b"}.fa-tags:before{content:"\f02c"}.fa-book:before{content:"\f02d"}.fa-bookmark:before{content:"\f02e"}.fa-print:before{content:"\f02f"}.fa-camera:before{content:"\f030"}.fa-font:before{content:"\f031"}.fa-bold:before{content:"\f032"}.fa-italic:before{content:"\f033"}.fa-text-height:before{content:"\f034"}.fa-text-width:before{content:"\f035"}.fa-align-left:before{content:"\f036"}.fa-align-center:before{content:"\f037"}.fa-align-right:before{content:"\f038"}.fa-align-justify:before{content:"\f039"}.fa-list:before{content:"\f03a"}.fa-dedent:before,.fa-outdent:before{content:"\f03b"}.fa-indent:before{content:"\f03c"}.fa-video-camera:before{content:"\f03d"}.fa-photo:before,.fa-image:before,.fa-picture-o:before{content:"\f03e"}.fa-pencil:before{content:"\f040"}.fa-map-marker:before{content:"\f041"}.fa-adjust:before{content:"\f042"}.fa-tint:before{content:"\f043"}.fa-edit:before,.fa-pencil-square-o:before{content:"\f044"}.fa-share-square-o:before{content:"\f045"}.fa-check-square-o:before{content:"\f046"}.fa-arrows:before{content:"\f047"}.fa-step-backward:before{content:"\f048"}.fa-fast-backward:before{content:"\f049"}.fa-backward:before{content:"\f04a"}.fa-play:before{content:"\f04b"}.fa-pause:before{content:"\f04c"}.fa-stop:before{content:"\f04d"}.fa-forward:before{content:"\f04e"}.fa-fast-forward:before{content:"\f050"}.fa-step-forward:before{content:"\f051"}.fa-eject:before{content:"\f052"}.fa-chevron-left:before{content:"\f053"}.fa-chevron-right:before{content:"\f054"}.fa-plus-circle:before{content:"\f055"}.fa-minus-circle:before{content:"\f056"}.fa-times-circle:before{content:"\f057"}.fa-check-circle:before{content:"\f058"}.fa-question-circle:before{content:"\f059"}.fa-info-circle:before{content:"\f05a"}.fa-crosshairs:before{content:"\f05b"}.fa-times-circle-o:before{content:"\f05c"}.fa-check-circle-o:before{content:"\f05d"}.fa-ban:before{content:"\f05e"}.fa-arrow-left:before{content:"\f060"}.fa-arrow-right:before{content:"\f061"}.fa-arrow-up:before{content:"\f062"}.fa-arrow-down:before{content:"\f063"}.fa-mail-forward:before,.fa-share:before{content:"\f064"}.fa-expand:before{content:"\f065"}.fa-compress:before{content:"\f066"}.fa-plus:before{content:"\f067"}.fa-minus:before{content:"\f068"}.fa-asterisk:before{content:"\f069"}.fa-exclamation-circle:before{content:"\f06a"}.fa-gift:before{content:"\f06b"}.fa-leaf:before{content:"\f06c"}.fa-fire:before{content:"\f06d"}.fa-eye:before{content:"\f06e"}.fa-eye-slash:before{content:"\f070"}.fa-warning:before,.fa-

exclamation-triangle:before{content:"\f071"}.fa-plane:before{content:"\f072"}.fa-calendar:before{content:"\f073"}.fa-random:before{content:"\f074"}.fa-comment:before{content:"\f075"}.fa-magnet:before{content:"\f076"}.fa-chevron-up:before{content:"\f077"}.fa-chevron-down:before{content:"\f078"}.fa-retweet:before{content:"\f079"}.fa-shopping-cart:before{content:"\f07a"}.fa-folder:before{content:"\f07b"}.fa-folder-open:before{content:"\f07c"}.fa-arrows-v:before{content:"\f07d"}.fa-arrows-h:before{content:"\f07e"}.fa-bar-chart-o:before,.fa-bar-chart:before{content:"\f080"}.fa-twitter-square:before{content:"\f081"}.fa-facebook-square:before{content:"\f082"}.fa-camera-retro:before{content:"\f083"}.fa-key:before{content:"\f084"}.fa-gears:before,.fa-cogs:before{content:"\f085"}.fa-comments:before{content:"\f086"}.fa-thumbs-o-up:before{content:"\f087"}.fa-thumbs-down:before{content:"\f088"}.fa-star-half:before{content:"\f089"}.fa-heart-o:before{content:"\f08a"}.fa-sign-out:before{content:"\f08b"}.fa-linkedin-square:before{content:"\f08c"}.fa-thumb-tack:before{content:"\f08d"}.fa-external-link:before{content:"\f08e"}.fa-sign-in:before{content:"\f090"}.fa-trophy:before{content:"\f091"}.fa-github-square:before{content:"\f092"}.fa-upload:before{content:"\f093"}.fa-lemon-o:before{content:"\f094"}.fa-phone:before{content:"\f095"}.fa-square-o:before{content:"\f096"}.fa-bookmark-o:before{content:"\f097"}.fa-phone-square:before{content:"\f098"}.fa-twitter:before{content:"\f099"}.fa-facebook-f:before,.fa-facebook:before{content:"\f09a"}.fa-github:before{content:"\f09b"}.fa-unlock:before{content:"\f09c"}.fa-credit-card:before{content:"\f09d"}.fa-feed:before,.fa-rss:before{content:"\f09e"}.fa-hdd-o:before{content:"\f0a0"}.fa-bullhorn:before{content:"\f0a1"}.fa-bell:before{content:"\f0f3"}.fa-certificate:before{content:"\f0a3"}.fa-hand-o-right:before{content:"\f0a4"}.fa-hand-o-left:before{content:"\f0a5"}.fa-hand-o-up:before{content:"\f0a6"}.fa-hand-o-down:before{content:"\f0a7"}.fa-arrow-circle-left:before{content:"\f0a8"}.fa-arrow-circle-right:before{content:"\f0a9"}.fa-arrow-circle-up:before{content:"\f0aa"}.fa-arrow-circle-down:before{content:"\f0ab"}.fa-globe:before{content:"\f0ac"}.fa-wrench:before{content:"\f0ad"}.fa-tasks:before{content:"\f0ae"}.fa-filter:before{content:"\f0b0"}.fa-briefcase:before{content:"\f0b1"}.fa-arrows-alt:before{content:"\f0b2"}.fa-group:before,.fa-users:before{content:"\f0c0"}.fa-chain:before,.fa-link:before{content:"\f0c1"}.fa-cloud:before{content:"\f0c2"}.fa-flask:before{content:"\f0c3"}.fa-cut:before,.fa-scissors:before{content:"\f0c4"}.fa-copy:before,.fa-files-o:before{content:"\f0c5"}.fa-paperclip:before{content:"\f0c6"}.fa-save:before,.fa-floppy-o:before{content:"\f0c7"}.fa-square:before{content:"\f0c8"}.fa-navicon:before,.fa-reorder:before,.fa-bars:before{content:"\f0c9"}.fa-list-ul:before{content:"\f0ca"}.fa-list-ol:before{content:"\f0cb"}.fa-strikethrough:before{content:"\f0cc"}.fa-underline:before{content:"\f0cd"}.fa-table:before{content:"\f0ce"}.fa-magic:before{content:"\f0d0"}.fa-truck:before{content:"\f0d1"}.fa-pinterest:before{content:"\f0d2"}.fa-pinterest-square:before{content:"\f0d3"}.fa-google-plus-square:before{content:"\f0d4"}.fa-google-plus:before{content:"\f0d5"}.fa-money:before{content:"\f0d6"}.fa-caret-down:before{content:"\f0d7"}.fa-caret-up:before{content:"\f0d8"}.fa-caret-left:before{content:"\f0d9"}.fa-caret-right:before{content:"\f0da"}.fa-columns:before{content:"\f0db"}.fa-unsorted:before,.fa-sort:before{content:"\f0dc"}.fa-sort-down:before,.fa-sort-desc:before{content:"\f0dd"}.fa-sort-up:before,.fa-sort-asc:before{content:"\f0de"}.fa-envelope:before{content:"\f0e0"}.fa-linkedin:before{content:"\f0e1"}.fa-rotate-left:before,.fa-undo:before{content:"\f0e2"}.fa-legal:before,.fa-gavel:before{content:"\f0e3"}.fa-dashboard:before,.fa-tachometer:before{content:"\f0e4"}.fa-comment-o:before{content:"\f0e5"}.fa-comments-o:before{content:"\f0e6"}.fa-flash:before,.fa-bolt:before{content:"\f0e7"}.fa-sitemap:before{content:"\f0e8"}.fa-umbrella:before{content:"\f0e9"}.fa-paste:before,.fa-clipboard:before{content:"\f0ea"}.fa-lightbulb-o:before{content:"\f0eb"}.fa-exchange:before{content:"\f0ec"}.fa-cloud-download:before{content:"\f0ed"}.fa-cloud-

upload:before{content:"\f0ee"},fa-user-md:before{content:"\f0f0"},fa-stethoscope:before{content:"\f0f1"},fa-suitcase:before{content:"\f0f2"},fa-bell-o:before{content:"\f0a2"},fa-coffee:before{content:"\f0f4"},fa-cutlery:before{content:"\f0f5"},fa-file-text-o:before{content:"\f0f6"},fa-building-o:before{content:"\f0f7"},fa-hospital-o:before{content:"\f0f8"},fa-ambulance:before{content:"\f0f9"},fa-medkit:before{content:"\f0fa"},fa-fighter-jet:before{content:"\f0fb"},fa-beer:before{content:"\f0fc"},fa-h-square:before{content:"\f0fd"},fa-plus-square:before{content:"\f0fe"},fa-angle-double-left:before{content:"\f100"},fa-angle-double-right:before{content:"\f101"},fa-angle-double-up:before{content:"\f102"},fa-angle-double-down:before{content:"\f103"},fa-angle-left:before{content:"\f104"},fa-angle-right:before{content:"\f105"},fa-angle-up:before{content:"\f106"},fa-angle-down:before{content:"\f107"},fa-desktop:before{content:"\f108"},fa-laptop:before{content:"\f109"},fa-tablet:before{content:"\f10a"},fa-mobile-phone:before,fa-mobile:before{content:"\f10b"},fa-circle-o:before{content:"\f10c"},fa-quote-left:before{content:"\f10d"},fa-quote-right:before{content:"\f10e"},fa-spinner:before{content:"\f110"},fa-circle:before{content:"\f111"},fa-mail-reply:before,fa-reply:before{content:"\f112"},fa-github-alt:before{content:"\f113"},fa-folder-o:before{content:"\f114"},fa-folder-open-o:before{content:"\f115"},fa-smile-o:before{content:"\f118"},fa-frown-o:before{content:"\f119"},fa-meh-o:before{content:"\f11a"},fa-gamepad:before{content:"\f11b"},fa-keyboard-o:before{content:"\f11c"},fa-flag-o:before{content:"\f11d"},fa-flag-checkered:before{content:"\f11e"},fa-terminal:before{content:"\f120"},fa-code:before{content:"\f121"},fa-mail-reply-all:before,fa-reply-all:before{content:"\f122"},fa-star-half-empty:before,fa-star-half-full:before,fa-star-half-o:before{content:"\f123"},fa-location-arrow:before{content:"\f124"},fa-crop:before{content:"\f125"},fa-code-fork:before{content:"\f126"},fa-unlink:before,fa-chain-broken:before{content:"\f127"},fa-question:before{content:"\f128"},fa-info:before{content:"\f129"},fa-exclamation:before{content:"\f12a"},fa-superscript:before{content:"\f12b"},fa-subscript:before{content:"\f12c"},fa-eraser:before{content:"\f12d"},fa-puzzle-piece:before{content:"\f12e"},fa-microphone:before{content:"\f130"},fa-microphone-slash:before{content:"\f131"},fa-shield:before{content:"\f132"},fa-calendar-o:before{content:"\f133"},fa-fire-extinguisher:before{content:"\f134"},fa-rocket:before{content:"\f135"},fa-maxcdn:before{content:"\f136"},fa-chevron-circle-left:before{content:"\f137"},fa-chevron-circle-right:before{content:"\f138"},fa-chevron-circle-up:before{content:"\f139"},fa-chevron-circle-down:before{content:"\f13a"},fa-html5:before{content:"\f13b"},fa-css3:before{content:"\f13c"},fa-anchor:before{content:"\f13d"},fa-unlock-alt:before{content:"\f13e"},fa-bullseye:before{content:"\f140"},fa-ellipsis-h:before{content:"\f141"},fa-ellipsis-v:before{content:"\f142"},fa-rss-square:before{content:"\f143"},fa-play-circle:before{content:"\f144"},fa-ticket:before{content:"\f145"},fa-minus-square:before{content:"\f146"},fa-minus-square-o:before{content:"\f147"},fa-level-up:before{content:"\f148"},fa-level-down:before{content:"\f149"},fa-check-square:before{content:"\f14a"},fa-pencil-square:before{content:"\f14b"},fa-external-link-square:before{content:"\f14c"},fa-share-square:before{content:"\f14d"},fa-compass:before{content:"\f14e"},fa-toggle-down:before,fa-caret-square-o-down:before{content:"\f150"},fa-toggle-up:before,fa-caret-square-o-up:before{content:"\f151"},fa-toggle-right:before,fa-caret-square-o-right:before{content:"\f152"},fa-euro:before,fa-eur:before{content:"\f153"},fa-gbp:before{content:"\f154"},fa-dollar:before,fa-usd:before{content:"\f155"},fa-rupee:before,fa-inr:before{content:"\f156"},fa-cny:before,fa-rmb:before,fa-yen:before,fa-jpy:before{content:"\f157"},fa-ruble:before,fa-rouble:before,fa-rub:before{content:"\f158"},fa-won:before,fa-krw:before{content:"\f159"},fa-bitcoin:before,fa-btc:before{content:"\f15a"},fa-file:before{content:"\f15b"},fa-file-text:before{content:"\f15c"},fa-

sort-alpha-asc:before{content:"\f15d"}.fa-sort-alpha-desc:before{content:"\f15e"}.fa-sort-amount-asc:before{content:"\f160"}.fa-sort-amount-desc:before{content:"\f161"}.fa-sort-numeric-asc:before{content:"\f162"}.fa-sort-numeric-desc:before{content:"\f163"}.fa-thumbs-up:before{content:"\f164"}.fa-thumbs-down:before{content:"\f165"}.fa-youtube-square:before{content:"\f166"}.fa-youtube:before{content:"\f167"}.fa-xing:before{content:"\f168"}.fa-xing-square:before{content:"\f169"}.fa-youtube-play:before{content:"\f16a"}.fa-dropbox:before{content:"\f16b"}.fa-stack-overflow:before{content:"\f16c"}.fa-instagram:before{content:"\f16d"}.fa-flickr:before{content:"\f16e"}.fa-adn:before{content:"\f170"}.fa-bitbucket:before{content:"\f171"}.fa-bitbucket-square:before{content:"\f172"}.fa-tumblr:before{content:"\f173"}.fa-tumblr-square:before{content:"\f174"}.fa-long-arrow-down:before{content:"\f175"}.fa-long-arrow-up:before{content:"\f176"}.fa-long-arrow-left:before{content:"\f177"}.fa-long-arrow-right:before{content:"\f178"}.fa-apple:before{content:"\f179"}.fa-windows:before{content:"\f17a"}.fa-android:before{content:"\f17b"}.fa-linux:before{content:"\f17c"}.fa-dribbble:before{content:"\f17d"}.fa-skype:before{content:"\f17e"}.fa-foursquare:before{content:"\f180"}.fa-trello:before{content:"\f181"}.fa-female:before{content:"\f182"}.fa-male:before{content:"\f183"}.fa-gittip:before{content:"\f184"}.fa-sun-o:before{content:"\f185"}.fa-moon-o:before{content:"\f186"}.fa-archive:before{content:"\f187"}.fa-bug:before{content:"\f188"}.fa-vk:before{content:"\f189"}.fa-weibo:before{content:"\f18a"}.fa-renren:before{content:"\f18b"}.fa-pagelines:before{content:"\f18c"}.fa-stack-exchange:before{content:"\f18d"}.fa-arrow-circle-right:before{content:"\f18e"}.fa-arrow-circle-o-left:before{content:"\f190"}.fa-toggle-left:before{content:"\f191"}.fa-dot-circle-o:before{content:"\f192"}.fa-wheelchair:before{content:"\f193"}.fa-vimeo-square:before{content:"\f194"}.fa-turkish-lira:before{content:"\f195"}.fa-plus-square-o:before{content:"\f196"}.fa-space-shuttle:before{content:"\f197"}.fa-slack:before{content:"\f198"}.fa-envelope-square:before{content:"\f199"}.fa-wordpress:before{content:"\f19a"}.fa-openid:before{content:"\f19b"}.fa-institution:before{content:"\f19c"}.fa-mortar-board:before{content:"\f19d"}.fa-yahoo:before{content:"\f19e"}.fa-google:before{content:"\f1a0"}.fa-reddit:before{content:"\f1a1"}.fa-reddit-square:before{content:"\f1a2"}.fa-stumbleupon-circle:before{content:"\f1a3"}.fa-stumbleupon:before{content:"\f1a4"}.fa-delicious:before{content:"\f1a5"}.fa-digg:before{content:"\f1a6"}.fa-pied-piper-pp:before{content:"\f1a7"}.fa-pied-piper-alt:before{content:"\f1a8"}.fa-drupal:before{content:"\f1a9"}.fa-joomla:before{content:"\f1aa"}.fa-language:before{content:"\f1ab"}.fa-fax:before{content:"\f1ac"}.fa-building:before{content:"\f1ad"}.fa-child:before{content:"\f1ae"}.fa-paw:before{content:"\f1b0"}.fa-spoon:before{content:"\f1b1"}.fa-cube:before{content:"\f1b2"}.fa-cubes:before{content:"\f1b3"}.fa-behance:before{content:"\f1b4"}.fa-behance-square:before{content:"\f1b5"}.fa-steam:before{content:"\f1b6"}.fa-steam-square:before{content:"\f1b7"}.fa-recycle:before{content:"\f1b8"}.fa-automobile:before{content:"\f1b9"}.fa-cab:before{content:"\f1ba"}.fa-taxi:before{content:"\f1ba"}.fa-tree:before{content:"\f1bb"}.fa-spotify:before{content:"\f1bc"}.fa-deviantart:before{content:"\f1bd"}.fa-soundcloud:before{content:"\f1be"}.fa-database:before{content:"\f1c0"}.fa-file-pdf-o:before{content:"\f1c1"}.fa-file-word-o:before{content:"\f1c2"}.fa-file-excel-o:before{content:"\f1c3"}.fa-file-powerpoint-o:before{content:"\f1c4"}.fa-file-photo-o:before{content:"\f1c5"}.fa-file-picture-o:before{content:"\f1c6"}.fa-file-image-o:before{content:"\f1c7"}.fa-file-audio-o:before{content:"\f1c8"}.fa-file-video-o:before{content:"\f1c9"}.fa-vine:before{content:"\f1ca"}.fa-

codepen:before{content:"\f1cb"}.fa-jsfiddle:before{content:"\f1cc"}.fa-life-bouy:before,.fa-life-buoy:before,.fa-life-saver:before,.fa-support:before,.fa-life-ring:before{content:"\f1cd"}.fa-circle-onotch:before{content:"\f1ce"}.fa-ra:before,.fa-resistance:before,.fa-rebel:before{content:"\f1d0"}.fa-ge:before,.fa-empire:before{content:"\f1d1"}.fa-git-square:before{content:"\f1d2"}.fa-git:before{content:"\f1d3"}.fa-y-combinator-square:before,.fa-yc-square:before,.fa-hacker-news:before{content:"\f1d4"}.fa-tencent-weibo:before{content:"\f1d5"}.fa-qq:before{content:"\f1d6"}.fa-wechat:before,.fa-weixin:before{content:"\f1d7"}.fa-send:before,.fa-paper-plane:before{content:"\f1d8"}.fa-send-o:before,.fa-paper-plane-o:before{content:"\f1d9"}.fa-history:before{content:"\f1da"}.fa-circle-thin:before{content:"\f1db"}.fa-header:before{content:"\f1dc"}.fa-paragraph:before{content:"\f1dd"}.fa-sliders:before{content:"\f1de"}.fa-share-alt:before{content:"\f1e0"}.fa-share-alt-square:before{content:"\f1e1"}.fa-bomb:before{content:"\f1e2"}.fa-soccer-ball-o:before,.fa-futbol-o:before{content:"\f1e3"}.fa-tty:before{content:"\f1e4"}.fa-binoculars:before{content:"\f1e5"}.fa-plug:before{content:"\f1e6"}.fa-slideshare:before{content:"\f1e7"}.fa-twitch:before{content:"\f1e8"}.fa-yelp:before{content:"\f1e9"}.fa-newspaper-o:before{content:"\f1ea"}.fa-wifi:before{content:"\f1eb"}.fa-calculator:before{content:"\f1ec"}.fa-paypal:before{content:"\f1ed"}.fa-google-wallet:before{content:"\f1ee"}.fa-cc-visa:before{content:"\f1f0"}.fa-cc-mastercard:before{content:"\f1f1"}.fa-cc-discover:before{content:"\f1f2"}.fa-cc-amex:before{content:"\f1f3"}.fa-cc-paypal:before{content:"\f1f4"}.fa-cc-stripe:before{content:"\f1f5"}.fa-bell-slash:before{content:"\f1f6"}.fa-bell-slash-o:before{content:"\f1f7"}.fa-trash:before{content:"\f1f8"}.fa-copyright:before{content:"\f1f9"}.fa-at:before{content:"\f1fa"}.fa-eyedropper:before{content:"\f1fb"}.fa-paint-brush:before{content:"\f1fc"}.fa-birthday-cake:before{content:"\f1fd"}.fa-area-chart:before{content:"\f1fe"}.fa-pie-chart:before{content:"\f200"}.fa-line-chart:before{content:"\f201"}.fa-lastfm:before{content:"\f202"}.fa-lastfm-square:before{content:"\f203"}.fa-toggle-off:before{content:"\f204"}.fa-toggle-on:before{content:"\f205"}.fa-bicycle:before{content:"\f206"}.fa-bus:before{content:"\f207"}.fa-ioxhost:before{content:"\f208"}.fa-angellist:before{content:"\f209"}.fa-cc:before{content:"\f20a"}.fa-shekel:before,.fa-sheqel:before,.fa-ils:before{content:"\f20b"}.fa-meanpath:before{content:"\f20c"}.fa-buysellads:before{content:"\f20d"}.fa-connectdevelop:before{content:"\f20e"}.fa-dashcube:before{content:"\f210"}.fa-forumbee:before{content:"\f211"}.fa-leanpub:before{content:"\f212"}.fa-sellsy:before{content:"\f213"}.fa-shirtsinbulk:before{content:"\f214"}.fa-simplybuilt:before{content:"\f215"}.fa-skyatlas:before{content:"\f216"}.fa-cart-plus:before{content:"\f217"}.fa-cart-arrow-down:before{content:"\f218"}.fa-diamond:before{content:"\f219"}.fa-ship:before{content:"\f21a"}.fa-user-secret:before{content:"\f21b"}.fa-motorcycle:before{content:"\f21c"}.fa-street-view:before{content:"\f21d"}.fa-heartbeat:before{content:"\f21e"}.fa-venus:before{content:"\f221"}.fa-mars:before{content:"\f222"}.fa-mercury:before{content:"\f223"}.fa-intersex:before,.fa-transgender:before{content:"\f224"}.fa-transgender-alt:before{content:"\f225"}.fa-venus-double:before{content:"\f226"}.fa-mars-double:before{content:"\f227"}.fa-venus-mars:before{content:"\f228"}.fa-mars-stroke:before{content:"\f229"}.fa-mars-stroke-v:before{content:"\f22a"}.fa-mars-stroke-h:before{content:"\f22b"}.fa-neuter:before{content:"\f22c"}.fa-genderless:before{content:"\f22d"}.fa-facebook-official:before{content:"\f230"}.fa-pinterest-p:before{content:"\f231"}.fa-whatsapp:before{content:"\f232"}.fa-server:before{content:"\f233"}.fa-user-plus:before{content:"\f234"}.fa-user-times:before{content:"\f235"}.fa-hotel:before,.fa-bed:before{content:"\f236"}.fa-viacoin:before{content:"\f237"}.fa-train:before{content:"\f238"}.fa-

subway:before{content:"\f239"}.fa-medium:before{content:"\f23a"}.fa-yc:before,.fa-y-combinator:before{content:"\f23b"}.fa-optin-monster:before{content:"\f23c"}.fa-opencart:before{content:"\f23d"}.fa-expeditedssl:before{content:"\f23e"}.fa-battery-4:before,.fa-battery:before,.fa-battery-full:before{content:"\f240"}.fa-battery-3:before,.fa-battery-three-quarters:before{content:"\f241"}.fa-battery-2:before,.fa-battery-half:before{content:"\f242"}.fa-battery-1:before,.fa-battery-quarter:before{content:"\f243"}.fa-battery-0:before,.fa-battery-empty:before{content:"\f244"}.fa-mouse-pointer:before{content:"\f245"}.fa-i-cursor:before{content:"\f246"}.fa-object-group:before{content:"\f247"}.fa-object-ungroup:before{content:"\f248"}.fa-sticky-note:before{content:"\f249"}.fa-sticky-note-o:before{content:"\f24a"}.fa-cc-jcb:before{content:"\f24b"}.fa-cc-diners-club:before{content:"\f24c"}.fa-clone:before{content:"\f24d"}.fa-balance-scale:before{content:"\f24e"}.fa-hourglass-o:before{content:"\f250"}.fa-hourglass-1:before,.fa-hourglass-start:before{content:"\f251"}.fa-hourglass-2:before,.fa-hourglass-half:before{content:"\f252"}.fa-hourglass-3:before,.fa-hourglass-end:before{content:"\f253"}.fa-hourglass:before{content:"\f254"}.fa-hand-grab-o:before,.fa-hand-rock-o:before{content:"\f255"}.fa-hand-stop-o:before,.fa-hand-paper-o:before{content:"\f256"}.fa-hand-scissors-o:before{content:"\f257"}.fa-hand-lizard-o:before{content:"\f258"}.fa-hand-spock-o:before{content:"\f259"}.fa-hand-pointer-o:before{content:"\f25a"}.fa-hand-peace-o:before{content:"\f25b"}.fa-trademark:before{content:"\f25c"}.fa-registered:before{content:"\f25d"}.fa-creative-commons:before{content:"\f25e"}.fa-gg:before{content:"\f260"}.fa-gg-circle:before{content:"\f261"}.fa-tripadvisor:before{content:"\f262"}.fa-odnoklassniki:before{content:"\f263"}.fa-odnoklassniki-square:before{content:"\f264"}.fa-get-pocket:before{content:"\f265"}.fa-wikipedia-w:before{content:"\f266"}.fa-safari:before{content:"\f267"}.fa-chrome:before{content:"\f268"}.fa-firefox:before{content:"\f269"}.fa-opera:before{content:"\f26a"}.fa-internet-explorer:before{content:"\f26b"}.fa-tv:before,.fa-television:before{content:"\f26c"}.fa-contao:before{content:"\f26d"}.fa-500px:before{content:"\f26e"}.fa-amazon:before{content:"\f270"}.fa-calendar-plus-o:before{content:"\f271"}.fa-calendar-minus-o:before{content:"\f272"}.fa-calendar-times-o:before{content:"\f273"}.fa-calendar-check-o:before{content:"\f274"}.fa-industry:before{content:"\f275"}.fa-map-pin:before{content:"\f276"}.fa-map-signs:before{content:"\f277"}.fa-map-o:before{content:"\f278"}.fa-map:before{content:"\f279"}.fa-commenting:before{content:"\f27a"}.fa-commenting-o:before{content:"\f27b"}.fa-houzz:before{content:"\f27c"}.fa-vimeo:before{content:"\f27d"}.fa-black-tie:before{content:"\f27e"}.fa-fonticons:before{content:"\f280"}.fa-reddit-alien:before{content:"\f281"}.fa-edge:before{content:"\f282"}.fa-credit-card-alt:before{content:"\f283"}.fa-codiepie:before{content:"\f284"}.fa-modx:before{content:"\f285"}.fa-fort-awesome:before{content:"\f286"}.fa-usb:before{content:"\f287"}.fa-product-hunt:before{content:"\f288"}.fa-mixcloud:before{content:"\f289"}.fa-scribd:before{content:"\f28a"}.fa-pause-circle:before{content:"\f28b"}.fa-pause-circle-o:before{content:"\f28c"}.fa-stop-circle:before{content:"\f28d"}.fa-stop-circle-o:before{content:"\f28e"}.fa-shopping-bag:before{content:"\f290"}.fa-shopping-basket:before{content:"\f291"}.fa-hashtag:before{content:"\f292"}.fa-bluetooth:before{content:"\f293"}.fa-bluetooth-b:before{content:"\f294"}.fa-percent:before{content:"\f295"}.fa-gitlab:before{content:"\f296"}.fa-wpbeginner:before{content:"\f297"}.fa-wpforms:before{content:"\f298"}.fa-envira:before{content:"\f299"}.fa-universal-access:before{content:"\f29a"}.fa-wheelchair-alt:before{content:"\f29b"}.fa-question-circle-o:before{content:"\f29c"}.fa-blind:before{content:"\f29d"}.fa-audio-description:before{content:"\f29e"}.fa-volume-control-phone:before{content:"\f2a0"}.fa-braille:before{content:"\f2a1"}.fa-assistive-listening-systems:before{content:"\f2a2"}.fa-asl-interpreting:before,.fa-american-sign-language-

interpreting:before{content:"\f2a3"}.fa-deafness:before,.fa-hard-of-hearing:before,.fa-deaf:before{content:"\f2a4"}.fa-glide:before{content:"\f2a5"}.fa-glide-g:before{content:"\f2a6"}.fa-signing:before,.fa-sign-language:before{content:"\f2a7"}.fa-low-vision:before{content:"\f2a8"}.fa-viadeo:before{content:"\f2a9"}.fa-viadeo-square:before{content:"\f2aa"}.fa-snapchat:before{content:"\f2ab"}.fa-snapchat-ghost:before{content:"\f2ac"}.fa-snapchat-square:before{content:"\f2ad"}.fa-pied-piper:before{content:"\f2ae"}.fa-first-order:before{content:"\f2b0"}.fa-yoast:before{content:"\f2b1"}.fa-themeisle:before{content:"\f2b2"}.fa-google-plus-circle:before,.fa-google-plus-official:before{content:"\f2b3"}.fa-fa:before,.fa-font-awesome:before{content:"\f2b4"}.fa-handshake-o:before{content:"\f2b5"}.fa-envelope-open:before{content:"\f2b6"}.fa-envelope-open-o:before{content:"\f2b7"}.fa-linode:before{content:"\f2b8"}.fa-address-book:before{content:"\f2b9"}.fa-address-book-o:before{content:"\f2ba"}.fa-vcard:before,.fa-address-card:before{content:"\f2bb"}.fa-vcard-o:before,.fa-address-card-o:before{content:"\f2bc"}.fa-user-circle:before{content:"\f2bd"}.fa-user-circle-o:before{content:"\f2be"}.fa-user-o:before{content:"\f2c0"}.fa-id-badge:before{content:"\f2c1"}.fa-drivers-license:before,.fa-id-card:before{content:"\f2c2"}.fa-drivers-license-o:before,.fa-id-card-o:before{content:"\f2c3"}.fa-quora:before{content:"\f2c4"}.fa-free-code-camp:before{content:"\f2c5"}.fa-telegram:before{content:"\f2c6"}.fa-thermometer-4:before,.fa-thermometer:before,.fa-thermometer-full:before{content:"\f2c7"}.fa-thermometer-3:before,.fa-thermometer-three-quarters:before{content:"\f2c8"}.fa-thermometer-2:before,.fa-thermometer-half:before{content:"\f2c9"}.fa-thermometer-1:before,.fa-thermometer-quarter:before{content:"\f2ca"}.fa-thermometer-0:before,.fa-thermometer-empty:before{content:"\f2cb"}.fa-shower:before{content:"\f2cc"}.fa-bathtub:before,.fa-s15:before,.fa-bath:before{content:"\f2cd"}.fa-podcast:before{content:"\f2ce"}.fa-window-maximize:before{content:"\f2d0"}.fa-window-minimize:before{content:"\f2d1"}.fa-window-restore:before{content:"\f2d2"}.fa-times-rectangle:before,.fa-window-close:before{content:"\f2d3"}.fa-times-rectangle-o:before,.fa-window-close-o:before{content:"\f2d4"}.fa-bandcamp:before{content:"\f2d5"}.fa-grav:before{content:"\f2d6"}.fa-etsy:before{content:"\f2d7"}.fa-imdb:before{content:"\f2d8"}.fa-ravelry:before{content:"\f2d9"}.fa-eercast:before{content:"\f2da"}.fa-microchip:before{content:"\f2db"}.fa-snowflake-o:before{content:"\f2dc"}.fa-superpowers:before{content:"\f2dd"}.fa-wpexplorer:before{content:"\f2de"}.fa-meetup:before{content:"\f2e0"}.sr-only{position:absolute;width:1px;height:1px;padding:0;margin:-1px;overflow:hidden;clip:rect(0, 0, 0, 0);border:0}.sr-only-focusable:active,.sr-only-focusable:focus{position:static;width:auto;height:auto;margin:0;overflow:visible;clip:auto}

Script modern-business

```

/*!
 * Start Bootstrap - Modern Business (https://startbootstrap.com/template-overviews/modern-business)
 * Copyright 2013-2017 Start Bootstrap
 * Licensed under MIT (https://github.com/BlackrockDigital/startbootstrap-logomodern-business-nav/blob/master/LICENSE)
 */

body {
  padding-top: 54px;
}

@media (min-width: 992px) {
  
```

```
body {  
  padding-top: 56px;  
}
```

```
.carousel-item {  
  height: 65vh;  
  min-height: 300px;  
  background: no-repeat center center scroll;  
  -webkit-background-size: cover;  
  -moz-background-size: cover;  
  -o-background-size: cover;  
  background-size: cover;  
}
```

```
.portfolio-item {  
  margin-bottom: 30px;  
}
```

Script sb-admin.min

```
html {  
  position: relative;  
  min-height: 100%;  
}
```

```
body {  
  overflow-x: hidden;  
}
```

```
body.sticky-footer {  
  margin-bottom: 56px;  
}
```

```
body.sticky-footer .content-wrapper {  
  min-height: calc(100vh - 56px - 56px);  
}
```

```
body.fixed-nav {  
  padding-top: 56px;  
}
```

```
.content-wrapper {  
  min-height: calc(100vh - 56px);  
  padding-top: 1rem;  
}
```

```
.scroll-to-top {  
  position: fixed;  
  right: 15px;  
  bottom: 3px;
```

```
display: none;
width: 50px;
height: 50px;
text-align: center;
color: white;
background: rgba(52, 58, 64, 0.5);
line-height: 45px;
}

.scroll-to-top:focus, .scroll-to-top:hover {
  color: white;
}

.scroll-to-top:hover {
  background: #343a40;
}

.scroll-to-top i {
  font-weight: 800;
}

.smaller {
  font-size: 0.7rem;
}

.o-hidden {
  overflow: hidden !important;
}

.z-0 {
  z-index: 0;
}

.z-1 {
  z-index: 1;
}

#mainNav .navbar-collapse {
  overflow: auto;
  max-height: 75vh;
}

#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-nav .nav-item .nav-link {
  cursor: pointer;
}

#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav .nav-link-collapse:after {
  float: right;
  content: '\f107';
  font-family: 'FontAwesome';
}
```

```
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav .nav-link-collapse.collapsed:after {
  content: '\f105';
}
```

```
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav .sidenav-second-level,
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav .sidenav-third-level {
  padding-left: 0;
}
```

```
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav .sidenav-second-level > li > a,
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav .sidenav-third-level > li > a {
  display: block;
  padding: 0.5em 0;
}
```

```
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav .sidenav-second-level > li > a:focus, #mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav .sidenav-second-level > li > a:hover,
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav .sidenav-third-level > li > a:focus,
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav .sidenav-third-level > li > a:hover {
  text-decoration: none;
}
```

```
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav .sidenav-second-level > li > a {
  padding-left: 1em;
}
```

```
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav .sidenav-third-level > li > a {
  padding-left: 2em;
}
```

```
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .sidenav-toggler {
  display: none;
}
```

```
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-nav > .nav-item.dropdown > .nav-link {
  position: relative;
  min-width: 45px;
}
```

```
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-nav > .nav-item.dropdown > .nav-link:after {
  float: right;
  width: auto;
  content: '\f105';
  border: none;
  font-family: 'FontAwesome';
}
```

```
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-nav > .nav-item.dropdown > .nav-link .indicator {
  position: absolute;
  top: 5px;
}
```

```
left: 21px;
font-size: 10px;
}
```

```
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-nav > .nav-item.dropdown.show > .nav-link:after {
  content: '\f107';
}
```

```
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-nav > .nav-item.dropdown .dropdown-menu > .dropdown-item >
.dropdown-message {
  overflow: hidden;
  max-width: none;
  text-overflow: ellipsis;
}
```

```
@media (min-width: 992px) {
  #mainNav .navbar-brand {
    width: 250px;
  }
  #mainNav .navbar-collapse {
    overflow: visible;
    max-height: none;
  }
  #mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav {
    position: absolute;
    top: 0;
    left: 0;
    -webkit-flex-direction: column;
    -ms-flex-direction: column;
    flex-direction: column;
    margin-top: 56px;
  }
  #mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item {
    width: 250px;
    padding: 0;
  }
  #mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item > .nav-link {
    padding: 1em;
  }
  #mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-second-level,
  #mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-third-level {
    padding-left: 0;
    list-style: none;
  }
  #mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-second-level > li,
  #mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-third-level > li {
    width: 250px;
  }
  #mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-second-level > li > a,
  #mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-third-level > li > a {
    padding: 1em;
  }
}
```

```

}
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-second-level > li > a {
  padding-left: 2.75em;
}
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-third-level > li > a {
  padding-left: 3.75em;
}
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-nav > .nav-item.dropdown > .nav-link {
  min-width: 0;
}
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-nav > .nav-item.dropdown > .nav-link:after {
  width: 24px;
  text-align: center;
}
#mainNav .navbar-collapse .navbar-nav > .nav-item.dropdown .dropdown-menu > .dropdown-item
> .dropdown-message {
  max-width: 300px;
}
}

#mainNav.fixed-top .sidenav-toggler {
  display: none;
}

@media (min-width: 992px) {
#mainNav.fixed-top .navbar-sidenav {
  height: calc(100vh - 112px);
}
#mainNav.fixed-top .sidenav-toggler {
  position: absolute;
  top: 0;
  left: 0;
  display: flex;
  -webkit-flex-direction: column;
  -ms-flex-direction: column;
  flex-direction: column;
  margin-top: calc(100vh - 56px);
}
#mainNav.fixed-top .sidenav-toggler > .nav-item {
  width: 250px;
  padding: 0;
}
#mainNav.fixed-top .sidenav-toggler > .nav-item > .nav-link {
  padding: 1em;
}
}

#mainNav.fixed-top.navbar-dark .sidenav-toggler {
  background-color: #212529;
}
}

```

```
#mainNav.fixed-top.navbar-dark .sidenav-toggler a i {
  color: #adb5bd;
}
```

```
#mainNav.fixed-top.navbar-light .sidenav-toggler {
  background-color: #dee2e6;
}
```

```
#mainNav.fixed-top.navbar-light .sidenav-toggler a i {
  color: rgba(0, 0, 0, 0.5);
}
```

```
body.sidenav-toggled #mainNav.fixed-top .sidenav-toggler {
  overflow-x: hidden;
  width: 55px;
}
```

```
body.sidenav-toggled #mainNav.fixed-top .sidenav-toggler .nav-item,
body.sidenav-toggled #mainNav.fixed-top .sidenav-toggler .nav-link {
  width: 55px !important;
}
```

```
body.sidenav-toggled #mainNav.fixed-top #sidenavToggler i {
  -webkit-transform: scaleX(-1);
  -moz-transform: scaleX(-1);
  -o-transform: scaleX(-1);
  transform: scaleX(-1);
  filter: FlipH;
  -ms-filter: 'FlipH';
}
```

```
#mainNav.static-top .sidenav-toggler {
  display: none;
}
```

```
@media (min-width: 992px) {
  #mainNav.static-top .sidenav-toggler {
    display: flex;
  }
}
```

```
body.sidenav-toggled #mainNav.static-top #sidenavToggler i {
  -webkit-transform: scaleX(-1);
  -moz-transform: scaleX(-1);
  -o-transform: scaleX(-1);
  transform: scaleX(-1);
  filter: FlipH;
  -ms-filter: 'FlipH';
}
```

```
.content-wrapper {
```

```
overflow-x: hidden;
background: white;
}
```

```
@media (min-width: 992px) {
  .content-wrapper {
    margin-left: 250px;
  }
}
```

```
#sidenavToggler i {
  font-weight: 800;
}
```

```
.navbar-sidenav-tooltip.show {
  display: none;
}
```

```
@media (min-width: 992px) {
  body.sidenav-toggled .content-wrapper {
    margin-left: 55px;
  }
}
```

```
body.sidenav-toggled .navbar-sidenav {
  width: 55px;
}
```

```
body.sidenav-toggled .navbar-sidenav .nav-link-text {
  display: none;
}
```

```
body.sidenav-toggled .navbar-sidenav .nav-item,
body.sidenav-toggled .navbar-sidenav .nav-link {
  width: 55px !important;
}
```

```
body.sidenav-toggled .navbar-sidenav .nav-item:after,
body.sidenav-toggled .navbar-sidenav .nav-link:after {
  display: none;
}
```

```
body.sidenav-toggled .navbar-sidenav .nav-item {
  white-space: nowrap;
}
```

```
body.sidenav-toggled .navbar-sidenav-tooltip.show {
  display: flex;
}
```

```
#mainNav.navbar-dark .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav .nav-link-collapse:after {
```

```

    color: #868e96;
}

#mainNav.navbar-dark .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item > .nav-link {
    color: #868e96;
}

#mainNav.navbar-dark .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item > .nav-link:hover {
    color: #adb5bd;
}

#mainNav.navbar-dark .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-second-level > li > a,
#mainNav.navbar-dark .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-third-level > li > a {
    color: #868e96;
}

#mainNav.navbar-dark .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-second-level > li >
a:focus, #mainNav.navbar-dark .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-second-level >
li > a:hover,
#mainNav.navbar-dark .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-third-level > li >
a:focus,
#mainNav.navbar-dark .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-third-level > li >
a:hover {
    color: #adb5bd;
}

#mainNav.navbar-dark .navbar-collapse .navbar-nav > .nav-item.dropdown > .nav-link:after {
    color: #adb5bd;
}

@media (min-width: 992px) {
    #mainNav.navbar-dark .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav {
        background: #343a40;
    }
    #mainNav.navbar-dark .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav li.active a {
        color: white !important;
        background-color: #495057;
    }
    #mainNav.navbar-dark .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav li.active a:focus, #mainNav.navbar-dark
.navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav li.active a:hover {
        color: white;
    }
    #mainNav.navbar-dark .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-second-level,
    #mainNav.navbar-dark .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-third-level {
        background: #343a40;
    }
}

#mainNav.navbar-light .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav .nav-link-collapse:after {
    color: rgba(0, 0, 0, 0.5);
}

```

```
#mainNav.navbar-light .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item > .nav-link {
  color: rgba(0, 0, 0, 0.5);
}
```

```
#mainNav.navbar-light .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item > .nav-link:hover {
  color: rgba(0, 0, 0, 0.7);
}
```

```
#mainNav.navbar-light .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-second-level > li > a,
#mainNav.navbar-light .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-third-level > li > a {
  color: rgba(0, 0, 0, 0.5);
}
```

```
#mainNav.navbar-light .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-second-level > li >
a:focus, #mainNav.navbar-light .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-second-level >
li > a:hover,
#mainNav.navbar-light .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-third-level > li >
a:focus,
#mainNav.navbar-light .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-third-level > li >
a:hover {
  color: rgba(0, 0, 0, 0.7);
}
```

```
#mainNav.navbar-light .navbar-collapse .navbar-nav > .nav-item.dropdown > .nav-link:after {
  color: rgba(0, 0, 0, 0.5);
}
```

```
@media (min-width: 992px) {
  #mainNav.navbar-light .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav {
    background: #f8f9fa;
  }
  #mainNav.navbar-light .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav li.active a {
    color: #000 !important;
    background-color: #e9ecef;
  }
  #mainNav.navbar-light .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav li.active a:focus, #mainNav.navbar-light
.navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav li.active a:hover {
    color: #000;
  }
  #mainNav.navbar-light .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-second-level,
  #mainNav.navbar-light .navbar-collapse .navbar-sidenav > .nav-item .sidenav-third-level {
    background: #f8f9fa;
  }
}
```

```
.card-body-icon {
  position: absolute;
  z-index: 0;
  top: -25px;
  right: -25px;
}
```

```
font-size: 5rem;
-webkit-transform: rotate(15deg);
-ms-transform: rotate(15deg);
transform: rotate(15deg);
}
```

```
@media (min-width: 576px) {
  .card-columns {
    column-count: 1;
  }
}
```

```
@media (min-width: 768px) {
  .card-columns {
    column-count: 2;
  }
}
```

```
@media (min-width: 1200px) {
  .card-columns {
    column-count: 2;
  }
}
```

```
.card-login {
  max-width: 25rem;
}
```

```
.card-register {
  max-width: 40rem;
}
```

```
footer.sticky-footer {
  position: absolute;
  right: 0;
  bottom: 0;
  width: 100%;
  height: 56px;
  background-color: #e9ecef;
  line-height: 55px;
}
```

```
h1.text-admin {
  text-align: center;
  padding: 60px;
  text-transform: capitalize;
  font-weight: 300;
  line-height: 1.4;
}
```

```
label.wrap-check {
```

```

width: 100%;
}

.panel-primary {
border-color: #337ab7;
}

.panel {
margin-bottom: 20px;
background-color: #fff;
border: 1px solid #337ab7;
width: 100%;
border-radius: 4px;
-webkit-box-shadow: 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.05);
box-shadow: 0 1px 1px rgba(0,0,0,.05);
}

.panel-primary>.panel-heading {
color: #fff;
background-color: #337ab7;
border-color: #337ab7;
}

.panel-heading {
padding: 10px 15px;
border-bottom: 1px solid transparent;
border-top-left-radius: 3px;
border-top-right-radius: 3px;
}

.panel-body {
padding: 15px;
}

@media (min-width: 992px) {
footer.sticky-footer {
width: calc(100% - 250px);
}
}

@media (min-width: 992px) {
body.sidenav-toggled footer.sticky-footer {
width: calc(100% - 55px);
}
}

```

Script style

```

body {
background: #f7f7f7;
}

```

```

    color: #6e6e6e;
    margin: 0;
    padding: 0;
    font: 12px Roboto,Helvetica,Arial,sans-serif;
    line-height: 140%;
}

.wrapper {
    max-width: 100%;
    min-height: 100vh;
    margin: 0 auto;
    padding: 0;
    border: solid 1px #eee;
    box-shadow: 0 0 12px rgba(0,0,0,.17);
    overflow: hidden;
    position: relative;
}

.navbar {
    margin-bottom: 0;
    border-radius: 0;
}

/* Set height of the grid so .sidenav can be 100% (adjust as needed) */
.row.content {height: 500px}

/* Set gray background color and 100% height */
.sidenav {
    padding-top: 20px;
    background-color: #f1f1f1;
    height: 100%;
}

/* Set black background color, white text and some padding */
footer {
    background-color: #555;
    color: white;
    padding: 15px 0 5px;
}

/* On small screens, set height to 'auto' for sidenav and grid */
@media screen and (max-width: 767px) {
    .sidenav {
        height: auto;
        padding: 15px;
    }
    .row.content {height:auto;}
}

.modal-header, h4, .close {
    background-color: #3b5998;
    color:white !important;
    text-align: center;
}

```

```
    font-size: 30px;
}

.sidenav ul {
  padding: 0;
  list-style: none;
}

.sidenav li {
  margin-bottom: 10px;
}

.head-title {
  font-size: 22px;
  font-weight: bold;
  line-height: 30px;
  margin: 15px 0 10px 0;
  padding: 0;
  color: #EF3B3A;
}

.banner img {
  border: solid 1px #ddd;
  width: 100%;
  max-width: 100%;
  height: 320px;
}

.image_wrapper {
  padding: 0;
}

.text-view {
  font-size: 14px;
  line-height: 1.4;
  padding-left: 40px;
}

.text-second {
  font-size: 14px;
  line-height: 1.4;
  margin-top: 10px;
}

.col-md-9 {
  background: #fff;
}
```

Script style-admin

```
.form {
```

```
position: relative;
z-index: 1;
background: #FFFFFF;
max-width: 300px;
margin: 0 auto 100px;
padding: 30px;
border: solid 1px rgb(224, 223, 223);
border-top-left-radius: 3px;
border-top-right-radius: 3px;
border-bottom-left-radius: 3px;
border-bottom-right-radius: 3px;
text-align: center;
}
.form .thumbnail {
margin: 0 auto;
padding: 0px 15px 15px;
border-top-left-radius: 100%;
border-top-right-radius: 100%;
border-bottom-left-radius: 100%;
border-bottom-right-radius: 100%;
box-sizing: border-box;
}
.form .thumbnail img {
display: block;
width: 100%;
}
.form input {
outline: 0;
background: #c5c2f5;
width: 100%;
border: 0;
margin: 0 0 15px;
padding: 15px;
border-top-left-radius: 3px;
border-top-right-radius: 3px;
border-bottom-left-radius: 3px;
border-bottom-right-radius: 3px;
box-sizing: border-box;
font-size: 14px;
}
.form button {
outline: 0;
background: rgb(27, 104, 248);
width: 100%;
border: 0;
padding: 15px;
border-top-left-radius: 4px;
border-top-right-radius: 4px;
border-bottom-left-radius: 4px;
border-bottom-right-radius: 4px;
color: rgb(41, 250, 104);
```

```
font-size: 14px;
transition: all 0.3 ease;
cursor: pointer;
}
.form .message {
margin: 15px 0 0;
color: #b3b3b3;
font-size: 12px;
}
.form .message a {
color: rgb(255, 2, 2);
text-decoration: none;
}
.form .register-form {
display: none;
}

.container {
position: relative;
z-index: 1;
max-width: 300px;
margin: 0 auto;
}
.container:before, .container:after {
content: "";
display: block;
clear: both;
}
.container .info {
margin: 30px auto;
text-align: center;
}
.container .info h1 {
margin: 0 0 15px;
padding: 0;
font-size: 36px;
font-weight: 300;
color: #1a1a1a;
}
.container .info span {
color: #4d4d4d;
font-size: 12px;
}
.container .info span a {
color: #000000;
text-decoration: none;
}
.container .info span .fa {
color: rgb(255, 0, 0);
}
```

```
body {
  background: #ccc;
  font-family: "Roboto", sans-serif;
  -webkit-font-smoothing: antialiased;
  -moz-osx-font-smoothing: grayscale;
}
body:before {
  content: "";
  position: fixed;
  top: 0;
  left: 0;
  display: block;
  background: #f1f1f1;
  width: 100%;
  height: 100%;
}
```

SURAT TUGAS

No. 805/3.01/STMIK-NM/III/2019

Tentang

**PENELITIAN YANG TELAH TERCATAT DALAM DAFTAR UMUM CIPTAAN
NOMOR DAN TANGGAL PERMOHONAN : EC00201934198, 28 Maret 2019
NOMOR PENCATATAN : 000138802
PADA SURAT PENCATATAN CIPTAAN
KEMENTERIAN HUKUM DAN HAK ASASI MANUSIA REPUBLIK INDONESIA**

Judul :

**“Program Aplikasi Sistem Pakar Pendeteksi Kerusakan Dini
Mesin Suzuki All New Ertiga Bensin Menggunakan Metode
Forward Chaining”**

MEMUTUSKAN

- PERTAMA** : Menugaskan kepada saudara
Akmaludin, S.Kom., MMSI
Sebagai Pemegang Hak Cipta yang mempublikasikan
Penelitian Yang Telah Tercatat Dalam Daftar Umum
Ciptaan Pada Surat Pencatatan Ciptaan Kementerian
Hukum dan Hak Asasi Manusia Republik Indonesia
- KEDUA** : Mempunyai tugas sbb:
Melaksanakan tugas yang diberikan dengan penuh rasa
tanggung jawab.
- KETIGA** : Keputusan ini berlaku sejak tanggal ditetapkan, dengan
ketentuan apabila dikemudian hari terdapat kekeliruan
akan diubah dan diperbaiki sebagaimana mestinya.

Jakarta, 25 Maret 2019

Ketua

**STMIK
NUSA MANDIRI**

Dr. Dwiza Riana, S.Si, MM, M.Kom

Tembusan :

1. Ketua STMIK Nusa Mandiri
2. Ka. Divisi SDM
3. ybs

STMIK NUSA MANDIRI

- Jl. Kramat Raya No.18, Jakarta Pusat
- Jl. Margonda Raya No. 545, Depok
- Jl. Ciledug Raya No.108, Cipulir, Jakarta Selatan
- Jl. Jatiwaringin Raya No. 18, Jakarta Timur
- Jl. Kamal Raya No.18, Ring Road Barat, Cengkareng, Jakarta Barat
- Jl. Raya Kaliabang No.8, Perwira, Bekasi
- Jl. Daan Mogot No.31, Tangerang

